

**THE WTO DISPUTE
SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING
AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS
FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL
EXPORTS**

Prepared by: Aisha W Umar

Institution: University of West Scotland

August 2024

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA’S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENT	2
LIST OF TABLES	6
LIST OF FIGURES	8
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	9
ABSTRACT	10
CHAPTER ONE.....	13
1.1 Background to the study	13
1.2 Trade Dispute Resolution: Overview	20
1.3 Developing Countries and DSU: Overview of Challenges.....	21
1.4 The Nigeria Economy: Structural Considerations	26
1.5 Africa Continental Free Trade Agreement (AfCTA)	30
1.6 African Countries and Engagement with the DSU	42
1.7 Rationale for the Research	13
1.8 Research Aim	15
1.9 Research Questions.....	15
1.10 Scope of the Research.....	15
1.11 Overview of Research Methodology.....	16
1.12 Structure of the Thesis	17
CHAPTER TWO	43
2.1 Institutional Structure of the WTO.....	44
2.1.2 Objectives and functions of the WTO	45
2.1.3 Functions of the WTO	46
2.1.4 Membership and Institutional Structure	47
2.1.5 Decision-Making within the WTO.....	48
2.2 Laws of the WTO	52
2.2.1 Need for Rules to Govern International Trade	55

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA’S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

2.2.2 WTO Rules	54
2.3 Rules and Procedures for Settlement of Disputes	63
2.4 Dispute Resolution: Litigation, Conciliation, and Negotiation	64
2.4.1 Economic Interests and Capacity	65
2.4.2 The Choice between Litigation and Negotiation in Dispute Settlement	66
2.5 Dispute Settlement Understanding/System: Operational Framework	67
2.5.1 DSS: Operational Process	70
2.5.2 Elements of the Dispute Settlement Process	72
2.5.3 Adjustments to the Operation of the DSU	76
2.6 Challenges with the DSU	78
2.7 Developing Countries and Engagement with the DSU	82
2.7.1 Africa and Engagement with the DSU	85
2.8 Evaluating the Effectiveness of the WTO’s Dispute Settlement System: Issues Arising	90
2.9 Dispute Settlement Management System	94
CHAPTER THREE	98
3.1 Introduction	98
3.2 Theoretical Frameworks in International Trade	98
3.2.1 Transaction Cost Theory	98
3.2.2 Economics of Non-Tariff Measures	102
3.2.3 New Trade Theory	103
3.2.4 Strategic Trade and Resource Dumping	104
3.2.5 Country Size and Trade Facilitation	105
3.2.6 Theory of Mercantilism	106
3.2.7 Trade Creation versus Trade Diversion	107
3.2.8 The Principal- Agent theory	110
CHAPTER FOUR	118
4.1 Introduction	118
4.2 Research Philosophy	118
4.3 Research Approach	121

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA’S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

4.4 Research Design	123
4.4.1 Research Hypotheses	124
4.5 Data Collection Methods	126
4.5.1 Primary Data.....	126
4.5.2 Secondary Data.....	127
4.5.3 <i>Data Analysis</i>	128
4.6 Sampling Methods.....	131
4.7 Validity, Reliability and Generalizability	132
4.8 Limitations of the Study	133
4.9 Ethical Considerations	133
CHAPTER FIVE.....	134
5.0 Introduction.....	135
5.1 Analysis of Survey Data	135
5.2 Data description.....	136
5.2 Data Analyses and Interpretation	147
5.2.1 Probit Regression - Sesame	157
5.2.2 Hypothesis Testing- Sesame	165
5.2.3 Probit Regression - Cocoa.....	168
5.2.5 Probit Regression - Shea Nut	179
5.2.6 Hypothesis Testing- Shea Nuts	187
5.3 Summary of Findings	189
CHAPTER SIX.....	227
6.0 Introduction.....	228
6.1 Sample Composition of the Focus Group Participants	228
6.2 Thematic Findings	229
6.3 Summary of the Thematic Analysis of the Focus Group Discussion.....	242
CHAPTER SEVEN	244
7.0 Introduction.....	244
7.1 Sample Composition of the Focus Group Participants	244
7.2 Thematic Findings	244

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA’S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

7.3 Summary of the Thematic Analysis of the Interview	257
CHAPTER EIGHT	259
8.0 Introduction.....	259
8.1 Discussion of findings.....	259
8.1.1 Discussion of findings at the downstream level comprised of Nigerian Agricultural producers	259
8.1.2 Discussion of findings from the midstream level comprised of Nigeria’s Trade Institutions.....	268
8.1.3 Discussion of findings from the upstream level comprised of Nigeria’s WTO Representatives.....	269
8.1.3.2 External factors	273
8.2 Overall Findings.....	277
8.3 The principal-agent theory and the research outcomes.....	278
8.4 Summary	281
REFERENCES	290
ANNEX A: QUESTIONNAIRE.....	304
ANNEX B: FOCUS GROUP GUIDE	305

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Top ten intra-African Exporters (2017-2019).....	23
Table 2: Disputes in which an African Country was a respondent or` Complainant	70
Table 3: Dispute in which an African Country was a Third Party	71
Table 4: African Countries Participation in the Appellate Body as Panelists	72
Table 7.1: Level of Engagement with FMARD	113
Table 7.2: Level of Engagement with FMITI	113
Table 7.3: Understanding of SPS	114
Table 7.4: Application of SPS	114
Table 7.5: Understanding of Technical Rules.....	115
Table 7.6: Application of Technical Rules	115
Table 7.7: Understanding of Rules of Origin	116
Table 7.8: Application of Rules of Origin	116
Table 7.9: Model Information	121
Table 7.10a: Parameter Estimate	121
Table 7.12a: Parameter Estimates	123
Table 7.11a: Parameter Estimates	124
Table 7.12 a: Parameter Estimates	125
Table 7.13a: Parameter Estimates	126
Table 7.14 a: Parameter Estimates	127
Table 7.10b: Parameter Estimates	129
Table 7.11b: Parameter Estimates	130
Table 7.12b: Parameter Estimates	131
Table 7.13b: Parameter Estimates	132
Table 7.14b: Parameter Estimates	133
Table 7.15b: Parameter Estimates	134

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Table 7.10c: Parameter Estimates.....	136
Table 7.11c: Parameter Estimates.....	137
Table 7.12c: Parameter Estimates.....	138
Table 7.13c: Parameter Estimates.....	139
Table 7.14c: Parameter Estimates.....	140
Table 7.15c: Parameter Estimates.....	141
Table 8.1 Sample Composition.....	145
Table 8.2: Participants 'Perceptions of the Role of the Midstream Level.....	146
Table 8.3: Participants 'Perceptions of the Midstream's Readiness to perform its Role	147
Table 8.4: Participants 'Perceptions of the Midstream's Performance.....	151
Table 8.5: Participants 'Perceptions of the challenges of the Midstream.....	154
Table 9.1: Participants 'Perceptions of the Role of the upstream Level.....	158
Table 9.2: Participants 'Perceptions of the Role of the upstream Level.....	159
Table 9.3: Participants 'Perceptions of the challenges of the Midstream.....	161

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA’S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Structure of the Nigerian economy by sector (2011-2021) based on % of GDP at current basic enterprises.....	18
Figure 2: Evolution of Nigerian Exports (2010 to 2022)	19
Figure 3: Schematic for Thesis Report	24
Figure 4: Overview of the WTO Dispute Settlement System.....	57
Figure 7: Trade Diversionary Effects of Preferential Trade Agreements.....	86
Figure 5: Categorization of Nigeria’s Trade Stakeholders	90
Figure 6: The Three Is Framework	91
Figure 7: Research Onion	96
Figure 7.1: Gender Distribution.....	107
Figure 7.2: Age distribution	108
Figure 7.3 Educational Qualification	108
Figure 7.4 Experience	109
Figure 7.5 Output.....	109
Figure 7.6: Ownership	110
Figure 7.7 Export Status.....	111
Figure 7.8: Intention to Export.....	111
Figure 7.9: Engagement with SON	112
Figure 7.10: Engagement with NAQS.....	112

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Firstly, I express my deep gratitude to the Almighty God for granting the good health and the strength to complete my doctoral studies.

I would like to extend profound appreciation to my lead supervisor, Professor John Struthers, Professor, School of Business and Creative Industries, University of the West of Scotland, for his guidance, inspiration and substantial contributions throughout my research journey. Additionally, I would like to acknowledge Dr Allan Moore, my second supervisor, for his advice and unique ideas that deepened the legal aspects of my research, and Dr Salisu Mohammed Adaya, Special Advisor to Nigeria's former President Muhammad's Buhari, who despite his tight schedule in the Presidency, acted informally as my third supervisor and continuously provided vital data and up to date information on the Nigerian economy.

I must also thank respondents who participated in interviews, focal group discussions and responded to my questionnaires. I am deeply grateful to Mr. Wilson Agaba and Mr. Gerald Ogboku, for their guidance in various aspects of my research. Furthermore, my heartfelt thanks go to Mr Sunday Ogwuche, Senior Counsellor in the Nigerian Mission in Geneva, for his insightful knowledge of Nigeria's navigation within the WTO.

I would also like to acknowledge Nigeria's former Minister of Industry, Trade, and Investment, Otunba Adeniyi Adebayo for facilitating my meetings with various trade institutions under his watch. My debt of gratitude goes to the brilliant Ambassador Yonov Agah, Director General & Chief Trade Negotiator, Nigerian Office for Trade Negotiations, formerly a Deputy Director General of the WTO for sharing his expertise from his vast experience in WTO matters. Immense appreciation also goes to His Excellency Ambassador Adamu Abdulhamid for responding to my interview and sharing his technical insights as Nigeria's Ambassador to the World Trade Organization,

Additionally, I want to acknowledge Dr. Bright Okogwu, the Special Advisor to the Director-General of the World Trade Organization, for his unwavering support, which granted me access to valuable relevant staff at the DG WTO for interviews.

Thank you to my family and dear friends for every word of encouragement and support. I am forever grateful to my wonderful husband Dr Tajuddeen Umar and amazing children uplifting me throughout the journey of my doctoral study. This thesis is a testament to your unwavering dedication to seeing me succeed, and I hope that it will make you all proud.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Finally, I dedicate this thesis to my parents starting with my father, late Alhaji Waziri Ibrahim, for my education and intellectual development. His words of wisdom have been instrumental in shaping my character and values. My dearest mother, Fatime Waziri Ibrahim, an amazing woman of substance, for being a constant source of strength and a rock-solid sounding board for all my major life decisions. I am eternally grateful for her endless love and prayers.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

ABSTRACT

This research examines the DSU as a tool for reducing or eliminating market access barriers for Nigeria's Agricultural exports. Participation in the DSU is key to shaping trade jurisprudence that guide and determine trade agreements and negotiations. Consequently, this research examines the degree to which Nigeria has engaged with this instrument to ensure that agreements reached by the WTO –both by the General Council and Appellate Body- do not hamper its trade interests. It is necessary to note that African countries were in support of the rule-based approach of the DSU at the time of its inception –mainly because of what they saw as a perceived advantage emanating from SDT provisions- without much thought to the challenges they would face in the future. While the rule-based approach was welcomed and formalized by member countries at the Uruguay Round, few of them –particularly African countries- could have anticipated the increased complexity of this instrument with the nature and frequency of cases filed over the years since the DSU's inception in 1995. This and other challenges associated with the DSU also informed this research especially as African countries including Nigeria show suboptimal results with respect to engaging with and participating in DSU processes.

The agency theory is used to explore Nigeria's trade infrastructure to identify the peculiar barriers inhibiting its engagement with the WTO's dispute settlement system. In applying this framework to the study, the researcher was able to broadly categorize stakeholders in Nigeria's trade environment into three main groups namely: the upstream players; the midstream players and the downstream players. The downstream consists of Nigeria's WTO representative based in Geneva; the midstream consists of trade-related or trade support institutions in Nigeria (i.e. the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade & Investment (FMITI); the Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC); the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD); and the upstream players consists of producers and exporters of agricultural commodities. The framework also influenced data collection and analysis for the study.

For this research, the case study research design was used. Nigeria formed the case study for investigating developing countries' engagement with the WTO's Dispute Settlement System. Since Nigeria was selected as a case study for this research, questionnaires and interviews were used to collect data from key actors and stakeholders across the upstream (exporters and producers of shea nuts, sesame and cocoa), midstream (trade-related or trade support institutions such as the FMITI and NEPC), and downstream (i.e. Nigeria's WTO trade representative based in Geneva) layers of the trade environment in Nigeria.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Overall, the study concluded that the upstream actors are unable to identify market access barriers given their low participation in export and limited understanding and application of WTO rules (i.e. SPS and TBT). Furthermore, the midstream lacks the capacity to investigate identified market access barriers, gather data and communicate to the upstream for further actions. The downstream level faces both internal and external factors preventing them from initiating cases on behalf of the upstream actors. This confirms the study's main hypothesis which states that the Nigerian trade architecture is subdivided into three distinct segments namely downstream, midstream, and upstream. Effective engagement with the WTO dispute settlement process relies on strengthening the capacity of these three segments to carry out their respective responsibilities in the trade process.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

This research explores the WTO's Dispute Settlement Understanding (DSU) and how African countries, especially Nigeria, can effectively engage with this instrument to obtain favourable conditions and agreements that support the diversification of their economies with particular emphasis on the growth of their agricultural exports. Participation in the DSU is key to shaping trade jurisprudence that guides and determines trade agreements and negotiations for years to come. Consequently, this research examines the degree to which Nigeria has engaged with this instrument to ensure that agreements reached by the WTO –both by the General Council and Appellate Body- do not hamper its trade interests and development especially as Africa accounts for only about 3% of global trade (Coulibaly et al., 2022). On the other hand, Nigeria accounts for about 0.33% of global trade (Salawu et al., 2021).

1.1.1 Rationale for the Research

In the preliminary literature review, some inherent challenges associated with the DSU in its current form have been identified. However, countries still use it as a useful means of resolving bilateral trade disputes. Nigeria, on the other hand, is backward in this regard as it has yet to file a single case through the DSU despite being the largest economy in Africa by GDP. This represents a challenge to the government's intention of diversifying the country's economy away from dependence on crude oil exports and hampers its capacity to achieve the policy objectives of the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP). A key policy thrust of the ERGP is achieving sustained macroeconomic stability through increased export of agricultural commodities. The degree to which this is achieved is dependent on the level of development of Nigeria's trade policy infrastructure with particular emphasis on sufficient understanding of WTO rules and procedures, particularly its dispute settlement mechanisms.

Preliminary assessment of conditions in the FMITI indicates that Nigeria's trade infrastructure is underdeveloped coupled with limited legal capacity to address the market barriers that its agricultural commodities face in the international market. These issues highlight the challenges limiting Nigeria from optimal use of DSU procedures to improve its trade outcomes. Even at the upstream or consultative phase of dispute settlement,

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

African countries lack the capacity to effectively negotiate favourable outcomes from consultations with bilateral trade partners without necessarily having to proceed to downstream activities. Consequently, this research will examine pre-downstream activities in trade negotiations with a view to identifying meaningful approaches to securing favorable trade agreements for Nigeria. To improve Nigeria's trade policy infrastructure, there is a need to understudy the trade infrastructure of developed member countries with a view to identifying potential areas for improvement especially quick wins.

African countries, including Nigeria, are not without blame for their inability to leverage the DSU mechanism to improve their trade outcomes. The countries have not taken advantage of opportunities provided by third party consultations and participation in cases where they have a special interest. This is where the developed countries, including the BRIC Nations, are ahead as they leverage the opportunities provided by being a third party to a case to further strengthen their existing trade policy infrastructure whilst expanding their knowledge about the DSU's legal procedures. To address some of the questions posed by this research, there is a need to investigate the degree to which Nigeria has utilized third party participation¹ to improve its technical capacity in trade negotiations and WTO procedures. This should help outline practical steps that should be taken by the FMITI to improve Nigeria's trade infrastructure.

At the point the DSU was conceived, there was limited consideration for international development. The perceived lack of developmental focus in the DSU instrument may have also placed African countries at a disadvantage. While the SDT provisions are supposed to give preference to developing countries in trade disputes, experience shows that the lack of legal certainty in such provisions have failed to deliver the market access that African and other developing countries expect. The implicit biases underlying the system of trade rules, including the DSU, in favour of developed countries –reinforced through the dominance of judicial types of rule-making- are well documented in literature (Busch and Reinhardt, 2001; Picciotto, 2005). Consequently, this research will critically examine the current SDT provisions in the DSU procedure with a view to identifying gaps and suggesting appropriate amendments (i.e. tightening of language) that will favour Nigeria. In doing so, close attention will be devoted to the vagueness of certain provisions in the DSU's procedures that leave them open to interpretation by member countries. One instance of this is the failure of the DSU to define the term "substantial trade interest". Again, Article 4.10 reads "...during consultations Members should give special attention

¹ It is necessary to note that participating as a third party can be costly especially where the member country concerned chooses to use a private lawyer or law firm to represent it in the proceedings. Nevertheless, the costs associated with engaging a lawyer in third party participation is lower than the costs associated with participation as a respondent or complainant especially where the third party only addresses issues of direct relevance to it.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

to the particular problems and interests of developing country Members”, without elaborating further. In addition to understudying critical provisions of the DSU, this research will further explore the degree to which Nigeria has access to critical information about trade partners that it consults with. The WTO's Trade Policy Review Mechanism (TPRM) will also be examined closely with a view to identifying instruments that Nigeria can use to strengthen its trade policy infrastructure.

1.2 Research Aim

The main aim of this research is to explore the challenges and opportunities associated with the WTO's Dispute Resolution Mechanism and effective approaches to leveraging this instrument to boost the export of key agricultural commodities in Nigeria.

1.3 Research Questions

To fulfil the overriding aim of this research, the following questions have been developed for this research:

- i. What are the challenges limiting Nigeria from using the WTO's dispute settlement understanding to eliminate market access barriers for its agricultural commodities?
- ii. What institutional linkages for trade exist in Nigeria and how can these be improved to leverage increased and effective participation of its organized private sector in trade negotiations?
- iii. What is the level of understanding of SPS standards and other technical standards among agricultural producers in Nigeria?

1.4 Scope of the Research

To respond to the questions developed for this study, the preliminary review of literature highlights some key areas that need to be explored in more detail. These areas are as follows:

- a. Understanding of SPS and other technical standards by agricultural producers in Nigeria
- b. Nigeria's engagement with the DSU
- c. Nature of trade policy infrastructure in Nigeria
- d. Africa Free Trade Agreement and implications for Nigeria's agriculture sector
- e. Trade institutions in Nigeria

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

1.5 Overview of Research Methodology

This section summarizes the methodology to be used in conducting this research. A detailed discussion of the methodology is provided subsequently in this research. This research employed the positivist and interpretivist paradigm. The positivist paradigm enables the researcher to use quantitative approaches to assess agro-producers' understanding of the requirements for export of agricultural commodities. On the other hand, this research will also employ the interpretivist research paradigm because it accommodates the human-interest element (Collis & Hussey, 2005). International trade is a human-interest issue that impacts societies on a collective level. Furthermore, trade issues usually involve diverse interests and arguably a zero-sum game that demands a qualitative approach to understanding the issues raised in the research questions especially those dealing with the disadvantages that African countries face in trade negotiations and disputes compared to their developed counterparts. Based on the mercantilist theory of trade, trade is a zero-sum game as one country's trade surplus is another's trade deficit as evidenced by the trade relations between the US and China (Aher, 2022). The US's goods trade gap with China widened by \$29.4 billion to \$382.9 billion in 2022 (Cash, 2023). Furthermore, the Political Economy Analysis (PEA) framework which is used for national-level analysis will be adapted and used to understudy the power dynamics that exist in the WTO and how these dynamics influence the form and perceived outcomes of its legal instruments especially the DSU.

The case study design will also be used in this research. Using the case study design provides a practical approach for investigating how African countries have engaged with the WTO's dispute resolution mechanisms and helps to narrow the scope of this study. In this sense, Nigeria is the case study for this research and will form the basis for exploring the range of issues posed by the research questions. Saunders et al., (2005) suggest that the case study design offers the opportunity to conduct an empirical investigation of an issue. In this case, Nigeria is the case study for examining the challenges that developing countries face with respect to the WTO's dispute resolution mechanisms and how these can be addressed to improve their export of agricultural commodities.

Both primary and secondary data will be collected and analyzed in this research. The primary data will be collected through Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) with officials in the Trade Negotiations Office of FMITI, the Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC), government representatives at the WTO, and exporters of agricultural commodities. The desk review aspect of this research will involve secondary data accessed from relevant policy documents obtained from the FMITI, documents and publications by the NIPC, the

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

mandate documents of the DSU, academic journals, previous decisions reached by the DSU where Nigeria is deemed to have substantial interest, trade agreements, and other relevant documents dealing with dispute resolution at the WTO. The desk review will also involve understudying the trade policy documents of developed member countries with a view to identifying what Nigeria needs to do right to improve its trade policy infrastructure.

1.6 Structure of the Thesis

This doctorate thesis consists of eight chapters with each chapter addressing a specific requirement for the research (see Figure 1.4). The first chapter is the introductory chapter for the research and discusses the background of the study using relevant information and statistical data around Nigeria's foreign trade and its engagement with the WTO as a member country. The background of study section also provides a brief situational overview of African countries' engagement with the WTO's dispute settlement system, overview of the structure of the Nigerian economy, and overview of the recently ratified African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement (AfCFTA). This chapter also outlines the study aim, study objectives, scope of the study, and overview of research methodology.

The second chapter of the thesis discusses the legal and institutional framework for international trade. The discussions provide an overview of how the WTO emerged from the previous GATT regime -including its membership structure- coupled with outlining the objectives and functions of the WTO. This chapter also looks at decision-making processes within the WTO from two main perspectives namely: theoretical and practical perspectives. Another issue discussed concerns the laws and rules of the WTO including citing examples of compliance and non-compliance by member countries. This chapter also discusses rules and procedures for settlement of trade disputes between member countries. It further presents and discusses relevant literature about the WTO's dispute settlement system (DSS) framework. Issues discussed include: the role of litigation and negotiation in the settlement of trade disputes between member countries; the DSS's operational framework; the DSS's operational processes including steps in the dispute settlement process; adjustments that have been made to the DSS over the years to improve its effectiveness as a veritable settlement mechanism for trade disputes; and challenges with the DSU. This chapter concludes by examining the degree to which developing countries have utilized or engaged with the DSS with emphasis on the experience of African countries including Nigeria.

Chapter three contains the theoretical framework for the research. Using relevant literature, this chapter presents and discusses some relevant theories of international trade as a basis for formalizing the theoretical framework for the research. The theories

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

discussed are: transaction cost theory; economics of non-tariff measures; new trade theory; strategic trade and resource dumping; theory of country size; theory of mercantilism; and the agency theory. The agency theory or principal-agent perspective is discussed in added detail as it is the chosen theory for this research. This chapter also discusses the roles and responsibilities of trade-related institutions and stakeholders in Nigeria's trade environment (i.e. downstream, midstream and upstream). Further, the researcher developed a three Is framework (i.e. Identification, Investigation and Initiation). The chapter concludes by evaluating the effectiveness of the WTO's DSU in settling trade disputes between member countries over the years.

Chapter four presents and discusses the methodology used to conduct the research. Discussions looked at the study approach, study design, sampling approaches, methods for collecting and analyzing data. This chapter also develops and discusses the hypotheses developed for the research including addressing the issues of validity, reliability, and generalizability. The chapter concludes by discussing the study's limitations alongside the required ethical considerations given the use of primary data to conduct the research.

Chapter five presents and analyses quantitative data collected for the study. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze responses to the questionnaires shared to the sample for the downstream segment of Nigeria's trade environment. The chapter concludes with a discussion of findings from the range of analyses conducted. The results from the analyses are triangulated with the analyses of responses from the focus group and Key Informant Interviews (KIIs). These analyses also inform the discussions conducted in the concluding chapter.

Chapter six presents and analyses qualitative data collected for the study. Here, feedback from the focus group discussions conducted with representatives of relevant trade institutions in Nigeria (midstream) were presented and analyzed. Participants in the focus group discussions were drawn from relevant national trade institutions including Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD), the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment (FMITI), Nigerian Agricultural Quarantine Services (NAQS), the Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC), Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON), and the National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC).

Chapter seven presents and analyses feedback collected from the Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) conducted with the midstream and upstream segment of Nigeria's trade ecosystem.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Chapter eight contains the conclusions and recommendations of the research. This chapter presents and discusses the key findings of the study while demonstrating how they meet the study's objectives. In addition, this chapter uses some of the gaps and critical concerns identified during the study to suggest areas of future research while highlighting the contributions of the research to the trade discourse.

Figure 1.4: Schematic Diagram of Thesis Structure

Source: Author (2024)

1.7 Synopsis of Literature Review

This section of the chapter presents a synopsis of the literature review for this thesis. It presents an overview of the some key issues that are discussed subsequently in the detailed literature review chapters including the WTO trade dispute resolution, challenges with developing countries' engagement with the DSU, overview of the Nigerian economy, and the African Continental Free Trade Agreement.

1.7.1 Trade Dispute Resolution: Overview

The WTO's dispute settlement system is widely regarded as one of the central pillars of the multilateral trading system. The credibility of the WTO as a multilateral institution is largely derived from its capacity to enforce commitments entered by its members. In fact, Article 3.2 of the Dispute Settlement Understanding provides that the dispute settlement mechanism is a central element in providing security and predictability to the multilateral trading system. Since coming to existence in 1995 following negotiations at the Uruguay Round, there has been a proliferation of bilateral trade disputes. As of 31 December 2021, WTO members referred 607 disputes to the Dispute Settlement Body. Not all of these disputes required formal rulings to resolve them.² For one, the specificity of the DSU and increased membership of the WTO over the years partly accounts for the volume of cases filed under this instrument.

Narayanan (2003) notes that the DSU is here to stay especially as it addresses the perceived weaknesses of the GATT's dispute settlement system. Some of these weaknesses were systemic in nature; for one, the GATT's dispute resolution system places more focus on diplomacy, positive consensus, and negotiation. As a result, any party to a dispute under the GATT arrangement could at any stage block the process coupled with the lack of deadlines for the settlement process (Alavi, 2007). These systemic issues were discussed during the Uruguay Round by members leading to resolutions for the establishment of a formalized rule-based system to address the specificity of cases filed by parties to a dispute and emerging trade areas such as 'services' and 'intellectual property'. It is necessary to note that the US has always been in favour of a rule-based approach to dispute settlement compared to the European Union that favours a diplomatic approach.

Countries involved in negotiations for the establishment and formalization of the DSU had two main objectives in mind: one, the DSU should be able to issue mandatory rulings and have the organizational structure to address the increased range and complexity of trade-related issues; and two, the inclusion of Special Differential Treatment (SDT) for developing and least developed countries in consideration of developmental intentions of international trade (Sitonik, 2017). It is necessary to note that African nations were in support of the rule-based approach of the DSU at the time of its inception –mainly because of what they saw as a perceived advantage emanating from SDT provisions–without much thought to the challenges they would face in the future.

² WTO (2021) Dispute Settlement Activity – Some Figures. Accessed from: https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/dispu_e/dispustats_e.htm [10 April 2023]

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

It is the challenges that are associated with the DSU that have informed this research especially as African countries including Nigeria have fallen short when it comes to engaging with and participating in DSU processes. In fact, only two countries stand out when it comes to engaging with the DSU's processes: South Africa and Egypt and understandably so, given that both countries are among the second and third largest economies in Africa respectively by their Gross Domestic Product (GDP).³ With a total GDP of \$432.3 billion, Nigeria has become the biggest economy on the African continent over the last 30 years (Zandt, 2021) yet, it has never filed a case with the DSU.⁴ South Africa and Egypt are way ahead in this regard because of their diversified economies unlike Nigeria where crude oil accounts for 90% of its exports (Bown, 2005).⁵ In this respect, the more diversified a country's economy, the more likely it is to engage actively with the DSU to resolve disputes with trade partners. Having said this, Nigeria is at a crossroads especially considering that one of the main policy thrusts of the current administration's Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP)⁶ focuses on the diversification of the Nigerian economy from crude oil exports to export of agricultural commodities (Federal Ministry of Budget & National Planning, 2020). The capacity to achieve this depends on its trade infrastructure especially in relation to its capacity to leverage the DSU to address the barriers and other supply-side constraints that its agricultural producers face in the global market.

1.7.2 Developing Countries and DSU: Overview of Challenges

Several studies have been carried out to examine the constraints limiting African countries from actively engaging with the dispute settlement processes of the WTO. Some of these studies are focused on 'how the DSU is used' with limited emphasis on 'why it has not been used' (Horlick, 2005; Sionik, 2017). This research builds on existing knowledge by placing more emphasis on why it has not been optimally exploited by developing countries to address trade disputes and market access barriers faced by their agricultural commodities. These studies consider different aspects of the problem including power dynamics, complexity of WTO agreements and DSU procedures, legal costs, retaliatory capacity, access to information, and the quality of trade infrastructure.

³ South Africa has a GDP of US\$340bn and Egypt's GDP is US\$270bn according to UNCTAD's 2018 Economic Development in Africa report.

⁴ Nigeria had a GDP of about US\$440bn in 2021 according to Statista.

⁵ Statista (2022) Oil industry in Nigeria: statistics and figures. Accessed from: <https://www.statista.com/topics/6914/oil-industry-in-nigeria/#topicOverview> [13 April 2023]

⁶ The Plan (ERGP) focuses on achieving macroeconomic stability and economic diversification. Macroeconomic stability will be achieved by undertaking fiscal stimulus, ensuring monetary stability and improving the external balance of trade. Similarly, to achieve economic diversification, policy focus will be on the key sectors driving and enabling economic growth, with particular focus on agriculture, energy and MSME led growth in industry, manufacturing and key services by leveraging science and technology.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

These factors will be addressed in more detail in this research with particular focus on Nigeria. Since its inception in 1995, questions have been raised about the degree to which the DSU has been supportive to the interests of African countries.

With respect to power dynamics, Modlin (2019), for instance, notes that a country's share of global trade and the volume of traded products and services is a determinant of their participation in DSU processes. The reasoning here is that the probability of encountering disputable trade measures is proportional to the degree to which a country's export portfolio is diversified (Cepal, 2014). Basically, countries with a diversified export portfolio are more likely to submit more cases to the DSU than countries with a smaller or narrow export portfolio. This explains why Egypt and South Africa are the few countries in Africa that have pursued litigation against trade disputes through the DSU. Even at that, cases filed by both countries represent about 3% of the total cases filed by member countries with developed and larger countries accounting for about 80% of cases filed with the DSU. In fact, statistically, only 36 per cent of all the cases submitted under WTO dispute settlement system are from developing countries between 1995 and 2001 (Razaranaina, 2022). Most of their requests are for consultations, they constitute over two thirds of the requests for consultation. The countries that are most active in the dispute settlement system are Brazil, India, Mexico, Thailand, and Chile. Added to this, most developing countries do not have a permanent representative in Geneva while all developed countries do.

Furthermore, with respect to power dynamics, Gokmen et al., (2020) note that global trade is dominated by larger and more powerful countries such as the United States, the European Union member countries, China, etc. Consequently, these countries possess the capacity to influence the trajectory of global trade arrangements in their favour to the detriment of smaller less powerful countries. Contrastingly, Horn et al., (1999) downplays the level of importance of power relationships in explaining the limited participation of developing countries in the DSU. Having said, Cepal (2014) raised concerns about Horn et al., (1999)'s position on limited emphasis of power dynamics in explaining developing countries' limited participation in the DSU's upstream and downstream processes.⁷ Moreover, Horn et al., (1999) ignore the tendency of developing countries to pick their fights especially as some of them already receive or enjoy special or preferential bilateral trade arrangements with some larger countries and as such, are less willing to file complaints that may put such arrangements at risk. Despite this, Alavi (2007) notes that

⁷ Upstream activities involve consultations and other activities such as the processes of documenting a trade dispute before a case is filed. On the other hand, downstream activities characterize the activities that happen when a case is officially filed with the DSU. Usually, downstream activities are triggered by the concerned parties –especially the plaintiff- when consultations fail to resolve the specific trade dispute.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

the Special and Differential Treatment (SDT) provisions in the DSU have not yielded considerable benefits to developing countries thus, leaving them as bystanders. This is because at the point of formalizing the DSU, member countries failed to operationalize SDT provisions leaving them open to varying interpretation by concerned member countries especially developed countries. These observations raise questions about whether underlying power dynamics influence the outcomes of cases and recommendations adjudicated and proffered by the Appellate body and panels.

While the rule-based approach was welcomed and formalized by member countries at the Uruguay Round, few of them –particularly African countries- could have anticipated the increased complexity of this instrument with the nature and frequency of cases filed over the years since the DSU's inception in 1995. Reich (2017) suggests that one of the main issues with the DSU is that it has become too technically complex and demanding for African countries to use effectively in the absence of sufficient legal assistance and trade policy infrastructure. Underlying this is the observation by Busch & Reinhardt (2003) that there is too much focus on law and less emphasis on politics. Weak trade policy infrastructures, shortage of trained personnel (i.e. skilled trade experts and lawyers), and lack of knowledge about how the WTO and its instruments characterize the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment (FMITI) in Nigeria, and this has restricted the country's ability to navigate barriers to export of some of its agricultural commodities to international markets. WTO agreements are too complex and voluminous that in the absence of the requisite technical expertise, developing countries are deterred from engaging the DSU to address trade disputes. This also raises cost implications for many African countries who lack the significant financial resources needed to engage international law firms to pursue litigation on their behalf.

The weight of legal costs coupled with the legal capacity of each country to support these costs influence the resolution of disputes filed through the DSU (Breuss, 2001; Bown, 2003; Reich, 2017). Trade-related litigation usually takes considerable amount of time thus, protracted legal procedures generate significant costs for the plaintiff and defendant. Such costs can be unbearable for many African countries especially those that are aid-dependent. Furthermore, lack of institutional leakages between government and private sector in many developing countries mean that there is limited incentive for the government to pursue litigation as it would bear the legal costs alone. The situation is different for developed countries where the filing and pursuit of cases through the DSU is largely at the instance of private sector companies, some of whom are multinational corporations that can afford the legal costs associated with litigation. To put this into

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

proper perspective, lawyers for Kodak and Fuji in the *Japan-Photographic Film case* respectively charged their clients fees in excess of US\$10mn.

What is clear from this is that the prohibitive rates charged by international law firms with the requisite expertise in trade law and adjudication –usually based in Washington and Brussels- deter many African countries from filing cases through the DSU. This situation is worsened by the non-membership of the WTO's Advisory Centre by many of them (Reich, 2017). For many African countries, including Nigeria, it would simply make no sense for them to spend such huge amounts when the total value of their export of a specific commodity may not significantly be in excess of the legal fees, they would incur especially considering their minute share of the global trade market. Furthermore, Shaffer (2003) notes that the inability of many African countries to muster or mobilize the resources needed to pursue litigation makes them not to be taken seriously when they threaten to resort to the DSU.

Related to the challenge of legal costs are costs associated with access to information. Sufficient information is needed to build a case against the defendant; this information includes information about the defendant's proposed approach to responding to such a case. Essentially, Hoekman and Mavroidis (2000) note that asymmetry in access to information on litigation and DSU-specific legal procedures also places African countries at a disadvantage. Following from this is the inability of African countries to identify suspicious trade barriers and prepare an appropriate response. In response to associated gaps in legal capacity and trade policy infrastructure, some African countries have either established or collaborated with international NGOs –based in Brussels, Geneva or Washington- to support them with addressing trade disputes. This route has yet to yield significant results in terms of the outcomes of trade agreements and cases and understandably so. The problem is that some of these NGOs –given their developmental focus- are more advocacy-based and as such, lack the technical capacity to navigate the specific and complex legal procedures of the DSU.

Another factor that has stifled the participation of African countries in the DSU concerns the effectiveness of economic retaliatory measures (Davey, 2009). Should cases submitted to the DSU proceed to the end, there could be rulings and recommendations in favour of the plaintiff taking economic retaliatory measures against the defendant. There are different economic retaliatory measures that can be taken by affected parties including imposing higher tariffs (Chang, 2002). Economic retaliation ought to be one of the effective punitive measures for getting parties in a dispute to act accordingly, especially in relation to decisions reached by the Appellate body. Experience shows that such measures are ineffective, especially in relation to less powerful countries. The nature

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

of a trade dispute, chances of winning and implementation of award, a country's negotiating influence/power and its capacity to retaliate can also impact its ability to realize the full benefits of WTO DSU participation.

As noted earlier, African countries usually have bilateral trade agreements with the parties that they have a dispute against and as such, could be reluctant to initiate any form of economic retaliatory measure which could potentially put such agreements at risk. Kessie & Addo (2002) suggest that African countries lack the incentive or motivation to institute proceedings at the WTO considering that majority of their exports already receive preferential treatment in some of their major export markets, i.e. the Europe and the United States. These preferential measures –such as the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) and the Cotonou Agreement- are largely non-reciprocal and could be revoked at any time by the country providing the preferential treatment and are under no obligation to give any reason for such decision.

While the weak capacity of African countries reinforces the perceived ineffectiveness of retaliatory measures, it is equally important to note that developed countries also face the same challenge. The potential trade war between China and the US highlights this observation. It remains to be seen as to how the WTO can intervene to resolve this situation especially considering the hardline hawkish stance of the previous Trump and current Biden administration to negotiations. Consequently, it appears to be more effective to utilize consultations or bilateral negotiations to resolve trade disputes than relying on economic retaliation. Given that consultations or bilateral negotiations between parties to a trade dispute can be more effective in resolving trade disputes, questions arise as to why African countries have not adequately exploited the consultative phase to resolve the trade challenges that they face in international markets. Addressing these questions will entail, amongst other things, exploring the information asymmetry that exists –from African countries' perspective- when it comes to access to information about illegal trade practices. More specifically, the research will explore if and what national procedures exist to obtain and collect information about the trade practices of trade partners.

Another factor that has stifled the participation of African countries in the DSU concerns 'non-tariff barriers' such as Sanitary and Phytosanitary standards (SPS)⁸ which may not be evidence-based. AfreximBank (2020) defines non-tariff trade barriers as measures

⁸ According to the WTO, The SPS Agreement allows WTO members to set their own standards on food safety and animal and plant health. But these standards must be based on science, applied only to the extent necessary to protect human, animal or plant life or health, and not arbitrarily or unjustifiably discriminate between countries where identical or similar conditions prevail.

THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS

that fall outside the scope of ordinary custom tariffs but have an adverse effect on trade flows between countries. These usually include certain traditional trade policy instruments such as trade quotas, import restriction, sanitary and phytosanitary standards with the potential to limit imports from trading partners. In certain occasions, these non-tariff barriers are used by the implementing country to achieve certain policy objectives such as protecting certain industries, protecting the health of citizens, reducing environmental risks etc. Having said this, it is equally important to note that these non-tariff barriers can be protectionist in nature depending on how they are applied by the implementing country. UNCTAD (2018) notes that technical barriers to trade, and sanitary and phytosanitary measures account for the largest share of non-tariff measures and valorem tariff equivalents for most product categories. In addition to the complexity of these measures that often makes interpretation challenging for the exporting country concerned, they impose disproportionately increased trade costs on informal and formal traders, who may lack the capacity to comply with technical requirements. AfreximBank (2020) notes that these technical barriers form the largest restriction of access for agricultural exports from developing countries, especially African countries. The challenge associated with interpreting these technical requirements also makes it challenging for some developing countries to provide the necessary evidence required to sufficiently prepare their case and process complaints through the WTO's DSU. Having provided an overview of the challenges associated with developing countries' engagement with the DSU, the next section offers an overview of the structure of the Nigerian economy.

1.7.3 The Nigeria Economy: Structural Considerations

Nigeria is one of the countries in West Africa and assumed the status of being the largest economy in Africa after the GDP rebasing exercise in 2014. In 2022, Nigeria's GDP was US\$472bn (Statista, 2022). Following the rebasing exercise, the structure of the Nigerian economy underwent significant transformation especially with respect to its sectoral structure. For one, oil and gas –which was the largest sector of its economy and source of 90% of its foreign exchange revenues- has now been superseded by the services sector particularly telecoms and banking. In fact, between the period 2011 and 2021, the services sector contributed the most to Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as highlighted in Figure 1.1. In 2022, the services sector contributed 43.79% to Nigeria's GDP compared to 31.41% and 23.36% for industry and agriculture sectors respectively (Statista, 2023). This is the reason why the recent administration of President Muhammadu Buhari hinged its economic development agenda on the diversification of Nigeria's economy from dependence on oil and gas through the expansion of the agriculture sector including driving the growth of agriculture-related exports.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Figure 1.1: Structure of the Nigerian economy by sector (2011-2021) based on % of GDP at current basic enterprises

Source: Statista (2021)

Based on the information contained in Figure 1.1, the services sector has been a major contributor to Nigeria's GDP over the years; however, the country remains heavily dependent on the oil and gas sector especially for foreign exchange inflows. High dependence on oil production is a critical variable in the contraction or slowdown of the Nigerian economy. A steep decline in oil production in 2013, caused by militancy and youth restiveness, in the oil-rich Niger Delta region, further decreased Nigeria's revenues from oil from 23% in 2011 to 7% in 2013 (PwC, 2019).

The economy is also characterized by significant fiscal risks. Barring 2011 when the country recorded a budget surplus from record high crude oil prices, Nigeria has operated a budget deficit since 2012 to 2022 (PwC, 2020). The heavy dependence on oil and gas exposes the country's public finances to external shocks; for instance, its public revenues declined significantly between 2011 and 2015 because of the sharp decline in the oil and gas sector's contribution to the economy from 23% of GDP in 2011 to 4% of GDP in 2015 (WTO Trade Policy Review, 2017). According to the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the country recorded N6.4tn deficit in 2021 equivalent to 2% of GDP, i.e. this takes Nigeria's aggregate debt-to-GDP ratio to 14%.⁹ Although its debt-to-GDP ratio is not extreme by global standards, the main concern stems from its capacity to sustain such

⁹ IMF, Nigeria: Country Report, 2016.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

deficit given declining public revenues. To put things into proper perspective, interest payments on existing debt consume 40% of federal government revenue raising concerns about its capacity to sustain public debt. Given these concerns, in 2016, the IMF advised the government to increase its non-oil revenues (e.g. income from corporate tax, federation account levies, value added tax (VAT), customs and excise duties etc) to enhance fiscal sustainability while maintaining infrastructure and expenditure on social/public services. In response to this, the federal government recently signed the 'Finance Bill' into law which paved the way for an increase in VAT rate from 5% to 7.5% (Deloitte, 2019).

The passage of the Finance Bill into law comes on the heels of the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP) which seeks to increase the agricultural sector's share of GDP designed to position the country to export more agricultural commodities. While the ERGP has been greeted with so much optimism, the actualization of its policy objectives hinges on external considerations, most of which are outside the control of the government. For one, the government's inability to exploit the WTO's dispute resolution mechanism to address the barriers that its agricultural commodities face in foreign markets has hampered desired outcomes from the policy. This issue is discussed subsequently in the third chapter although briefly discussed in section 1. The ERGP is designed to reduce Nigeria's excessive dependence on revenues from crude oil which has not resulted in significant economic development despite over four decades of oil exploration. Otaha (2012) notes that the revenue that Nigeria generates when oil prices are high tends to cause "Dutch-Disease", high oil revenue raises exchange rates, promotes an adverse balance of payments when prices fall, reduce the incentive to risk investment in non-oil sectors like agriculture and manufacturing. It is hoped that effective implementation of the ERGP should diversify the country's economy from its dependence on revenues from oil to non-oil exports, particularly export of agricultural commodities.

1.7.3.1 Foreign Direct Investment

Over the years, there has been significant foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows into critical sectors of the economy. Some of these inflows have followed significant reforms implemented by different administrations in the country. For instance, the deregulation of the telecommunications sector in 1999 resulted in significant investment inflows into the sector that deepened mobile telephony across the country (Templars Law, 2002). Another reform that has contributed to significant FDI inflows into the country is the consolidation of the banking sector in 2005 by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). Jeroh & Okoye (2015) notes that the consolidation exercise strengthened the banking sector by making it more

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA’S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

resilient to liquidity risks that contributed to the collapse of several banks during the pre-consolidation era.

Some of the major sources of FDI inflows for Nigeria include the United States, United Kingdom, India, China, Canada, and France. For instance, there has been a growth in trade between India and Nigeria reaching about US\$15bn in 2021 motivated by a Double Tax Treaty arrangement (Observatory of Economic Complexity, 2021). In fact, the value of Nigeria’s exports to India was about US\$9bn in 2021 according to a report by the Observatory of Economic Complexity (OEC).

1.7.3.2 Power

The entire value chain of the Nigerian electricity industry from power generation to distribution is almost completely privatized. Currently, there are 23 grid-connected power generating plants operating across the six geopolitical regions of the country with installed capacity of about 10,000MW and available capacity of 6,000MW (Nigeria Electricity Regulatory Commission, 2022). It is essential to note that progress in improving the quality of power supply since the deregulation of the sector has been slow owing to several factors including: limited technical capacity among power distribution companies, poor distribution and transmission infrastructure, power theft as a result of high numbers of unmetered customers, limited access to much needed capital to improve distribution networks, and revenue leakages amongst power distribution companies (PwC, 2014). In response to the need for much needed investment in the power sector, two agreements were signed involving the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), key players in the sector, Deposit Money Banks (DMBs), and the National Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC). Both agreements are intended to provide financial support to power generation companies (GENCOs) and power distribution companies (DISCOs) through the Nigerian Electricity Market Stabilization Facility (NEMSF).¹⁰

1.7.3.3 Employment

According to Statista (2022), “the unemployment rate in Nigeria reached 32.5% and was projected to reach 35% by the end of 2023”. With the labour force reclassification carried out by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) in 2021, youth unemployment rate was about 38% at the end of 2021. The informal sector accounts for most of the employment

¹⁰ The Nigeria Electricity Market Stabilization Facility (NEMSF) -spearheaded by the CBN and the NERC- aims at settling outstanding payment obligations due to market participants, service providers and gas suppliers that accrued during the Interim Rules Period (IRP Debts) as well as the Legacy Gas Debts of the Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN) generation companies owed to gas suppliers and the Nigeria Gas Company (NGC) which have been transferred to the Nigeria Electricity Liability Management Company Limited (NELMCO). Overall, the NEMSF seeks to place the Nigerian Electricity sector on a part to economic viability and sustainability following its privatization in 2013.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

while the formal sector accounted for 10% of jobs in the country (World Bank, 2021). The country's workforce mainly consists of informal workers, i.e. four out of five workers have informal employment, many of whom work in agriculture and retail. Furthermore, there is also a high level of contractual work across the labour market coupled with weak enforcement of labour laws in both the informal and formal sectors; although this situation is more prevalent in the informal sector (Bandura & Hammond, 2018). Recently, the minimum wage in the country at NGN30,000 or US\$70 monthly was raised on account of sustained negotiations between the Federal Government and the Labour Unions in response to soaring inflation which was about 33% at the end of the 4th Quarter of 2024.

1.7.3.4 Business and Investment Environment

According to the 2022 World Bank's Ease of Doing Business Ranking, "Nigeria ranked 131 out of 190 countries sampled in the ease of doing business". While this represents a slight improvement from being ranked 148 in 2018, it highlights the significant challenges of doing business in Nigeria. Several factors have been highlighted as being responsible for Nigeria's poor ease of doing business ranking including: epileptic power supply, high levels of corruption, poor road infrastructure, policy inconsistency contributing to heightened regulatory risks, high levels of insecurity, limited skilled workforce etc (Pwc 2022). In fact, a report by the UK Department of International Trade and Overseas Business notes that, "the Nigerian economy is characterized by extreme inequality and significant economic disparities between the Northern and Southern parts of the country, poor infrastructure, a complex and opaque regulatory environment, high levels of corruption, and a burgeoning population" (Foreign & Commonwealth Development Organization, 2022)

Although the previous administration of President Muhammadu Buhari implemented different policies and programmes, such as the 2017 Economic Growth and Recovery Plan (EGRP), to improve the business climate for domestic and foreign businesses, there is still need to improve standards at all levels in both the private and public sectors. The need to improve standards should also be enforced for products imported into and exported out of the country. Again, the issue of complex and opaque regulation coupled with multiple taxation can be addressed by solving the challenge of overlapping mandates amongst statutory or regulatory agencies that add to the cost of doing business in Nigeria.

1.7.4 Africa Continental Free Trade Agreement (AfCTA)

The main objective of the African Free Trade Agreement (AfCTA) is to contribute to the economic transformation of Africa by stimulating intra-continental trade and driving

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

industrialization. Whether this can be achieved, given structural constraints, remains to be seen. So far, AU member countries –including Nigeria- have signed up to the agreement, which proposes the creation of a pan-African single market and subsequently, the creation of a single customs union (AfCFTA, 2023). Before providing an overview of the potential costs and benefits to the country, it is essential to provide an overview of Africa's trade and Nigeria's trade with Africa. The aggregate trade in goods by Africa countries in 2017 was US\$930.65bn consisting of US\$504.17bn of imports and US\$427bn of exports (International Trade Center, 2017). Although Africa's aggregate trade in commodities increased by 17% in 2017, it remained well below the US\$1.1tn recorded in 2014. In similar vein, the percentage of Africa in global trade reduced from 2.95% in 2015 to 2.63% in 2017 (UNCTAD, 2019). Furthermore, at the continental level, intra-African trade in commodities was US\$135bn in 2017, representing only 15% of Africa's aggregate trade. This implies that more than 85% of Africa's aggregate trade (i.e. exports and imports) was with countries outside the continent. This contrasts sharply with the intra-EU trade (69.8%), intra-American trade (46%) and intra-Asian trade (59.6%) ((Presidential Committee on Impact & Readiness Assessment of AFCTA, 2019). Specifically, in terms of trade at the regional economic community level, SADC¹¹ accounted for 35% of Africa's global trade and 54% of intra-African trade in 2017. This was followed by COMESA¹² with 26% share each of Africa's global and intra-African trade (Presidential Committee on Impact & Readiness Assessment of AFCTA, 2019).

The top 10 most traded products among African countries are: natural gas, crude oil, refined petroleum products, gold and non-industrial diamonds, frozen fish, ships and light vessels, sugar, vehicles, and cement. Figure 1.2 outlines the top African trading countries categorized by amount of trade exports with other African countries and exports with the rest of the world. Based on the information in Figure 1, Nigeria makes the list of the top 10 intra-African exporters between 2020 and 2021. According to the International Trade Center (ITC), in 2020, the top 10 exporters in Africa were South Africa, Nigeria, Morocco, Egypt, Algeria, Angola, Ghana, DR Congo, Tunisia, and Cote d'Ivoire. These top 10 countries exported \$271 billion (70% of total African exports) worth of goods and services in 2020. The other African countries exported an additional \$117.25 billion in the same year. As shown in Figure 1, with an export value of \$85.69 billion, the resource abundant South Africa was the top exporter and contributed to over 20% of the total exports from Africa.

¹¹ SADC – Southern Africa Development Committee

¹² COMESA – Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 1.2: Top ten African Trading Countries (2020-2021)

Source: International Trading Center (2020)

As noted earlier in this chapter, the Nigerian economy is dominated by services (i.e. telecommunications, finance, business, education, recreation, tourism, transportation, etc.) accounting for 44% of the country's GDP in 2021, followed by agriculture (25%), manufacturing (9%), and mining & quarrying (8.8%). Trade between Nigeria and the rest of Africa stood at US\$6.3bn in 2020, representing 8% of its aggregate trade in commodities, making the country the 4th highest intra-African trader in commodities after South Africa (US\$23.3bn). According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2017), the major destinations of Nigeria's commodities in Africa include Cameroun, South Africa, Togo, Cote d'Ivoire, Egypt, and Swaziland. On the other hand, the main commodities that Nigeria imports from other African countries include fertilizers, refined petroleum products, chemicals, frozen meat and fish, apples, and palm oil (NBS, 2021).

When the numbers are looked at in added detail (Figure 1.2), the trade between African countries is much lower than the trade with the rest of the world. For example, only \$19.80 billion (23%) of the South African exports were destined for African countries, whereas South Africa exported \$65.89 billion worth of goods and services to non-African countries. The same situation can be observed in almost all African countries. The intra-African trade between the top 10 African exporters was only \$44.75 billion, about 16.5% of the total African exports. Similarly, for the rest of the African countries the intra-African trade was about \$23.93 billion, responding to 21% of the total exports. In the same year,

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

European countries exported \$6.5 trillion worth of goods and services, where \$4.5 trillion of this trade (69%) happened with each other. Those numbers suggest that the trade potential between African countries is way underutilized.

Figure 1.3: Evolution of Nigerian Exports (2010 to 2022)

Source: World Bank

Having provided an overview of Nigeria's trade in Africa, it is now time to explore the case for regional trade blocs after which its benefits and costs to the country is discussed. Economic transformation is critical for sustained economic development as it supports wealth creation, job creation, and improvements in the livelihoods of a country's citizens. Having said this, McMillan et al., (2017) note that rapid economic development alone cannot guarantee development as the quality of growth matters as much as magnitude. This is understandable especially considering that growth in few primary products may not imply improvements in productivity, which is the main origin of improved livelihoods. Jouanjean et al., (2015) suggest that this increased economic productivity hinges on the expansion of trade and investment. Furthermore, there is a regional dimension to improvements in national economic productivity as economic activities need to be regionally and globally competitive as countries do not operate in a vacuum. Positioning production structures for export enables a country to access significant markets which will make it easier to reach minimum efficient scales of production. Melitz (2003) and Girma

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

et al., (2004) note that there is a positive correlation between productivity and export growth.

The AfCFTA also encourages competition between member countries. Facilitating imports via tariff reduction and non-tariff barriers (NTB) also introduces competition in the domestic market that will benefit organizations by enabling them to source inputs –with limited restrictions- from countries that are party to a regional trade agreement. This observation is at the core of the improvements in national economic productivity stemming from regional trade agreements. Furthermore, competition –stemming from regional trade arrangements- will introduce incentives in business organizations to remain competitive by producing innovative products and services. This is also beneficial to consumers especially as they will be exposed to a variety of cheaper and quality products from different countries or sources. While these observations highlight the potential positive outcomes from regional trade arrangements, it is not easy to implement a generalized unilateral trade reform because varying groups might be impacted differently, and complementary economic policies (i.e. fiscal and monetary) are needed to enhance the benefits whilst reducing the costs of regional trade arrangements. This observation is critical with respect to the efficacy of the AfCFTA and remains unclear as to what trade reforms have been implemented by parties to the agreement to reduce the costs to all those involved. Again, it remains unclear as to what comparative advantages –especially on a sectoral level- will be explored to improve the net benefits to member countries.

1.7.4.1 Potential Benefits of the AfCFTA

Having explored critical considerations for developing or entering regional trade arrangements, it is now time to explore some of the potential benefits for such arrangements with particular emphasis on the AfCFTA. These are briefly discussed in this section with more detailed discussions conducted subsequently in this research. As mentioned earlier, the overriding outcome of the AfCFTA is, “to contribute to the economic transformation of Africa by stimulating intra-continental trade and driving industrialization. With 55 member countries, a combined GDP of \$2.4-trillion and a total population of 1.2 billion, the agreement will create the world’s largest free trade area. Its aim is to promote trade between African countries, which is abysmally low at 16% as at 2017 (NBS, 2018).

Investment Growth

One of the potential benefits of regional trade arrangements to countries, such as Nigeria, is investment growth. Exposure to a larger market is more appealing to domestic and foreign investors as investment opportunities increase. Foreign markets offer firms opportunities to increase sales of existing products whilst providing them with information

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

and other inputs that they require to develop new product or service lines. For Nigeria, the AfCTA offers opportunities for the Nigerian government to increase investments by its public and private sector organizations in other African countries with more ease. This is because the agreement aims to encourage investment by establishing provisions that enhance access to the relevant information and transparency of domestic regulatory frameworks. The agreement also contains provisions that offers protection to investments by Nigerian organizations, decreasing associated risks and, consequently, resulting in an increase in investments. It is expected that both inward and outward investments will contribute to improving the productivity of Nigerian businesses which in turn should have a positive effect on GDP. For once, inward investments bring about the capital and technical expertise needed to boost labour productivity while outward investments, on the other hand, helps in consolidating the domestic production profile including the potential for integrating into regional value chains.

Expansion of Trade

The AfCTA offers Nigeria the opportunity to expand its exports in other non-oil products, such as agricultural commodities. This should benefit its economy regardless of the efficiency of product and service-based firms. The elimination of trade barriers and tariffs which the AfCTA seeks to achieve should lead to improvements in exports that will contribute to increased efficiency in certain firms and consolidate their position in others. Products that were challenging to export prior to the AfCTA, because of high tariffs, may be competitive after the tariff is removed post-AfCTA. Essentially, if product-based companies are efficient suppliers, for instance, the AfCTA should increase exports and consolidate the position of Nigeria in that market. Its efficiency guarantees that additional liberalization by the partner country will not affect it significantly as it is likely that it will be able to match whatever preferential market a third country may have in the partner country. Balchin et al., (2018) suggest that the capacity of member countries to a regional agreement to benefit from increased trade opportunities offered by the agreement depends on the efficiency of firms in respective countries. The same applies to Nigeria where the efficiency has been called to the question by business associations and pressure groups. This is why national trade reforms are needed to enhance the comparative advantage of local businesses.

From a policy perspective, the opportunity to expand export is key to the federal government's agricultural transformation agenda which seeks to diversify Nigeria's economic dependence on crude oil revenues. This economic diversification agenda is at the heart of the current administration's Economic Recovery & Growth Plan (ERGP). Viner (2014) notes that in a bilateral or regional trade agreement, tariffs are decreased

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

for member countries, who then gain preferential access to other countries, i.e. trade creation versus trade diversion effects.

Economic Transformation

The AfCTA is expected to have critical effects on trade and investment which in turn will create the environment for effective transformation of the Nigerian economy. This agreement should contribute to the diversification of its exports, stimulate improved efficiency in production, and support the integration of local firms into regional value chains for different products and services. As noted, the AfCTA has the potential to contribute to realizing the objectives of the ERGP especially in relation to the intention of the federal government to diversify the Nigerian economy from excessive dependence on the oil sector which accounts for 90% of foreign exchange revenues (National Bureau of Statistics, 2017). While this is an expectation, it is necessary to note that achieving the desired objectives of the ERGP depends on honest and purposeful structural reforms in the economy. Large export revenues usually result in a structurally overvalued exchange rate, decreasing the competitiveness of other sectors. The fluctuations in crude oil process can lead to balance of payment shocks which can trigger devaluations of the Naira, introducing fluctuations in revenues from exports.

Therefore, one of the main benefits associated with the AfCTA is the possibility of diversifying the export structure of African countries into other products, such as agricultural commodities. Considering that Africa has the capacity to absorb other non-oil products, there is potential benefit to Nigeria from improved market access for its agricultural commodities (Balchin et al., 2018). Some of the information/statistics earlier presented on the scope of Nigeria's trade with Africa highlight the potential for increasing its exports to other African countries –especially signatories to the AfCTA- in many final and intermediate goods and consequent integration of local businesses into regional value chains. Having discussed some of the benefits to Nigeria from the AfCTA, the next section briefly examines some of the costs associated with signing up to it.

Product Specialization

Regional trade agreements create incentives for countries to specialize in products and services where they enjoy comparative advantage. This is because countries that are party to such agreements will look for inefficient suppliers for import of inputs or finished products whilst exporting products and services where it has comparative advantage. For Nigeria, the AfCTA can potentially create a platform for the government to achieve the objectives of the ERGP which seeks to diversify the country's exports away from oil to non-oil exports especially agricultural commodities. Even within the export of agricultural

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

commodities, it is not every commodity that Nigeria must export leveraging the AfCTA. Essentially, it must identify and focus on improving the value chain for those agricultural commodities that it can produce efficiently and at scale. This will enhance the benefits to Nigeria from the reduced trade barriers elicited by the AfCTA.

Alignment to National Development Plans

The AfCTA can complement the ERGP's economic diversification objectives by offering preferential access to the African market worth US\$504bn in imported commodities and services (i.e. US\$475bn of market expansion and US\$29bn of import substitution).¹³ Africa's main imports are manufactured commodities and include agricultural commodities that Nigeria has marked as priority commodities for industrialization and economic diversification, in the ERGP. AfCFTA provides a strong incentive for duty free cross border movement of goods from non-African countries disguised as African goods. This risk is high for Nigeria considering that 92% of Nigeria's imports come from the rest of the world.

1.7.4.2 Potential Costs to Nigeria from AfCTA

In the previous section, some of the benefits to Nigeria from AfCTA were discussed. This section, on the other hand, examines some of the disadvantages of the agreement especially as some local associations, such as the Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (MAN), remain opposed to it.

Trade Creation vs Trade Diversion

When it comes to addressing the potential negative impacts of the AfCTA, it is necessary to consider the issue of whether the agreement would lead to trade creation or trade diversion. Of course, most countries would expect that the AfCTA would lead to trade creation as opposed to trade diversion. Balchin et al., (2018) note that whether an agreement will be trade creating or trade diverting demands a critical analysis involving the assessment of the comparative advantage of partners, the scope of domestic barriers, and the scope of the domestic or local demand. However, some critical considerations for analyzing the possibility of whether a trade agreement, such as the AfCTA, leads to either trade creation or diversion include:

- i. ***The higher the percentage of the partner in imports, the greater the probability that the agreement will lead to trade creation.*** Essentially, a greater

¹³ The market expansion opportunity is based on aggregate imports from other African countries, import substitution opportunity represents aggregate value of Nigeria's imports (source: Trademap.org)

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

percentage or share indicates that most of their imports come from that country in products where it is an efficient supplier. Consequently, removing tariffs is likely to raise imports from this efficient supplier. Contrastingly, if the percentage of the partner is low, an agreement is likely to replace efficient suppliers in products that the country is not importing from that partner. Paying particular attention to non-oil trade –such as trade in agricultural commodities, the African continent represents about 30% of the aggregate exports to Nigeria. Although 2% is exclusively from ECOWAS, the remaining 6% suggests that there is a very limited scope for trade diversion (NBS, 2018). This implies that AfCTA is beneficial to Nigeria especially in relation to the export of non-oil exports.

ii. ***The more the number of countries involved in the agreement, the higher the chance of trade creation.*** In similar vein, as the previous scenario, it is more likely among a larger number of partners in the agreement to identify an efficient supplier. In this situation, the country will orient its imports from that specific efficient country, leading to a rise in welfare in those products. The AfCTA covers 49 African countries hence, the risk of trade diversion is significantly reduced. This suggests that there is more likelihood of identifying efficient suppliers for Nigerian imports.

iii. ***Finally, the more the production structure of the partners look similar, the more likely is it that the agreement will support trade creation.*** A trade agreement will support further specialization in products of comparative advantage. If production structures are less similar, there is an increased chance that the agreement will not transform specialization patterns, leading to no gains in efficiency. This indicates a mechanism for the operation of value chains, resulting in finer specialization (Blomstrom & Kokko, 1997). Despite this, it is possible to consider that less similar production structures may result in improvement in citizens' welfare and may expand the array of quality products and services that they can choose from (Dixit & Stiglitz, 1977). For instance, consumer from a country producing certain variety of cheese may benefit from importing countries producing other varieties of cheese. Among signatories to the AfCTA, there is a broad range but also similar production profiles that support the possibility that Nigeria may gain both specialization as well as the increase in varieties. Again, Nigeria imports intermediate products which are crucial for the integration of companies into domestic and regional value chains. Therefore, decreasing import duties for these commodities will benefit Nigerian companies currently supplying the domestic market and exporting to the other African

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

countries. Consequently, the AfCTA is likely to contribute to the integration of Nigeria into regional value chains through backward linkages. Furthermore, the elimination of duties on Nigerian exports to African countries will enhance existing and new forward linkages.

Lack of Market Access

Despite concerns from some business pressure groups, such as the Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (MAN) and the Lagos Chamber of Commerce and Industry (LCCI), a failure to join the AfCTA could have potentially denied Nigeria access to the markets in non-ECOWAS member countries including those where it enjoyed relative access to in Eastern and Southern Africa (PwC, 2019). Together with a non-diversified export structure, Nigeria has limited market access beyond ECOWAS. Even though Nigeria has access to the United States (US) under the African Growth and Opportunities Act (AGOA), it has failed to benefit from it in a significant way (Osabohien, 2022). In the European Union (EU), it has access to the standard Generalized System of Preferences (GSP) regime that offers limited preferential access to around a third of the imported commodities in EU-member countries.

Since being enacted in 2000, the AGOA has been central to the US government's economic and trade policy with Africa. AGOA offers eligible sub-Saharan African countries with duty free access to the US market for over 1,800 commodities, coupled with the more than 5,000 products that are eligible for duty-free access under the Generalized System of Preferences program.¹⁴ To satisfy AGOA's rigorous eligibility requirements, countries must establish or make continual progress toward establishing a market-based economy, the rule of law, political pluralism, and the right to due process. Additionally, countries must eliminate barriers to U.S. trade and investment, enact policies to reduce poverty, combat corruption, and protect human rights.¹⁵ The AGOA and standard Generalized System of Preferences (GSP) are discussed in more detail subsequently in this research with a view to accessing the degree to which non-oil exports, especially agricultural commodities, have benefitted from these and other international trade agreements relative to the degree to which such agreements are accommodated in the WTO's existing dispute resolution systems. Again, Nigeria does benefit from certain limited access under the Global System of Trade Preferences Among Developing Countries, including certain African countries, India and Brazil. However, preferential access under the unilateral trade regimes is mostly reserved and maximized

¹⁴ Office of the United States Trade Representative

¹⁵ Ibid.

THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS

for Least Developing Countries (LDCs) (i.e. it is essential to note that Nigeria is not a LDC) (Olapade & Onyekwena, 2021). Consequently, countries with the same export profile manage to compete with and sometimes drive out Nigerian suppliers or firms in key markets.

Overall, the AfCTA supports improvements in the Nigerian market access as explained and can also encourage future negotiations. This is because AfCTA can both make Nigeria become more attractive to foreign and local investors as well as help reduce the general resistance to engage in meaningful trade negotiations. AfCFTA's ambition to eliminate tariff on 90% of tariff lines in 5 years plus "national treatment"¹⁶ in the agreement, provide opportunities to level the playing field for Nigeria's exports in Africa.

Erosion of Preferential Access Enjoyed in ECOWAS

A failure to join AfCTA could threaten some of the existing preferences it enjoys within ECOWAS including losing some of such preferences to non-ECOWAS countries such as South Africa. Some of the ECOWAS member countries have both signed and ratified the AfCTA (e.g. Ghana). Therefore, other non-ECOWAS countries (e.g. Kenya and South Africa) will have similar preferential market access in ECOWAS members compared to Nigeria. This will either decrease exports and/or potentially displace current Nigerian suppliers into these markets making it more difficult for Nigeria to achieve the policy thrust of the ERGP which hinges on the diversification of its exports. The Presidential Committee on Impact & Readiness Assessment of AfCTA (2019) notes that although Nigeria can do little to prevent its ECOWAS member countries from joining the AfCTA, it can offset these impacts by gaining market access in other countries. By so doing, the loss of market share in an ECOWAS member can be compensated by gaining share in other African country.

Harmonization of SPS Standards

Another critical challenge with the AfCFTA concerns the harmonization of SPS measures for effective implementation of the agreement considering that some member countries have national SPS regulations, while others take ad hoc decisions for each health issue that crops up, simply based on their general legal framework. This may, or not, be WTO-compatible; but with the operationalization of the AfCFTA, both will have to review their policies and practices. Another problem with implementing SPS measures under AfCFTA concerns member countries' compliance, especially pursuant to the respective RECs,

¹⁶ National treatment implies that the beneficiary's exports will enjoy the same treatment as local products of the importing African country.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

with core substantive provisions of risk assessment and determination of the appropriate level of SPS protection.

High Levels of Protection

Non-involvement or non-participation in the AfCTA could make it challenging for Nigeria to transform its economy thereby losing opportunities to improve the welfare of its citizenry. Currently, Nigeria's trade policy has failed to create a conducive environment that supports economic transformation. This situation does not benefit consumers and does not create incentives for Nigerian businesses to be innovative and competitive (Krishna & Mitra, 1998). Here, not signing up to the AfCTA would deny Nigerian businesses the opportunity to access cheaper and better inputs for their products and services. Nigeria does not operate in a silo as increasingly, countries are interconnected in many ways than previously imagined, largely occasioned by globalization. Given this interconnectedness, it is difficult for countries to take unilateral trade decisions without consideration for its effects on other countries. In fact, Krishna & Mitra (1998) note that it is extremely challenging for countries to implement unilateral trade reforms. Overall, the AfCTA has the potential to support economic growth and development in Nigeria especially as it gives citizens and local firms the opportunity to access foreign capital and technical expertise that was absent prior to the AfCTA.

Unilateral and Unfair Trade Practices/Decisions by some AfCTA Member Countries

When it comes to bilateral, regional or multilateral trade agreements, a major concern is the capacity of countries –which are party to the agreement- to abide by all obligations expected. A threat to the sustainability and effectiveness of such agreements is the unilateral actions or decisions by one or more parties to the agreement. A case in point is the recent decision of the Federal Government of Nigeria -under the Muhammadu Buhari-led administration- to close its land borders; a decision that has been noted with much angst among ECOWAS member countries. Liedong (2019) notes that to restrict trade flows so shortly after this important feat is a serious blow to integration efforts. It also demonstrates how unprepared African countries might be for free trade. It's hard to see how the free trade deal can increase intra-Africa trade to 60% by 2024, as projected, when it is being undermined from the start. The border closure –albeit with some legitimate reasons such as the issue of government-subsidized petroleum being smuggled out of Nigeria and sold in neighboring countries- underscores the existing trade tensions that exist between Nigeria and its neighbors. These existing trade tensions must be addressed if cordial and seamless free trade is to be achieved by the AfCTA.

1.7.5 African Countries and Engagement with the DSU

Based on available information, only Egypt and South Africa have been the main participants in the WTO's DSU mostly as respondents in trade disputes. However, with respect to third party status, some African countries have participated in the DSU including Nigeria, Cameroun, Benin, Cote d'Ivoire, Egypt, Chad, Zimbabwe, Swaziland, Tanzania, Kenya, Ghana, Malawi, Mauritius, Senegal and Madagascar.¹⁷ African countries participation in the WTO Dispute Settlement System has been low; and in situations where they participated, it was mainly to defend their interest in particular commodities such as Sugar, Bananas, and generalized system of preferences.¹⁸

One of the main reasons for the low participation of African countries in the DSU is their relative smaller trade volume and variety of exports. For instance, Africa's trade, as a continent, accounts for 2% of international trade coupled with trade between African countries being limited to about 10.5% of the continent's trade volume.¹⁹ African countries are placed at a disadvantaged position compared to their American and European counterparts hence, the reason why American and European countries have significant participation in the DSU as both respondent and complainant. Africa's low trade volumes also contribute to the low representation of African countries in dispute settlement panels.

Another reason for African countries' low participation in the DSU concerns the high cost of initiating an individual dispute which can be prohibitive for many of them. This is understandable bearing in mind that WTO panels and appellate body use a case-based approach where individual case opinions can number hundreds of pages leading to increased costs of litigation. Furthermore, the complexity of documentation/disputes also adds to the high cost of litigation that is unaffordable for some African countries.²⁰

There is also the problem of limited human and institutional capacity to file and pursue cases with the DSU; and even where African countries decide to opt for the use of private legal firms to pursue disputes, the fees charged by those firms can be too high and prohibitive. From the perspective of weak institutional perspective, most African countries lack the trade policy infrastructure -trade departments, qualified international trade experts, national trade policies- required to effectively engage with the WTO's DSU. The

¹⁷ Presentation on 'The DSU Negotiations and African Countries' by Dr. Edwin Kessie during a conference organized by TRALAC in Cape Town, South Africa on 31st March 2005.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*,

¹⁹ Mavis Marongwe, *African Countries and the WTO Dispute Settlement System*. Accessed from: <http://www.tralac.org/scripts/content.php?id=2718> [3 July 2022]

²⁰ See example, Communication from the Appellate Body, United States-Import Prohibition of Certain Shrimp and Shrimp Products, WT/DS58/13 (October 12, 1998) (Rejecting a generic analysis based on categories of trade measures in favour of a fact-specific analysis based on the 'specific case').

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

increased volume and complexity of WTO agreements amplify the challenges associated with the absence of such infrastructures, since they increase the demand for expert legal and in-depth understanding of how to utilize the DSU and how to proceed with a case.

CHAPTER TWO

LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF INTERNATIONAL TRADE & WTO DSS

2.1 Institutional Structure of the WTO

The WTO was established and became operational on 1st of January 1995 making it the youngest of all major multilateral institutions. Despite this recent history, it is one of the most influential international organizations in a globalized environment. The origins of the WTO lie in *the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade of 1947*, also referred to as 'GATT 1947' or 'GATT'. Understanding the origins of the WTO is key to the decisions, procedures and customary practices of the GATT that still influence and inform some present actions and practices of the WTO.

Despite its influence, the WTO has come under criticism from different quarters especially from developing countries and civil society organizations (CSOs). One of such criticisms is the perception among developing countries that the WTO is a 'rich men's club' especially because of a perceived marginalization in critical decisions that have somewhat contributed to the domination of international trade by the developed and more powerful nations such as the Group of 7 (G7) countries. Another criticism against the WTO is the perception among both developed and developing countries of the WTO's inability to conclude long-running negotiations on further trade liberalization coupled with its perceived inability to address the challenges faced by global trade in the twenty first century (Bronckers, 2001).

Between 1950 and 1985, the GATT was the de facto international organization for trade and the principal instrument/multilateral institution for dealing with issues arising from trade relations. During this period, the GATT was successful in decreasing trade tariffs on commodities, specifically on industrial commodities from developed countries. In eight rounds of negotiation between 1947 and 1994, the average level of tariffs imposed by developed countries on industrial commodities was brought down to about 4%. Following the GATT was the Uruguay Round of Multilateral Trade Negotiations which led to the establishment of the WTO as a multilateral trade organization despite resistance from the United States. The agreement that resulted in the formal establishment of the World Trade Organization, also referred to as the 'WTO Agreement', was signed in Marrakesh in April 1994, and entered into force on the 1st of January 1995. Sampson (1995) notes that those who constructed the WTO are delighted with establishing what has been described as the most significant achievement in institutionalized global economic cooperation. Also, the Sutherland Report on the future of the WTO indicated: "the creation

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

of the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 1995 was the most dramatic advance in multilateralism since the inspired period of institution building of the late 1940s” (Panitchpakdi, 2004). Having provided an overview of the history of the WTO, it is equally important to highlight the objectives and functions of the WTO.

2.1.2 Objectives and functions of the WTO

The reasons behind the establishment of the WTO and the policy objectives of this multilateral institution are outlined in the preamble to the ‘WTO Agreement’. The objectives of the WTO are as follows (Van den Bossche, 2017):

- The increase in standards of living for citizens of member countries;
- The attainment of full employment;
- The growth of real incomes and effective demand;
- The expansion of production of, and trade in, goods and services.

In pursuing the aforementioned objectives, it is highlighted in the preamble to the WTO Agreement that the WTO must consider the need for preservation of the environment and the needs of developing countries. The agreement buttresses the significance of sustainable development as well as social development; this is pertinent as civil unrest and climate change have emerged as the greatest threat to global security (Van den Bossche, 2017). The agreement also emphasizes the significance of the integration of developing countries, and specifically, least-developed countries, in the global trading system (Van den Bossche, 2017).

According to the Preamble to the WTO Agreement, the two major tools for achieving the WTO’s objectives are as follows:

1. The reduction of tariff barriers and other barriers to trade; and
2. The elimination of discriminatory treatment in global trade relations.

With respect to the second tool, which ought to address the issue of discriminatory practices in trade, developing countries’ expectations have not been satisfactorily met as besides tariffs, commodities from developing countries still face non-tariff barriers that inhibit their access to international markets, especially developed countries. The challenges faced by developing countries in the international trading system is discussed subsequently in this research report. In the Doha Ministerial Declaration of 14th November 2001, member countries indicated, with respect to the mandate, objectives and instruments of the WTO (Doha Ministerial Declaration, 2001):

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

“Global trade can play a critical part in promoting socio-economic development and poverty alleviation. We acknowledge the demands of all our peoples to benefit from improved economic opportunities and welfare gains that the multilateral trading system offers. Most WTO members are developing countries; we seek to place their interests and needs at the core of the Work Programme adopted in this declaration.....we strongly reaffirm our commitment to the objective of sustainable development, as highlighted in the Preamble to the Marrakesh Agreement. We are convinced that the objectives of upholding and safeguarding an open and non-discriminatory multilateral trading system, and acting for the protection of the environment and the promotion of sustainable development, can and must be mutually supportive.”²¹

The aforementioned affirmation stresses the importance of protecting the interests of all WTO members especially the least powerful countries. Sustainable socio-economic development, on a global scale, can only be achieved with increased trade liberalization. Having outlined the mandated and objectives of the WTO, it is now time to discuss its functions.

2.1.3 Functions of the WTO

The overriding function of the WTO is to: “provide the common institutional framework for the facilitation of trade relations among its members in matters related to the agreements and related legal instruments included in the Annexes to the WTO Agreement”.²² Deriving from this overriding objective are the following sub-objectives:²³

- The WTO shall facilitate the facilitation, administration and operation, and advance the objectives, of this agreement and of the multilateral trade agreement, and also provide the framework for the facilitation, administration and operation of the plurilateral trade agreements;
- The WTO shall provide the platform for trade negotiations among member countries concerning their multilateral trade relations in matters dealt with under agreements in the annexes to this agreement. The WTO may also offer a forum for additional negotiations among its members concerning their multilateral trade relations, and a framework for the implementation of the results of such negotiations, as may be decided by the Ministerial Conference;

²¹ Ministerial Conference, Doha Ministerial Declaration, WT/MIN(01)/DEC/1.

²² Article II: 1 of the WTO Agreement

²³ Ibid.,

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- The WTO shall administer the understanding on rules and procedures governing the *Settlement of Disputes* (hereinafter referred to as the 'Dispute Settlement Understanding (DSU)') in Annex 2 of the WTO Agreement;
- The WTO shall administer the Trade Policy Review Mechanism (TPRM) provided for in Annex 3 to this agreement; and
- With a view to achieving increased coherence in global economic policy-making, the WTO shall cooperate, as appropriate, with the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and with the International Bank for Reconstruction & Development (IBRD) and its affiliated agencies;
- Provide technical assistance to developing countries –who are members of the WTO- in support of their proper integration into the global trade system.

2.1.4 Membership and Institutional Structure

The WTO consists of 164 member countries representing about 99% of the world's population and 98% of global trade; this makes the WTO a universal organization (World Population Review, 2023).²⁴ The current membership composition structure is very diverse and consists of overlapping groups, coalitions and alliances pursuing varying objectives. For one, majority of the 164 member countries of the WTO are 'developing countries'. There is no WTO definition of what a 'developing country' is. The status of 'developing country-member' is dependent, to a significant degree, on self-selection. Here, members indicate whether they consider themselves 'developing countries'. This poses some challenges as some countries may claim 'developing country' status when they are not especially as developing country members receive special and differential treatment (SDT) available to such countries.

Regarding the issue of who or what a developing country is, a case in point is the 'accession negotiations' where China claimed the status of developing country when in reality, it is not. China's developing member status per se is not a problem in relation to its commitments undertaken at its accession as a WTO member, neither following accession as far as the three agreements that China participated in are concerned. For one, China relinquished most special and differential treatment provisions at its accession, and many of its commitments are WTO-plus in nature (Hu, 2019). Within this remit, the problem lies in China's lack of faithful compliance with certain accession commitments, such as notification and transparency. However, China's status as a developing country-member could pose a challenge for the ongoing fisheries subsidies

²⁴ World Population Review: <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/wto-countries>

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

negotiations, especially given its world-leading fishing capacity (Hu, 2019). This presumption could also be true for other negotiations, for example, those regarding the joint initiative on the trade-related aspects of ecommerce.

To carry out the functions and tasks entrusted to the WTO, the WTO Agreement provides for different bodies or instruments. There are 35 organs within the WTO consisting of different committees and councils such as the General Council, Ministerial Conference, Committees, trade negotiations committee, appellate body (i.e. dispute settlement panels), council for trade in goods, council for trade in services, council for trade-related aspects of intellectual property rights etc. These organs facilitate the different aspects of trade relations between member countries. It is essential to note that the ministerial conference is the supreme body of the WTO that comprises of the representatives of all WTO member countries and meets at least once every two years.²⁵ While the WTO's institutional structure is in many respects similar to that of other intergovernmental/multilateral organizations, it lacks an executive body of the most critical members and a section of other members, unlike, for instance, the United Nations, the IMF and the World Bank.

It is essential to note that most of the WTO's organs earlier identified are political in nature. The WTO also has several judicial, quasi-judicial and other non-political bodies. The most notable among the judicial and quasi-judicial organs are the standing Appellate body and the ad hoc dispute settlement panels respectively. In addition, the WTO has non-political bodies such as the Permanent Group of Experts (PGE) provided for under the SCM²⁶ Agreement; the PGE consists of five independent individuals with a high level of expertise in the fields of subsidies and trade relations and are appointed by the SCM Committee to provide technical assistance and advisory support on critical trade-related issues. Although the PGE can provide specific technical advice to any member on trade related issues, especially subsidies, till date, no use has yet been made of the PGE.

2.1.5 Decision-Making within the WTO

This section discusses the decision-making processes within the WTO which is a key element of its institutional framework. Understanding the decision-making processes within the WTO is key to understanding the challenges faced by African countries in international trade. Its decision-making processes is at the core of some of the criticisms

²⁵ Article IV of the WTO Agreement.

²⁶ SCM-Subsidies and Countervailing Measures: the SCM Agreement creates two fundamental types of subsidies: those that are prohibited, those that are actionable (i.e., subject to challenge in the WTO or to countervailing measures).

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

that the WTO has come under in recent times especially from civil society. For instance, War on Want, a British NGO fighting poverty in developing countries, noted:

“From formulating the agenda to reaching a decision, the process is dominated by the most powerful and richest countries. Consequently, trade negotiations are a fertile ground for horse-trading that inevitably disadvantages the least powerful countries. To keep abreast of the WTO’s agenda, rich nations such as the US, the EU, Japan and Canada possess large teams of technical specialists in Geneva. Majority of the poorest and developing countries lack the resources to maintain such teams”.²⁷

To understand the decision-making processes within the WTO, two perspectives are looked at the: the theoretical/procedural perspective and the practical perspective.

Theoretical/procedural perspective

The standard decision-making procedure for WTO organs is set out in Article IX of the WTO Agreement which reads as follows:

“The WTO shall continue the practice of decision-making by consensus used under the GATT 1947. Except as otherwise provided, where a decision cannot be arrived at by consensus, the matter in question shall be decided by voting. At meetings of the Ministerial Conference and the General Council, each WTO member shall have one vote...Decisions of the Ministerial Conference and the General Council shall be taken by a majority of the votes cast, unless otherwise provided in this Agreement or in the relevant multilateral trade agreement”.²⁸

Following from the above, it is essential to note that the rules of procedure of the different WTO organs set out the quorum requirement. For instance, Rule 16 of the Rules of Procedure for the Meetings of the General Council states that, “a simple majority of the members shall constitute a quorum”. Most WTO organs possess the same quorum requirement. In actual practice, is not usually checked. Van den Bossche & Zdouc (2017) note that decision-making by consensus gives member countries veto power and involves a degree of deference to economic power. It is only in situations where it is perceived that such decisions could negatively impact national and economic interests that a voting member can consider blocking the consensus. As noted by Hoekman & Kostecki (2001:57), “decision-making by consensus is a meaningful mechanism for ensuring that only decisions which stand a good chance of being implemented are adopted because

²⁷ Excerpt from the 5th Ministerial Conference: Free Trade on Trial. Available from: www.waronwant.org.

²⁸ Article IX of the WTO Agreement.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

the decisions adopted are all decisions to which there was no major opposition". However, decision-making by consensus reinforces conservative tendencies in the global trading system. Essentially, proposals for change can be adopted only if unopposed, creating the potential for paralysis. In a situation whereby a consensus cannot be achieved, Article IX;1 of the WTO Agreement provides for voting. For a decision to be adopted by members, it must have a simple majority of the votes cast bearing in mind that each member has one vote.

In addition to the standard decision-making procedure provided for in the WTO Agreement, there are several decision-making processes which deviate from the standard procedure of decision-making by consensus. For instance, with respect to the Dispute Settlement Body (DSB), there are situations where decisions are not taken by consensus such as the adoption of dispute settlement reports or on the authorization of retaliation measures by negative consensus. Again, with respect to the authoritative interpretations of the provisions of the WTO Agreement and the multilateral agreements of Annex 1, 2, and 3 of Article IX of the WTO Agreement, the Ministerial Conference and the General Council shall have the exclusive authority to adopt such interpretations²⁹ and that decision to adopt an authoritative interpretation shall be taken by a three-quarter majority of members.

Decisions regarding the accession of new members and waiving an obligation imposed on a member also deviate from the standard procedure of decision-making by consensus. With respect to decisions on the accession of new members, Article XII:2 of the WTO Agreement provides that such decisions are taken by the Ministerial Conference or the General Council by a two-thirds majority of the members. With respect to waiving an obligation imposed on a member country, Article IX:3 of the WTO Agreement differentiates between waivers of obligations under the WTO Agreement and waivers of obligations under the multilateral trade agreements of Annex 1. Decisions on waivers of the first type require consensus, and if consensus cannot be reached within a specific timeframe (i.e. not exceeding 90 days), a three-quarters majority of members. Decisions on waivers of the second type, on the other hand, require only three-quarters majority of members. Having discussed the theoretical/procedural perspective of decision-making within the WTO, the next section discusses the practical perspective.

²⁹ On the variance between 'authoritative interpretations' of provisions of WTO Agreements by the Ministerial Conference and the General Council, on the one hand, and 'clarification' of those provisions by panels and the Appellate Body.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Practical perspective

Though the WTO Agreement provides for the possibility to take decisions by voting, it is very exceptional for many of its organs to vote. In reality, WTO decisions are taken by consensus. In 1999, when discussion on the recruitment of a new Director General for the WTO Secretariat reached a deadlock, certain developing countries indicated that the selection of the Director General should be done by voting as contained in Article IX:1 of the WTO Agreement. However, this suggestion met with opposition from developed countries who argued that this was contrary to the traditions of the institution. Regarding this issue, Jackson (1998) notes that, “the spirit and practice of the GATT has always been to try to accommodate through consensus negotiation procedures the views of as many members as possible, but certainly to give weight to the views of powerful members that make up the trading system. This is not likely to change soon”. Further reinforcing this position, Mike Moore, the Director General of the WTO from 1999 to 2002 at the time indicated that: “the consensus principle which is at the heart of the way things are done at the WTO –and which is a fundamental democratic guarantee- is not negotiable”.

While decision-making by consensus tends to have more legitimacy than decisions reached outside consensus arrangements because of its democratic nature (also reinforced by the Sutherland Report), Hoekman & Kostecki (2001) note that the consensus requirement does, of course, make decision-making in the WTO very burdensome and unnecessarily prolonged. The consensus approach to decision-making is no doubt participatory in nature. However, it will be unrealistic to involve all 164 members directly in negotiations aimed at reaching an agreement on difficult trade issues. Involving all members in decisions would ultimately make negotiations difficult and ineffective.

Over the years, the WTO has created mechanisms to facilitate negotiations and decision-making in the WTO. One of such frequently used mechanisms is the ‘green room meeting’ that brings together major powers in the WTO (i.e. European Union, United States, Canada etc) and a select number of other members that have an interest in the issue under consideration. In recent times, these green room meetings have proven effective in addressing some trade-related concerns especially as it gives room for developing countries, especially African countries, to be involved in decision-making (Van den Bossche & Zdouc, 2017). In recent times, members from developing country are now increasingly involved in decision-making within the WTO as a result of increased provision of trade-related technical assistance and the systematic coordination of positions and the pooling of resources and expertise in groups, coalitions and alliances involving developing countries. While this is seen as a welcome development by developing

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

countries and civil society groups, the downside to this is that decision-making is now more difficult and protracted. Having discussed the institutional and governance frameworks for the establishment and operation of the WTO, it is now time to look at the laws of the WTO in the next section.

2.2 Laws of the WTO

In this section, attention is devoted to discussing the laws and rules of the WTO including the rules that govern international trade. Pursuant to Article VIII of the WTO Agreement, the WTO has legal personality and shall be accorded by each of its members such legal capacity together with such privileges and immunities as may be necessary for the exercise of its mandate and functions (Bagwell & Staiger, 2015). According to Article VIII:4 of the WTO Agreement, “the privileges and immunities to be accorded by a WTO member, its officials, and the representatives of its members shall be similar to the privileges and immunities stipulated in the 1947 United Nations Convention on the Privileges and Immunities of the Specialized Agencies”. Again, Article III:4 of the Agreement stipulates that: “the specialized agencies...shall enjoy immunity from every form of legal process except in so far as in any specific case they have expressly waived their immunity”. The implication of this observation is that any concerns that any member may have regarding the decisions and actions of the WTO must be addressed through the dispute resolution mechanisms of the WTO and not an external judicial body.

The main economic challenge facing the globe is the need to create a global system that not only maximizes global growth but also achieves an increased measure of equity, a system that both integrates emerging economies and assists currently marginalized countries in their efforts to participate in global economic expansion. Legal norms and values are a significant aspect of the governance institutions that are responsible for making markets function. The same observation applies to the international trade system.

There are four reasons why a rule-based system for international trade is required. First reason is that countries need to be restrained from adopting restrictive trade practices that not only damages their own interest but also the collective interest. The rules that form the basis on which the WTO operates are designed to ensure that countries do not adopt restrictive or insular trade practices (Jackson, 1998). Despite this, it is essential to note that national governments usually face considerable pressures from interest groups to adopt restrictive trade practices designed to protect particular markets or industries. The rules-based system of the WTO is designed to ensure that countries do not bow to such pressure at the expense of broader national and international economic interests. Global trade rules are the shield behind which a government, with the interests of its

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

citizens in mind, can seek protection or redress against pressures from significant national interest groups calling for restrictive trade measures (Jackson, 1998). Moreover, governments are aware that if they adopt trade restrictive measures, other countries or trade partners could retaliate in response thus, placing international trade in an unfavourable position.

The second reason for having international trade rules is the need to provide security and protection to traders and give predictability to global trade relations. In similar vein as the ease of doing business, having international trade rules gives investors and traders alike the confidence to interact or trade with foreign nations. Jackson (1998) notes that the predictability and security offered by international trade rules encourages more trade thus, improving the welfare of citizens of the countries that participate. Essentially, the rules-based system of the WTO can be viewed as a de-risking measure for international transactions (Van den Bossche & Zdouc, 2017). Without such rules, countries and ultimately consumers, would have to pay a risk premium for international transactions; so, in essence, having trade rules improves the efficiency and effectiveness of international trade.

The third reason why rules are required for international trade is the need to integrate a values-based approach to respond to the rising levels of trade and its attendant impact on the environment (i.e. climate change) and public health. Such rules exist to ensure that trade relations do not erode important national values. The WTO is aware of the potential adverse effects that can arise from international trade and as such, gives countries the room to take necessary measures –where necessary- to protect their national or societal values. Jackson (2007) notes that international trade rules may also introduce a degree of harmonization of domestic regulatory measures and as such, promote an effective, international protection of these societal values and interests.

The fourth reason for having trade rules stems from the need to achieve an increased measure of equity in global economic relations. In the absence of having rules which are binding on developed as well as developing countries, many countries –especially developing ones- would find it challenging to full integrate into the global trade system and derive an equitable share of the gains thereof. Essentially, without international trade rules which are binding and enforceable on both rich and poor countries, there are bound to be trade-related conflicts coupled with scenarios where poorer nations are denied the benefits of global trade. Jackson (2007) suggests that while media and civil society are quick to highlight breaches of WTO rules, it is necessary to stress that global trade rules are generally well observed by member countries. Overall, the benefits of having rules to govern international trade far outweighs the costs of having none in place. In the absence

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

of such rules, weaker countries would suffer the most even though the argument can be made that developing countries have not really benefitted from international trade compared to their developed counterparts. Having discussed the justification for having rules to govern international trade, the next section discusses some of these fundamental rules as a basis for deconstructing the legal framework for the WTO.

2.2.1 WTO Rules

The rules and laws governing the WTO are complex in nature especially considering the broad spectrum of goods and services that are traded daily among member countries. Furthermore, the WTO also has to contend with other complex issues from over 150 countries including intellectual property rights, tariffs, customs formalities, import quotas, food safety standards, licensing etc. The institutional WTO rules encompass what it is generally referred to as the 'multilateral trading system' (Wolf, 2001).

For the purposes of discussions in this section, five main rules will be discussed in this section namely: (1) rules of non-discrimination; (2) rules of market access; (3) rules on unfair trade; (4) rules on the conflict between trade liberalization and other national values and interest; and (5) institutional and procedural rules, including those associated with decision-making, trade policy review and dispute settlement (Van den Bossche & Zdouc, 2017).

Rules of Non-discrimination

Under this rule, there are two main categories namely: (1) the most favoured nation treatment; and (2) the national treatment obligation.

The Most Favored Nation (MFN) Treatment

The most favoured nation (MFN) treatment requires a WTO member country that grants certain favourable treatment to any country to grant that same favourable treatment to all other WTO member countries. A WTO member country is not permitted to discriminate between and among its trading partners by, for instance, giving the commodities imported from some countries more favorable treatment with respect to market access than the treatment it accords to the 'like' products of other member countries (Van den Bossche & Zdouc, 2017). Given different deviations and exceptions from this obligation, the MFN treatment obligation is arguably the most significant rule among the gamut of WTO laws. In the absence of this rule, the multilateral trading system could and would be non-existent.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

The National Treatment Obligation

The national treatment obligation requires a WTO member to treat foreign products, services, and service suppliers no less favorably than it treats 'like' domestic products, services, and service suppliers. In situations where the national treatment obligation is applicable, foreign products, for example, should, once they have crossed the border and entered the domestic market, not be subject to less favorable taxation or regulation than 'like' domestic products. Based on the national treatment obligation, a WTO member country is not permitted to discriminate against foreign goods, services, and service suppliers. Given its importance in the WTO legal framework, the national treatment obligation has been a source of some major trade disputes among member countries. Having said this, Jackson (2007) notes that this obligation is more applicable to trade in goods than trade in services.

Again, it is important to note that with respect to the rules of non-discrimination, Article XIII:1 of the GATT 1994 notes that quantitative restrictions, when applied, should be enforced in a non-discriminatory manner. Article XIII:1 notes:

“No prohibition or restriction shall be applied by any member on the importation of any product of the region of any other or on the exportation of any product desired for the region of any other member, unless the importation of the like product of all third countries or the exportation of the like product to all third countries or the exportation of the like product to all third countries is similarly prohibited or restricted.”

What Article XIII:1 demands is that, if a WTO member country imposes a quantitative restriction on products to or from another member country, products to or from all other countries are 'similarly prohibited or restricted'. This requirement of Article XIII:1 is an MFN-like obligation. As the Appellate Body noted in *EC – Bananas III (1997)*, the essence of the non-discrimination obligation of Article 1:1 and XIII of the GATT 1994 is that: “like products should be treated in equal vein, irrespective of where they emanate from”.³⁰

Rules on Market Access

WTO law contains four categories of rules that address the issue of market access namely: (1) rules on tariffs (i.e. custom duties); (2) rules on other duties and financial charges; (3) rules on quantitative restrictions; and (4) rules on other non-tariff barriers. These other non-tariff barriers to trade can be viewed as broad, residual group of measures, actions or omissions of member countries including the lack of transparency in the application of trade laws, regulations and procedures. Non-tariff barriers also

³⁰ Appellate Body Report, EC – Bananas III (1997), para. 190.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

include technical barriers to trade, sanitary and phytosanitary measures, customs procedures, and lack of adequate protection for intellectual property rights (Wolfrum et al., 2007).

With respect to tariff barriers to trade, it is necessary to note that the imposition of custom duties is permitted under WTO law. In fact, the WTO views custom duties as a legal trade instrument that can be used by the governments of member countries; hence, countries can impose duties on certain products. Nevertheless, WTO law requires member countries to negotiate mutually beneficial decreases in custom duties.³¹ Such negotiations could lead to tariff concessions, i.e. on products for which a tariff concession is reached between member countries, the duties imposed may no longer exceed the maximum level of duty agreed to.

Although custom duties are a legitimate trade policy instrument, quantitative restrictions on trade in commodities are, as a general rule, forbidden under WTO law. Unless one of many exceptions apply, WTO members are not permitted to ban the importation or exportation of goods or to subject them to quotas.³² With regards to trade in services, quantitative restrictions are only prohibited in services sectors for which market-access commitments have been agreed between the countries concerned.

Among 'other non-tariff barriers' to trade, the lack of transparency of national trade regulations is one of the main barriers to international trade because it creates an environment of uncertainty and confusion around applicable national trade regulations (Jackson, 1998). In similar vein, the arbitrary application of national trade regulations does not encourage traders and negatively impacts trade. This is why transparency and fair application of national trade regulations are central to the 'rules on market access'. Van den Bossche & Zdouc (2007) indicate that 'other non-tariff barriers' to trade can also take the shape of technical barriers to trade, sanitary and phytosanitary measures, and inadequate protection of intellectual property rights.

When it comes to market access, some members –especially developing countries with emphasis on Africa- have not enjoyed satisfactory access to the markets of other countries especially developed countries. One of the congenital challenges faced by African countries has been the issue of market access for African products and services on the international market. The access of both developing countries to developed countries markets and developed countries to developing country-markets tends to be

³¹ Article XXVIII of GATT 1994.

³² Article XVI of the GATS. Specifically, the prohibition of Article XVI of the GATS applies to 'market access barriers' as defined in Article XVI:2. All but one category of 'market access barriers' are quantitative restrictions.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

viewed in terms of how high (or low, in Africa's case) a country's barriers (both tariff and non-tariff barriers) are to imports from other countries (Muuka, 2001). This is the reason why the World Trade Organization –following the Uruguay Round in 1993- was established to police the international trading system and curtail unfair trade practices among member countries. The degree to which the WTO has achieved this, with respect to the market interests of developing countries, is open to debate and has been the subject of campaigns by civil society organizations against the WTO.

Many African countries, which are members of the WTO, have liberalized their economies following interventions (i.e. Structural Adjustment Programs) by the World Bank and the IMF, and feel that they have received the same reciprocity from developed countries (Muuka, 2001). Despite this, it is necessary to point out that certain initiatives –such as the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) and the EU's Everything But Arms (EBA) initiative- have helped to increase Africa's access to the markets of developed countries. While these initiatives are welcome, some African countries have failed to benefit from such initiatives because of internal structural problems (i.e. economic and political) and limited technical capacity to meet the requirements or conditions of such initiatives. More of these initiatives, coupled with technical assistance, is needed to address the perceived marginalization of Africa in global trade. The issue of Africa's access to international markets is discussed in more detail subsequently in this paper. Having discussed the rules on market access, the next section looks at the rules on unfair trade.

Market Access for Developing Countries

The integration that global trade offers has proven effective in reducing poverty, increasing economic growth, and increasing economic development especially where developing countries are concerned. The multilateral trade system has arguably raised living standards and increased access to economic opportunities for both developed and developing countries especially member countries of the WTO. Some African countries' share of global trade has increased significantly over the years since the launch of the multilateral trading framework. The multilateral trade framework has given many African countries access to export markets internationally.

Despite the seeming benefits of global trade, IMF (2001) notes that the process of trade integration has been uneven especially when comparing outcomes between developed and developing countries. Progress has been somewhat impressive for some developing countries in Asia and, to a lesser degree, in Latin America, which have become successful participants in global trade and attracted a significant share of foreign direct investment in developing countries. Notably, China and India coupled with some countries in Asia

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

have implemented some economic and trade-related reforms that have helped in improving their participation in international trade. The same cannot be said of African countries whose integration into the global trading system has been slow owing to a variety of factors including weak trade policy infrastructure, discriminatory trade practices that deny them access to export markets, etc. In contrast to their developed counterparts, developing countries rely disproportionately on production and exports of traditional commodities. OECD (1997) notes that the reasons for their marginalization are multi-faceted, including deep-seated structural challenges, weak policy frameworks and institutions, and protection at nationally and internationally.

Again, it is necessary to note that most developing countries continue to largely rely on traditional commodity exports. Even at this, agricultural commodities from developing countries, especially those from Africa, face trade barriers and discriminatory practices that limit their access to international markets. As African countries deal with major challenges in their desire to expand trade in agricultural commodities with industrial countries, another major challenge limits progress in this regard. Given agreements negotiated at the WTO, Mutume (2006) notes that traditional protection mechanisms - such as tariffs and quotas- are reducing; however, these protection mechanisms are being replaced by technical regulations and standards that restrict access to agricultural commodities from developing countries. Some of these standards are considered extremely prohibitive because of the inability of some of these countries to fulfil them. Some of the regulatory obstacles consists of measures supposedly aimed at protecting citizens from food-related hazards widely referred as 'sanitary and phytosanitary measures (SPS)'. In fact, Mutume (2006) notes that non-tariff barriers have emerged as a significant market access barrier for commodities or products exported from developing countries especially African countries.

The use of technical barriers -as a protectionist measure- has increased over the years. For one, the SPS Agreement which came into force in 1995 has on occasions been used by some country to restrict access to their markets for exports from other countries. The SPS Agreement was initiated as a response to the need to protect human, animal and plant health from dangerous or contaminated products from other countries (WTO SPS Agreement, 1995). It is equally necessary to note that the Agreement was intended to prevent WTO member countries from using SPS measures to restrict access to trade stating clearly that the measures cannot be employed in "a manner which would be views as a disguised restriction to global trade". Although importing countries are expected to use existing international standards for trade in a variety of commodities, they are equally allowed to implement stricter regulatory measures as long as there is scientific justification

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

for them (WTO SPS Agreement). This is why WTO recommends that SPS measures implemented by the importing country is based on scientific evidence rather than arbitrary measures.

Yuan and Zhang (2018) notes that because the SPS Agreement is based on standards established by developed countries during the Uruguay Round, they tended to reflect mainly the interests and concerns of those nations. During the Uruguay Round of negotiations, most African countries lacked the capacity to send qualified and experience trade negotiators to represent them and as a result, played little role in influencing the outcome of negotiations especially negotiations bordering on agriculture-related issues. It is equally important to note that many developing countries are not represented in international standard-setting agencies that set standards and govern trade in agricultural commodities. This challenge also reflects the inability of African countries to effectively engage with the DSS in relation to unfair trade practices that limit their access to international markets. Relating to the risk of SPS measures being used in a protectionist fashion, Simonetta Zarrilli of the UN Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) notes:

“While there is a clear need for SPS measures to protect consumers, the benefits and advantages of trade liberalization in the agriculture sector achieved by the Uruguay Round of negotiations could be undermined by the protectionist use of sanitary and phytosanitary measures”.

There have been situations where SPS measures have been used to restrict market access to agricultural commodities from developing countries -especially African countries- in ways that can be viewed as protectionist. For instance, during the 1990s, European countries banned fish exports from some East African countries -Kenya, Mozambique, Tanzania, and Uganda- owing to concerns about sanitary standards and control systems around the fish value chain in these countries. As a result of this ban, these countries lost significant financial income; Uganda, for instance, is estimated to have lost about US\$37mn in potential earnings as a result of this ban (Mutume, 2006). Furthermore, in Tanzania, where fish and fish products represent 10 percent of its annual exports, fishermen dependent on sales to the European Union lost 80 percent of their income (World Bank, 2000). In response to the EU's decision to ban fish exports from East Africa, Trevor Manuel -the Finance Minister of South Africa- noted:

“The issue is not the global trade is inherently opposed to the needs and interest of poor countries, but that the rules that govern it are rigged in favour of rich countries”.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Furthermore, in response to the use of SPS measures by some WTO member countries in a protectionist fashion, Mutume (2006) notes:

“While some of these SPS measures or technical standards are legitimate as it concerns the need for food safety, the problem is that many African countries find it challenging to satisfy these standards owing to technical and resource-capacity constraints”.

To put the aforementioned statement into context, studies in Kenya indicate that farmers would have to spend 10 times more than they currently do if they are to comply with the EU's high standards around food safety. Furthermore, Mutume (2006) notes that for Uganda to meet the EU's food safety standards for honey and coffee, it would need to spend about US\$300mn to upgrade its honey processing plants and producers of coffee would spend 200 percent more to produce coffee at the required standard. These resource and capacity constraints place most African countries in a difficult position as they are unable to meet these rigorous standards; and this contributes to their products being rejected by developed countries. This can be considered as unfair especially bearing in mind that import standards in African countries are not equally rigorous leading to a situation of unequal benefits from international trade when comparing the fortunes of developing countries with those of developed countries.

Nigeria has also faced technical barriers to trade for its horticultural and agricultural commodities. In 2017, for instance, Mexico banned some containers of hibiscus flower - also referred to as 'zobo leaves'- because of pesticide infestation. It is estimated that Nigeria lost about US\$110mn in foreign exchange revenues because of the ban thus, affecting the country and farmers of hibiscus flower (Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade & Investment, 2019). This situation strained relations between both countries. However, in recent times, both countries have signed bilateral trade agreements which ought to renew Nigeria's export of hibiscus flower to Mexico. To avert a situation where its export of hibiscus flowers is rejected due to pesticide-related contamination -owing to Mexico's standards around use of pesticides- the Federal Government has committed to working with off-takers and exporters of hibiscus flower through the Nigeria Agricultural Quarantine Service (NAQS) to facilitate the building of chambers dedicated to methyl bromide fumigation of hibiscus. Furthermore, in the spirit of renewed trade ties between both countries, the FMITI has also indicated that the government will work with the NAQS to ensure that the required plant health certificates are provided for all hibiscus export from Nigeria. Although a complaint was filed by Nigeria at the time of the ban, it appears that bilateral engagements between both countries have yielded more results in resolving

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

this conflict. The fulfilment of these commitments has resulted in Mexico lifting the ban on hibiscus exports from Nigeria.

Rules on Unfair Trade

In its current shape, WTO law does not provide for general rules on unfair trade practices, but it does have detailed rules that apply to particular types of unfair trade. For example, rules dealing with dumping and subsidized trade.

Dumping, which entails bringing a good into a country at a price lower than the actual value or market price of that product, is condemned but not prohibited under WTO law. However, when dumping causes or threatens to cause material injury to the domestic industry of a member country producing alike product, WTO law allows the member to impose antidumping duties on the dumped products to offset the dumping.³³ Preventing anti-dumping is a central role of the WTO.

Dumping issues has been at the core of some major trade disputes between some WTO member countries, notably, between China and the United States. The Trump administration blames China for the challenges faced by some of its domestic industries –such as its steel, textiles, and clothing industry- as a result of dumping by Chinese exporters (Bown, 2019). This has led to the imposition of tariffs (i.e. anti-dumping duties) on a broad spectrum of Chinese imports in a bid to protect some domestic industries. In fact, the special tariffs imposed by the Trump administration raised the average US tariff on imports from China from 3% to 12% (Bown, 2019). The trade dispute between China and the US highlights perceived weaknesses in the WTO's litigation measures for dealing with unfair trade practices. The US refers to its special tariffs against China as a 'national security' issue due to the costs of China's unfair and costly trade practices to its economy. This indicates the need for a review of the WTO's rules on unfair trade practices.

Subsidies, which can be referred to as financial contributions by governments or public bodies that confer a benefit, are subject to a complex set of rules (Roberts, 2008). Certain subsidies, such as export and import subsidies, are, as a rule, prohibited. Other subsidies are not prohibited, but when they cause adverse impacts to the interests of other member countries, the subsidizing member should withdraw the subsidy or take proper measures to eliminate the adverse impacts. If the subsidizing member fails to act, countermeasures commensurate with the degree and scope of the adverse impact may be authorized. If a prohibited or other subsidy inflicts material harm to the domestic industry of a member country producing a 'like' product, the member is authorized to impose countervailing

³³ See Article VI of the GATT 1994 and the *Anti-Dumping Agreement*.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

duties on the subsidized products to offset the subsidization (Bown, 2019). Having discussed the rules on unfair trade practices, the next section discusses the rules on conflict between trade liberalization and other societal values and interests.

Rules on the Conflict between Trade Liberalization and other Societal Values and Interests

WTO law provides for rules that address the conflict between trade liberalization and other societal values and interests and that allow to strike the intended balance. These rules, which are commonly referred to as 'exceptions', allow WTO member countries to deviate –under specific conditions- from basic WTO rules to consider economic and non-economic values and interest that compete or conflict with free trade (Van den Bossche & Zdouc, 2017). The non-economic values and interest include the protection of the environment, public health, public morals, national treasures, and national security. The relevant rules, in this respect, are contained in Articles XX and XXI of the GATT 1994 and Article XIV of the GATS. The economic interests, on the other hand, include: the protection of a domestic industry from serious harm inflicted by an unexpected and sharp surge in imports; the safeguard of a country's balance of payments; and the pursuit of regional economic integration.

Acknowledging the need for positive initiatives designed to ensure that developing country members, and particularly the least-developed countries among them, are integrated into the multilateral trading system, WTO law includes many provisions offering a degree of special and differential treatment to developing country members (Van den Bossche & Zdouc, 2017). These provisions try to consider the special needs of developing country members. Having discussed the rules between trade liberalization and other societal values, the next section discusses the institutional and procedural rules of the WTO.

Institutional and Procedural Rules of the WTO

The previous four fundamental rules discussed are generally referred to as 'substantive rules'. However, the multilateral trading system also includes, and depends on, institutional and procedural rules associated with WTO decision-making, trade policy review and dispute settlement. The WTO decision-making processes have already been discussed earlier in this chapter. The trade policy review mechanism exists to get member countries to be aware of the trade regulations of member countries. Its purpose is to ensure that national trade regulations align to WTO rules and procedures. The WTO's dispute resolution mechanism is discussed in more detail in the next chapter even though

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

an overview of procedures and rules for settlement of disputes is discussed in the next section.

2.2 Rules and Procedures for Settlement of Disputes

Trade conflicts are unavoidable in an increasing interdependent global economy that is rife with complex rules, competition and regulations. In addition to the fact that each country has its own domestic or national laws, the WTO also has its own set of rules governing global trade. Issues concerning conflict between national laws and WTO rules have been noted in existing literature (Chang, 2011; Graewert, 2020; Devuyt & Serdarevic, 2007). Graewert (2020) notes that with emerging new regional trade agreements and the stagnating of the Doha Round of negotiations, the conflict of overlapping laws and jurisdictions has emerged as a serious concern in global trade. The examination of the DSU indicates that the WTO treaty negotiators failed to perceive potential conflicts of jurisdictions especially in relation to regional trade agreements (RTAs). Given that there is an absence of a general rule of primacy between WTO norms and RTA norms, some authors (Chang, 2011) have suggested that the DSU should be amended and that under certain conditions, choice of forum and/or exclusive forum clauses of RTAs could lead a panel to suspend jurisdiction until the issue has been addressed.

The dispute settlement procedure of the WTO is one of the institution's most critical functions. Essentially, when a member state finds its trading partner(s) in violation of WTO rules, it is expected to follow the WTO's dispute settlement procedure to seek remediation. The rules and procedures for the settlement of disputes in the WTO is also referred to as 'dispute settlement understanding (DSU)' (Chang, 2011). The DSU is arguably the single most important achievement of the Uruguay Round Negotiations especially considering that trade disputes are likely to arise in the international or multilateral trade system. The WTO dispute settlement mechanism is applicable to all disputes between WTO member countries arising under the WTO agreements. With respect to the dispute settlement mechanism of the WTO, Ruggiero (1997) remarks:

"The DSU is in many ways the central pillar of the multilateral trading system and the WTO's most individual contribution to the stability of the global economy".

Building on five decades of experience with settling trade disputes in the context of the GATT 1947, Ruggiero (1997) notes that the DSU outlines a dispute settlement system that is characterized by compulsory jurisdiction, limited time frames, an appellate review process, and an enforcement mechanism. The DSU provides for rules on the coverage and scope of the dispute settlement mechanism, its objectives, its administration, and its

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

operations on mandatory pre-litigation consultations, conciliation, and mediation. The DSU is there to prevent unilateral action by member countries; the sort witnessed in the dispute between China and the US. It should be noted that because of the unilateral action –placing tariffs on Chinese imports- taken by the US, the WTO gave permission for China to place tariffs on US\$3.6bn American imports in retaliation. The DSU provides an avenue for member countries to seek redress where they feel that another country has carried out unfair trade practices. The degree to which the DSU has helped in reducing the marginalization of developing country members is open to discourse and is explored in detail in the next chapter which focuses on the WTO's dispute resolution mechanism.

2.3 Dispute Resolution: Litigation, Conciliation, and Negotiation

The dispute settlement procedures of the multilateral trading mechanisms have gradually evolved from an approach based on mediation of disputes that were fundamentally between the members of a small circle of developed, like-minded countries towards a more rules-based procedure that increases the participation of more members. Despite this intention, some member countries have engaged less with the WTO dispute settlement system than others. Several reasons have been proffered as being responsible for limited engagement of some member countries. Adams et al., (2003) highlighted some reasons including size of economy and weak trade infrastructure. Some members, especially African countries, lack the staffing capacity to pursue litigation for trade-related disputes.

When perceived from a high level, there are two major distinctions that one might draw between the political cultures and legal traditions of WTO members. First is the difference between what might be called 'litigious' versus conciliatory cultures, with the former being marked by popular belief that trade disputes are normal and that the courtroom is the best place to resolve them, and the latter being driven by the concern that confrontation is destructive, leads to hard feelings between winners and losers, and ought to be avoided whenever possible (Adams et al., 2003). The second difference between litigation and conciliation concerns those legal traditions that are based on the English common law, which stresses the significance of precedent, versus the civil law that stress the terms of the particular law in question (Adams et al., 2003). The first of these major divisions helps in explaining the differing degrees to which individual members use the dispute settlement mechanism, such that the more traditional litigious countries in Europe and the Americas generally account for the larger number of complaints brought before the Dispute Settlement Body (DSB), while members from Africa, the Middle East and Asia bring complaints less frequently.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

What is clear from the discussions in this section is that disputes are bound to arise as countries interact with each other on the basis of trade. The need to create a platform for resolving this dispute is key to the utility of the WTO's DSB making it one of the most important organs in the multilateral trade system. There are basically two main approaches to resolving trade disputes between member countries namely: the traditional litigious approach and the conciliatory approach where conflicting parties settle outside the court or DSB in this case. Having explored the role of litigation and conciliation in the DSB's procedure, the next section discusses the role of economic interests and capacity in dispute resolution.

2.3.1 Economic Interests and Capacity

The increased litigiousness of the developed countries compared to developing countries may also reflect that developed countries have more economic interest to gain or lose from trade disputes hence, they have the legal capacity to pursue litigation within the WTO (Grasstek, 2013). This explains why China engages significantly with the DSU given that most of its economic growth is tied to its trade exports. In so doing, China has increased its familiarity with the DSU's procedures. Developing countries have a lot to learn from China when it comes to gradual strengthening of their respective trade infrastructure. While some developing countries, including some members from Africa argue that they lack the technical capacity to effectively pursue litigation procedures; they must understand that constant engagement with the DSU's procedures is a steep learning curve that takes time to master. What is clear from the discussions thus far is that perceived economic interests –how much one has to gain or lose from trade disputes- significantly influence a member country's engagement with the WTO's dispute settlement procedures.

Another factor that influences a country's level of engagement with the DSU is the issue of 'resources and inherent capacity' (Grasstek, 2013). Grasstek (2013), for instance, notes that the complexity and cost of the WTO's dispute resolution system partly explains the limited engagement of some member countries. Furthermore, Bown (2009) notes that another concern for developing countries when it comes to engagement with DSU is that they are not adequately represented on panels and the aim of the system is not development but legal compliance. In addition to lacking resources to pursue litigation within the WTO, some countries lack dedicated trade missions. Adams et al., (2003) suggest that countries with dedicated WTO missions are more likely to file cases with the DSU compared to those that do not have dedicated missions. WTO (2014) notes that 26 of the 36 members that filed cases with the DSU between 1995 and 2012 had dedicated missions in 2012, while only one non-resident member had ever done so. Furthermore,

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

only about one quarter of all WTO member countries have dedicated trade missions and these members were responsible for about three quarters of all complaints filed with the DSU (WTO, 2014).

These challenges of limited resources and capacity faced by African countries can be offset by the existence of the Advisory Center on WTO law³⁴ and also by the practice of bringing in outside counsel that might be paid for by the private sector. Despite this, Grasstek (2013) notes that no amount of technical assistance can change the fact that countries that account for small amounts of trade have less leverage if a case comes down to retaliation. Essentially, there is a correlation between trade capacity and level of engagement with the WTO's dispute settlement mechanisms.

2.3.2 The Choice between Litigation and Negotiation in Dispute Settlement

When it comes to settling trade disputes, countries can either go the litigation route or the negotiation route. In the previous sections, the litigation route to addressing trade disputes was discussed; however, countries can also address trade disputes through negotiation. Even those members that come from more litigious cultures, or that have grown to the stage where they overcome cultural barriers to litigation, still face the same choice when deciding about the preferred approach to trade disputes.

While unilateral action is discouraged under the WTO, when one member has a trade dispute with another it still must choose whether to handle the problem through the legislative or the judicial functions of the WTO. Grasstek (2013) suggests that litigation and negotiation need not be viewed as mutually exclusive choices, but can instead be utilized sequentially in pursuit of the same objective of resolution. Weekes (2004:1) notes that, "a good agreement can persuade governments to accept a dispute settlement system capable of rendering impartial, definitive judgments in an expeditious way just as a good dispute settlement mechanism reinforces the obligations in the agreement and can contribute significantly to any negotiation of that agreement". Grasstek (2013) notes that the judicialization of the WTO may make members less willing to produce agreements via the traditional practice of constructive ambiguity, by which negotiators were willing (but less eager) to settle on compromises that enabled each party to claim some victory but might leave the precise meaning in doubt. Even as parties can negotiate themselves out a trade dispute, they still must keep in mind that decisions of the panel are binding on all parties. Again, Imboden & Nivet-Claeys, 2008) note that multilateral

³⁴ The Advisory Center on WTO Law (ACWL) offers legal assistance to developing countries in dispute settlement cases. The ACWL was created in 2001 as an organization independent of the WTO. Its mission is to provide least-developed countries (LDCs) and other developing countries with the legal capacity they need to enforce their rights under the DSU. The charge subsidized fees to developing countries for legal advice on WTO law including dispute settlement procedures.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

trade negotiations seek to transfer the existing rules in order to create a global trade system that is based on new principles (i.e. changes for the future), whereas legal procedures seek the application of the rules already in force but not respected by certain member countries. What is clear from this observation is that negotiations between parties to a trade dispute can bring about new laws within the WTO designed to address similar issues subsequently. This demonstrates that there are strong linkages between negotiation and litigation especially as it relates to the evolution of the WTO's legal and institutional frameworks. Having provided a background to the issue of trade disputes between member countries, it is now essential to delve into the DSU and how it operates. This is done in the next section.

2.4 Dispute Settlement Understanding/System: Operational Framework

Created in 1995, the WTO's Dispute Settlement System (DSS) is used to resolve trade-related disputes between member countries of the WTO. The DSS or DSU is a part of the grand bargain reached in the Uruguay Round to address trade disputes between member states. The DSS replaces GATT procedures for resolving trade disputes because the latter was marred by certain weaknesses. Among the weaknesses of dispute resolution under the GATT include inconsistent rules, absence of right to appeal, no power to enforce judgments or rulings etc (Tirkey, 2019). Again, the DSS emerged as a replacement for the GATT because of the perception among developing countries that their interests were not being protected. Essentially, the DSS replaced power-based bent of the GATT dispute resolution framework. This is possible because the DSS consists of critical principles for its operationalization with a view to enhancing the 'stability and predictability' of the multilateral trading system. It contains rules and procedures for fairly and objectively resolving trade disputes between member countries. Tirkey (2019) notes that the DSS is a more rules-based system compared to the GATT that was perceived as largely 'power-based'.

Since its inception, the WTO –through the DSS- has received over 500 complaints and uses both political negotiation and adjudication for dispute resolution. The high frequency with which the DSS is invoked is an indication that the member countries have confidence in its capacity to resolve trade disputes and protect the rights and obligations of members. Before discussing how the DSS operates, it is essential to briefly discuss the fundamentals of dispute settlement. The dispute settlement process usually starts when one or more WTO members formally challenge another member's measures or actions that are seen as being in violation of that member's commitments. These claims of violation are usually based on the contention that the measure in question contravenes, for instance, either or both main principles of non-discrimination. Put simply, most-

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

favoured-nation (MFN)³⁵ treatment prevents a country from discriminating between one trading partner and another at entry points (i.e. ports) for commodities, while national treatment³⁶ prevents a country from discriminating between its own commodities and those of another country behind the border (Alvarez-Jimenez, 2009). The MFN principle implies, for instance, that Australia must apply the same tariffs to imports of Norwegian salmon that it applies to imports of similar Chilean Salmon.³⁷ On the other hand, the national treatment principle implies, for instance, that Brazil cannot apply sales taxes or other barriers to French products that are more restrictive than those applied to goods produced by Brazilian companies.³⁸

When it comes to filing complaints at the DSS, it is common to find a member pursuing several complaints of perceived violations by the actions or measures of another member. In such cases, the complainant tends to cite different provisions from different agreements when making a complaint about how a member's laws and policies are alleged to violate their commitments. In response, the respondents usually cite the existence of exceptions in different agreements in defense against complaints filed against them. Some of these exceptions are as follows (Tirkey, 2019):

- Protection of public morals
- Protection of human, animal or plant life
- Protection of prison labour
- Protection of national treasures of artistic, historic or archaeological importance
- Conservation of limited or scarce natural resources
- Intergovernmental commodity-related agreements
- Restrictions on exports of local materials
- Products in short supply

In most cases, respondents usually respond to complaints filed against them by citing any of the abovementioned exceptions even though it does not accord them a 'free pass' to

³⁵ GATT Article I

³⁶ GATT Article III

³⁷ It is essential to note that there are exceptions to these general rules. If Australia has a bilateral trade agreement with Chile, for instance, it is not obliged to grant concessions granted to Chile to Norway.

³⁸ The national-treatment obligation of GATT Article III is only applicable to situations that are particularly identified in the article, especially sales taxes and regulations affecting internal sales. Subsequent agreements negotiated at the Uruguay Round provided for national treatment in other areas, such as trade in service (GATS Article XVII) and trade-related investment measures (Article II of TRIMs Agreement).

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

engage in restrictive trade practices. According to Article XX of the WTO, “exceptions are subject to the requirement that such measures are not applied in a way that constitutes arbitrary or unjustifiable discrimination between countries where the same conditions prevail, or a disguised restriction on global trade”. The application of exceptions also faces a ‘necessity test’ where the measure must be necessary to achieve the stated objective and that no WTO consistent or less trade-restrictive option is financially and technically available (Alvarez-Jimenez, 2009). The necessity test is at the core of the work done by the dispute settlement panel that is responsible for examining the arguments put forward by the parties to the dispute.

Judgments that do not favour the respondent do not automatically result in the invalidation of existing laws. Rulings of a WTO panel are not comparable to, for instance, decisions reached by a domestic court that has the power to strike down laws that it views as unconstitutional. Alvarez-Jimenez (2009) notes that provisions for dispute settlement depend in the first instance on the willingness of the parties to the dispute to abide by rulings. In a situation whereby a panel finds a member country’s laws and policies to be in violation of its GATT obligations, all panel and Appellate Body reports end with the same obligatory recommendation: it should bring the challenged measure into conformity with its WTO obligations. It is then up to the member in question to decide what action it will adopt. The preferred alternative is to bring its laws into conformity with the ruling, which might entail the law’s appeal, amendment, or replacement with some new law. Only in extreme instances does the system contemplate that the affected party or complainant will request, receive, and exercise the right to retaliate. Tirkey (2019) notes that despite the increased frequency of dispute-related cases filed at the WTO, the aggregate number of instances in which a petitioner was ultimately given the permission to retaliate against another member country totaled 17 by the end of 2012.

When it comes to compliance with dispute settlement rulings, WTO members comply with the rulings in about ninety percent of cases. Compliance may take some time especially if the member’s parliament needs to change or abolish the measure that is at the core of the ruling, i.e. it could take some considerable amount of time to amend or change a national law or policy given the bureaucracy within the public sector. The DSU gives considerable amount of time to respondents to comply with rulings however, members must remember that such rulings are reasonably time-bound (WTO, 2018). The member is usually given a “reasonable period of time” -ranging from eight to fifteen months– to implement the dispute settlement rulings. During the implementation period, the member respondent that is required to comply with the rulings must provide a status report at each meeting of the DSB. In a situation where a member fails to bring its measures into

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

conformity with the relevant WTO agreements within the allotted time, the complainant may request the DSB to authorize retaliation in the shape of trade sanctions, such as restrictions on imports, for an amount equivalent to the level of trade affected by the offending measure (WTO, 2018). Having discussed the fundamental principles underlying the WTO's dispute settlement system, the next section looks at its operational framework.

2.4.1 DSS : Operational Process

The DSS process consists of three main stages namely: (1) consultations between parties involved in the dispute; (2) adjudication by panels, or the appellate body (if appealed); and (3) implementation of the ruling, including the possibility of countermeasures if the losing party does not implement the ruling³⁹ (see Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Overview of the WTO Dispute Settlement System

Source: Zimmerman (2007)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

³⁹ WTO Handbook

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

The WTO's jurisdiction over disputes is compulsory and all members are subject to it by virtue of having signed and ratified the agreement (Zimmerman, 2007). A trade dispute usually arises when a member country adopts a trade policy that one or more members consider to be inconsistent with the obligations outlined in WTO trade agreements. In such a situation, a member is entitled to challenge the policy measure by invoking the procedure of the DSS. At this point, it is essential to discuss the three stages of the dispute settlement process.

Stage 1: Consultations

In the consultation stage (60 days), parties are given an opportunity to meet bilaterally and arrive at a mutually agreed solution. The WTO DSU gives priority to a mutually acceptable solution and encourages parties to arrive at the same at any stage of the dispute.⁴⁰

Most disputes do not go beyond the consultation stage, either because parties reach a mutually satisfactory solution or because the complainant decided against pursuing the matter for other reasons. Consequently, consultations are a critical aspect of the DSS and enable parties to clarify facts, understand claims of the complainant and dispel any misunderstandings as to the actual nature and scope of the measure at issue.

Stage 2: Adjudication by Panel and the Appellate Body

In a situation where no solution is reached, the complainant may request the establishment of a panel to adjudicate the dispute. After hearing the parties, the panel makes an objective assessment of the complainant's claim and issues its decision in a report. If the report is appealed, the dispute will go to appellate proceedings. An appeal is only limited to legal questions and cannot examine new evidence. The Appellate Body (AB) may uphold, modify, or reverse legal findings and conclusions of the panel. The Dispute Settlement Body (DSB) must adopt, and the parties unconditionally accept, the AB report through the negative consensus mechanism.

Stage 3: Implementation and Countermeasures

If the proceedings before the DSU end against the respondent, it is likely that the Panel or the AB will recommend the respondent member state to bring its "measures in conformity with the relevant WTO Agreement". If it is not practical to do so immediately, the parties may determine a "reasonable period of time" for implementation through arbitration proceedings. If the implementation is non-satisfactory, a compliance panel will

⁴⁰ Article III of the WTO Dispute Settlement

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

be established to scrutinize whether the implementing measure complies with the ruling, and if it is also consistent with the covered agreement.

In case of non-implementation, the prevailing complainant can also resort to temporary measures, i.e. compensation or suspension of WTO obligations (WTO, 2018). Suspension consists of retaliatory trade sanctions and demands the authorization of the DSB and must be “equivalent to the degree of nullification or impairment caused by non-compliance. In a situation whereby a dispute arises about the shape or manner of suspension of concessions invoked, it can be referred to arbitration to the original panel.⁴¹

The DSB continues surveillance –even where compensation has been agreed to or obligations have been suspended- as long as recommendation to bring trade measures into conformity has not been implemented.⁴² Having examined the three stages of the trade dispute settlement process, the next section concentrates on the main elements of the process.

2.4.2 Elements of the Dispute Settlement Process

This section concentrates on the main elements or organs of the WTO's dispute settlement process. The elements discussed in this section are as follows: dispute settlement body (DSB); appellate body (AB); and Special Differential Treatment for Developing Countries and LDCs.

Dispute Settlement Body (DSB)

The General Council, the highest organ of the WTO, consists of representatives from member countries and also meets as the Dispute Settlement Body (DSB). The DSB is basically a political body and is created to administer rules and procedures of the DSU and has been tasked with carrying out different functions. The DSB has the authority to create panels, adopt panel and Appellate Body reports, maintain surveillance of implementation of rulings and recommendations, and authorize suspension of concessions and other obligations under the covered agreements (Steinberg, 2002).

The DSB's decision with regards to creating panels, adopting panel and appellate body reports, and authorizing retaliation, is adopted by the 'negative' or 'reverse' consensus method. All other decisions, such as the appointment of panel or appellate body (AB) members, are taken through the positive consensus mechanism.

⁴¹ Article 22.6 of Dispute Settlement Understanding

⁴² Article 22.8 of Dispute Settlement Understanding

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Appellate Body (AB)

The AB represents one of the major variances between dispute settlement in the WTO versus GATT. It consists of seven individuals serving four-year terms (each of which may be renewed once), all of whom have reputations for probity and integrity and are among the most experienced and trusted members of the trade community. As per the DSU, the AB members shall be individuals of recognized authority with demonstrable expertise in law, international trade and the subject matter of the WTO agreements (Alvarez-Jimenez, 2009). In fact, most members of the AB have been legal luminaries, university professors, senior judges, and past government officials or bureaucrats.

When panel decisions are appealed, there are three AB members assigned by a random process, who then have a clear timeline of 90 days in which to render a decision. Cases brought to the AB are usually assigned through randomization and rotation. Article 6 of the Working Procedures for Appellate Review provides for selection “on the grounds of rotation, while considering the principles of random selection, unpredictability and opportunity for all Members to serve irrespective of their national origin”. This method of random selection helps ensure that no AB member knows in advance which cases they will be assigned or which of their six colleagues will be named to the same appellate panel (Van Grastek, 2013). Once an assignment is made, the only condition for a member of the AB not to accept a case is situations where there is a ‘conflict of interest’ which may impair their judgment. Again, AB members are compensated for their services based on a ‘retainer’. The retainer that AB members receive is intended to ensure that whatever other duties they may take on elsewhere (e.g. teaching, serving on an arbitration panel etc) will not interfere with their availability to discharge their AB responsibilities, i.e. the retainer ensures that they are available throughout the year to adjudicate over trade disputes submitted to the DSU (Tirkey, 2019).

The Appellate Body has had a direct and indirect impact on jurisprudence within the WTO. The direct impact surrounds the decisions that it reaches. These decisions reach judgments on the meaning of WTO agreements coupled with the conduct of disputes themselves, as is the case for its rulings concerning outside counsel and *amicus* briefs.⁴³ In terms of indirect impacts, the appellate body gives panelists an incentive to ‘appeal-proof’ their decisions. What distinguishes the WTO regime from GATT is that panelists are more likely to become invested in their decisions, and want to avoid the implied criticism of a reversal (Tirkey, 2019). This motivation may be responsible for the growing

⁴³ **Amicus briefs** are legal documents filed in appellate court cases by non-litigants with a strong interest in the case or subject matter. The **briefs** advise the court of additional, important information or arguments that the court might wish to consider. Amicus briefs help in improving the quality of jurisprudence within the WTO.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

length and complexity of the decisions that panels reach. The same concerns also encourage countries to insist that at least one of the panelists appointed to cases in which they are involved be lawyers, and to prefer that the chairman also be a lawyer. Unlike the WTO regime, the make-up of panelists consisted of local missions and diplomats rather than lawyers.

Special and Differential Treatment for Developing Countries and LDCs

As developing and least developed countries (LDCs) face legal, financial and political constraints in filing trade-related disputes, the WTO makes provisions for “special and differential treatment” for these countries, to create a level playing field for all members irrespective of economic status. Some examples of this special and differential treatment involve paying ‘special attention’ to peculiar challenges and interests of developing countries, according sufficient time to prepare and present its defence or complaints,⁴⁴ and provision for accelerated DSS procedure on their request.

The “special and differential treatment” element of the DSS will guide discussions in subsequent chapters including paying particular attention to how this element operates in actual practice citing relevant cases, examining how developing countries have utilized this particular provision, and identifying perceived gaps in its application. Developing country members and LDCs can also utilize the technical assistance provided by the Advisory Center on WTO Law (ACWL), a Geneva-based legal aid center established in 2001 to provide support in dispute settlement, legal advice, legal services and training. Essentially, developing countries and LDCs can leverage the ACWL to strengthen their trade infrastructure. While the legal support services provided by the ACWL are provided free of charge, assistance in processing trade disputes through the DSS are chargeable at a discounted or subsidized cost. Though these rates are subsidized, they remain prohibitive for some developing countries and LDCs. For instance, since the establishment of the ACWL, India has so far used its services in only four cases, all against the United States covering the following sectors: textile and clothing; steel; fisheries/marine; services; and renewable energy equipment.⁴⁵

The SDT exists to ensure that the multilateral trading system serves the interest of developing countries as well. Despite this being the case, it is also important for developing countries to understand that developed countries also have their own valid trade interests. Consequently, the SDT should be viewed as a means of modifying pursuit

⁴⁴ Article 12.10 of the DSU

⁴⁵ Report on Operations 2017”, Advisory Centre on WTO Law, http://www.acwl.ch/download/general_assembly_mmeeting_documents/11.07.2018_meeting/Final_Report_on_Operations_2017_-website.pdf.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

of the central trade goals and objectives of the WTO, not as a substitute for them (Kleen & Page, 2005). This is understandable bearing in mind that trade is not the only way of promoting economic development or decreasing poverty. The existence of the WTO and global trade indicates that all members believe that integration into the multilateral trading system is a critical component of national strategies, even though it is not a purpose in itself. Consequently, the SDT should not contradict its primary purpose: it should avoid creating obstacles to a country's future development or integration into the system, and should normally promote, not restrict trade.

One of the challenges with the SDT concerns determining eligibility for 'differentiation'. Essentially, there are no agreed measures of 'level of development'. Kleen & Page (2005) note that varying political priorities would inform what weight should be given to varying indicators. It can be challenging to establish indicators of a country's institutional capacity to undertake trade-related commitments, or agree who should make such an assessment. Even if indicators could be agreed, the fact that SDT represents a balance between a country's needs and the damage to others from relaxing an agreed rule means that the boundary must be negotiated. If countries attempt to define criteria, the choice of criteria will be influenced by their knowledge of where they will fall.

Formally defining which countries are eligible, and then a procedure for graduating them would cause controversy, and there are contradictory criteria for such definitions (Monyakane, 2006). Furthermore, two changes which have failed to occur have also stimulated renewed interest in special arrangements for developing countries. First, the formation of bilateral free trade agreements between developed and developing countries such as the North Atlantic Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA), the EU's FTAs with South Africa, the Africa Growth and Opportunities Act (AGOA) etc. These bilateral agreements have the potential to erode preferences. Second, the general decline in tariffs and other barriers to trade, which was expected to decrease the value of preference, has not reached commodities in key sectors particularly agriculture and textiles and clothing that are key exports for many developing countries (Kleen & Page, 2005). As noted earlier in this section, the SDT is discussed in more detail in the next chapter. However, for the purposes of discussions in this section, there are three types of SDT arrangements addressing different needs:

- Increased access to developed country markets: this increases trade benefits;
- Decreasing the costs imposed by the international system: this improves the ratio of benefits to costs of the global system for these countries; and

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- Permission to adopt policies that would otherwise be against WTO rules and procedures because they decrease the benefits other countries can receive from trade: this shifts the balance between promoting countries' own interests and conserving a fair-trading mechanism for all in favour of developing countries.

The aforementioned types of SDT are discussed in more detail in the next chapter with emphasis on assessing the degree to which developing countries have benefited from its existence. The next section discusses adjustments to the operationalization of the DSU.

2.4.3 Adjustments to the Operation of the DSS

Since its creation, some adjustments have been made to the operational framework of the DSU. Some of these changes are discussed in this section. The rules and procedures that govern the settlement of trade disputes have been adjusted since the Uruguay Round through actual practice, particularly with respect to certain landmark Appellate Body decisions, and through what is regarded as the 'Jara' process. The Appellate Body set a critical precedent when it ruled that panels may consider *amicus* briefs. This is a principle that it stated in 1998 in the case of United States – Import Prohibition of Certain Shrimp and Shrimp Products⁴⁶ and affirmed in different subsequent cases. The Appellate Body found that the panels' comprehensive authority to seek information from any important source (as provided in Article 13) and to add to or depart from the Working Procedures in DSU as provided in Article 12.1 permits panels to accept or reject information and advice even if it was unsolicited. This remains a contentious issue among WTO member countries and see no role for any other parties, stakeholders or experts, and are wary of any involvement on the part of NGOs. Developing countries, particularly, tend to take a cautious perspective on this point.

Even more critical was the Appellate Body's 1997 determination in *European Communities – Regime for the Importation, Sale and Distribution of Bananas* that members can be represented by outside counsel.⁴⁷ When Saint Lucia first tried to bring in private lawyers during the panel deliberations this was broadly resisted, but the Appellate Body permitted it and thus changed the nature of dispute settlement cases. It said that there are no provisions in the WTO Agreement, in the DSU, or in the Working Procedures "that outline who can represent a government in making its presentations in

⁴⁶ See United States – Import Prohibition of Certain Shrimp and Shrimp Products: Report of the Appellate Body, WTO document WT/DS58/AB/R, 12 October 1998.

⁴⁷ See United States – Import Prohibition of Certain Shrimp and Shrimp Products: Report of the Appellate Body, WTO document WT/DS58/AB/R, 12 October 1998.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

an oral hearing of the Appellate Body”, nor could it find any “previous GATT panel report which speaks specifically to this matter in the context of panel meetings with parties”. It further indicated that:

“representation by counsel of a government’s own choice may well be a matter of particular importance –especially for developing-country members- to enable them to full participate in dispute settlement proceedings. Moreover, considering the AB’s mandate to review only matters of law or legal representation in panel reports, it is especially critical for governments to be represented by qualified counsel in AB proceedings”.⁴⁸

The aforementioned statement from the AB has resulted in trade lawyers in private practice becoming accredited to a member’s WTO delegation for purposes of pursuing a case with the DSS. This also provides an indirect way by which the WTO partially and indirectly relaxes the general rule that disputes are solely pursued state-to-state, without a private right of action. Private firms and trade associations still have no independent standing in the WTO, but they may nonetheless ask member countries to bring complaints on their behalf (Van Grassek, 2013). When making such a request, they can now promise to underwrite the often-significant legal costs associated with such a case. *This may provide a reason why developing countries are less reluctant to bring formal complaints in the WTO.* Essentially, legal costs associated with filing or processing cases with the WTO is one of the significant barriers to development of trade infrastructure in developing countries and their perceived exclusion from the benefits of multilateral trade. Under the GATT period, such a country might not even have had a permanent mission in Geneva, much less one staffed with an experienced litigator, but matters are quite distinct when both the expertise and the bankroll can be outsourced.

The *Jara* Process is another adjustment to the operation of the DSU. Coined after Deputy Director-General Alejandro Jara, the objective of the *Jara* process is to make the dispute settlement procedures more efficient and less expensive. The main concern here are the burdens imposed by a more judicialized system, as measured both by the time that panelists must commit and the budgetary costs of translating and even transporting the documents. Some panelists report that the paperwork or paper trail they receive from the parties is excessive, some of which are irrelevant to the case in question (Van Grassek, 2013). These concerns were at the core of broad consultations carried out by Alejandro Jara to streamline the dispute settlement process to make it more efficient for relevant

⁴⁸ See European Communities – Regime for the Importation, Sale and Distribution of Bananas: Report of the Appellate Body, WTO Document WT/DS27/AB/R, 9 September.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

stakeholders. This is a useful instance of how reforms and innovations may create demand for new changes to the existing system. It is essential to note that the creation of the AB represents one of the reforms to the DSU.

Another adjustment to the DSU concerns the issue of 'double-briefing', a process in which parties' first written submissions, coupled with rebuttals and the submissions of third parties, are sent to a panel before first hearing. This is one of the reforms that emerged from Alejandro Jara's consultations. According to Jara (2012), "this reform would probably delay the first hearing with the parties given the time it takes for AB to read through all submissions; however, it speeds up the panel process by moving forward the maturity of the parties' discussion on the critical issues, thus probably eliminating some exchanges at the written question and answer phase". It might also forestall the need for a second hearing. Another reform concerns early questions for the panel meeting. Panels generally utilize the first substantive meeting to determine fundamental factual and legal questions, and sometimes the parties are not prepared to answer panelists' questions at these meetings (Jara 2012). It was therefore suggested that panels provide in advance a list of questions that might be posed. Other critical reforms include the use of electronic means to file cases, time limits on oral statements, advance distribution of a proposed agenda or structure for the meeting, page limits for executive summaries, and decrease in the number of annexes. These reforms have not only sped up the adjudication process for trade disputes but also reduced the paperwork involved. Having discussed extensively, the critical reforms or adjustments to the DSU process, the next section addresses the inherent challenges with the DSU; some of which have been highlighted in this section.

2.5 Challenges with the DSS

One of the defining features of the DSS is the shared commitment of all concerned stakeholders to the belief that a rules-based framework for international trade is a global public good that can be sustained only by a predictable, fair and prompt adjudication of trade-related disputes between member countries. In line with the vision of the drafters of the operational framework for the DSU, the WTO DSS ought to be central in improving the security and certainty of international trade, by preserving the rights and obligations of members coupled with clarifying the provisions as they exist in covered agreements (Bhatia, 2017). One of the promises of the WTO DSU is that it is supposed to be prompt when dealing with trade disputes between member countries given the relationship between commerce and money. However, this has not been the case given its complex and expensive procedures that discourage some ill-equipped countries from engaging with it. In fact, over the last couple of years, the Appellate Body has continuously informed its members that given its limited resources (especially in terms of qualified personnel)

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

available to it, the increase in appeals is steadily resulting in considerable delays in processing these complaints (Bhatia, 2017). The mismatch between the resources available to the Appellate Body and the number, size and complexity of appeals has considerably intensified in recent times. Essentially, large and complex appeals usually require a large legal teams and support staff hence, prolonged delays may be expected for some appeals given the Appellate Body's limited resources.

Building on the above, another challenge faced by the DSU concerns the limited resources available to the Appellate Body (AB), the chief organ for adjudicating over trade disputes between member countries. Over the past few years, the AB has repeatedly informed WTO members that, in view of the limited resources at its disposal, the increasing build-up of appeals is steadily leading to considerable delays in their disposal. The mismatch between AB resources and the number, size and complexity of appeals has considerably intensified this year. In view of the number of cases coupled with their complexity, the AB lacks the resources –especially personnel- to quickly adjudicate over cases (Bhatia, 2017). Essentially, the workload of the AB is huge and this is likely to lead to delays in adjudicating over pending cases. The consequential delays in handling appeals carry far-reaching implications not only for the dispute settlement process of the WTO, but also for the WTO itself. For one, some member countries may benefit from the delays at the expense of another member(s). To further highlight the importance of reducing delays in addressing appeals, the representative from the Republic of Korea remarked during the DSB meeting on 31st August 2015:

“Long delays created perverse incentives by lowering the cost of adopting and maintaining WTO-inconsistent measures. Interest groups seeking protection would pressure Members to adopt these measures, insisting rightly, that they would not be subject to review by the WTO for years. Members could therefore expect more protectionist measures, and more, not less, disputes brought to the WTO”.

Based on the statement above, delays in addressing cases or appeals can impose significant costs on the member country affected especially the complainant. Bhati (2017) suggests that when delays in WTO dispute resolution become the standard, they cast doubt on the importance of the WTO's rules-based system itself. Basically, an erosion of trust in this system can result in the re-emergence of power orientation in the multilateral trading system. Such delays could lead to affected member countries looking for other solutions that are outside the legal and institutional framework of the WTO, such as taking unilateral action. Again, Bhati (2017) notes that developing countries tend to suffer the most from delays in processing cases. Given the inherent negative effects of delays in addressing trade disputes, Zimmerman (2006) stresses the importance of concerted

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

action by member countries to address the capacity constraints of the DSU, particularly the Appellate Body. In a rapidly changing international trade environment, and a sustained increase in dispute settlement activity, it is critical that adaptations are made whenever required, so that the DSS can continue to respond properly to the dynamic environment. Addressing the capacity constraints within the AB represents a reform to strengthen the WTO's dispute settlement instrument.

The DSU also faces the fundamental question of whether the DSU should operate on a 'power orientation' basis or 'rules-based' basis. For the purposes of clarity, the rules-based route implies significant dependence on procedural and material rules for the settlement of trade disputes, ideally involving independent third-party adjudication. On the other hand, the power-orientation route is largely dependent on political negotiations and consequently, on the political power of the parties involved. In such a situation, the part of procedural and material rules for the settlement of disputes is restricted. The role and independence of third-party adjudication is also subject to narrow limits in a power-oriented situation. The power-oriented approach was prevalent during the GATT but replaced with the rules-based approach under the WTO. Some developing country members appear to favour the rules-based route over the power-oriented route because powerful members can impose their position and interest on less powerful members. In fact, this was what gave birth to the adoption of the rules-based approach in the operationalization of the DSU.

While the current rules-based approach of the DSU is intended to create a level playing field for all members so that all interests and considerations are treated in a fair and equitable manner. Despite this, concerns remain about the enforcement of judgments reached by the DSU. There are concerns that some members, especially developed countries, may be slow or lackadaisical about their compliance with the rulings of the appellate body (Zimmerman, 2006). Different proposals to strengthen the compliance and the enforcement of material WTO law have been submitted, mostly by emerging or developing countries. Their fundamental rationale for improving compliance is to increase the cost of a violation for defendants and thus, the incentives for prompt compliance. At the same time, they seek to ensure that reciprocity is maintained and that the negotiated balance of rights and obligations is protected. These submissions include proposals on collective retaliation, freedom of cross-retaliation, retroactive determination and application of nullification and impairment, including the allocation of litigation expenses, mandatory (financial) compensation, including for measures withdrawn during proceedings; and the negotiability of the right to suspend concessions or other

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

obligations.⁴⁹ In conclusion, some of these proposals for strengthening the enforceability of DSU rulings may be challenging to adopt and implement. These proposals share a similar trait in that they would restrict the capacity of Members to reach policy objectives by means of trade policy interventions in contravention of WTO disciplines.

Another challenge with the DSS concerns associated political costs of retaliatory measures or confronting a powerful WTO member. This challenge can be analyzed using the 'power hypothesis' where less powerful countries find themselves in a weak negotiating position relative to powerful members. Furthermore, least developed countries may lack the capacity to bear the costs of pursuing complaints through the DSS coupled with reluctance to cause frictions or conflict in its international relations. This is not surprising especially as the enforcement mechanism of the system leaves the responsibility for retaliation solely on the complainant. Least developed or poorer countries also tend to be less sophisticated than their richer or high-income counterparts; consequently, poorer countries lack the legal infrastructure to pursue cases through the WTO's DSS given the complexity of its procedures or requirements (Davey, 2009). Essentially, least developed countries tend to be less familiar with the complex provisions of GATT and other WTO agreements, and of the inter-governmental dispute settlement mechanism provided by the WTO.

Furthermore, developing countries are also discouraged from engaging with the WTO DSU because most of them do not have the required domestic mechanisms to identify and communicate trade barriers to WTO lawyers. With respect to this challenge, Shaffer & Melendez-Ortiz (2012) recommends that developing countries request the assistance of development agencies and foundations to address this gap. Another approach to dealing with this gap was suggested by Abbot (2009) who advised that an independent Special Prosecutor or Advocate could be engaged to identify potential breaches of WTO rules on behalf of developing countries. Reich (2017) carried out a study to determine the correlation between a country's GDP and GNI with number of complaints filed with WTO's DSU and found a positive correlation between both variables. Essentially, the political costs associated with confronting another WTO member are challenging to bear for a country with a low GDP than a country with a high GDP. Furthermore, countries with a large GDP are equipped to leverage the WTO's enforcement mechanism to retaliate against discriminatory measures by another member country. The economic divide between countries with high and low GDP also influences the degree of their engagement with the WTO's DSU. In addition to limited economic power, the legal and administrative costs associated with filing complaints through the DSU – especially with respect to

⁴⁹ See TN/DS/W/33 (Ecuador); and TN/DS/W/29, No.2 (China)

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

possessing the in-house legal expertise required- also discourages low GDP countries from active engagement with the DSS.

Aside from the above challenges, a major challenge which the DSU currently faces is the obstruction from powerful nations such as the United States which considers the appellate body to be overreaching in interpreting WTO rules. The US government therefore refused to support new appointments to the appellate body, leaving it without the quorum necessary to function properly. This has resulted in a growing backlog of unresolved cases. The appellate body is a crucial component of the global trading system, and its paralysis threatens to undermine the rules-based nature of international trade (Lester, 2022). WTO members are pushing for resolution of the impasse. At a meeting of the DSU on 28th March 2023, a large group of members expressed concern over the lingering crisis arguing that the continued delay in resolving the crisis was damaging to the interest of members and to the multilateral trading system (WTO,2023b).

2.6 Developing Countries and Engagement with the DSS

Effective utilization of the WTO's DSS relies on useful collaboration among various governmental agencies as well as between public and private sectors. In other words, the decision to file a complaint with the DSU is the responsibility of the governments of member countries. Essentially, it is the responsibility of the governments of member countries to identify a case, evaluate its validity, determine if the case should be filed with the DSU, and ultimately manage the litigation process. This is why information management is a critical aspect of the litigation process when pursuing cases through the DSU (Shaffer & Melendez-Ortiz, 2012). This case-specific information is usually obtained from industry/sector players and legal advisors coupled with historical knowledge on the part of the country concerned. Consequently, there are fixed costs associated with obtaining this information coupled with understanding of WTO DSU processes (Davis & Bermeo, 2009). The capacity to meet these costs is required to effectively engage with dispute settlement processes. Davis (2009) further notes that the member countries that find it challenging to effectively engage with dispute settlement processes are the developing countries because the lack the experience and legal expertise require to formally pursue complaints. Developing countries have also been known to be weak when it comes to prioritizing litigation coordination. Having said this, it is essential to note that age-old maxim of 'learning by doing' is key to improving developing countries engagement with the DSU. This implies that when developing countries are repeat players -in terms of making the effort to pursue complaints through the DSS- they will over time develop the experience and knowledge required to improve institutional

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

arrangements, especially at the national level, to address market access barriers they face in international markets.

The WTO experience of Pakistan – a developing member country- exemplifies the effectiveness of learning by doing. The first case filed by Pakistan as a sole complainant was against the US concerning a transitional safeguard measure on combed cotton yarn from Pakistan (*US-Cotton yarn*).⁵⁰ Before this particular occasion, Pakistan had already filed two cases under the GATT and joined a WTO case with multiple complainants.⁵¹ It is worth noting that at the time of filing the complaint in the US-cotton yarn case, Pakistan did not have any institutional framework within its Ministry of Commerce to deal with trade-related disputes. However, during the course of the dispute including engagement with the WTO's dispute settlement mechanism, it was able to establish WTO departments in the permanent mission in Geneva and the Ministry of Commerce; thus, strengthening its national trade policy infrastructure to deal with international trade disputes. To further reiterate the effectiveness of learning by doing, the Pakistan Ambassador highlighted the experience accruing to the country from its engagement with dispute settlement processes:

“It is encouraging when we get positive results, so we are more likely to see dispute settlement as an effective strategy. We know about the selection of lawyers and how to enter consultations. If it were the first time we would be completely lost but if we have experience, it helps...”

In addition to the Pakistan's experience, it is equally essential to note that WTO's DSS has been effective in resolving trade disputes between developing countries and developed countries despite the existence of the issue of 'power hypothesis' earlier discussed in this chapter. Costa Rica's trade dispute with the United States in a case involving the use of transitional safeguard provisions for cotton underwear (i.e. *US – Underwear Case*).⁵² At the time the complaint was filed by Costa Rica, Costa Rican officials were reluctant to pursue the case given wariness around harming relations with a powerful nation as the US. However, trade ministry officials decided to pursue the case as a way of demonstrating the transparent and unbiased nature of the WTO's dispute

⁵⁰ World Trade Organization – Dispute Settlement: Dispute DS192 'United States – Transitional Safeguard Measure on Combed Cotton Yarn from Pakistan', <http://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/dispu_e/cases_e/ds192_e.htm> accessed 11 December 2012

⁵¹ World Trade Organization – Dispute Settlement: Dispute DS58 'United States – Import Prohibition of Certain Shrimp and Shrimp Products', http://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/dispu_e/cases_e/ds58_e.htm accessed 11 December 2012

⁵² World Trade Organization – Dispute Settlement: Dispute DS24 'United States Restriction on Imports of Cotton and Man-made Fibre Underwear' <http://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/dispu_e/cases_e/ds24_e.htm> accessed 12 December 2012

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

settlement system. Despite concerns around engaging with the DSS, Costa Rica utilized mechanisms available to it as a member country and was able to resolve the dispute.

It is also necessary to note that there are situations where the consequences of not pursuing a complaint outweighs the high cost of filing the complaint. Referring back to the US-Cotton underwear case between Costa Rica and the US, the Costa Rican government had to pursue the case or it risked losing about US\$100mn worth of trade.⁵³ Furthermore, the case involving Ecuador illustrates this point in the banana case where its engagement with the WTO's dispute settlement helped in reducing losses due to restrictions imposed by the European Union.⁵⁴ The WTO DSS has also proven effective in resolving trade disputes between member countries through mediation. One example of this is the case of Thailand regarding export of Tuna to the European Community (now referred to as the European Union). The participants in this particular case were Thailand and Philippines versus the EC.⁵⁵ The initial difficulty faced by Thailand concerned how to persuade the EC to engage in formal discussions on the matter. After this challenge had been surmounted, a formal letter requesting mediation was jointly submitted to the Director General (DG) of the WTO. Following this, the matter was resolved amicably between all parties involved without having to go the whole length of formal dispute settlement processes. Again, this example shows how developing countries leveraged their WTO rights to resolve trade disputes with developed countries. Following the resolution of the dispute with the European Community, Thailand's Minister of Commerce notably remarked:

"...in resorting to the dispute settlement process, we did not seek to confront, but opted for friendly persuasion and understanding. After all, the EC is one of our major trading partners, and a very important consumer not only of Thai tuna but in other sectors as well. We intended to avoid at all costs doing anything that would jeopardize our long-standing and good relationship with the EU."⁵⁶

Having discussed and examined developing countries' engagement with the WTO DSU, it is equally necessary to streamline discussions involving African countries' engagement with this dispute settlement instrument. This is done in the next section.

⁵³ Anabel Gonzalez - Costa Rican Legal Team in the Underwear Case telephone interview by Davis and Bermeo, 11 August 2008 cited in Christina Davis and Sarah Bermeo (n 50) 1038

⁵⁴ James Smith 'Compliance Bargaining in the WTO: Ecuador and the Bananas Dispute' [2006] GWU 3

⁵⁵ Nilaratna Xuto, 'Thailand Conciliating a Dispute on Tuna Export to the EC' in Peter Gallagher, Patrick Low and Andrew Stoler (eds), *Managing the Challenges of WTO Participation: 45 Case Studies* (CUP 2005)

⁵⁶ Nilaratna Xuto, 'Thailand Conciliating a Dispute on Tuna Export to the EC' in Peter Gallagher, Patrick Low and Andrew Stoler (eds), *Managing the Challenges of WTO Participation: 45 Case Studies* (CUP 2005)

2.6.1 Africa and Engagement with the DSS

In the previous section, developing countries' engagement with the DSS was discussed extensively. Discussions highlighted examples of situations where the DSS has resolved trade disputes between member countries especially between developing and developed countries. At this point, discussions will be deepened by examining the experience of Africa where most parties are developing countries.

African countries have largely been less engaged with the WTO DSS over the last twenty years. Some of the studies already discussed in this document pointed several reasons for this including low volume of trade and weak national trade infrastructure. As highlighted in the first chapter, Africa accounts for about 2% of global trade with an export base that is largely characterized by non-contentious single unprocessed or unrefined commodities.⁵⁷ Low trade volume on the continent acts as a disincentive to full and active engagement with the various processes and procedures of the WTO including the dispute settlement mechanism. Another factor that has repeatedly been identified as the reason for Africa's low engagement with the WTO's dispute settlement processes concerns the expensive and complicated nature of the underlying procedures. Mosoti (2005) notes that, on average, pursuing litigation procedures through the DSU could cost about US\$500,000. This high cost coupled with the lack of experience and legal expertise also explains Africa's low engagement with the process. Although developing countries' engagement with the process has improved over the years, the same cannot be said for developing countries in the African continent. Abdul-Latif (2021) further opines that the limited participation of African countries in the DSS could be symptomatic of deeper structural economic weaknesses in the continent, and perhaps not necessarily a reflection of the failure of the DSS itself. Having stated this, the limited involvement of African countries in the DSS could serve as a negative factor for the long term 'predictability' function of the WTO and could undermine the usefulness of the process eventually. It is therefore in the interest of all member countries to put in place measures to support full and active participation of African countries in the DSS especially given the number of African member countries that make up the WTO.

Since 1995, over 600 disputes have been filed with the DSS and over 350 rulings have been issued.⁵⁸ This number includes all complaints initiating a formal proceeding by one or more members against another member. As noted earlier whilst looking at the

⁵⁷ International Trade Center, 2019

⁵⁸ WTO Dispute Settlement. Accessed from:

https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/dispu_e/dispu_e.htm#:~:text=The%20WTO%20has%20one%20of,350%20rulings%20have%20been%20issued. <13 November 2022>

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

operational structure of the WTO's dispute settlement processes, once a petition is filed with the WTO, informal consultations between parties outside the WTO have proven unsuccessful and the formal dispute resolution process of the DSS has been deemed necessary by the complaining party. This is not the situation in the large number of disputes that get resolved at the consultations phase, formally within the WTO or even bilaterally. Under these circumstances, negotiating in the shadow of the WTO law has usually aided the parties involved in arriving at a mutual resolution that the parties involved accept. Furthermore, there have been over 55 standard adopted Appellate Body reports, and over 10 Article 21.5 Appellate Body reports, and over 80 adopted panel reports.⁵⁹ In all these processes, Africa's participation has been very low. Table 2 shows that no African country has ever been a complainant in any dispute and in only 6 cases has an African country been a respondent. Out of the 6 disputes, Egypt was a respondent in 4 while South Africa was a respondent in 2. Given this information, Egypt appears to be one of the most experienced African countries when it comes to engaging with the WTO's DSS.

Table 2.1: Disputes in which an African Country was a respondent or Complainant

Country	Dispute	Complainant	Respondent
Egypt	Egypt -Anti-dumping on duties on matches from Pakistan (WT/DS327)		X
Egypt	Egypt -Measures affecting imports of textile and apparel products (WT/DS305)		X
Egypt	Egypt -Definitive anti-dumping measures on steel rebar from Turkey (WT/DSS211)		X
Egypt	Egypt -Import prohibition on canned Tuna with Soybean oil from Thailand (WT/DS205)		X
Egypt	Egypt - Egypt — Registration requirements relating to the importation of certain products from the European Union (WT/DS609)		X

⁵⁹ John Jackson, "Dispute Settlement and the WTO: Emerging Problems", 1(3) Journal of International Economic Law (1998) 329-351, 340.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

South Africa	South Africa -Anti-dumping duties on certain pharmaceutical products from India (WT/DS168)		X
South Africa	South Africa -Definitive anti-dumping measures on blanketing from Turkey (WT/DS288)		X
South Africa	South Africa — Anti-Dumping Duties on Frozen Meat of Fowls from Brazil (WT/DS439)		X
South Africa	South Africa - Anti-Dumping Measures on Uncoated Woodfree Paper from Pakistan (WT/DS374)		X
South Africa	South Africa – Provisional Anti-Dumping Duties on Portland Cement from Pakistan (WT/DS/500)		X
South Africa	European union — Measures concerning the importation of citrus fruit from South Africa (WT/DS613)	X	
Tunisia	Morocco — Provisional Anti-Dumping Measures on School Exercise Books from Tunisia (WT/DS555)	X	
Tunisia	Morocco — Definitive Anti-Dumping Measures on School Exercise Books from Tunisia (WT/DS578)	X	
Totals		3	10

Source: WTO

Despite the low participation of African countries in pursuing disputes through the WTO DSS, one area where African countries have been relative active with respect to WTO dispute settlement processes is their participation as third parties in the settlement of trade disputes between WTO member countries. Based on the information in Table 2.2, 15 African countries have been involved as third parties in 10 disputes over the last ten years. Nigeria was involved as a third party in two disputes while Mauritius has been involved in five disputes.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Table 2.2: Dispute in which an African Country was a Third Party

Country	Dispute (Panel/AB)	Total
Cameroon, Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, Senegal	<i>European Communities- Regime for the Importation, Sale and Distribution of Bananas (WT/DS27/R/)</i> (Panel & AB)	4
Nigeria, Senegal,	<i>United States-Import Prohibition of Certain Shrimp and Shrimp Products (WT/DS58/R)</i> (Panel & AB)	2
Cameroon, Côte d'Ivoire, Mauritius	<i>European Communities-Regime for the Importation, Sale and Distribution of Bananas (WT/DS27/RW/EEC)</i> (panel)	3
Mauritius	<i>Mexico-Anti-dumping Investigation of High Fructose Corn Syrup (HFCS) from the United States (WT/DS132/R)</i> (Panel)	1
Egypt	<i>European Communities-Antidumping Duties on Imports of Bed Linen from India (WT/DS141/R)</i> (Panel & AB)	1
Zimbabwe	<i>European Communities-Measures Affecting Asbestos and Asbestos-Containing Products (WT/DS135/R)</i> (Panel & AB)	1
Mauritius	<i>European Communities-Conditions for of Tariff Preferences to Developing Countries (WT/DS246/R)</i> (Panel & AB)	1
Benin, Chad	<i>U.S-Subsidies on Upland Cotton, (WT/DS267/R)</i> (Panel)	2
Côte d'Ivoire, Madagascar, Tanzania, Malawi, Mauritius, Swaziland, Kenya	<i>European Communities-Export Subsidies on Sugar (WT/DS265/R)</i> (Panel)	7
Totals: 15	10	

Source: WTO

Often, African countries involvement in trade disputes has mainly been as observers, but in a few cases, certain countries actually made substantive submissions in the resolution of disputes; for instance, Nigeria in the *Shrimp* case⁶⁰ and Egypt in the *Bed Linen* case. Nigeria was a third party in the United States-Imports of Certain Shrimp and Shrimp Products case, both at the panel level and Appellate levels. In the panel hearing, Nigeria stated that it shared the unanimous concern for the conservation and protection of sea turtles. However, this particular dispute did not relate to the desirability of protecting and conserving sea turtles but rather to the methods and measures for doing so. In this respect, Nigeria supported the multilateral approach to conservation as explained in the 1996 report of the Committee on Trade and Environment.

Another area that highlights Africa's limited involvement in WTO dispute settlement processes concerns their participation as members of the panel or as members of the Appellate Body in the resolution of trade disputes between member countries (see Table 4). In fact, only seven Africans from three African countries (Egypt, Mauritius, and South Africa) (see Table 2.3). Their participation was even dismal under the GATT as only three

⁶⁰ States-Imports of Certain Shrimp and Shrimp Products, Panel Report, WTO Doc. WT/DS58/R, (15 May 1998).

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Africans served as panel members during the period of GATT. Mr. G.O Niyi was one of these three Africans and he later went on to become the Chief Executive of the Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC). He served as one of the GATT panelists in the *United Kingdom-Dollar Area Quotas* dispute in 1973.⁶¹

Table 2.3: African Countries Participation in the Appellate Body as Panelists

Country	Panellists and No. of Disputes Served in	Panel Disputes in which they Served	AB Members	Total
Egypt	M. Abdel-Fattah 6	<i>Brazil-Coconut; Canada-Aircraft; Canada-Aircraft (Art. 21.5); EC-Pipe Fittings; Indonesia-Autos; U.S-Byrd Amendment; U.S-Wheat Gluten.</i>	S. El-Naggar (1995-2000)	4
	M. Shahin 1		G. Abi-Saab (2000-present)	
Mauritius	U. Dwarka-Canabady 2	<i>Canada-Aircraft II; U.S-Wheat Gluten</i>		1
South Africa	J. Human 4	<i>Guatemala-Cement II; Turkey-Textiles; U.S-1916 Anti-dumping Act; U.S-Underwear</i>		4
	C. McCarthy 1		<i>Chile – Alcohol</i>	
	A. Swart 1		<i>EC-Butter</i>	
	D. Unterhalter 1		<i>U.S-Steel Sunset Review</i>	
Totals			2	9

Source: WTO

Overall, the information presented in this section indicates that the participation of African countries in the WTO DSS has been very low compared to developing countries in Asia. This was equally the case under the GATT. Although they have never participated as either a complainant or respondent, they have been actively involved as third parties and observers in trade disputes. Increased involvement in the DSS -in line with the notion of learning by doing as exemplified by Pakistan- is key to building African countries' experience in WTO dispute settlement processes. This is the only way that they can build the experience and national policy infrastructure required to pursue cases through the DSS in response to market access barriers faced by their exports.

⁶¹ United Kingdom-Dollar Area Quotas, (L/3891 - 20S/236) Report of the Panel adopted on 30 July 1973.

2.7 Evaluating the Effectiveness of the WTO's Dispute Settlement System: Issues Arising

The legalized WTO dispute settlement system (DSS) is widely viewed as a recent development in global economic relations in which law, more than power, might reign. In fact, trade law represents an advancement in international law. While the DSS is seen as a mechanism for promoting law and order in international trade, concerns have been expressed over its effectiveness in adjudicating over trade disputes between WTO member countries. One of such concerns deals with the degree to which smaller countries -which lack market power- are adequately protected by this legal framework for international trade relations. As highlighted earlier in this research report and related to this concern is the degree to which developing, poorer or smaller countries can mobilize the legal capacity and financial resources required to pursue a case through the WTO's somewhat complicated procedure for settling trade disputes between member countries. Shaffer (2005) notes that the increased legalization of the process for settling trade disputes does not come without costs; the demands on human resources have significantly increased for a member country that seeks to invoke its international trading rights. Although the legalization of WTO dispute settlement constitutes a significant achievement in international law, the system remains far from a neutral technocratic process with respect to its actual operation.

Developed and richer countries seem to be better positioned to exploit the resource-demanding procedures of the DSS legal framework and have, not surprisingly, done so. Referring back to Mexico's ban of Hibiscus flower or zobo leaves from Nigeria, it is necessary to note that although Nigeria made a complaint to the WTO about this, it was unable to follow through with this complaint due to limited legal and financial capacity. This ban was only recently addressed bilaterally between both countries outside the WTO's dispute settlement framework. Like Nigeria, many developing countries - especially African countries- face similar constraints especially when having a dispute with a richer or developed country. It is equally necessary to note that SPS framework sits within the WTO's legal framework for international trade hence, countries can exploit the SPS agreement to implement measures that are challenging to determine as protectionist by poorer exporting countries.

Absolute trading stakes appears to be the main determinant of a WTO member country's use of the DSS. Some studies (e.g. Nordstrom & Mavroidis, 1999) suggest, however, that a residual explanation for discrepancies in participation lies in the increased difficulty that developing or poor countries face in mobilizing the required financial and legal resources to take part in an increasingly complex legal system. Nordstrom & Mavroidis (1999) note

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

that the seeming over representation by richer countries, or the mirror image under-representation of developing countries, to a significant degree reflect the differences in the diversity and value of trade. Essentially, the bigger a WTO member country's economic stakes in the system, the more likely that member will invest in developing and mobilizing legal resources, including through coordinating with its private sector and outside legal counsel.

For much of the literature review in this document, the term 'developing countries' has been used to describe nations that lack the financial resources or legal capacity to effectively engage with the WTO's DSS to benefit from international trade. Having clarified this, it is necessary to note that the term 'developing country' does not clearly differentiate between those who are more likely to benefit from the WTO legal system's use. For instance, some developing countries, such as Brazil, India, and China, may have low per capita income, but they nonetheless have the capacity to defend their interests (than other developing countries) in the international trade landscape as a result of the scale and scope of their markets and economies. These countries have relatively higher aggregate trading stakes than most countries in Africa. Put simply, developed countries and countries with economic scope seem to be better positioned to leverage existing WTO instruments, including dispute settlement mechanisms, to protect their trade interests. Even relatively small developed countries, such as New Zealand, Norway and Switzerland, possess the domestic legal and financial capacity to effectively engage with the WTO's DSU to protect their trade interests.

Although some of the studies highlighted in this literature review suggest that richer countries are better positioned to effectively and fully engage with the WTO's DSS compared to developing or poorer countries, some studies -such as Busch & Reinhardt, (2003)- suggest that a complainant's income, financial capacity and market size has limited impact on its prospects of winning judgment through the DSU. Furthermore Busch & Reinhardt (2003) note that there is limited evidence of political bias in the judicial system itself. The same study also suggests that a complainant that is a developed country has no special advantage over a poor but equal-sized complainant in securing compliance from the defendant found to have violated WTO laws and obligations. Despite these findings, Bown (2004) notes that developing countries have been less able to settle complaints advantageously during the consultation phase of the dispute settlement process. Given the well-established constraints that developing countries in Africa face with respect to engagement with the WTO's DSS, it may be in their interest to explore the possibility of bilateral settlement of disputes with a WTO member country before considering pursuing the process in its entirety.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Although it has been established by some of the studies discussed in this research that resource and capacity constraints are among the main factors limiting many African countries from fully and effectively engaging with the WTO's dispute settlement process, Busch & Reinhardt (2000) suggest that one of the ways that such countries can improve their capacity to engage with the process is through participation. Participation in the WTO dispute settlement system is helpful in three main respects. Firstly, it matters in specific adjudication to the degree that WTO legal decisions affect particular economic outcomes, as they have done. Busch & Reinhardt (2000) note that two-thirds of complaints ending prior to a ruling (whether before or after the creation of an appellate panel) exhibited full or partial concessions by the defendant. Furthermore, Bown (2004) note that statistical regressions have shown that these concessions have mattered economically. Secondly, and more broadly, participation matters where WTO jurisprudence determines the interpretation, application and public perceptions of the law over time, and thus influences future bargaining positions with respect to these understandings (Galanter, 2001). Put simply, in similar vein as national or domestic law, the result of a specific WTO case possesses both a tangible component and a systemic one. The tangible component indicates that a measure is found either to violate or comply with a legal obligation, and if it is in violation, results in a remedy (Galanter, 2001). The systemic component, on the other hand, affects the understanding of the law's application in subsequent cases, as well as for future bargaining in the shadow of potential litigation. Thirdly, WTO laws and rules influence bilateral and national political bargaining in the shadow of a potential case without any formal complaint being filed. It is necessary to note that the WTO's legal framework offers domestic or national governments leverage over economic sectors that demand protection.

Domestic governments can now argue that such protection is costly because it can lead to authorized trade retaliation (Shaffer, 2005). It also generally offers strategic actors with arguments that they may use in domestic political debates as it concerns regulatory initiatives (Shaffer, 2005). Essentially, WTO law, jurisprudence and legal procedures ultimately influence bilateral bargaining over trade disputes carried out in the legal system's shadow (Busch & Reinhardt, 2000). This particular observation applies to many countries in Africa with respect to ensuring that even as they pursue litigation through the WTO's DSS, they should be open to bilateral negotiations with defendants. As shown earlier in this report with respect to the *Hibiscus dispute* between Nigeria and Mexico, bilateral engagements at the country level can negate the need for pursuing redress through the WTO's dispute settlement process in its entirety. Basically, WTO members are encouraged to leverage a two-pronged approach consisting of both litigation and negotiation to settle trade disagreements or conflict.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

From the discussions carried out so far in this section, there is limited evidence to suggest that the judgments from the WTO dispute settlement process is politically biased or rigged to favour richer or developed countries. The issue lies with capacity to effectively navigate the complex bureaucracy underlying the process. The bureaucratic nature of the process should not be viewed as an excuse for limited engagement especially as the WTO has put in place mechanisms to provide relief to countries facing resource-related constraints owing to the costly and personnel demands of the process. In addition to leveraging these mechanisms coupled with exploring bilateral settlements with defendants at the consultation phase of the dispute settlement process, African countries can enhance their learning curve through active participation. Active participation in the process provides the basis for gradual strengthening of domestic capacity to effectively engage with the process to resolve market access barriers faced by their agricultural and horticultural commodities in international export markets.

Having reviewed and discussed some of the matters arising from the legitimization of the WTO's dispute settlement system, it is equally important to discuss some of the strengths and weaknesses of the process. Some strengths and weaknesses of the process have been identified in existing literature. Beginning with its strengths, the WTO dispute settlement system has been far more effective than the former dispute settlement system of GATT 1947 given its quasi-judicial and quasi-automatic character that enables it to handle complex trade dispute cases (WTO, 2004). Furthermore, the features of the DSS are such that it offers increased guarantees for WTO member countries that are intent on defending their rights especially where unfair trade practices and unfair technical market access barriers have been identified (WTO, 2004).

Compared with other multilateral and regional systems of dispute resolution in international law, Madhumitha (2020) notes that the compulsory nature and the enforcement mechanism of the WTO dispute settlement system stands out. Despite the identified strengths of the system, weaknesses have also been identified. One of the main weaknesses of the system concerns the length of time to address disputes. Given the extended time it takes to settle disputes owing to its rigorous and bureaucratic process, the complainant suffers economic harm during the adjudication process until judgment is reached. To address this particular challenge, Madhumitha (2020) recommends that the WTO institutes provisional measures -such as interim relief- to protect the trade interests and minimize economic harm to the complainant while the process runs its course. The manner in which this recommendation can be implemented is open to discourse especially considering the difficulty in determining who bears the potential financial cost of interim relief. It is necessary to note that the complainant does not receive any financial

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

compensation nor does the 'winning party' receive any reimbursement from the other party for legal costs incurred during the period of adjudication over the dispute (WTO, 2004). Another weakness of the system concerns effective implementation of judgments and rulings reached by the WTO dispute settlement system. In some cases, a suspension of concessions has proven ineffective in bringing about implementation. However, such cases can be regarded as an exception rather than the rule. Having discussed the theoretical framework underpinning the conduct of this research, the next chapter discusses the methodology used to conduct the study.

2.8 Dispute Settlement Management System

Institutional design

Efficient Dispute Settlement management will depend on the institutional design and framework the WTO member state adopts. This requires engaging specialists in the appropriate institutional framework. It is also essential that those responsible of WTO dispute settlement should be part of the entity responsible of the trade policy.

Dispute Settlement focal point

This is the unit/division/ in the member state responsible for conducting the dispute settlement processes, as well as coordinating with other related institutions, the legal, economic, political and other assessments. The focal point is responsible for coordination at two levels:

- Internal coordination: Ministries and other public entities.
- External coordination: Industry, other local stakeholders, lawyers, and members, WTO.

The unit receives and transmits information to and from the industry and coordinates actions with them; formal procedure of consultation for WTO Dispute

Receives and conveys information to and from other trade related ministries (agriculture, industry, tourism, environment) and coordinates actions with them;

Receives and transmits information to and from Geneva (Delegation, ACWL, WTO, other members)

Delegation in Geneva

The Delegation to the WTO in Geneva is the connection between the capital and organization, between the focal point and WTO Dispute Settlement. The Delegation

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

collects and transmits to the focal point all relevant information and contributes to monitor and process relevant information

WTO committees

These are various WTO Committees in Geneva, which are responsible for monitoring the implementation of WTO Agreements. Member states Delegations engages with these committees in order to keep abreast with other member states trade activities

Advisory Center on WTO Law (ACWL)

Advisory Center in WTO Law (ACWL). It provides excellent legal services for a fraction of the cost of other firms. However, a ACWL Legal adviser cannot substitute the functions of the government representatives to the WTO nor the focal point. Participating in a dispute is ultimately a government decision.

2.9 Chapter Summary

This chapter focused considerably on decision-making processes within the WTO from two main perspectives namely: theoretical/procedural perspective and practical perspective. This chapter helped in understanding the nature of the rules-based system governing international trade and how decisions are made on trade agreements. This chapter is critical because it provides an understanding of the underlying mechanisms through which these rules are established so that the researcher can understand the foundations of these rules with a view to understanding the degree to which developing countries are involved in the process coupled with subsequently understanding challenges with engagement from their perspective. From a theoretical or procedural perspective, Article IX of the WTO Agreement reads as follows: "the WTO shall continue the practice of decision-making by consensus used under the GATT 1947. Except as otherwise provided, where a decision cannot be arrived at by consensus, the matter in question shall be decided by voting. At meetings of the Ministerial Conference and the General Council, each WTO member shall have one vote. Decisions of the Ministerial Conference and the General Council shall be taken by a majority of the votes cast, unless otherwise provided in this Agreement or in the relevant multilateral trade agreement". From a practical perspective, though the WTO Agreement provides for the possibility to take decisions by voting, it is very exceptional for many of its organs to vote. In reality, WTO decisions are taken by consensus. While decision-making by consensus tends to have legitimacy than decisions reached by majority vote because of its democratic nature, the consensus requirement does, of course, make decision-making in the WTO very burdensome and unnecessarily prolonged. The consensus approach to decision-making is no doubt participatory in nature however, it will be unrealistic to involve all 164 members directly in negotiations aimed at reaching an agreement on difficult trade issues. Involving all members in decisions would ultimately make negotiations difficult and ineffective.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

The WTO consists of 164 member countries representing about 99% of the world's population and 98% of global trade; this makes the WTO a universal organization. It was established to strengthen trade relations between different countries with particular attention to eliminating trade barriers and discriminatory treatment in global trade relations. At the core of its functions is expanding trade in goods and services between member countries and in the process, increasing standards of living for citizens of member countries. To effectively carry out the functions and tasks entrusted to the WTO, the WTO Agreement provides for different bodies or organs. There are 35 organs within the WTO consisting of different committees and councils such as the General Council, Ministerial Conference, Committees, trade negotiations committee, appellate body (i.e. dispute settlement panels), council for trade in goods, council for trade in services, council for trade-related aspects of intellectual property rights etc. These organs facilitate the different aspects of trade relations between member countries.

The WTO functions on a rules-based system where rules and laid down procedures govern trade relations between member countries. There are four reasons why a rule-based system for international trade is required. First reason is that countries need to be restrained from adopting restrictive trade practices that damage not only their own interest but also the collective interest. The second reason for having international trade rules is the need to provide security and protection to traders and give predictability to global trade relations. In similar vein as the ease of doing business, having international trade rules give investors and traders alike the confidence to interact or trade with foreign nations. The third reason why rules are required for international trade is the need to integrate a values-based approach to respond to the rising levels of trade and its attendant impact on the environment (i.e. climate change) and public health. Such rules exist to ensure that trade relations do not erode important national values. The fourth reason for having trade rules stems from the need to achieve an increased measure of equity in global economic relations. In the absence of binding rules on developed as well as developing countries, many countries –especially developing ones- would find it challenging to full integrate into the global trade system and derive an equitable share of the gains thereof. However, one of the questions that arose concerned the degree to which these rules are less complex for developing countries to engage with it as a way of addressing restrictions they face in international trade especially when trading with developed countries who have the infrastructure, capital, and human resources (fully staffed delegation with expertise in trade jurisprudence) to fully engage with set international trade rules. This challenge informed the development of one of the research questions for this thesis: “what are the challenges limiting Nigeria from using the WTO's dispute settlement understanding to eliminate market access barriers for its agricultural commodities?”

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

In addition to the underlying laws governing trade relations between member countries, there are rules that member countries must adhere to enhance smooth trade relations between member countries. These rules emanate from existing WTO laws. One of such substantive rules, which is at the core of this research, is the 'dispute settlement understanding (DSU)'. The DSU is arguably the single most important achievement of the Uruguay Round Negotiations especially considering that trade disputes are likely to arise in the international or multilateral trade system. The WTO dispute settlement mechanism is applicable to all disputes between WTO member countries arising under the WTO agreements. The DSU provides for rules on the coverage and scope of the dispute settlement system, its objectives, its administration, and its operations on mandatory pre-litigation consultations, conciliation, and mediation. The DSU also exists to prevent unilateral trade-related actions by member countries.

CHAPTER THREE

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE RESEARCH

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents and discusses the theoretical framework for this research. Existing literature on the agency theory and its applications to international trade are discussed. In doing this, the agency framework provides the funnel for understanding challenges inhibiting developing countries' engagement with the WTO's Dispute Settlement System (DSS). Essentially, data collected for this study will form the basis for examining Nigeria's engagement with the WTO's dispute settlement system. The theory used to achieve this is the principal-agent theory or agency theory. Before discussing the application of the principal-agent theory in international trade, some other useful theoretical frameworks are introduced and discussed to provide an overview of useful theories in international trade.

3.2 Theoretical Frameworks in International Trade

This section of the thesis identifies and discusses some of the useful theories in international trade. Although the main theory that will form the theoretical framework for this research is the 'agency or principal-agent theory', it makes sense to introduce and discuss other useful theories in international trade. The theories introduced and discussed in this section are: transaction cost theory; economics of non-tariff measures; new trade theory; strategic trade and resource dumping; theory of country size; theory of mercantilism; and the agency theory.

3.2.1 Transaction Cost Theory

Transactions are at the core of most business activity given the transactional nature of business enterprise. Taking from the seminal work of Coase (1937) and Williamson (1985), transaction cost theory is one of the most pertinent theories in economics. This is because the theory can be used to understand a wide range of organizational phenomena, including horizontal diversification, the operations of multinational corporations across borders, the formation of strategic alliances, entry mode choices/decisions, supply chain relationships, public private partnerships (PPPs) etc (Cuypers et al., 2020). Beyond business or for-profit activities, the transaction cost theory (TCT) has also been found to be useful in studying and understanding how a range of variables influence governance choices together with the performance consequences of such choices.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Rindfleisch (2019) notes that transaction cost theory indicates that there are costs to carrying out transactions or activities and varying modes of organizing transactions (e.g. within a market, firm or trade environment) entail different costs. Cuypers et al., (2020) notes that the transaction cost theory's fundamental thesis or proposition is that organizational actors attempt to maximize the benefits of interdependence by assigning transactions (i.e. which have varying attributes) to governance structures (i.e. the adaptive capacities and associated costs of which differ) in a discriminatory manner. Building on the behavioural assumptions of bounded rationality and opportunism, Williamson (1985) suggests that transactions will be assigned to governance structures based on three key characteristics namely: (i) asset specificity; (ii) uncertainty; and (iii) frequency. Williamson (1985) further notes that the most critical of these characteristics is 'asset specificity' which refers to the extent of specific investment involved in a given transaction. Essentially, an asset is specific to a particular transaction if its value in its next-best use (i.e. in a transaction with a different party) is lower than in the present transaction, i.e. the higher the difference between the value of an asset in its first-best and next-best use, the higher the degree of asset specificity (Williamson, 1985; Klein et al., 1978).

Earlier in this section, two behavioural assumptions of TCT were highlighted: bounded rationality and opportunism. With respect to bounded rationality, this assumption is based on various perspectives in economic studies such as the costs associated with collecting and analyzing information, and the way this information is accessed by different actors (Holmstrom & Milgrom, 1991; Rindfleisch, 2019). The assumption of bounded reality goes beyond information costs to acknowledge that agents have restrictions with respect to their analytical and processing capacities, and as such, these agents experience constraints in processing information and in formulating and solving complex challenges even when information is readily available or accessible. In simple terms, economic actors are intendedly rational, but only limitedly so. On the other hand, the assumption of opportunism describes the selfish motives of economic actors involved in a transactional setting. Essentially, economic actors do not always share full information, provide objective assessment of likely outcomes from a transaction, or behave collaboratively during the execution of transactions or economic activities.

This lesser willingness on the part of economic actors to share full information about economic exchanges with other parties to a transaction can also be linked to the need of economic actors to gain competitive advantage over their counterparties. In the context of this research which deals with developing countries' engagement with the WTO's DSU, the opportunism assumption bears some relevance given that countries that have the

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

capacity to understand the DSU's processes are likely to have much success with it compared to countries with limited capacity to understand and engage with this dispute settlement mechanism. In similar vein as the assumption of bounded reality, the opportunism assumption seems consistent with some economists' position of self-interested or self-seeking behaviour in which actors involved in a transaction or economic exchange take actions that maximize their payoffs (Moore, 1990; Holmstrom & Milgrom, 1991) but goes beyond this to acknowledge that actors may also commit acts of omission or commission deliberately to tilt the balance of payoffs in their favour. Consequently, in an environment where opportunism is rife, there will always be risks of market hazards where the cost-benefit equation is disproportionately distributed between different parties involved in a transaction or economic exchange.

Having discussed what the transaction cost theory is all about including its underlying assumptions, it makes sense to explore its applicability in international trade. Models of imperfect competition and rising returns highlight the critical role of transaction costs, i.e. those costs associated with transferring goods or services from producers to consumers, in influencing the pattern of trade. For instance, Krugman (1980) demonstrates that in the case of two identical countries, except for market size, the country with the larger home market (manufacturing) for a particular commodity subject to economies of scale will inadvertently be the net exporter of this commodity, but only on the condition that transaction costs are neither too low or too high. Krugman (1980) describes this situation as the "home market effect". Essentially, increasing returns to scale serves as an incentive for firms to establish production in a particular location and in order to reduce transaction costs, they prefer to be located near the larger market (Davis, 1998). With respect to international trade, countries with a larger market size and GDP are likely to have more advantage over developing countries when it comes to share of global trade. This also influences their clout when it comes to trade negotiations and resolving trade disputes. For instance, even when developing countries' complaints about market access barriers are adjudged by the DSU to be accurate, they often lack the capacity to implement retaliatory measures which could lead to increased transaction costs on their part. This situation could also explain the reason for the difficulty in achieving balanced trade between developed and developing countries.

Although discussions about trade costs have proved very appealing to some people, the analytical foundation for the concept remains somewhat unclear. For instance, if trade between two countries normally raises real income in both (which ought to be one of the main objectives of global trade), the question then arises as to how the countries concerned resolve potential discrepancies between production costs and trade costs.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Several studies (De, 2005; De, 2006; * Duval, 2006) carried out in the context of the European Union suggest that it is possible that a trading economy may be affected if trade costs are not addressed separately, especially in situations where structural asymmetries exist within or between trading partners. This is why one of the main objectives of trade liberalization initiatives is to reduce or eliminate trade barriers (i.e. both quantitative and qualitative) between trade partners.

The levying of tariffs on imported goods tends to be highly politicized. One of the arguments in favour of tariffs is the possibility that increased competition from imported goods can threaten domestic and infant industries in the recipient countries. These domestic companies may fire workers or shift production abroad to cut costs, which could result in a higher rate of unemployment and consequently, a less happy electorate. An example of a tariff barrier is the recent imposition of provisional countervailing duties on imports of battery electric vehicles (BEVs) from China by the European Commission. Based on the investigation, the Commission has concluded that the BEV value chain in China benefits from unfair subsidization, which is causing a threat of economic injury to EU BEV producers.⁶²

Although the world has witnessed a significant drop in tariffs over the last two decades, there are still more barriers that restrict some countries from active engagement in international trade. These barriers can broadly be categorized into two namely: soft and hard barriers (De, 2006). The soft barriers deal with issues around business facilitation, technical barriers (i.e. non-tariff barriers) and intermediation in trade while the hard barriers deal with physical and infrastructure barriers. In a different vein, the costs that emanate from these soft and hard barriers can be viewed as transaction costs in trade. In addition to denying developing countries (including those in Africa) access to foreign markets, these barriers increase trade costs for these countries thus, making their commodities or services uncompetitive in international markets. Essentially, technical barriers, such as rigorous or technical standards not based on evidence, increase trade costs for developing countries. Furthermore, hard barriers such as weak infrastructure also contribute to increased trade-related transaction costs for developing countries (especially African countries) thus, limiting them from reaping the full benefits of globalization. Duval (2006) suggests that regional integration could help in addressing infrastructure deficiencies (e.g. those associated with transportation costs) and gradually build or strengthen the capacity of countries in such regional integration to expand their

⁶² European Commission, Commission imposes provisional countervailing duties on imports of battery electric vehicles from China while discussions with China continue, *Press Release*, 4 July 2024.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

trade enterprise beyond the region. Having introduced and discussed the transaction cost theory including its applicability in international trade, the next section discusses another useful theoretical framework: the economics of non-tariff measures.

3.2.2 Economics of Non-Tariff Measures

Trade barriers can broadly be categorized into tariffs and non-tariff measures. For the purposes of this section, attention is devoted to discussing non-tariff measures as it relates broadly to theoretical frameworks around trade barriers. UNCTAD (2020)⁶³ notes that non-tariff measures (NTMs) are policy measures other than tariffs that can potentially have an economic effect on international trade in goods. They are increasingly shaping trade, influencing who trades what and how much. For exporters, importers and policymakers, NTMs represent a major challenge. Though many NTMs aim primarily at protecting public health or the environment, they also substantially affect trade through information, compliance and procedural costs (UNCTAD, 2020). Non-tariff measures (NTMs) produce categories of economic effects which are not prima facie a trade-cost effect (Beghin, 2008) although they could have similar effect on traded prices and quantities as is the case with tariff measures. This observation is applicable with respect to measures such as Technical Barriers to Trade (TBTs) and Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards (SPS) standards or associated technical regulatory specifications. While there is an assumption that TBTs and SPS are used by governments to protect local industries, these measures have other political intent behind their application including the need to regulate domestic industries.

Developed countries utilize non-tariff barriers as an economic strategy to control the amount or volume of trade with other countries. An example of a non-tariff barrier is the use of Sanitary and Phyto-sanitary measures to limit agricultural imports from another country. Plant and animal health standards and codes can be used to limit trade exports as exemplified with Mexico's ban on hibiscus from Nigeria citing issues with the use of insecticides.

Roberts et al., (1999) notes that achieving the objectives of NTMs could lead to a shift in the supply or demand curve as is the case with the application of trade quotas. With regards to shifting the demand curve, technical standards could lead to the internalization of potential damage from using a foreign commodity thus, affecting demand or reducing demand for such commodities even when such commodities may not have any potentially

⁶³ UNCTAD (2020) Non-tariff measures. Accessed from: [https://unctad.org/topic/trade-analysis/non-tariff-measures#:~:text=Non%2Dtari%20measures%20\(NTMs\)%20are%20policy%20measures%20other%20than,NTMs%20represent%20a%20major%20challenge](https://unctad.org/topic/trade-analysis/non-tariff-measures#:~:text=Non%2Dtari%20measures%20(NTMs)%20are%20policy%20measures%20other%20than,NTMs%20represent%20a%20major%20challenge) [2 April 2023]

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

damaging effects from use. This situation could give unfair advantage to alternative commodities produced in the host country. With respect to shifting the supply curve, NTMs lead to increased production and trade costs for exporters which also makes their prices higher than that of alternative commodities in the importing country. Cali & Montfaucon (2021) describe how technical specifications affect or impede trade by raising the costs for exporters. Again, this implies that NTMs could lead to disproportionate trade-related transaction costs for exporters. NTMs have a more negative impact than import tariffs in most cases. Cali & Montfaucon (2021) suggested that markups provide a useful channel for mediating the effects of NTMs.

Again, the impact of a specific NTM on price and quantity may be challenging to identify in a situation where different NTMs are implemented for a particular commodity. Fugazza (2013) notes that whether from a theoretical or empirical standpoint, the simplest approach is to consider that the aggregate effect is related to the relative strength in trade restrictiveness of each NTM in place, i.e. there is a dominant NTM in terms of impact which includes the impact of all other NTMs. Among the methodologies expected to be more reliable in quantifying NTMs are price comparison, inventory and quantifying impact which tend to be widely used. However, even in the simplest theoretical framework, the economic and welfare effects of NTMs cannot be unequivocally ascertained (Fugazza, 2013). This issue is not exclusively attributable to multiple NTMs but also to NTMs such as SPS measures and TBTs. The main objective in quantifying NTMs has been to generate price effect estimates and translating them into ad-valorem equivalent measures, i.e. implicit tariffs or implicit rates of protection. This methodological approach seems attractive as it synthesizes in one particular metric the effect of an instrument with multiple dimensions usually interrelated with each other. Having discussed the economics of non-tariff measures framework, the next section discusses the new trade theory.

3.2.3 New Trade Theory

New trade theory expands the neoclassical trade theory by incorporating aspects of imperfect markets, strategic firm behaviour and other aspects of industrial organization theory, endogenous growth theory and political economy issues (Deraniyagala & Fine, 2001). With respect to trade flows, the new trade theory opines that the existence of economies of scale implies that companies or organizations only produce a particular number of all the possible categories of a product in a particular country. Once trade is initiated, foreign varieties become available, and a country's firms will specialize in particular varieties to exploit economies of scale. Given the existence of demand for variety, this will generate intra-industry trade in different varieties which could raise welfare both by increasing choice and by lowering costs because of economies of scale

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

(Cattaneo & Fryer, 2002). Dodd and Cattaneo (2006) argues that the internal distributional results of intra-industry trade expansion are less significant than those associated with inter-industry trade expansion, both in the short and long term. Essentially, inter-industry trade expansion carries welfare benefits for the citizenry.

The new trade theory has also proven useful in understanding the impact of trade reforms especially in relation to rural versus urban inequality and poverty. Stevens et al., (2005) consider the implications of reducing trade costs on the spatial distribution of economic activity and on factor returns, allowing for varying possible assumptions with respect to factor mobility. Put simply, reduced trade costs are assumed to promote the de-concentration of economic activity, while the impact on real wages is reliant on the assumption made about factor mobility. Reduced real returns in the periphery can persist in the case of immobile factors specifically, which may include land, for example, but may also denote a factor such as unskilled labour. The notion of 'trade costs' was highlighted in the transaction cost theory section. Increased trade costs could make a country's exports uncompetitive in the international market. Consequently, governments can implement trade reforms that could help reduce trade-related costs for its exports. Having discussed the new trade theory, the next section discusses another useful trade-related theoretical framework: strategic trade.

3.2.4 Strategic Trade and Resource Dumping

By the provisions of Article VI of the GATT, which is derived from the United States Anti-Dumping Act of 1921, "dumping is defined as an export of a product by a producer or seller at less than its normal value (Wigwe & George, 2017). Put simply, dumping is a pricing strategy in which a firm charge less price for exported goods than it does for the same good domestically i.e. dumping is any sales made by a surplus to unjustly improve competitiveness relative to competing products in the export market. It is essential to note that an extreme version of dumping occurs when a country exports a commodity at a price lower than what it costs to produce it domestically. This is usually done to gain market access. Globalization and by extension, global trade, appears to have eliminated the protections put in place to protect producers against unfair trade practices. This is why Serences & Kozelova (2021) suggest that the existence of imperfect competition in global trade leads to some producers unfairly adjusting their prices in export markets. This is the reason why there is anti-dumping legislation in the WTO, EU and the US.

Imperfect markets with the potential for reciprocal dumping by nations in each other's market led to the development of the notion of 'strategic trade'. Brander & Spencer (1985) notes that strategic trade deals with situations where demand curves are subject to

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

elasticities that differ in the two countries. Using the example of the situation between Airbus and Boeing industries, the strategy entailed aggressive preemption, by creating a market niche through subsidized dumping of exports. A parallel possibility also exists with internal economies of scale at the national level, when countries that are historically ahead of others (i.e. possess first mover advantage) in producing a particular commodity have an advantage over others, with the capacity to produce at a reduced cost than what other countries could offer at the starting point. In similar vein as Listian's 'infant industry' scenario, the challenge of first mover advantage by advanced trade nations justify the development and use of strategic trade policy by governments to protect national infant industries (Sen, 2010). Strategic trade policy imperatives could involve offering subsidies in the high-cost country to enjoy the benefits of economies of scale.

3.2.5 Country Size and Trade Facilitation

This section looks at the theory of country size and its application to trade-related issues. There is a growing body of studies that suggest that small countries are likely to benefit more from international trade or a liberal trade regime than bigger countries. Alesina (2002) notes that the smallness of market constrains the capacity to exploit economies of scale, leading to a situation whereby small countries expand market size through international trade beyond their political borders. Nevertheless, there is evidence suggesting that the relationship between trade openness and country size is largely focused on measures of trade openness that involve trade volume (i.e. exports plus imports as a proportion of GDP) and border taxes (tariffs) (Rose, 2006). There is limited evidence on the manner that country size influences trade facilitation at the micro level. For instance, using a sample of over 80 countries and controlling for several other determinants of trade openness, Alesina & Wacziarg (1998) discover that increasing country size as measured by aggregate population is connected with a nine-percentage point decrease in trade to GDP ratio. In qualitative terms, similar results are found for macro level trade policy measures including tariff rates (Rose, 2006).

In discussing the relationship between country size and trade facilitation, the size of documentation required for export and import clearance is more for larger countries compared to small countries. This could also explain the reason for the position of Alesina (2002) that small countries are more open to trade than their larger counterparts. The issue of documentation in import and export clearance also bears some relevance to this research. The observation about number of documentations required for import and export clearance may not be applicable to some African countries. The documentation required for import and export clearance is large and complicated in some African countries adding to transaction costs for exporters. This problem is worsened by the

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

excessive red tape and bureaucracy that characterize trade institutions and processes in some African countries including Nigeria. Despite market access barriers, Nigeria's non-oil export challenges are also internal. Ajayi-Kadir (2020) highlights some of Nigeria's internal non-oil export challenges: weak trade facilitation framework; poor ports administration resulting in delays in handling and processing cargos; inadequate port infrastructure and poor transportation networks (e.g. poor road linkage at ports and absence of cargo rail at the port; multiple documentation and approval processes required for export; inconsistent implementation of port regulation; and multiplicity of trade facilitation agencies leading to duplication of roles and responsibilities). These challenges limit the country's capacity for trade economies and taking advantage of economies of scale.

3.2.6 Theory of Mercantilism

The theory of mercantilism is one of the earliest theories of international trade, i.e. one of the earliest classical theories of trade. This theory is the first current economic thinking and stresses the quantities of precious metals available to countries and obtaining these metals being based on export promoting initiatives whilst restricting imports (Terzea, 2016). Madgearu (1938) notes that as a trader or exporter of commodities tries to earn from his trading partner as much profit as possible, so the state, according to the idea of mercantilism, must have profits to its side. The mercantilist perspective of trade was popular during the time when monarchies and colonialism was prevalent. The theory was based on two main foundations:

- Wealth is made up of precious metals, and money made of these metals; and
- Profit is obtained from foreign trade with export as an effective means of building national wealth

Given both aforementioned foundations or pillars, proponents of mercantilism constantly demand the intervention of the state in trade relations with foreign partners with the ultimate objective being the achievement of trade surplus (Terzea, 2016). This particular observation still bears some relevance today especially as it relates to explaining the market access barriers faced by some countries -especially developing countries- in international trade. Essentially, there is the possibility that trade instruments -tariff and non-tariff instruments- could be exploited by some countries to achieve a trade surplus in either bilateral or multilateral trade settings. Complex and non-evidenced based SPS measures could be used by developed countries to enhance their relative advantage in trade over their developing counterparts. Overall, the mercantilist perspective of trade

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

remains relevant today as it can be used to explain the use of protectionist measures by some countries to gain advantage over their trading counterparts.

3.2.7 Trade Creation versus Trade Diversion

Regional economic integration is an economic circumstance where different countries - usually within a regional geographical structure or setting- come together to improve their common or collective trade outcomes by entering into agreements to reduce trade barriers and promote market access. Over the last two decades, there has been a growth in regional trade agreements (RTAs) around the world. According to the World Trade Organization (WTO), at the end of December 2022, there were 355 RTAs in force including the African Continental Free Trade Agreement (AfCFTA) established in May 2019 (WTO, 2022).⁶⁴ These correspond to 582 notifications from WTO members, counting goods, services and accessions separately. This reflects the significance of regionalism as an economic development alternative that promotes competitiveness of trade bloc members and accelerates their integration into the global economy (Joshi, 2012). Put simply, RTAs basically eliminates tariffs on intra-bloc trade in commodities among members or parties to the agreement.

Building on the concept of RTAs, there has been considerable attention in academia about its impacts on member countries and global trade especially in relation to trade creation and trade diversion. Varma et al., (2017) notes that one of the trade creation impact of RTAs or free trade agreements (FTAs) is that it improves resource allocation within a region and income for member countries by decreasing or eliminating trade barriers. Essentially, it gives more choice of improved commodities at competitive prices. In his classic analysis of trade effects, Viner (1950) notes that trade creation enhances economic efficiency given that the FTA or RTA member country turns out to be a low-cost producer, compared to domestic producers of the commodity that is imported more as a consequence of such agreements. Furthermore, trade creation leads to improvements in resource allocation and economic welfare, while trade diversion worsens efficiency in resource allocation especially as a result of potential price discrimination (Mattoo et al., 2019). On the other hand, the trade diversion impact implies that RTAs or FTAs could replace the imports of highly efficient non-member countries by imports from less efficient member countries (Viner, 1950; Varma et al., 2017). Again, trade diversion could have a

⁶⁴ WTO, Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs). Accessed from: https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/region_e/region_e.htm#:~:text=As%20of%201%20December%202022,goods%2C%20services%20and%20accessions%20separately. [4 April 2023]

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

negative effect on the export fortunes of some member and non-member countries as they lose export opportunities.

An example of trade diversion is the entry of Britain into the European Common market in 1973. It started sourcing dairy and wool imports from within the common market rather than from New Zealand as was the case for decades. Assume the most efficient producer of lamb in the world is New Zealand. Before joining the European customs union, the UK will place an identical tariff on lamb imported from any country as shown in Figure 3.1. Before joining the customs union, French lamb was more expensive than New Zealand lamb once the tariff was paid. There are no imports from France. After joining the EU, the tariff on French lamb will be removed and this leads to trade diversion which does not benefit consumers on a pricing basis.

Figure 3.1: Trade Diversionary Effects of Preferential Trade Agreements

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Source: Viner (1950)

While consumers in FTA or RTA member countries could see an improvement in their welfare given that they have more options, one or member countries risk a reduction in government revenues from tariffs which could exceed consumers' gains. Although Viner (1950)'s classic analysis of trade effects of RTAs and FTAs provides a useful framework for analysing or understanding the trade creation or trade diversion effects of such agreements, some gaps have been highlighted in its approach. For one, Mattoo et al., (2019:2) notes that, "Vinerian analysis was developed in a world where trade agreements were "shallow" and focused mainly on bilateral trade liberalization. This is not the case presently as FTAs or RTAs are increasingly "deep" and include behind-the-border policy concerns, such as competition policy, investment, intellectual property rights, labour, and other regulatory issues.

Overall, a FTA or RTA would lead to some degree of both trade creation and trade diversion effects. If the trade diversion is significantly large relative to the trade creation effects, the FTA or RTA could end up being harmful to the member countries concerned. Having said this, Varma et al., (2017) highlighted three critical conditions for the benefits of RTAs or FTAs to exceed its costs to member countries:

- One, successful regional integration tends to be accompanied by reduction in tariffs for all member countries. Hence, trade shares may not increase despite an increase in regional trade volume;
- Two, regional trade agreements that lay out frameworks for the reduction or elimination of trade costs associated with tariffs other than those associated with formal trade policies (i.e. improved customs procedures, port efficiency etc), may stimulate trade from other sources; and
- Three, majority of RTAs or FTAs address non-trade issues such as investment, services, and labour issues, and these can have significant consequences for growth and incomes. Consequently, it is critical to consider that an agreement may be successful even if the propensity for member countries to trade among themselves does not grow significantly.

The AfCFTA can build upon the notion of trade creation and trade diversion to enhance its potential success. The success of the AfCFTA is, to a significant degree, dependent

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

on how it draws upon the successes and challenges faced by the regional economic communities (RECs). Regarding regional integration in Africa, the rhetoric rarely matches the reality on ground. While the growing ambition of the continent to reduce poverty and promote rapid economic growth provides momentum for achieving the objectives of regional integration, the experience of some previous regional integration has been fraught with challenges and failure. Effective regional integration goes beyond just eliminating or reducing tariffs to other critical concerns such as the direct and indirect costs associated with trading commodities across borders. In their study examining the trade diversionary and trade creation effects of RECs in Africa, Kassa & Sawadogo (2021) found out that ECOWAS registered the lowest score for the quality of trade and transport-related infrastructure. Drawing on this result, one can infer that the success of the AfCFTA will draw from some other critical concerns including the level of efficiency of customs and border management as it influences trading costs. Again, Kassa & Sawadogo (2021) note that a significant aspect of the drag on trade costs is derived from the higher cost and increased time associated with transit of commodities from production to the point of exit at the border and the cross-border transactions. Having reviewed some of the useful international trade theories, it is now time to discuss another equally important trade theory: the principal-agent or agency theory. This particular theory forms the theoretical framework for this research.

3.2.8 The Principal- Agent theory

The principal-agent theory revolves around the relationship between a principal and an agent and the issues that may surface due to their different risk perspectives and the moral hazards, which may arise during their interactions whilst pursuing their objectives (Benhold & Niklas, 2021). One of the common examples of the theory can be seen in the way a government in a country operates. The citizens elect political representatives to run the country in a way that maximizes their interests. Here the citizens act as agents who elect government to act as their agents. The theory is pertinent to economic and political discourse given its usefulness in explaining the context and relationship between agents and principals. Whilst agents ought to act on behalf of their principals, there are situations where agents' behavior or actions do not align, address, or support the interests of principals (Lane, 2014). Such situations are referred to as moral hazards.

The agency theory was developed by Jensen & Meckling (1976) and describes governance structures within organizations based on conflicts of interest between the company's owners (i.e. principal) and its managers (i.e. agents). The principal-agent theoretical framework provides yet another useful framework for analyzing and understanding the organization of human activities (White, 1992; Ackere, 1993). One of

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

the strengths of the agency framework is that it underscores incentives more than rules as in many organization approaches. Its focus is on the web of contracts that link individuals together in an organization, analysing them with newly developed concepts such as the economic theory of information (Bircher & Butler, 2007). Observing the relationship between actors as contractual connections between principals and agents has proven effective with respect to understanding work relationships in a variety of sectors. The agency theory captures the framework of rational choice, in which certain actors (the principals) utilize whatever actions are available to provide incentives for some other actors (the agents) to make decisions that are in the interest of the principal (Gailmard, 2012). Given that the principal-agent framework stresses the responsiveness of the agent's decisions to the goals and objectives of the principal, and the manner this responsiveness is mediated by actions available to each actor together with institutional settings in which they interact, it has proven to be a useful framework in analyzing or studying the accountability of political and public institutions.

The issue of instituting accountability mechanisms to govern the relationship between the agent and principal cannot be left to agents as highlighted by the issue of excessive risk-taking by bank executives that led to the collapse of the subprime mortgage market and subsequently the global financial crisis of 2008. Lenz (2012) notes that public accountability is a function of the capabilities of principals to assess the performance of their agents or representatives; but it is also, in part, a function of institutions. The agency theory has become a widely used or popular framework for assessing the degree to which public institutions are accountable. Gailmard (2012) notes that the usefulness of the principal-agent framework stems from the fact that it provides a flexible framework for modelling innumerable variations in institutional arrangements and comparing their potential for inducing or influencing expected behaviour by agents. Bolton and Dewatripont (2004) suggest that the analysis and evaluation of public accountability needs a specification of who is or is supposed to be accountable to whom. This is the fundamental tenet of the principal-agent framework.

It is essential to note that the agency theory is not a single overarching theory with a particular set of assumptions or conclusions. It is best described as a group of formal models that addresses related concerns with similar styles of analysis. Consequently, one of the main assumptions of agency theory is that for any given actors viewed as 'principal' and 'agent', and any pattern of interactions between the two, a principal-agent model can be written down with that pattern as an equilibrium outcome – and modelers may consider it a game of sorts to do that (Lenz, 2012). Given this observation, researchers should be careful when seeking to empirically test the principal-agent theory. In similar vein, it is

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

equally possible to defend any status quo interaction between a 'principal' and an 'agent' as reflecting the highest degree of accountability to which the agent can be assessed by the principal, given different informational asymmetries and commitment issues.

Over the years, several principal-agent models have been developed to respond to different agency scenarios or situations. One basic distinction in the types of principal-agent models concerns those dealing with moral hazard or hidden actions, and those dealing with adverse selection or hidden information. With respect to moral hazard issues, the agent takes one of different possible actions that has an impact on the principal's utility, i.e. the principal and agent have varying preferences over the possible actions the agent can take, and the principal cannot directly influence the agent's actions (Lane, 2014; Struthers, 2017; Nziku and Struthers, 2018). Nevertheless, to make the problem more interesting, the principal observes certain information affected by the agent's action and implements a reward or punishment based on that information. Having said this, it is essential to note that it is perfectly plausible for a moral hazard problem to lack this attribute, but then the agent simply takes its own preferred action irrespective of the principal's interest. With respect to adverse selection challenges, the agent is privy to certain information that the principal requires to decide in her own interest, but the agent prefers that the information is used differently. In pure adverse selection models, the principal may be able to indicate costs the agent must incur when taking certain decisions, or even outrightly prohibit some decisions by the agent. All of these types of direct control over the agent's action are unavailable in pure moral hazard frameworks. In adverse selection, the challenge for the principal is that he or she does not know action to influence the agent to take.

Central to analyzing and understanding moral hazard and adverse selection problems is 'incentive compatibility'. Gailmard (2012) notes that incentive compatibility imposes constraints on the principal, i.e. the principal must trade off the benefits of an improved decision from its own perspective, against the costs of directing and incentivizing the agent to take that particular decision. The application of incentives by principals to control or influence the action of agents should be put into proper context given the capacity for incentives to potentially influence agents to engage in actions that are not in the interest of the principal. Again, the global financial crisis of 2008 provides as useful context for exploring this observation. In this regard, incentives applied by shareholders (i.e. high performance bonuses) seemed to have encouraged some bank executives to take excessive risks which ultimately led to significant losses, e.g. bankruptcy of Lehman Brothers and Northern Rock.

THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS

The principal-agent theory is the theoretical framework adopted for this research. Essentially, agency theory is used to explore Nigeria's trade infrastructure to identify the barriers inhibiting its engagement with the WTO's dispute settlement system. In the context of this research, stakeholders in Nigeria's trade environment are broadly categorized into three main groups namely: the *upstream players*; the *midstream players* and the *downstream players*. The upstream players consist of producers and exporters of agricultural commodities. The upstream players consist of Nigeria's WTO representative based in Geneva; and the midstream consists of trade-related or trade support institutions in Nigeria (i.e. the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade & Investment; the Nigeria Export Promotion Council; the Federal Ministry of Agriculture etc), and the downstream players consists of producers and exporters of agricultural commodities (see Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2: Categorization of Nigeria's Trade Stakeholders

Illustration of Downstream, Midstream Upstream players

Source: Author (2024)

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

In this case, the agent includes the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade, & Investment (FMITI) while the principals are producers and the trade groups in Nigeria such as the Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (MAN), Nigeria Association of Small & Medium Enterprises (NASME), Cocoa Farmers Association of Nigeria, and Rice Farmers Association of Nigeria. The Principal Agent Theory will be used to understand the degree to which the FMITI has acted in the interest of these stakeholders. Dealing with multiple stakeholder interests presents a challenge for the FMITI and can lead to moral hazard issues such as prioritizing a particular stakeholder group's interest over another. The data collected for this study will examine and help explain how the FMITI balances diverse interests from multiple stakeholder entities in Nigeria. Furthermore, the data collected would help ascertain how stakeholder groups navigate inherent bureaucracies within the FMITI to protect their respective interests. Here, the aim is to develop framework for mitigating the challenges faced by trade groups in Nigeria from a principal-agent perspective.

Furthermore, in understanding the roles and responsibilities of trade-related institutions and stakeholders in Nigeria's trade environment, the researcher developed a three Is framework (i.e. Identification, Investigation, and Initiation) as follows (see Figure 3.3):

- *Identification*: the identification of trade or market access barriers is mainly the responsibility of the downstream players, i.e. agricultural producers and exporters. The upstream players identify market access barriers faced when exporting their agricultural commodities to other countries and flag such challenges with the necessary authorities. The 'identification' component concerns the downstream stakeholders in Nigeria's trade environment.
- *Investigation*: the investigation of market access challenges flagged by downstream players is mainly the responsibility of midstream players, i.e. FMITI, NEPC etc. Essentially, midstream players or institutions are responsible for investigating potential breaches of WTO trade regulations as it relates to unfair market access challenges encountered by Nigerian producers or exporters of agricultural commodities. The 'investigation' component concerns the midstream stakeholders in Nigeria's trade environment.
- *Initiation*: this aspect of the Is framework mainly concerns the initiation of complaints with the WTO (upstream) based on the outcome of investigations by midstream players. Once investigations confirm that there is a breach of trade regulations, midstream players are expected to flag these breaches to Nigeria's WTO trade representative (upstream) for onward processing through required

THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS

WTO trade complaints channels especially the DSU. The 'initiation' component of the three Is framework concerns the upstream stakeholders in Nigeria's trade environment.

Figure 3.3: The Three Is Framework

Source: Author (2024)

In developing this chapter, it is necessary to note that while there is abundant literature highlighting the unique challenges faced by developing countries when it comes to utilization of the WTO's DSS, there is limited literature specifically dealing with principal-agent issues arising from developing countries' limited engagement with the DSS. Despite this limitation, principal-agent issues arising from trade facilitation issues should provide the taxonomy or framework for addressing gaps in literature.

In developing this chapter, it is necessary to note that while there is abundant literature highlighting the unique challenges faced by developing countries when it comes to utilization of the WTO's DSS, there is limited literature specifically dealing with principal-agent issues arising from developing countries' limited engagement with the DSS.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Despite this limitation, principal-agent issues arising from trade facilitation issues should provide the taxonomy or framework for addressing gaps in literature.

In building the theoretical framework for this research, focus is placed on Nigeria's trade environment including the various stakeholder relationships in this environment and how they interact with each other keeping in mind the earlier mentioned three Is framework that outlines the fundamental roles of trade institutions in Nigeria. Further information and insights into Nigeria's limited engagement with the DSS will be provided by the analysis of quantitative and qualitative data to be collected later on. The chapter would begin by outlining the barriers that developing countries face when it comes to utilizing the DSS and looks at the national institutional factors that contribute to this. The examination of national institutional factors should highlight potential conflicts of interests that may arise with regards to how trade institutions manage the trade interests of their exporters. These discussions should provide useful insights into the national trade infrastructure of developing countries, particularly Nigeria, and how this contributes to limited or ineffective engagement with the WTO's DSU.

To meet the objectives of this study, both quantitative and qualitative data will be collected. This implies that the *mixed methods* research approach will be used to conduct this study. Both primary and secondary data will be collected for this research. The primary data will be collected using questionnaires and interviews. The sample for the questionnaires and interviews would reflect the following: officials of the FMITI; representatives trade groups; agricultural commodity producers; exporters of agricultural commodities; and other exporters in Nigeria.

Factors for consideration by Agents in instituting a claim before the DSS.

The factors for consideration by an agent before instituting a claim against measures that constitute barriers to market access are described below:

Legal Considerations

- The Agent must identify of the measure affecting its trade interests and its rights under the WTO agreements.
- The legal bases of the claim are the main consideration, the legal merit in light of the WTO Agreements. WTO members go to dispute settlement when chances of victory are assessed to be no less than 75% to 90%.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Economic Considerations

- The impact of the measure in the local industry constitutes the usual local economic impact. Exporters are the first to notice the existence of a measure that distorts the market or limits its access to the other country. Cost-benefit consideration
- The benefits that could be obtained as a result of the dispute with regards to the litigation costs. It is a common practice that industries contribute to pay the litigation costs.

Political Considerations

- Fear of reprisals from big players. Small players may fear the reaction of big trade actors. A request of establishment of a panel under the DSU is not an act of belligerence. Trade disputes make part of normal relations among the closest partners.
- Apprehension to initiate a case against a friendly country/all. Over the years it has become a common practice in most regions.
- Requests of support. Small players should not allow themselves to participate in disputes lead by political reasons.

Other domestic political issues

- Some issues may have political weight at home even when the economic impact is limited. Cases related to health, environment or cultural issues may have additional political implications to consider.

Participation as a Third party

- A way to learn to use the system, to reduce litigation costs, to participate when the interest is systemic. The rights of third parties are limited compared to those of parties.

Foreign Direct Investment Policy

- Developing the capacity to use the WTO DSM to defend the interest of local producers can be a positive signal to potential investors.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the methodology that will be used to conduct this research. It explains the research philosophy, research approach and study design used to conduct this research. The study design also outlines the data collection methods used to investigate developing countries' engagement with the WTO's dispute settlement understanding. The issues of validity, reliability and generalizability are also discussed in this chapter with a view to ensuring that the methodology selected is suitable to address the research questions and hypotheses developed for this research.

4.2 Research Philosophy

The research philosophy can be viewed as the outer layer of the research onion which must be considered when carrying out research (see Figure 4.1). This is because it influences the study approach and study design used to investigate a research problem or topic. Saunders et al., (2005) define research philosophy as a system of beliefs and assumptions about how knowledge is developed or created. The research philosophy underscores how the researcher interprets data about a phenomenon with a view to generating conclusions that can lead to new knowledge or build on existing knowledge. Bryman et al., (2011) notes that the research philosophy conceptualizes all the beliefs and assumptions about how knowledge is formed. Throughout the research process, the researcher consciously or unconsciously makes some assumptions that underpins his or her methodology for the research. These assumptions can be classified as either epistemological assumptions (i.e. assumptions about human knowledge) or ontological assumptions (i.e. realities that the researcher encounters when carrying out the research). These assumptions inform the research questions, research objectives, and the methods used to collect and analyse data (Tsoukas & Chia, 2011). The research philosophy is borne out of the fact that when researchers carry out research, they are likely to make assumptions about data or information that they come across in relation to a phenomenon that they come across. These assumptions include epistemological assumptions (i.e. assumptions about knowledge), ontological assumptions (i.e. assumptions about the realities that a researcher encounters whilst carrying out

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

research), and axiological assumptions (i.e. the way a researcher's personal values influence research) (Bryman & Bell, 2011).

It is important to think about these assumptions because they influence most aspects of the research process including data collection, analysis, and interpretation. A carefully thought-out assumption of a research problem aids the research in collecting the right information and analyzing this in a way that fulfils the study's objectives. Johnson & Clark (2006) note that, as business and management researchers, there is a need to be aware of the philosophical commitments we make through our conscious choice of research methods, since this will have a significant effect on what we do and how we understand what it is we are investigating.

There are different research philosophies out there that can be used to create the foundation for a study's methodology. While the multiplicity of research philosophies has been the subject of debate especially in business and management studies, what is most important to note is that each philosophy contributes something unique to the research process. In order to understand developing countries' engagement with the WTO's dispute settlement Understanding (DSU), the positivist and interpretivist paradigms are used. Both paradigms have their place in the research process given that they take deductive and inductive approaches respectively to interpreting information collected for research. From an epistemological perspective, the use of both study paradigms in this research aligns to the researcher's appreciation of the multidisciplinary context of business and the social sciences. The positivist paradigm enables the researcher to use quantitative approaches to assess agro-producers' understanding of the requirements for export of agricultural commodities. The interpretivist paradigm, on the other hand, enables the researcher to conduct a deep dive into the challenges affecting Nigeria's engagement with the WTO's process especially the DSU. Thomas & Hardy (2011) note that the multidisciplinary context of business and management implies that varying forms of knowledge –whether numerical or textual information- can all be considered as legitimate. As a result, some management and social science research employ more than one philosophy when conducting research. This is the case with this study that investigates developing countries' engagement with the WTO's DSU including issues around their participation in global trade.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Figure 4.1: Research Onion

Source: Collis & Hussey (2003)

Based on the information presented in Figure 4.1, the research philosophy is at the outer layer of the research onion and as such, must be addressed before you address other equally critical elements of the research methodology. The positivist research paradigm is a research philosophy that views reality as stable and as such, adopts a scientific or objective approach to investigation (Levin, 1988). This is why the positivist research philosophy supports the quantitative approach to research where numerical analysis is used to analyze data about phenomenon thus, resulting in objective conclusions. At the opposite end of the positivist paradigm is the interpretivism which advocates a qualitative approach to research especially bearing in mind that objective or numerical analysis may fail to consider the constraints –such as human behavior, change and risk- that can invalidate the results of a quantitative study (Collis & Hussey, 2005). Unlike the positivist study paradigm, the interpretivist paradigm advocates the qualitative research approach because it enables the researcher to collect qualitative information about phenomena that can offer useful insights into the results of numerical analysis especially

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

when the mixed methods approach is used. Having said this, one of the weaknesses of the interpretivist research paradigm is its subjective posture, i.e. analysis of qualitative information is subject to the researcher's underlying assumptions about phenomena.

Overall, both the positivist and interpretivist research philosophies were used to conduct this research. The positivist paradigm enabled the researcher to understand the degree of knowledge that upstream stakeholders have about WTO rules and procedures, evaluate the quantity of trade or export of the selected agricultural commodities (i.e. *Yam*, *Shea Butter*, and *Beans*) for this study, and evaluate downstream and midstream partners' perspectives on the main challenges inhibiting Nigeria's export of the selected agricultural commodities under investigation. In addition, quantitative data collected from respondents help in understanding the impact of SPS measures on Nigeria's export of agricultural commodities. The interpretivist approach, on the other hand, is key to understanding the institutional environment/arrangements for trade in agricultural commodities. Furthermore, the interpretivist paradigm enables the researcher to obtain in-depth information from downstream and midstream stakeholders about international market access, quality of national trade infrastructure, and political economy of trade negotiations especially in relation to selected agricultural commodities in Nigeria. These variables –which are largely qualitative in nature- offer the opportunity to understand the underlying socioeconomic variables influencing the level and quality of Nigeria's export of agricultural commodities to international markets. Having discussed the research philosophy used in conducting this research, the next section discusses the research approach.

4.3 Research Approach

Based on the research onion depicted in Figure 4.1, the research approach feeds off the research philosophy. The research approach is a key component of the research strategy as it influences how a researcher chooses to solve a research problem (Collis & Hussey, 2005). Essentially, the research approach describes the procedures or methods that are used by a researcher to collect, analyze, and interpret data. There are three main types of research approaches that can be used to conduct research: quantitative; qualitative; and mixed methods. Given that the interpretivist and positivist paradigm are used in this research, it is essential to note that the mixed methods research approach is used to investigate developing countries' engagement with the WTO's DSU. This implies that both the quantitative and qualitative research approaches were used to conduct this research.

The *quantitative* approach is central to the positivist research paradigm which adopts an objective or concrete approach to analyzing and interpreting data about a phenomenon

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

being investigated. Saunders et al., (2005) notes that the quantitative approach entails the use of quantitative or numerical data to analyze data about a research problem. The quantitative approach was used in this research given that questionnaires were used to collect data in relation to the research questions and research hypotheses. For instance, questionnaires were used to collect data from upstream partners to test their awareness of WTO rules and SPS measures for agricultural commodities. In addition, the questionnaires were used to collect information from upstream stakeholders about the challenges inhibiting Nigeria's export of agricultural commodities. These upstream stakeholders mainly consist of the farmers, processors, and other players involved in the value chain for agricultural commodities. The responses to the survey from upstream stakeholders are analyzed using statistical analyses, i.e. descriptive and inferential statistics.

In addition to the quantitative approach, the *qualitative* approach was used to collect data for this research. The qualitative research approach belongs to the interpretivist research paradigm and as such, is more subjective given that interpretation of data is largely dependent on the researcher's assumptions. Although subjective interpretation of data is one of the limitations of the qualitative research approach, it is equally essential to note that one of the main strengths of the qualitative research approach is its capacity to offer general deeper or insightful information that can be used to explain the results of quantitative analysis (Bryman & Bell, 2011). There are certain aspects of the research problem that require qualitative information to understand the phenomena being investigated. Issues such as the political economy of global trade and how this influences Nigeria's agricultural commodities' exports would best be addressed by obtaining qualitative information from key actors and institutions (i.e. downstream and midstream stakeholders) that make up the trade environment in Nigeria. Interviews with representatives of trade facilitation and trade promotion institutions in Nigeria would help in understanding how effective these institutions are in addressing market access barriers for agricultural commodities. Interviews with representatives of these institutions would also aid in understanding the dynamics of trade negotiations coupled with understanding the nature of coordination between producers or exporters of agricultural commodities and trade facilitation/trade promotion institutions such as the Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC), Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment (FMITI), National Office on Trade Negotiations (NOTN), Nigeria Incentive-Based Risk Sharing System for Agricultural Lending (NISRAL), etc. Interviews provide the opportunity to dig deeper into the challenges inhibiting Nigeria's engagement with the WTO's DSS to address trade barriers limiting export of agricultural commodities. Overall, the mixed methods approach

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

was used in this research to address the questions and hypotheses developed for this research.

4.4 Research Design

This section discusses the research design used to conduct this research. The research design can be likened to architectural blueprint for research. It encompasses the framework of research methods used by a researcher to answer research questions or fulfil a study's objectives. Saunders et al., (2003) defined the research design as a framework that encompasses the processes used to address a study's objectives. The study design also encompasses the methods used by a researcher to collect and analyze data for research that is relevant to the study's objectives. There are different study designs that can be used to conduct research. Collis & Hussey (2005) describes the study design as a clear and logical plan to address a research problem. For this research, the case study research design was used. Nigeria formed the case study for investigating developing countries' engagement with the WTO's Dispute Settlement System. The justification for using the case study research design is that it provides rich and in-depth understanding of a multi-faceted issue such as global. To understand the barriers limiting agricultural exports from developing countries, it makes sense to select a developing country as a case study for understanding this issue including how they engage with the WTO's dispute resolution to address the trade barriers -both tariffs and non-tariff- that their products face in international markets. Again, by selecting Nigeria (a developing country) as the case study for this research, the data collection and analysis helps the researcher to understand, in practical terms, the challenges that developing countries when engaging with the current trade regime especially in relation to trade dispute resolution.

The case study design is a study design where a subject or case is chosen as the basis for investigating a research problem or phenomena (Yin, 2014). Collis & Hussey (2003) notes that the case study is an in-depth, systematic investigation of an organization, system, or event as a basis for investigating and understanding a problem or situation. Nigeria formed the case study for investigating how developing countries' carry out trade facilitation and engage with instruments within the WTO to address international trade barriers especially those limiting access to foreign markets. Given that Nigeria is a developing country coupled with the current administration's decision to diversify its economy from dependence on crude oil exports to agricultural exports, three key agricultural commodities formed the basis for investigating the market access barriers faced by developing countries: Sesame, Shea nut, and Cocoa.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Since Nigeria was selected as a case study for this research, questionnaires and interviews were used to collect data from key actors and stakeholders across the upstream (exporters and producers of agricultural commodities), midstream (trade-related or trade support institutions such as the FMITI and NEPC), and downstream (i.e. Nigeria's WTO trade representative based in Geneva) layers of the trade environment in Nigeria. The case study design is not without its limitations; one of its limitations is the difficulty in generalizing the results generated (Collis & Hussey, 2005). So, for instance, what may apply in Nigeria may not apply to another developing country in Asia. Despite this, the case study provides a cost-effective approach to investigating a research problem or understanding phenomena. The questionnaires and interview questions were designed to collect information to test the various hypotheses developed for this study. The hypotheses developed for this research are as follows:

4.4.1 Research Hypotheses

This section outlines the hypothesis developed for this research. The collection and analysis of data, especially the survey, will help in determining the degree to which these hypotheses -outlined below are true or false.

1. A country's level of engagement with the WTO's DSS depends on the strength and quality of its trade infrastructure
2. The ability of developing countries to successfully engage with the WTO DSS system to enforce its WTO market access rights is highly contingent on the principal –agent synergy between the country's exporters and its domestic trade institutions
3. The ability of developing countries to successfully engage with the WTO DSS system to enforce its market access rights under the WTO laws is dependent on the strength of the Principal-Agent relationship between the country's exporters and its WTO trade representatives.
4. A country's success in engaging with the WTO DSS correlates with the expertise and efficiency which the country's domestic trade institutions discharge their duties as agents to the country's exporters.
5. Existence of local mechanisms to identify trade barriers faced by trade groups and exporters influences a country's level of engagement with the WTO's DSS

Downstream level

H0 – Producers Awareness of WTO standards has no significant influence on quantity of agriculture commodities exported from Nigeria.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

H1 – Producers Awareness of WTO standards has significant influence on quantity of agriculture commodities exported from Nigeria.

H0 --The extent, to which exporters of agriculture commodities are informed of WTO rules on agriculture, has no significant impact on the volume of agriculture commodities exports.

H2- The extent to which exporters of are informed of WTO rules on agriculture, has significant impact on the volume of agriculture commodities exports.

H0 - The level of understanding of WTO rules on agriculture, has no significant impact on the volume of exports of agriculture commodities.

H3- The level of understanding of WTO rules on agriculture, has significant impact on the volume of exports of agriculture commodities.

H0 --The extent to which exporters of agriculture commodities understand WTO rules on Agriculture does not affect the volume of their exports.

H4 - The extent to which exporters of agriculture commodities understand WTO rules on Agriculture affects the volume of their exports.

H0 – The existence of formal mechanism for reporting market access barriers has no significant effect on quantity of agriculture commodities exported from Nigeria.

H5 – The existence of formal mechanism for reporting market access barriers has significant effect on quantity of agriculture commodities exported from Nigeria.

H0 – The existence of formal mechanism for reporting violations of WTO rules has no significant impact on quantity of agricultural exports from Nigeria.

H6 – The existence of formal mechanism for reporting violations of WTO rules has significant impact on quantity of agriculture commodities exported from Nigeria.

Midstream level

H0 – The existence of investigative authority has no significant influence on quantity of agriculture commodities exported from Nigeria.

H1 – The existence of investigative authority has significant influence on quantity of agriculture commodities exported from Nigeria.

H0 – The existence of investigative procedure has no significant influence on quantity of agriculture commodities exported from Nigeria.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

H2 - Existence of investigative procedure has significant influence on quantity of agriculture commodities exported from Nigeria.

Upstream Level

H0 – The existence of effective communication between the downstream, midstream, and upstream levels has no significant influence on quantity of agriculture commodities exported from Nigeria.

H1 – The existence of effective communication between the downstream, midstream, and upstream levels has a significant influence on quantity of agriculture commodities exported from Nigeria.

4.5 Data Collection Methods

This section of the research describes the nature of data collected for this research and the tools used to collect them. Collecting the correct information is key to understanding the research problem and fulfilling the objectives of a research. Both primary and secondary data were collected for this research. In addition to describing the nature of data collected for this research, the methods used to analyse the primary data are also discussed.

4.5.1 Primary Data

Primary data is a useful data for conducting research given the original insights it generates on the phenomena being investigated (Collis & Hussey, 2005). It is information that is created by a researcher since he or she designs the tools that are used to collect such information. This is why primary data is sometimes referred to as 'raw' data because of its originality (Saunders et al., 2005). One of the reasons why primary data is critical for this research is that it can generate additional insights on the issue that is being investigated (Creswell, 2007). Consequently, it affords the researcher the opportunity to generate new knowledge on the subject matter being investigated. Despite this, primary data is not without its disadvantages; for one, primary data can be too expensive to collect especially when dealing with a large sample (Creswell, 2007).

Primary data was collected to investigate Nigeria's trade-related environment –including opportunities and challenges- especially as it relates to its level of engagement in the WTO's dispute settlement system to resolve trade barriers faced by producers/exporters of agricultural commodities. In order to assess and understand how Nigeria's engagement with the WTO's dispute settlement procedures, it is essential to collect data from key actors/stakeholders at the downstream, midstream and upstream levels of the trade

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

environment. This information was collected using both questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. 300 questionnaires were used to collect data from upstream actors such as farmers, agricultural processors, members of farmer groups or associations, and wholesale offtakers/exporters of agricultural commodities with specific focus on beans, shea butter and yam. a total of 100 questionnaires were distributed to the producers of each of the selected crops (Cocoa, Shea Nut and Sesame). The questionnaires with respect to the hypotheses developed to examine the downstream segment of Nigeria's trade environment (see section 5.4 for breakdown of the different hypotheses developed for this research). On the other hand, interviews were used to collect data from midstream and downstream actors (which consists of representatives of institutions involved in trade promotion and trade facilitation) in Nigeria's trade environment such as the National Office for Trade Negotiations (NOTN), Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade & Investment (FMITI), Nigeria Export Promotion Commission (NEPC), the Nigeria Incentive-Based Risk Sharing System for Agricultural Lending (NISRAL), and representatives of Nigeria's Trade Delegation to the WTO in Geneva.

The responses from downstream actors to the questionnaires aided in understanding the main challenges faced by producers and exporters of the selected agricultural commodities including assessing their level of understanding of trade rules and policies especially in international markets. Furthermore, responses to the questionnaires also provided information needed to understand the level and quality of engagement between producers/exporters of agricultural commodities and national trade institutions. The responses from midstream and downstream actors to the interviews enabled the researcher to assess the political economy of trade policies in Nigeria, assess the technical capacity of trade institutions in Nigeria, assess the level and quality of Nigeria's engagement with the WTO's DSS, identify –if any- the challenges limiting Nigeria's engagement with the DSS, assess the overall involvement and participation of Nigeria in the WTO's internal processes and organs, and evaluate Nigeria's experiences addressing trade barriers faced by producers of the selected agricultural commodities in Nigeria. Overall, the analysis of information collected through the questionnaires and interviews enabled the researcher to address the different hypotheses developed for this research.

4.5.2 Secondary Data

Unlike primary data, secondary data is information that is already existing, i.e. it is information that was created by other persons besides the researcher (Collis & Hussey, 2003). In other words, secondary data can be likened to information that already exists in the public domain. Even though secondary data is not as original as primary data, it still has its uses when doing research. For one, information from secondary sources is used

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

to develop the literature review and theoretical framework for research. Previous information on a subject matter that is not exploratory in nature can be used to generate background information on the phenomena under investigation.

Secondary data was used in this research when developing the literature review chapter for the research. The secondary data accessed from public domains provided relevant information about the WTO's organs, procedures for resolving trade disputes, trade statistics for some African countries including Nigeria, and challenges experienced by developing countries when resolving international trade disputes. The secondary data used in this research were accessed from academic journals especially trade publications, WTO's publications, textbooks on international trade (e.g. *The Law and Policy of the World Trade Organization* written by Peter Van den Bossche and Werner Zdouc), publications by national trade institutions such as the FMITI and NEPC, and relevant policy documents from other multilateral institutions such as the World Bank, IMF, ECOWAS, and AFDB. Some of the journals from which secondary data was collected for this research include: publications by the World Trade Institute and International Trade Center; other publications by the WTO (e.g. WTO SPS Agreement); UNCTAD publications; journal of economic behaviour and organization; Journal of World Trade etc. The information obtained from these sources were used to develop the literature review chapter and theoretical framework for the research.

4.5.3 Data Analysis

This section discusses the methods used to analyze the primary data collected for this research. As noted in 4.5.1, at the upstream level, the study aims to investigate the factors influencing the export status of the upstream players i.e. producers/exporters. The chosen model for analysing the factors affecting the export status of upstream stream players in this study is the Generalized Linear Model (GLM) Probit Regression. Probit regression is a type of regression used when the dependent variable is dichotomous, in this case, the export status of upstream players, which is measured as a binary outcome (1 = yes, 0 = no). The probit model assumes that the probability of the dependent variable being 1 is a function of a standard normal cumulative distribution function (CDF). This makes probit regression particularly suitable for modelling binary outcomes where the underlying distribution of the error terms is assumed to be normal. Probit regression is widely used in various fields, including economics and finance (McCullagh & Nelder, 1989; Long, 1997; Klieštík, Ševčík, & Ševčíková, 2015).

The primary advantage of the probit model is its appropriateness for binary dependent variables. Given that the export status in this study is a binary variable, probit regression

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

is a natural choice. Also, Probit regression assumes that the error terms are normally distributed, which often provides a better fit for certain types of binary data compared to other distributions. This normality assumption is particularly relevant in the context of socio-economic data where the underlying factors influencing the binary outcome (such as export status) are likely to be normally distributed. Additionally, the probit model provides a threshold interpretation, where the latent variable model defines a threshold above which the outcome is 1 and below which it is 0. This threshold concept is useful in understanding the binary decision-making process of downstream players regarding whether to export or not.

Logit regression is another popular method for analyzing binary dependent variables, which uses the logistic function for the CDF of the error terms. The choice between logit and probit regression often hinges on the specific characteristics of the data and the underlying theoretical assumptions (Williams, 2009). The primary difference between logit and probit models lies in the distribution of the error terms. While logit regression assumes a logistic distribution, probit regression assumes a normal distribution (Klieštík et al., 2015). In cases where the error terms are believed to follow a normal distribution, as theorized in this study, probit regression is preferred. Also, the marginal effects in a probit model are typically more intuitive and stable compared to logit models, especially when dealing with normally distributed predictors. This stability is crucial for accurately interpreting the influence of the independent variables on the probability of exporting. Studies comparing the performance of probit and logit models often find similar results in terms of predictive power (Williams, 2009; Klieštík et al., 2015). However, probit models are sometimes preferred in economic research due to their theoretical alignment with the normal distribution of latent variables influencing binary outcomes (Gourieroux, Monfort, & Trognon, 1984).

The use of probit regression is well-documented in the academic literature, particularly in studies involving binary outcomes in economics and social sciences. For instance, Long (1997) emphasizes the appropriateness of probit models for binary response data where the underlying latent variable follows a normal distribution. Furthermore, Gujarati and Porter (2009) highlight that probit models are often preferable in cases where the error terms' normality assumption is plausible, which aligns with the socio-economic nature of the data in this study.

In the context of this research, the probit model allows for a robust analysis of the factors influencing the export status of upstream players in Nigeria's agricultural sector. The model will help in understanding how various independent variables, measured using a 5-point Likert scale, affect the likelihood of these players engaging in export activities.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

The probit regression's ability to handle the dichotomous nature of the dependent variable and its alignment with the normal distribution assumption of the error terms makes it an optimal choice for this analysis.

In conclusion, GLM Probit Regression is the most suitable choice for this study due to its ability to handle binary outcomes, provide marginal effects, and offer interpretability. Although it has some disadvantages, such as computational complexity and interpretation challenges, the benefits of using probit regression outweigh the drawbacks. The study will employ a mixed-research design approach, gathering data from a systematic literature review, surveys, focus group discussions, and interviews. The use of probit regression will provide a clear understanding of the factors affecting Nigeria's participation in the WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism and its export performance, ultimately informing policy decisions to boost the country's agricultural exports.

Furthermore, as noted in section 4.5.1, interviews and questionnaires were used to collect data from key actors across the upstream, midstream and downstream segments of Nigeria's trade environment. Responses to the questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. With respect to descriptive statistics, responses were quantified using frequencies, percentages, and bar charts. The application of descriptive statistics to analyze the responses from upstream actors to the questionnaires enabled the researcher to assess the level of awareness of relevant WTO's policies, rules and procedures among agricultural commodity producers and exporters. The inferential statistics entailed the use of correlation and regression analysis (i.e. probit regression) to test the significance of the relationship between dependent and independent variables. On the other hand, responses to the questionnaires were further probed using inferential statistics, i.e. correlation analysis. Here, responses to some questions in the questionnaires are used to test the relationship between certain variables such as the relationship between awareness of WTO standards and level of understanding of WTO rules on agriculture.

Four interviews were conducted for this research. The interviews are mostly targeted at key actors in the downstream and midstream segments of Nigeria's trade environment. The interviews are intended to understand the challenges and opportunities associated with trade facilitation in Nigeria. The interview questions are designed to collect information on the nature of coordination between downstream, midstream, and upstream stakeholders and how these have helped to address market access barriers faced by agricultural commodity exports. The interviews are also designed to collect information about institutional arrangements for trade facilitation and trade promotion; and how effective these arrangements have been in enhancing exports of selected agricultural

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

commodities. Understanding these institutional arrangements is key to identifying what gaps exist in Nigeria's trade environment with regards to effective engagement with global trade rules and organs. The responses to the interview questions were analyzed using thematic analysis. This entails examining the responses provided by the interviewees to identify key themes that formed the focus of discussions. Using an inductive approach, several themes were developed from interviewees' responses based on the research focus of the interviews. The responses were sorted into these themes and analyzed further to understand the breadth of the research.

Having discussed the approaches that will be used to analyze responses to the questionnaires and interviews, the next section discusses the sampling methods used to select respondents for this research.

4.6 Sampling Methods

Sampling methods deal with the processes and procedures used to select respondents for the collection of primary data (Collis & Hussey, 2005). Creswell (2007) views sampling as systematic procedures for selecting a sample for research that is representative of the population being studied. This particular observation is key because incorrect sampling could invalidate the findings of a research. Sampling is at the core of the notion 'validity' in research which is discussed in the next section.

Random sampling was used to select respondents for the questionnaires distributed to downstream stakeholders. Random sampling is a sampling technique used to select a sample from a population where each member of the population has equal chance of being selected to participate in the surveys (Saunders et al., 2005). The population for the questionnaires consists of downstream stakeholders specifically farmers, processors, and exporters of the following agricultural commodities: yam, shea butter, and beans. The plan is to distribute the questionnaires to 150 respondents in the downstream segment of the trade sector. On the other hand, purposive or judgmental sampling was used to select respondents for the interviews. Purposive sampling is a sampling technique where the researcher chooses respondents that suit the specific needs of the research (Bryman & Bell, 2011). For instance, depending on the nature of the research problem or topic, the researcher could subjectively select respondents that he or she feels can provide the required information needed to address the research objectives. This was the case in this research where it made sense to use purposive sampling to select respondents for the interviews given the technical nature of the subject matter under investigation. To address the hypotheses developed for the midstream and upstream segments of the trade sector, it is best to select only key players in both segments with the requisite knowledge,

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

technical capacity and experience in trade facilitation, trade promotion, and global trade know-how. Consequently, representatives of the FMITI, NOTN, NEPC, NISRAL, the AfCTA Secretariat, and Nigeria's Trade Delegation to the WTO. These representatives are positioned to provide the requisite information needed to address issues or questions around institutional capacity for trade facilitation, experience in trade negotiations, and challenges with Nigeria's engagement with the DSU and other organs of the WTO. In total, 15 people across the midstream and upstream segments of Nigeria's trade environment formed the sample for the interviews.

4.7 Validity, Reliability and Generalizability

This section addresses how the issues of validity, reliability, and generalizability were considered in this research. *Validity* according to Bond (2003:179), "deals with the extent to which empirical evidence and theoretical rationales support the adequacy and appropriateness of interpretations and actions based on test result". It can also be likened to the accuracy of measurements which influences the degree to which research results can be trusted. To enhance the validity of results for this research, care was taken when designing the questionnaires and interviews to ensure that generate responses that are sufficient to address the hypotheses developed for this research. Again, validity in this research was enhanced using descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze responses to the questionnaires.

On the other hand, *reliability* deals with the extent to which a measure is the same each time it is performed and by whoever performs it (Bannigan & Watson, 2009). To enhance the reliability of the findings of this research, results from the surveys were cross validated with results from the analysis of interviews. This cross-validation helped in validating the reliability of patterns in responses provided by both interviewees and survey respondents; thus, enhancing the trustworthiness of findings and conclusions for this research. Furthermore, validity and reliability of findings from the analysis of the questionnaires and interviews were triangulated against findings from the literature.

Generalizability deals with the degree to which the findings of a research can be generalized broadly (Collis & Hussey, 2005). Bearing in mind that data for this research was collected from stakeholders in Nigeria, there is a degree to which its findings can be applied broadly. As Nigeria formed the case study for examining developing countries' engagement with the WTO's DSS, the findings of this research are likely to reflect the situation in other developing countries particularly those in Africa. The degree to which it can be applied to other regions, such as Asia for instance, may be limited given likely differences in global trade, national trade policies and institutional arrangements.

4.8 Limitations of the Study

This section discusses some of the limitations encountered while conducting this research. One of the limitations of this research concerns the sample size; essentially, the non-availability of some interviewees reduced the sample size for this research. The sample situation also affected the sample size for the surveys. Another limitation of this research stemmed from the researcher's inability to access certain documents about previous and current trade negotiations between Nigeria and other WTO member countries. The inability to access these documents made it challenging for the researcher to get a firsthand appreciation of Nigeria's experience handling trade disputes especially those around barriers to its export of its agricultural commodities.

Another limitation of this research concerns the level of awareness of WTO rules and policies on agriculture, which affected the quality of information or data obtained from downstream stakeholders about the market access barriers faced by agricultural commodities produced in Nigeria. Despite this limitation, the surveys –which are largely distributed to downstream stakeholders- aided in identifying what the gaps are around awareness of these rules and policies, and how these can be plugged by trade institutions in the country.

Another limitation of this research concerns the fragmented nature of trade-related institutions in Nigeria. This limitation made it difficult to categorize or define institutional arrangements for trade facilitation and trade promotion. There have been occasions in the past where some Ministries, Departments, and Agencies (MDAs) act outside their core mandates in either trade facilitation or promotion. For instance, there have been cases where the Ministry of Foreign Affairs have exceeded their diplomatic mandates to get involved in trade promotion and trade facilitation. This situation demands the need for a detailed political economy analysis of global trade in Nigeria to ascertain core roles and responsibilities as it relates to trade promotion, trade facilitation, and trade negotiations. The interviews with midstream and upstream stakeholders provided useful information around core mandates among existing trade-related institutions in Nigeria. Having discussed the study's limitations, the next section discusses the issue of ethical considerations for this research.

4.9 Ethical Considerations

Ethics or ethical considerations are a central component of the research process. Collis & Hussey (2005) suggest that research ethics is basically concerned with the social responsibilities expected of a researcher especially when collecting data or information from human beings. Considering that data for this research was collected from human

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

beings through questionnaires and interviews, there were certain ethical considerations adhered to by the researcher. For one, ethical approval was obtained from the University of West Scotland before the questionnaires and interviews were conducted. After ethical approval was secured, the surveys and interviews were pilot tested to ensure that they meet the information needs of the research. In addition, the researcher obtained the consent of respondents –using consent forms- before they were allowed to participate in the surveys and interviews. Secondly, the researcher informed the respondents that their responses and participation in the surveys and questionnaires is solely for the purposes of this research and as such, will be treated with utmost confidentiality. Finally, during the interviews, the researcher informed the interviewees that their participation was voluntary and as such, they were free to withdraw their participation at any point.

CHAPTER FIVE

ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION OF QUANTITATIVE DATA

5.0 Introduction

This chapter covered the presentation and data analysis of the quantitative aspect of the study. As noted in chapter one, the study was conducted at three different levels of the supply chain in Nigeria viz; downstream, midstream and upstream levels. The upstream players were identified as the producers of Nigeria's export commodities, the midstream comprises of Nigeria's trade institutions while the downstream are categorized as Nigeria's representatives at the World Trade Organization. Accordingly, specific objectives were developed and methodologies for data collection and analysis were contrived for each level. Therefore, this chapter involved the presentation and analysis quantitative data gathered using a well-structured questionnaire. These data are related to the ability of the downstream level to identify Market access barriers drawing from the principal-agent framework earlier discussed.

5.1 Analysis of Survey Data

The main objective of the research at the downstream level was to examine the ability of the downstream players - producers of the export commodities – to identify market access barriers. Accordingly, specific objectives are; to examine the extent to which the downstream players understand the WTO standards, evaluate level of application of the WTO standards by the downstream players, appraise the downstream players' level of participation in commodity export, and identify the factors influencing the export of agricultural commodities in Nigeria.

The above objectives are based on the assumption that, for producers to be able to identify market access barriers, they should be able to understand and apply the WTO rules concerning what they produce as well as participate in the export of the commodities. Regarding the WTO rules, this study focuses on the Sanitary and phytosanitary (SPS) measures, Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) and the Rules of Origin Agreement. To measure these variables, a well-structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data from producers of three selected top export crops (Cocoa, Shea Nut and Sesame) in Nigeria. A sample size of 100 was drawn for each crop to participate in the survey. The data were extracted from the questionnaires returned and completed and

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

used for analysis. The data description and outcome of data analysis are presented in the subsequent sections.

5.2 Data description

As noted in the previous section, a total of 100 questionnaires were distributed to the producers of each of the selected crops (Cocoa, Shea Nut and Sesame). After extracting and cleaning the data, only 96 observations were deemed usable. Thus, the data analysis was based on 96 observations. Furthermore, data on respondents' demographics were collected and analyzed. Variables included were age, gender, education, experience, capacity and ownership. Other variables considered include export status, intention to export, engagement with national trade institutions as well understanding and application of WTO's SPS standards, Technical Standards and Rules of Origin. For better understanding and visualization, these data are described below.

Figure 5.1: Gender Distribution

Source: Author, 2023

As shown in figure 5.1 above, there are more males (72.9%) involved in cocoa production than females who were only 27.1% of the respondents. Similarly, there are more males (83.3%) involved in the production of sesame compared to the 16.7% females. The statistics is drastically different in the case of shea nut as males make up only 14.6% while 85.4% of the respondents were females.

THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS

Figure 5.2: Age distribution

Source: Author, 2023

As shown in figure 5.2 above most producers of shea nut are within the age ranges of 25-35 years and 41-55 years accounting for 42.7% and 52.1% of the respondents respectively. Similarly, majority of sesame producers are within the age range of 25-35 years and 41-55 years comprising 34.4 % and 64.6% of the respondents respectively. The producers of cocoa however, are fairly distributed across 25-35 years, 41-55 years and 56 years & above accounting for 32.3%, 36.5% and 31.3% of the respondents respectively.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Figure 5.3 Educational Qualification

Source: Author, 2023

As depicted in figure 5.3 above, majority (56.3%) of the sesame producers have either Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) or Diploma. In the same vein, most of the cocoa producers have O’level Certificate (WAEC) and Other certificates accounting for 45.8% and 41.7% respectively. However, the producers of shea nut seem to be fairly distributed across NCE/Diploma, First Degree, and WAEC accounting for 24%, 31.3% and 26% respectively.

Figure 5.4 Experience

Source: Author, 2023

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

As shown in figure 5.4 above, most of the respondents- 52.1% for cocoa, 94.8% for sesame and 44.8% for shea nut- have 16 years and above experience in production. For cocoa and shea nut, a significant percentage; 26% and 34.4% respectively have experiences ranging from 1 to 5 years.

Figure 5.5 Output

Source: Author, 2023

Figure 5.5 above shows that 78.1 percent of cocoa farmers produce between 0-10 tonnes per annum while 95.8% of sesame farmers produce above 40 tonnes per annum. However, the output capacity of shea nut producers is fairly distributed across 0-10 tonnes, 10-20 tonnes and 20-30 tonnes accounting for 40.6%, 30.2% and 26% respectively.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Figure 5.6: Ownership

Source: Author, 2023

As shown in Figure 5.6 above, all of the cocoa farms are 100% owned by Nigerians. Similarly, 97.9% of sesame farms and 71.9% of Shea nut farms are 100% owned by Nigerians. A significant 22.9% of the shea nut farms are co-owned by foreigners with Nigerians owning more than 50% of the business. A paltry 2.1% of sesame farms and 5.1% of shea butter farms are equally distributed among Nigerian and foreign owners. This shows that the businesses involved in this survey are predominantly Nigerian owned.

Figure 5.7 Export Status

Source: Author, 2023

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

As depicted in figure 5.7 above, 92.7% of Cocoa farmers and 85.4% of shea butter farmers are currently not exporting their produce. This implies that majority of cocoa and sesame producers are not exporting. On the other hand, 77.1% of Sesame producers are currently exporting their produce.

Figure 5.8: Intention to Export

Source: Author, 2023

As may be observed in figure 6.8 above, 89.6% of Cocoa producers have no intention of exporting while 80.2% of sesame producers and 88.5% of shea nut producers have intention to export.

THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS

Figure 5.9: Engagement with SON

Source: Author, 2023

Figure 5.9 above shows that 69.8% of cocoa producers, 90.6% of Sesame producers and 55.2% of shea butter producers have never engaged the standard organisation of Nigeria. Only 30.2%, 9.4% and 44.8% of cocoa producers, sesame producers and shea nut producers respectively have had any sort of engagement with the agency.

Figure 5.10: Engagement with NAQS

Source: Author, 2023

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Figure 5.10 above indicates that 56.3% of cocoa producers, 63.5% of sesame producers and 72.9 % of shea nut producers have not had any engagement with the National Quarantine agency. This implies that most of these producers do not engage National Quarantine agency.

Table 5.1: Level of Engagement with FMARD

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Cocoa	96	1.00	5.00	3.1458	.94009
Sesame	96	1.00	5.00	2.9583	.38159
Shea Butter	96	1.00	5.00	1.9583	1.35271
Valid N (listwise)	96				

Source: Author, 2023

Table 5.1 above shows that cocoa producers have fairly good engagement with the ministry of Agriculture with an average of 3.1. However, the high standard deviation of 0.94 shows a wide variation in the response of the producers. Whereas both sesame and shea nut producers have low level of engagement with ministry of agriculture at an average of 2.9 and 1.96 respectively, the low standard deviation of 0.38159 for sesame indicates that the producers closely agreed while the high standard deviation of 1.35271 for shea nut implies that the respondents grossly disagree in their responses.

Table 5.2: Level of Engagement with FMITI

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Cocoa	96	1.00	5.00	1.9896	1.16524
Sesame	96	1.00	5.00	1.8646	.49460
Shea Butter	96	1.00	5.00	1.8854	1.23006
Valid N (listwise)	96				

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Source: Author, 2023

Table 5.2 above indicate that all the producers-cocoa, sesame, and shea nut-have very low engagement with the ministry of trade and investment yielding average of 1.9896, 1.8646 and 1.8854 respectively. However, the low standard deviation of 0.49460 for sesame producers implies that they are in close agreement whereas the high standard deviation of 1.16524, and 1.23006 for cocoa and shea butter respectively indicates that the respondents grossly disagree.

Table 7.3: Understanding of SPS

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Cocoa	96	1.00	5.00	3.4063	1.19277
Sesame	96	1.00	5.00	1.9167	.60986
Shea Butter	96	1.00	5.00	2.2396	1.45635
Valid (listwise)	N 96				

Source: Author, 2023

Table 5.3 above shows that cocoa producers have a fair understanding of SPS standards at an average of 3.4063. However, the high standard deviation of 1.19277 indicates that the respondents grossly disagree. The producers of sesame and shea nut on the other hand, have low understanding of SPS standards at an average of 1.9167 and 2.2396 respectively. The fair standard deviation of 0.60986 for sesame implies that the respondents closely agree with one another while the high standard deviation of 1.45635 for shea nut shows that the respondents widely disagree in their responses.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Table 5.4: Application of SPS

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Cocoa	96	1.00	5.00	2.9688	1.40265
Sesame	96	1.00	5.00	1.9792	.72517
Shea Butter	96	1.00	5.00	2.1979	1.47698
Valid N (listwise)	96				

Source: Author, 2023

Table 5.4 above indicate that cocoa producers apply SPS standards to a reasonable extent at an average of 2.9688 however, a high standard deviation implies that the respondents widely disagree in their responses. Sesame and shea nut producers on the other hand, do not apply the SPS standards enough with an average of 1.9792 and 2.1979 respectively. The high standard deviations of 0.72062 and 1.48467 also indicate that the respondents widely disagree.

Table 5.5: Understanding of Technical Rules

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Cocoa	96	1.00	5.00	3.7500	1.24816
Sesame	96	1.00	5.00	4.4792	1.07585
Shea Butter	96	1.00	5.00	2.3229	1.49733
Valid N (listwise)	96				

Source: Author, 2023

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Table 5.5 above demonstrates that both cocoa and sesame producers have very good understanding of WTO Technical Rules at an average of 3.7500 and 4.4792 respectively. Shea nut producers on the other hand have low understanding of the technical rules at an average of 2.3229. The high standard deviation of 1.24816, 1.07585 and 1.49733 indicate that the respondents are not in close agreement.

Table 5.6: Application of Technical Rules

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Cocoa	96	1.00	5.00	3.5313	1.30548
Sesame	96	1.00	5.00	4.2396	1.27935
Shea Butter	96	1.00	5.00	2.0521	1.45363
Valid (listwise)	N 96				

Source: Author, 2023

Table 5.6 above shows that cocoa producers apply the technical rules to a fair extent at a mean value 3.5313 while sesame producers apply the technical rules to a very good extent at an average of 4.2396. On the other hand, shea butter producers have a low level of application at a mean value of 2.0521. The high standard deviation of 1.30548, 1.27935 and 1.45363 respectively, implies a wide variation in the responses of the producers.

Table 5.7: Understanding of Rules of Origin

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Cocoa	96	1.00	5.00	3.3125	1.49605
Sesame	96	1.00	5.00	4.6771	.91185
Shea Butter	96	1.00	5.00	1.4167	1.06293

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Valid (listwise)	N	96				
---------------------	---	----	--	--	--	--

Source: Author, 2023

Table 5.7 above demonstrates that cocoa and sesame producers have very good understanding of WTO Rules of origin at an average of 3.3125 and 4.6771 respectively. Shea nut producers on the other hand, have low understanding of the rules of origin at an average of 1.4167. Again, the high standard deviation of 1.49605, 0.91185 and 1.06293 indicate that the respondents are not in close agreement.

Table 5.8: Application of Rules of Origin

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Cocoa	96	1.00	6.00	2.5729	1.55425
Sesame	96	1.00	5.00	4.6667	.96972
Shea nut	96	1.00	5.00	1.5000	1.09545
Valid N (listwise)	96				

Source: Author, 2023

Table 5.8 above shows that cocoa producers apply the rules of origin to some degree at a mean value 2.5729 while sesame producers apply the rules of origin to a very good extent at an average of 4.6667. On the other hand, shea butter producers have a low level of application at a mean value of 1.5. The high standard deviation of 1.55425, 0.96972 and 1.09545 respectively, implies a wide variation in the responses of the producers.

5.2 Data Analyses and Interpretation

This segment analyses the primary data collected and interprets the outcomes. The main inferential statistical techniques employed are Pearson Correlation analysis and probit regression using Generalized Linear Models (GLM) in SPSS. Various diagnostic tests

THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS

including and goodness-of-fit, Omnibus Test and Tests of Model Effects, were carried out on each data set to validate the model's performance and relevance to the research questions

Correlation Analysis

Before proceeding to probit regression, correlation analysis was estimated to determine the relationships between variables as well as the direction and strength of these relationships. Specifically, the correlation analysis aimed to find correlations between factors such as understanding and application of the WTO rules, Engagement with relevant national trade institutions and producer related factors and the export status of agricultural commodities (cocoa, sesame, shea nuts) producers in Nigeria. These correlations can shed light on the upstream-related factors that contribute most significantly to Nigeria's participation in the WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism and its ability to boost agricultural exports.

Probit Regression

The data analysis technique adopted for this research is the probit regression using Generalized Linear Models (GLM) in SPSS. Given the nature of the research questions, this choice is driven by the need to analyze binary dependent variables and their relationship with multiple predictor variables (McCullagh & Nelder, 1989). Since samples were collected for three different crops (coffee, cocoa, and another unspecified crop), and six equations were specified for testing the hypotheses in this segment, the GLM is estimated for each of the equations under each crop.

To ensure the robustness and reliability of the probit regression outcomes, several diagnostic and goodness-of-fit tests were carried out on each data set. These tests include Goodness of Fit, Omnibus Test, Tests of Model Effects, and Correlation analysis, which are essential to validate the model's performance and relevance to the research questions (Hosmer, Lemeshow, & Sturdivant, 2013).

Goodness of Fit

A goodness-of-fit test measures how well the observed data correspond to the fitted (assumed) model (Kenton, 2021). In this study, the goodness-of-fit test is used to evaluate how well each probit regression model fits the data. It helps assess the model's suitability and accuracy in explaining the relationship between the dependent and independent variables (Agresti, 2018).

There are several goodness-of-fit tests applicable to probit regression analysis, including the Hosmer-Lemeshow test, the Pearson chi-square test, and the deviance test. For this

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

study, the Pearson and deviance goodness-of-fit measures are employed. These tests compare the predicted probabilities from the model with the observed probabilities in the data. Higher p-values indicate that the model fits the data well, while lower p-values suggest that the model may not be appropriate and another distribution might be needed (Yazici et al., 2007).

Linking this to our specific research questions and hypotheses, the goodness-of-fit test ensures that our probit regression models accurately reflect the real-world relationships between the variables in our study. For instance, the study hypothesizes that understanding and applying WTO rules significantly influences export status. A good fit would indicate that the model reliably captures this relationship.

Omnibus Test

An omnibus test evaluates whether the explained variance in a set of data is significantly greater than the unexplained variance. This test is crucial because if the model coefficients are not significantly different from zero, the model would not be useful for predicting the occurrence of the event of interest (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). In this study, the Chi-squared test is used to compare the full model with the intercept-only model and obtain a p-value for the omnibus test.

The null hypothesis for the omnibus test is that the model coefficients are not jointly different from zero. A low p-value indicates that the model coefficients are significantly different from zero, suggesting that the model fits better than the intercept-only model. Conversely, a high p-value would indicate that the model does not fit better than the intercept-only model. Rejecting the null hypothesis implies that the model is a good fit for the data (Field, 2013).

This test is directly linked to the research hypotheses, as it validates whether the predictors included (e.g., understanding of WTO rules, and engagement with specific regulatory bodies) significantly contribute to explaining export status. A significant omnibus test result would support the hypothesis that these factors are important determinants of export activities.

Tests of Model Effects

Tests of model effects are necessary in probit regression analysis to assess the significance of each predictor variable in the model. These tests evaluate the contribution of each predictor to the overall model, allowing researchers to identify which variables are significant predictors of the event and which can be removed without significantly affecting the model's accuracy (Allison, 2012).

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

For this study, the Wald test is adopted. The null hypothesis of the Wald test is that the coefficient of a particular independent variable is equal to zero, meaning there is no relationship between that variable and the probability of the dependent variable taking a certain value. The alternative hypothesis is that there is a significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. A low p-value indicates that the predictor variable significantly affects the outcome and should be included in the model. Conversely, a high p-value suggests that the variable does not significantly affect the outcome and can be omitted (Hosmer, Lemeshow, & Sturdivant, 2013).

This is particularly relevant to the study's hypotheses, as it helps determine which specific aspects of understanding and applying WTO rules, or which engagements with regulatory bodies, significantly impact export status. Identifying significant predictors allows for more accurate models and better insights into the factors driving export success.

Parameter Estimates

The parameter estimates table summarizes the effect of each predictor. Although interpreting the coefficients in a probit model can be complex due to the nature of the link function, the signs of the coefficients and their relative magnitudes provide important insights into the effects of the predictors (Long & Freese, 2014).

Positive coefficients indicate a positive relationship between the predictor and the outcome, while negative coefficients suggest an inverse relationship (Long & Freese, 2014). This helps in understanding how different factors, such as understanding of WTO rules, application of the WTO rules, engagement with specific regulatory bodies and Producer attributes, influence the likelihood of being an exporter.

For this analysis, the following models were specified for each crop;

Model 1:

$$Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSU}_i + \beta_2 \text{TECH}_i + \beta_3 \text{ROOU}_i + \epsilon_i$$

where:

Y_i is the dependent variable for observation i

a is the intercept

SPSU_i is the value of the predictor variable SPSU for observation i

β_1 is the coefficient for SPSU

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

TECHU_i is the value of the predictor variable TECHU for observation i

β₂ is the coefficient for TECHU

ROOU_i is the value of the predictor variable ROOU for observation i

β₃ is the coefficient for ROOU

ε_i is the error term for observation i

Model 2:

$$Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSA}_i + \beta_2 \text{TECHA}_i + \beta_3 \text{ROOA}_i + \epsilon_i$$

where:

Y_i is the dependent variable for observation i

a is the intercept

SPSA_i is the value of the predictor variable SPSA for observation i

β₁ is the coefficient for SPSA

TECHA_i is the value of the predictor variable TECHA for observation i

β₂ is the coefficient for TECHA

ROOA_i is the value of the predictor variable ROOA for observation i

β₃ is the coefficient for ROOA

ε_i is the error term for observation i

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Model 3:

$$Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SON}_i + \beta_2 \text{NAQS}_i + \beta_3 \text{FMIT}_i + \beta_4 \text{FMARD}_i + \epsilon_i$$

where:

Y_i is the dependent variable for observation i

a is the intercept

SON_i is the value of the predictor variable SON for observation i

β_1 is the coefficient for SON

NAQS_i is the value of the predictor variable NAQS for observation i

β_2 is the coefficient for NAQS

FMIT_i is the value of the predictor variable FMITI for observation i

β_3 is the coefficient for FMITI

FMARD_i is the value of the predictor variable FMARD for observation i

β_4 is the coefficient for FMARD

ϵ_i is the error term for observation i

Model 4:

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

$$Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience}_i + \beta_2 \text{Education}_i + \beta_3 \text{Age}_i \times \text{Output}_i + \epsilon_i$$

where:

Y_i is the dependent variable for observation i

a is the intercept

Experience_i is the value of the predictor variable Experience for observation i

β_1 is the coefficient for Experience

Education_i is the value of the predictor variable Education for observation i

β_2 is the coefficient for Education

Age_i is the value of the predictor variable Age for observation i

Output_i is the value of the predictor variable Output for observation i

β_3 is the coefficient for Age x Output

ϵ_i is the error term for observation i

Model 5:

$$Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience}_i + \beta_2 \text{Education}_i + \beta_3 \text{Ownership}_i \times \text{Output}_i + \epsilon_i$$

where:

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Y_i is the dependent variable for observation i

a is the intercept

Experience i is the value of the predictor variable Experience for observation i

β_1 is the coefficient for Experience

Education i is the value of the predictor variable Education for observation i

β_2 is the coefficient for Education

Ownership i is the value of the predictor variable Ownership for observation i

Output i is the value of the predictor variable Output for observation i

β_3 is the coefficient for Ownership x Output

ϵ_i is the error term for observation i

Model 6:

$$Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience}_i + \beta_2 \text{Education}_i + \beta_3 \text{Ownership}_i \times \text{Output}_i + \epsilon_i$$

where:

Y_i is the dependent variable for observation i

a is the intercept

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Experience_i is the value of the predictor variable Experience for observation i

β_1 is the coefficient for Experience

Education

Gender_i is the value of the predictor variable Gender for observation i

Output_i is the value of the predictor variable Output for observation i

β_3 is the coefficient for Gender x Output

ϵ_i is the error term for observation

Model Information

Model Information is important in understanding the parameter output of probit regression because it helps in interpreting the effects of the predictor variables on the binary outcome variable and assesses the adequacy of the probit model. Basically, model information provides information about the binary response variable predicted by the model and the probability to admit an observation given the values of the predictors. The model information for all the probit regression models in this research is as presented in Table 5.9 below:

Table 5.9: Model Information

Dependent Variable	Export Status ^a
Probability Distribution	Binomial
Link Function	Probit

a. The procedure models 1.00 as the response, treating .00 as the reference category.

The model information in table 5.9 above shows that the procedure models 1 as the response while treating 0 as the reference category and the information is true for all the probit regressions in this section.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

5.2.1 Correlation Analysis - Sesame

This correlation analysis aimed to find correlations between factors such understanding and application of the WTO rules, Engagement with relevant national trade institutions and producer related factors and the export status of sesame producers in Nigeria. It will shed light on the relationships between variables as well as the direction and strength of these relationships. The outcome will also complement the probit regression output. The primary data collected from producers of sesame was coded appropriately and subjected to Pearson Correlation analysis. The outcome is presented in the table below;

Table 5.10a Correlation Matrix - Sesame

Variables	Export Stat	TECHU	SPSU	TECHA	SPSA	NQA	FMI	FMA	SON	Ownership	Output	Experience	Education	Age	Gender	ROOA
TECHU	0.013															
SPSU	0.007	0.158														
TECHA	-0.011	.513**	-0.121													
SPSA	0.053	0.107	.900**	-0.17												
NQA	0.104	-.501**	0.14	-.331**	.232*											
FMI	-0.049	.202*	.835**	-0.089	.726**	0.033										
FMA	-0.06	.331**	0.121	0.086	0.035	-0.088	.416**									
SON	0.09	-.244*	.398**	-.372**	.406**	.350**	0.161	-0.059								
Ownership	0.08	-0.133	.260*	-.277**	.409**	0.193	0.04	-.368**	.454**							
Output	-0.108	.365**	-0.19	0.082	-.234*	-0.192	0.079	.845**	-.275**	-.432**						
Experience	-0.075	0.191	-.399**	.365**	-.451**	-0.182	-0.038	.349**	-.588**	-.625**	.409**					
Education	-0.089	-.459**	0.06	-.334**	0.136	.551**	-0.019	-0.059	.206*	-0.007	-0.118	-0.065				
Age	-0.017	0.165	0.186	.274**	0.156	0.029	0.115	-0.019	0	-0.197	-0.067	0	-0.082			
Gender	-0.111	.226*	.676**	-0.145	.607**	-0.068	.786**	0.098	-0.048	0.065	0.088	-0.062	-0.087	0.094		
ROOA	-0.034	.558**	-0.065	.895**	-0.13	-.366**	-0.007	0.076	-.519**	-.328**	0.068	.382**	-.327**	.314**	-0.039	
ROOU	-0.003	.567**	-0.068	.828**	-0.138	-.375**	-0.005	0.082	-.555**	-.350**	0.075	.408**	-.357**	.295**	-0.036	.960**

**p < 0.01(2-tailed); * p < 0.05; N=96

Source: *Correlation Output,2024*

The correlation table illustrates the relationships between Export Status and various other variables, with Export Status representing whether a producer is currently exporting. The relationships observed are relatively weak across the board. The understanding of WTO Technical Rules (TECHU) and WTO sanitary rules (SPSU) both show negligible positive correlations with Export Status (0.013 and 0.007 respectively), indicating little direct influence on whether a producer exports. Similarly, the application of WTO Technical Rules (TECHA) and WTO sanitary rules (SPSA) also show minimal correlations (-0.011 and 0.053, respectively), suggesting that these factors are not strongly linked to export status.

Engagement with national institutions such as the Federal Ministry of Industries (FMI) and the Firm Market Access (FMA) also show weak and slightly negative correlations (-0.049 and -0.06 respectively), indicating that these engagements do not have a significant direct

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

impact on export status. The relationship between Export Status and SON (Standards Organisation of Nigeria) is slightly positive (0.09), suggesting a minor influence.

Ownership and Output exhibit modest correlations (0.08 and -0.108 respectively) with Export Status, showing that while ownership may have a minor positive relationship, higher output does not necessarily correspond to export status. Experience, Education, Age, and Gender all show weak negative correlations with Export Status (-0.075, -0.089, -0.017, and -0.111, respectively), suggesting these demographic factors do not significantly determine whether a producer exports. Lastly, the application and understanding of WTO Rules of Origin (ROOA and ROOU) also show minimal correlations (-0.034 and -0.003 respectively), indicating that these factors are not significant predictors of export status.

Overall, the data suggests that the variables examined have limited direct correlation with a producer's export status, highlighting that export activities may be influenced by a complex interplay of factors not fully captured in this table.

5.2.2 Probit Regression – Sesame

Model 1: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSU} + \beta_2 \text{TECHU} + \beta_3 \text{ROOU} + \epsilon_i$

This probit regression model investigates the likelihood of producers of Sesame being exporters based on their understanding of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSU), WTO technical rules (TECHU), and WTO rules of origin (ROOU). The theoretical significance of these variables lies in the assumption that understanding and compliance with international trade rules (SPSU, ROOU, and TECHU) might influence a producer's ability to access and compete in global markets.

The **Goodness of Fit Value/df** for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory. The **Omnibus Test** shows likelihood ratio chi-square indicates that the model as a whole is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was rejected. However, there can still be a legitimate significant effect within the model. The **Tests of Model Effects** show that individually, the terms SPSU, TECHU, ROOU do not contribute discernible effect in the models given all p-values are greater than 0.05. While the Parameter Estimates is as presented below:

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Table 5.11a: Parameter Estimate

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	0.712	0.9206	0.599	1	0.439	2.039
ROOU	-0.021	0.1938	0.012	1	0.912	0.979
TECHU	0.026	0.1644	0.025	1	0.876	1.026
SPSU	0.007	0.2572	0.001	1	0.978	1.007
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), ROOU, TECHU, SPSU						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of Sesame with understanding of WTO sanitary and Phyto sanitary rules (SPSU), estimated coefficient = 0.007, p value =0.978>0.05(not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters
- ii. producers of Sesame with understanding of WTO Rules of Origin (ROOU), estimated coefficient = -0.021, p value =0.912>0.05 (not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters
- iii. producers of Sesame with understanding of WTO Technical Rules (TECHU), estimated coefficient = 0.026, p value =0.876>0.05(not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

Model 2: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSA} + \beta_2 \text{TECHA} + \beta_3 \text{ROOA} + \epsilon_i$

This probit regression model investigates the likelihood of producers of Sesame being exporters based on their application of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSA),

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

WTO technical rules (TECHA), and WTO rules of origin (ROOA). The study assumes that application or compliance with international trade rules (SPSA, ROOA, and TECHA) might influence a producer's ability to access and compete in global markets.

The **Goodness of Fit-Sesame Value/df** for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory. Also, the **Omnibus Test** shows that the model as a whole is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was not rejected. However, there can still be a legitimate significant effect within the model. **Tests of Model Effects** show that individually, the variables SPSA, TECHA, ROOA do not contribute discernible effect in the models given all p-values are greater than 0.05. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below:

Table 5.12a: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	0.554	0.9526	0.339	1	0.561	1.741
ROOA	-0.298	0.5606	0.283	1	0.595	0.742
TECHA	0.284	0.5609	0.256	1	0.613	1.328
SPSA	0.128	0.2304	0.308	1	0.579	1.136
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), ROOA, TECHA, SPSA						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of Sesame who apply WTO sanitary and Phyto sanitary rules (SPSA), estimated coefficient = 0.128, p value =0.579>0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- ii. Producers of Sesame who apply WTO Technical rules (TECHA), estimated coefficient = 0.284, p value =0.613>0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.
- iii. Producers of Sesame who apply WTO Rules of Origin (ROOA), estimated coefficient = -0.284, p value =0.595>0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

Model 3: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SON} + \beta_2 \text{NAQS} + \beta_3 \text{FMITI} + \beta_4 \text{FMARD} + \epsilon_i$

This model assesses the impact of engagement with key regulatory bodies on export status. These variables represent key institutions that regulate and facilitate trade. The theoretical significance of these variables - key institutions that regulate and facilitate trade- lies in their roles in ensuring compliance with international standards and providing support for export activities.

The **Goodness of Fit Value/df** for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory while the **Omnibus Test** indicates that the model as a whole is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was not rejected. However, there can still be a legitimate significant effect within the model. The **Tests of Model Effects** show that individually, none of the variables contributes discernible effect in the models. The parameter estimates are as presented below:

Table 5.13a: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates							
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	
(Intercept)	1.477	1.4277	1.071	1	0.301	4.381	
NAQS	0.23	0.3238	0.504	1	0.478	1.258	
FMITI	-0.149	0.3568	0.174	1	0.677	0.862	
FMARD	-0.19	0.5441	0.123	1	0.726	0.827	
SON	0.443	0.6297	0.494	1	0.482	1.557	
(Scale)	1a						
Dependent Variable: Export Status							

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Model: (Intercept), NAQS, FMITI, FMARD, SON

a Fixed at the displayed value.

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of Sesame who engage with the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and rural development (FMARD), estimated coefficient = -0.19, statistically insignificant p-value =0.726>0.05 are less likely to be exporters.
- ii. Producers of Sesame who engage with the Federal Ministry of Industries, Trade and Investment (FMITI), estimated coefficient = -0.149, p value =0.677>0.05 (not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- iii. Producers of Sesame who engage with the Standards Organisation of Nigeria (SON), estimated coefficient = 0.443, p value =0.482>0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.
- iv. Producers of Sesame who engage with the National Agricultural Quarantine Services (NAQS), estimated coefficient = 0.23, p value =0.478>0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

.Model 4: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{ Experience} + \beta_2 \text{ Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Age} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of age and output on export status. These factors are significant in understanding how the demographics and capabilities of producers influence their export status. Theoretically, more experience and education might be expected to enhance export potential.

The **Goodness of Fit-Sesame Value/df** for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory. The **Omnibus Test** shows indicates that the model as a whole is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was not rejected. However, there can still be a legitimate significant effect within the model. While the **Tests of Model Effects** show that individually, none of the variables contribute discernible effect in the models. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below:

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Table 5.14a: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	2.427	1.6166	2.254	1	0.133	11.323
Education	-0.105	0.1098	0.922	1	0.337	0.9
Experience	-0.582	0.7618	0.584	1	0.445	0.559
Output_Age	-0.062	0.0995	0.394	1	0.53	0.939
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), Education , Experience , Output_Age						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of Sesame with higher level of education, estimated coefficient = -0.105, p value =0.337>0.05(not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- ii. Producers of Sesame who have more experience, estimated coefficient = -0.582, p-value =0.445>0.05(not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- iii. Producers of Sesame with higher output and are older, estimated coefficient = -0.062, p-value =0.53<0.05(statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.

Model 5: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{ Experience} + \beta_2 \text{ Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Ownership} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of ownership and output on export status. These factors are significant in understanding how producer-related factors influence their export status.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

The **Goodness of Fit Value/df** for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory. The **Omnibus Test** indicates that the model as a whole is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was not rejected. However, there can still be a legitimate significant effect within the model. While the **Tests of Model Effects** output shows that none of the variables contribute discernible effect in the models. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below:

Table 5.15a: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	2.897	2.2065	1.724	1	0.189	18.115
Education	-0.1	0.1092	0.847	1	0.358	0.904
Experience	-0.661	0.7585	0.76	1	0.383	0.516
Output_Ownership	-0.212	0.4133	0.262	1	0.608	0.809
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), Education , Experience , Output_Ownership						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of Sesame with higher level of education, estimated coefficient = - 0.1, p value =0.358>0.05(not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- ii. Producers of Sesame who have more experience, estimated coefficient = - 0.661, p-value =0.383>0.05(not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- iii. Producers of Sesame with higher output and more foreign ownership, estimated coefficient = -0.212, p-value = 0.608 > 0.05 (statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.

Model 6: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Gender} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of Gender and output on export status. These factors are significant in understanding how producer-related factors influence their export status.

The **Goodness of Fit** Value/df for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory. While the **Omnibus Test** indicates that the model as a whole is not statistically significant (appendix 6.2b). Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was not rejected. Although the likelihood ratio chi-square of 3.753 with a p-value 0.289 > 0.5 is not statistically significant, there can still be a legitimate significant effect within the model. The **Tests of Model Effects** shows that individually, none of the variables contribute discernible effect in the models. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below:

Table 5.16 a: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	3	1.6472	3.317	1	0.069	20.089
Education	-0.109	0.1094	1	1	0.317	0.896
Experience	-0.473	0.751	0.397	1	0.529	0.623
Output_Gender	-0.198	0.1378	2.058	1	0.151	0.821
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), Education , Experience , Output_Gender						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of Sesame with higher level of education, estimated coefficient = -0.109, p value =0.317>0.05(not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- ii. Producers of Sesame who have more experience, estimated coefficient = -0.473, p-value =0.529>0.05(not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- iii. Male Producers of Sesame with higher output, estimated coefficient = -0.198, p-value =0.151>0.05(not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.

5.2.3 Hypothesis Testing- Sesame

H₀₁ – There is no significant relationship between understanding of WTO rules on agriculture and the export behavior of agricultural commodity producers.

The model specified for testing this hypothesis is Model 1: $y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSU} + \beta_2 \text{TECHU} + \beta_3 \text{ROOU} + \varepsilon_i$. The outcome of the probit regression using the above model showed that all the independent variables, (understanding of the sanitary and Phyto sanitary rules (SPSU), estimated coefficient = 0.007, p value =0.978>0.05, understanding of Rules of Origin (ROOU), estimated coefficient = -0.021, p value =0.912>0.05 and understanding of Technical Rules (TECHU), estimated coefficient = 0.026, p value =0.876>0.05) have no statistically significant impact on export behaviour. Therefore, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis.

H₀₂ – There is no relationship between application of WTO rules on agriculture and the export behaviour of agricultural commodity producers.

The model specified for testing this hypothesis is Model 2: $y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSA} + \beta_2 \text{TECHA} + \beta_3 \text{ROOA} + \varepsilon_i$. The outcome of the probit regression using the above model showed that all the independent variables (application of sanitary and Phytosanitary rules (SPSA), estimated coefficient = 0.128, p-value =0.579>0.05, application of technical rules (TECHA), estimated coefficient = 0.284, p-value =0.613>0.05 and application of Rules of Origin (ROOA), estimated coefficient = -0.284, p-value =0.595>0.05) have no statistically significant impact on export behaviour. Therefore, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis.

H₀₃ – Level of engagement with national trade institutions does not affect the export behaviour of agriculture commodity producers.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

The model specified for testing this hypothesis is Model 3: $y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SON} + \beta_2 \text{NAQS} + \beta_3 \text{FMITI} + \beta_4 \text{FMARD} + \epsilon_i$. The outcome of the probit regression using the above model showed that all the independent variables (engagement with Federal Ministry of Agriculture and rural development (FMARD), estimated coefficient = -0.19, p-value = 0.726 > 0.05, engagement with Federal Ministry of Industries, Trade and Investment (FMITI), estimated coefficient = -0.149, p-value = 0.677 > 0.05, engagement with Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON), estimated coefficient = 0.443, p-value = 0.482 > 0.05, and engagement with National Agricultural Quarantine Services (NAQS), estimated coefficient = 0.23, p-value = 0.478 > 0.05) have no statistically significant impact on export behaviour. Therefore, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis.

H₀₄ – Producer-related factors do not affect the export behaviour of agriculture commodity producers

The model specified for testing this hypothesis are;

Model 4: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Age} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$,

Model 5: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Ownership} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$ and

Model 6: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Gender} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

First, the outcome of the probit regression using model 4 showed that output with a mediating effect of Age (Output*Age), estimated coefficient = -0.062, p-value = 0.53 < 0.05 has a statistically significant negative impact on export behaviour. Whereas all other variables have no significant impact on export behaviour. Secondly, the outcome of the probit regression using model 5 revealed that all the independent variables have no significant impact on export behaviour except output with a mediating effect of Ownership (Output*Ownership), estimated coefficient = -0.212, p-value = 0.608 > 0.05 which has a significant negative impact on export performance. Finally, the outcome of the probit regression using model 6 suggests that none of the independent variables has a statistically significant impact on export behaviour. Given that, at least one variable in models 4 and 5 has a significant impact on export behaviour, the study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate hypothesis which states that producer-related factors have a significant effect on the export behaviour of sesame producers in Nigeria.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

5.2.4 Correlation Analysis - Cocoa

This correlation analysis aimed to find correlations between factors such understanding and application of the WTO rules, Engagement with relevant national trade institutions and producer related factors and the export status of cocoa producers in Nigeria. It will shed light on the relationships between variables as well as the direction and strength of these relationships. The outcome will also complement the probit regression output. The primary data collected from producers of cocoa was coded appropriately and subjected to Pearson Correlation analysis. The outcome is presented in the table below;

Table 5.10b Correlation Matrix - Cocoa

Variables	Export Status	FMARD	FMITI	SON	SPSU	SPSA	TECHU	TECHA	Gender	Age	Education	Experience	Output	Ownership
FMARD	.385**													
FMITI	.452**	.424**												
SON	.339**	.213*	.515**											
SPSU	0.174	0.134	0.139	0.138										
SPSA	.236*	0.035	.354**	.275**	.568**									
TECHU	.278**	.264**	.275**	.320**	.621**	.343**								
TECHA	.315**	.339**	.568**	.538**	.267**	.558**	.559**							
ROOU	.758**	.276**	.299**	0.181	.336**	.316**	.344**	.419**						
ROOA	.731**	.426**	.221*	.237*	.459**	.407**	.440**	.539**	.895**					
Gender	0.171	-0.08	-0.026	-0.007	0.09	0.121	0.06	-0.13	0.241					
Age	0.007	-0.064	-0.022	-0.067	-0.056	-0.037	-0.046	-0.16	.415**					
Education	-.494**	-.309**	-.327**	-.341**	-0.191	-.223*	-.202*	-0.181	-0.111	-0.047				
Experience	0.127	-0.043	-0.2	-0.134	-0.121	-0.052	-0.089	-0.181	.210*	.215*	-0.028			
Output	.786**	.279**	.402**	.251*	.274**	.291**	.258*	.279**	0.153	-0.085	-.482**	0.022		
Ownership	.366**	0.094	0.178	0.156	0.051	0.002	0.112	0.096	0.063	0.003	-.225*	0.104	.343**	
NAQS	.764**	.234*	.447**	.425**	.234*	.375**	.223*	.386**	0.139	-0.094	-.417**	0.027	.768**	.337**

**p <0.01(2-tailed); * p < 0.05; N=96

Source: *Correlation Output,2024*

The analysis reveals that several factors are significantly associated with a producer's likelihood to export. Producers' understanding of WTO rules shows a significant positive correlation with Export Status. ROOU (producer's understanding of WTO Rules of Origin) at .758** and TECHU (producer's understanding of WTO Technical Rules) at .278** highlight that a deep knowledge of international trade rules is crucial for exporting success.

Also, the application of WTO rules positively correlates with Export Status. ROOA (application of WTO Rules of Origin) at .731** and TECHA (application of WTO Technical Rules) at .315** suggest that the practical implementation of these rules significantly boosts a producer's likelihood to export. Similarly, the application of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSA) at .236* supports this conclusion.

Among the producer-related factors, Output shows the strongest positive correlation with Export Status at .786**, indicating that higher production levels are a major determinant of export capability. Ownership, with a moderate correlation of .366**, suggests that the

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

ownership structure influences export decisions. Other demographic factors such as Gender (.171), Age (.007), Education (-.494**), and Experience (.127) show weaker or negative correlations with Export Status, implying these factors are less significant in determining export likelihood.

Finally, Engagement with national trade institutions and agencies is positively associated with Export Status. The Federal Ministry of Industries, Trade, and Investment (FMITI) at .452** and the Standards Organisation of Nigeria (SON) at .339** highlight the importance of institutional support and compliance with standards. Additionally, engagement with the National Agricultural Quarantine Services (NAQS) at .764** underscores the role of agricultural standards compliance in export readiness. The Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD) also shows a significant positive correlation with Export Status at .385**, emphasizing the importance of the ministry in facilitating exports.

5.2.5 Probit Regression - Cocoa

$$\text{Model 1: } Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSU} + \beta_2 \text{TECHU} + \beta_3 \text{ROOU} + \epsilon_i$$

This probit regression model investigates the likelihood of producers of Cocoa being exporters based on their understanding of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSU), WTO technical rules (TECHU), and WTO rules of origin (ROOU). The theoretical significance of these variables lies in the assumption that understanding and compliance with international trade rules (SPSU, ROOU, and TECHU) might influence a producer's ability to access and compete in global markets.

The **Goodness of Fit** *Value/df* for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory (see appendix 1.1b). The **Omnibus Test** shows likelihood ratio chi-square of 14.242 with a p-value $0.002 < 0.5$ indicates that the model as a whole is statistically significant (see appendix 1.2 b). Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was rejected. Thus, implying that the models fit significantly better than the (null) models with no predictors. The **Tests of Model Effects** show that individually, the terms SPSU, TECHU, ROOU do not contribute discernible effect in the models given all p-values are greater than 0.05. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Table 5.11b: Parameter Estimate

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	-6.948	2.4504	8.039	1	0.005	0.001
SPSU	-0.003	0.2244	0	1	0.991	0.997
ROOU	0.932	0.5608	2.761	1	0.097	2.539
TECHU	0.328	0.5303	0.382	1	0.536	1.388
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), SPSU, ROOU, TECHU						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of cocoa with understanding of WTO sanitary and Phytosanitary rules (SPSU), estimated coefficient = 0.003, p value = 0.991 > 0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters
- ii. producers of cocoa with understanding of WTO Rules of Origin (ROOU), estimated coefficient = 0.932, p value = 0.097 > 0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters
- iii. producers of cocoa with understanding of WTO Technical Rules (TECHU), estimated coefficient = 0.328, p value = 0.536 > 0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

Model 2: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSA} + \beta_2 \text{TECHA} + \beta_3 \text{ROOA} + \epsilon_i$

This probit regression model investigates the likelihood of producers of Cocoa being exporters based on their application of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSA), WTO technical rules (TECHA), and WTO rules of origin (ROOA). The study assumes that application or compliance with international trade rules (SPSA, ROOA, and TECHA) might influence a producer's ability to access and compete in global markets.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

The **Goodness of Fit Value/df** for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory.

Also, the **Omnibus Test** shows likelihood ratio chi-square of 12.266 with a p-value $0.007 < 0.5$ indicates that the model as a whole is statistically significant (appendix 2.2 b). Therefore, the null hypothesis that the intercept and all coefficients are zero was rejected. Thus, implying that the models fit significantly better than the (null) models with no predictors. While **Tests of Model Effects** show that individually, the variables SPSA, TECHA, ROOA do not contribute discernible effect in the models given all p-values are greater than 0.05. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below:

Table 5.12b: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	-4.274	1.3336	10.272	1	0.001	0.014
SPSA	0.134	0.2184	0.374	1	0.541	1.143
ROOA	0.203	0.2251	0.813	1	0.367	1.225
TECHA	0.424	0.3391	1.564	1	0.211	1.528
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), SPSA, ROOA, TECHA						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of cocoa who apply WTO sanitary and Phyto sanitary rules (SPSA), estimated coefficient = 0.134, p value = $0.541 > 0.05$ (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- ii. Producers of cocoa who apply WTO Technical rules (TECHA), estimated coefficient = 0.424, p value =0.211>0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.
- iii. Producers of cocoa who apply WTO Rules of Origin (ROOA), estimated coefficient = 0.203, p value =0.367>0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

Model 3: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SON} + \beta_2 \text{NAQS} + \beta_3 \text{FMITI} + \beta_4 \text{FMARD} + \epsilon_i$

This model assesses the impact of engagement with key regulatory bodies on export status. These variables represent key institutions that regulate and facilitate trade. The theoretical significance of these variables - key institutions that regulate and facilitate trade- lies in their roles in ensuring compliance with international standards and providing support for export activities.

The **Goodness of Fit** *Value/df* for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory while the **Omnibus Test- Cocoa** the likelihood ratio chi-square of 33.682 with a p-value 0.000<0.5 indicates that the model as a whole is statistically significant (appendices 3.2b). Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was rejected. Thus, implying that the models fit significantly better than the (null) models with no predictors.

The **Tests of Model Effects** show that individually, engagement with SON contributes discernible effect in the models given p-values 0.004 less than 0.05. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below;

Table 5.13b: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	-3.812	1.205	10.006	1	0.002	0.022
FMARD	0.379	0.3514	1.161	1	0.281	1.46
FMITI	-0.015	0.3292	0.002	1	0.965	0.986
SON	-0.093	0.8596	0.012	1	0.914	0.911

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

NAQS	0.71	0.2456	8.355		1	0.004	2.034
(Scale)	1a						
Dependent Variable: Export Status							
Model: (Intercept), FMARD, FMITI, SON, NAQS							
a Fixed at the displayed value.							

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of cocoa who engage with the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and rural development (FMARD), estimated coefficient = 0.379, statistically insignificant p-value = 0.281 > 0.05 are more likely to be exporters.
- ii. Producers of cocoa who engage with the Federal Ministry of Industries, Trade and Investment (FMITI), estimated coefficient = -0.015, p value = 0.965 > 0.05 (not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- iii. Producers of cocoa who engage with the Standards Organisation of Nigeria (SON), estimated coefficient = -0.093, p value = 0.914 > 0.05 (not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- iv. Producers of cocoa who engage with the National Agricultural Quarantine Services (NAQS), estimated coefficient = 0.71, p value = 0.004 < 0.05 (statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

Model 4: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Age} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of age and output on export status. These factors are significant in understanding how the demographics and capabilities of producers influence their export status. Theoretically, more experience and education might be expected to enhance export potential.

The **Goodness of Fit** Value/df for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory. The **Omnibus Test** shows the likelihood ratio chi-square of 35.459 with a p-value 0.000 < 0.5

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

indicates that the model as a whole is statistically significant (appendices 4.2b). Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was rejected. Thus, implying that the models fit significantly better than the (null) models with no predictors. While the **Tests of Model Effects** show that individually, Output_Age contributes discernible effect in the models given all p-values 0.034 is less than 0.05. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below;

Table 5.14b: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	-5.9	3.7893	2.424	1	0.119	0.003
Education	-0.366	0.2639	1.927	1	0.165	0.693
Experience	0.948	0.6832	1.926	1	0.165	2.581
Output_Age	0.366	0.1724	4.494	1	0.034	1.441
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), Education , Experience , Output_Age						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of Cocoa with higher level of education, estimated coefficient = -0.366, p value =0.165>0.05(not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- ii. Producers of Cocoa who have more experience, estimated coefficient = 0.948, p-value =0.165>0.05(not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.
- iii. Producers of Cocoa with higher output and are older, estimated coefficient = 0.366, p-value =0.034<0.05(statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

Model 5: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{ Experience} + \beta_2 \text{ Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Ownership} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of ownership and output on export status. These factors

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

are significant in understanding how producer-related factors influence their export status.

The **Goodness of Fit** *Value/df* for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicate that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory. Furthermore, the **Omnibus Test** likelihood ratio chi-square of 38.709 with a p-value $0.000 < 0.5$ indicates that the model as a whole is statistically significant (appendices 5.2 b). Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercepts and all coefficients are zero was rejected. Thus, implying that the models fit significantly better than the (null) models with no predictors. While the **Tests of Model Effects** output ownership contributes discernible effect in the given all p-values 0.003 less than 0.05. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below:

Table 5.15b: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	-8.763	5.5301	2.511	1	0.113	0
Education	-0.197	0.3203	0.38	1	0.538	0.821
Experience	1.312	0.9682	1.837	1	0.175	3.714
Output_Ownership	1.403	0.6723	4.353	1	0.037	4.066
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), Education , Experience , Output_Ownership						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of Cocoa with higher level of education, estimated coefficient = -0.197, p value =0.538>0.05(not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- ii. Producers of Cocoa who have more experience, estimated coefficient = 1.312, p-value =0.175>0.05(not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- iii. Producers of Cocoa with higher output and more foreign ownership, estimated coefficient = 1.403, p-value = 0.037 < 0.05 (statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

Model 6: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Gender} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of Gender and output on export status. These factors are significant in understanding how producer-related factors influence their export status.

The **Goodness of Fit Value/df** for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory. While the **Omnibus Test** shows the likelihood ratio chi-square of 39.051 with a p-value 0.000 < 0.5 indicates that the model as a whole is statistically significant (appendix 6.2b). Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was rejected. Thus, implying that the models fit significantly better than the (null) models with no predictors. The **Tests of Model Effects** shows that individually, Output_Gender contributes a discernible effect in the models given p-values 0.032 less than 0.05. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below;

Table 5.16b: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	-8.865	5.4152	2.68	1	0.102	0.000
Education	-0.196	0.3161	0.386	1	0.534	0.822
Experience	1.35	0.9559	1.995	1	0.158	3.859
Output_Gender	0.701	0.3273	4.589	1	0.032	2.016
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), Education, Experience, Output_Gender						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of Cocoa with higher level of education, estimated coefficient = -0.196, p value =0.534>0.05(not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- ii. Producers of Cocoa who have more experience, estimated coefficient = 1.35, p-value =0.158>0.05(not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.
- iii. Male producers of Cocoa with higher output, estimated coefficient = 0.701, p-value =0.032<0.05(statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

5.2.6 Hypothesis Testing- Cocoa

H₀1 – There is no significant relationship between the understanding of WTO rules on agriculture and the export behaviour of agricultural commodity producers.

The model specified for testing this hypothesis is Model 1: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSU} + \beta_2 \text{TECHU} + \beta_3 \text{ROOU} + \varepsilon_i$. The outcome of the probit regression using the above model showed that all the independent variables, (understanding of sanitary and Phytosanitary rules (SPSU), estimated coefficient = 0.003, p-value =0.991>0.05;

understanding of Rules of Origin (ROOU), estimated coefficient = 0.932, p-value =0.097>0.05 and understanding of Technical Rules (TECHU), estimated coefficient = 0.328, p value =0.536>0.05) have no statistically significant relationship on export behaviour. Therefore, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis.

H₀2 – There is no relationship between the application of WTO rules on agriculture and the export behaviour of agricultural commodity producers

The model specified for testing this hypothesis is Model 2: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSA} + \beta_2 \text{TECHA} + \beta_3 \text{ROOA} + \varepsilon_i$. The outcome of the probit regression using the above model showed that all the independent variables (application of sanitary and Phytosanitary rules (SPSA), estimated coefficient = 0.134, p-value =0.541>0.05; application of Technical rules (TECHA), estimated coefficient = 0.424, p-value =0.211>0.05 and application of Rules of Origin (ROOA), estimated coefficient = 0.203, p-value =0.367>0.05) have no statistically significant impact on export behaviour. Therefore, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis.

H₀₃ – Level of engagement with national trade institutions does not affect the export behaviour of agriculture commodity producers

The model specified for testing this hypothesis is Model 3: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SON} + \beta_2 \text{NAQS} + \beta_3 \text{FMITI} + \beta_4 \text{FMARD} + \varepsilon_i$. The outcome of the probit regression using the above model showed that engage with the National Agricultural Quarantine Services (NAQS), estimated coefficient = 0.71, p value = 0.004 < 0.05, has a positive significant impact on export behaviour while all the others (engagement with the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and rural development (FMARD), estimated coefficient = 0.379, p-value = 0.281 > 0.05; engagement with the Federal Ministry of Industries, Trade and Investment (FMITI), estimated coefficient = -0.015, p-value = 0.965 > 0.05 and engagement with the Standards Organisation of Nigeria (SON), estimated coefficient = -0.093, p-value = 0.914 > 0.05) have no statistically significant impact on export behaviour. Given that, at least one independent variables in the model have a significant impact on the dependent variable, the study rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis which states that the level of engagement with national trade institutions has a significant effect on the export behaviour of Cocoa producers in Nigeria.

H₀₄ – Producer-related factors do not affect the export behaviour of agriculture commodity producers

The model specified for testing this hypothesis are;

Model 4: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Age} \times \text{Output} + \varepsilon_i$,

Model 5: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Ownership} \times \text{Output} + \varepsilon_i$ and

Model 6: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Gender} \times \text{Output} + \varepsilon_i$

First, the outcome of the probit regression using model 4 showed that output with a mediating effect of Age (Output*Age), coefficient = 0.366, p-value = 0.034 < 0.05 has a statistically significant positive impact on export behaviour. Whereas all other variables have no significant impact on export behaviour. Secondly, the outcome of the probit regression using model 5 revealed that all the independent variables have no significant impact on export behaviour except output with a mediating effect of Ownership (Output*Ownership), estimated coefficient = 1.403, p-value = 0.037 < 0.05 which has a significant positive impact on export performance. Finally, the outcome of the probit regression using model 6 suggests that output with the mediating effect of Gender (Output*Gender), estimated coefficient = 0.701, p-value = 0.032 < 0.05 has a statistically significant impact on export behaviour. Given that, at least one variable in each of the

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

models 4, 5 and 6 has a significant impact on export behaviour, the study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate hypothesis which states that producer-related factors have a significant effect on the export behaviour of Cocoa producers in Nigeria.

5.2.7 Correlation Analysis - Shea Nut

This correlation analysis aimed to find correlations between factors such understanding and application of the WTO rules, Engagement with relevant national trade institutions and producer related factors and the export status of Shea Nut producers in Nigeria. It will shed light on the relationships between variables as well as the direction and strength of these relationships. The outcome will also complement the probit regression output. The primary data collected from producers of Shea Nuts was coded appropriately and subjected to Pearson Correlation analysis. The outcome is presented in the table below;

Table 5.10c Correlation Matrix - Cocoa

Variables	Export Status	FMARD	SON	NAQS	SPSU	SPSA	TECHU	TECHA	ROOU	Age	Education	Experience	Output	Ownership	Gender
FMARD	.232*														
SON	.399**	0.137													
NAQS	.213*	.263**	0.158												
SPSU	.217*	.465**	.241*	.304**											
SPSA	0.185	.378**	.221*	.301**	.824**										
TECHU	.227*	.490**	.311**	0.183	.698**	.609**									
TECHA	.292**	.461**	.290**	0.2	.638**	.543**	.782**								
ROOU	.758**	.276**	.299**	0.181	.336**	.316**	.344**	.419**							
Age	.287**	0.095	0.054	0.083	-0.049	-0.091	-0.062	-0.007	.251*						
Education	-0.09	0.102	-0.074	.296**	0.152	0.177	0.082	.279**	-0.114	0.097					
Experience	0.087	0.082	-0.041	0.002	0.053	-0.036	-0.004	0.036	0.023	.219*	0.022				
Output	0.106	.347**	-0.01	.269**	.259*	0.189	.218*	.236*	0.126	.256*	.207*	.311**			
Ownership	.486**	.203*	.325**	0.132	.259*	0.188	.201*	.235*	.405**	.254*	-0.03	0.128	.350**		
Gender	0.066	.397**	-0.157	0.061	.246*	0.137	.253*	.296**	0.129	0.099	0.088	.307**	.364**	0.046	
ROOA	.731**	.426**	.221*	.237*	.459**	.407**	.440**	.539**	.895**	.308**	-0.052	0.146	.216*	.369**	.408**

**p < 0.01(2-tailed); * p < 0.05; N=96

Source: *Correlation Output, 2024*

The correlation table reveals that several factors are significantly associated with a producer's likelihood to export. A producer's understanding of WTO rules is significantly associated with export status. Specifically, SPSU (producer's understanding of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules) shows a correlation of .217*, TECHU (producer's understanding of WTO Technical Rules) correlates at .227*, and ROOU (producer's understanding of WTO Rules of Origin) correlates highly at .758**, indicating that comprehensive knowledge of international trade regulations is crucial for exporting.

Also, the application of WTO rules also demonstrates significant correlations with export status. TECHA (application of WTO Technical Rules) has a correlation of .292**, and SPSA (application of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules by producer) has a correlation of .185. Moreover, ROOU (application of WTO Rules of Origin by producer) shows a

THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS

strong correlation of .758**, highlighting that the practical implementation of these rules is essential for successful exporting.

Among producer-related factors, Output (.106) and Ownership (.486**) show positive correlations with export status, indicating that higher production levels and ownership structures that favor local producers enhance the likelihood of exporting. Age (.287**) and Gender (.066) have minor positive correlations, suggesting a slight influence on export status. However, Education (-.09) and Experience (.087) show weaker or non-significant relationships, implying these factors are less influential in determining export capability.

Finally, engagement with national trade institutions and agencies significantly correlates with export status. FMARD (level of engagement with the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development) has a correlation of .232*, SON (level of engagement with the Standards Organisation of Nigeria) shows a correlation of .399**, and NAQS (level of engagement with the National Agricultural Quarantine Services) correlates at .213*. This highlights the importance of institutional support and compliance with national standards in facilitating exports.

In conclusion, the result indicates that export status is primarily correlated with the producer's understanding and application of WTO rules, engagement with trade institutions, output levels, and ownership structure, while demographic factors such as age, gender, education, and experience have a more nuanced or lesser impact.

5.2.8 Probit Regression - Shea Nut

Model 1: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSU} + \beta_2 \text{TECHU} + \beta_3 \text{ROOU} + \varepsilon_i$

This probit regression model investigates the likelihood of producers of Shea Nut being exporters based on their understanding of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSU), WTO technical rules (TECHU), and WTO rules of origin (ROOU). The theoretical significance of these variables lies in the assumption that understanding and compliance with international trade rules (SPSU, ROOU, and TECHU) might influence a producer's ability to access and compete in global markets.

The **Goodness of Fit** *Value/df* for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory across. The **Omnibus Test** shows likelihood ratio chi-square of 41.689 with a p-value $0.000 < 0.5$ indicates that the model as a whole is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was rejected. Thus, implying that the models fit significantly better than the (null) models with no predictors. The **Tests of**

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Model Effects shows that individually, the terms SPSU and TECHU do not contribute discernible effect in the models given p-values greater than 0.05. However, it can be observed that ROOU Wald Chi-Square =18.615, P-value=0.000<0.05 contribute discernible effect in the models for Shea nut. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below;

Table 5.11c: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	-2.519	0.462	29.727	1	0.000	0.081
SPSU	-0.068	0.252	0.072	1	0.788	0.934
TECHU	-0.139	0.278	0.252	1	0.615	0.870
ROOU	1.141	0.265	18.615	1	0.000	3.131
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), SPSU, TECHU, ROOU						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of Shea nut with understanding of WTO sanitary and Phyto sanitary rules (SPSU), estimated coefficient = -0.068, p value =0.788>0.05(not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- ii. producers of Shea nut with understanding of WTO Rules of Origin (ROOU), estimated coefficient = 1.141, p value =0.000 <0.05 (statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.
- iii. producers of Shea nut with understanding of WTO Technical Rules (TECHU), estimated coefficient = -0.139, p-value =0.615>0.05(not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.

Model 2: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 SPSA + \beta_2 TECHA + \beta_3 ROOA + \epsilon_i$

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

This probit regression model investigates the likelihood of producers of Shea Nut being exporters based on their application of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSA), WTO technical rules (TECHA), and WTO rules of origin (ROOA). The study assumes that application or compliance with international trade rules (SPSA, ROOA, and TECHA) might influence a producer's ability to access and compete in global markets.

The **Goodness of Fit** *Value/df* for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory for Shea Nut. Also, the **Omnibus Test** shows likelihood ratio chi-square of 43.443 with a p-value $0.000 < 0.5$ indicates that the model as a whole is statistically significant for shea nut (appendix 2.2c). Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was rejected. Thus, implying that the models fit significantly better than the (null) models with no predictors. While **Tests of Model Effects** show that individually, the variables SPSA and TECHA, do not contribute discernible effect in the models given all p-values are greater than 0.05. However, it can be observed that ROOA Wald Chi-Square =9.806, P-value=0.002<0.05 contribute discernible effect in the models for Shea Nut. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below;

Table 5.12c: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	-2.262	0.434	27.186	1.000	0.000	0.104
SPSA	-0.438	0.444	0.976	1.000	0.323	0.645
TECHA	-0.344	0.337	1.043	1.000	0.307	0.709
ROOA	1.578	0.504	9.806	1	0.002	4.843
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), SPSA, TECHA, ROOA						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- i. Producers of Shea nut who apply WTO sanitary and Phytosanitary rules (SPSA), estimated coefficient = -0.438, p-value=0.323>0.05 (not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- ii. Producers of Shea nut who apply WTO Technical rules (TECHA), estimated coefficient = -0.344, p-value =0.307>0.05 (not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- iii. Producers of Shea nut who apply WTO Rules of Origin (ROOA), estimated coefficient = 1.578, p value =0.002<0.05 (statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

Model 3: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SON} + \beta_2 \text{NAQS} + \beta_3 \text{FMITI} + \beta_4 \text{FMARD} + \epsilon_i$

This model assesses the impact of engagement with key regulatory bodies on export status. These variables represent key institutions that regulate and facilitate trade. The theoretical significance of these variables - key institutions that regulate and facilitate trade- lies in their roles in ensuring compliance with international standards and providing support for export activities.

The **Goodness of Fit- Shea Nut** Value/df for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory while the **Omnibus Test** the likelihood ratio chi-square of 22.177 with a p-value 0.000<0.5 indicates that the model as a whole is statistically significant (appendices 3.2c). Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was rejected. Thus, implying that the models fit significantly better than the (null) models with no predictors. The **Tests of Model Effects** show that individually, engagement with SON contributes discernible effect in the models given p-values 0.002 less than 0.05. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below:

Table 5.13c: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	-2.734	0.5703	22.991	1	0.000	0.065
FMARD	0.139	0.161	0.747	1	0.387	1.149
FMITI	0.087	0.170	0.265	1	0.606	1.091

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

SON	1.525	0.499	9.319	1	0.002	4.594
NAQS	0.472	0.394	1.433	1	0.231	1.603
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), FMARD, FMITI, SON, NAQS						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of Shea nut who engage with the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and rural development (FMARD), estimated coefficient = 0.139, statistically insignificant p-value = 0.387 > 0.05 are more likely to be exporters.
- ii. Producers of Shea nut who engage with the Federal Ministry of Industries, Trade and Investment (FMITI), estimated coefficient = 0.087, p value = 0.60 > 0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.
- iii. Producers of Shea nut who engage with the Standards Organisation of Nigeria (SON), estimated coefficient = 1.525, p value = 0.00 < 0.05 (statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.
- iv. Producers of Shea nut who engage with the National Agricultural Quarantine Services (NAQS), estimated coefficient = 0.472, p-value = 0.231 > 0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

Model 4: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{ Experience} + \beta_2 \text{ Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Age} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of age and output on export status. These factors are significant in understanding how the demographics and capabilities of producers influence their export status. Theoretically, more experience and education might be expected to enhance export potential.

The **Goodness of Fit** *Value/df* for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory. The

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Omnibus Test- Shea Nut shows the likelihood ratio chi-square of 6.467 with a p-value $0.009 < 0.5$ indicates that the model as a whole is statistically significant (appendices 4.2c). Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was rejected. Thus, implying that the models fit significantly better than the (null) models with no predictors. While the **Tests of Model Effects** show that individually, Output_Age contributes discernible effect in the models Shea nut given p-values 0.029 less than 0.05. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below;

Table 5.14c: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	-1.421	0.4998	8.079	1	0.004	0.242
Education	-0.125	0.094	1.760	1	0.185	0.883
Experience	0.041	0.134	0.094	1	0.760	1.042
Output_Age	0.066	0.030	4.787	1	0.029	1.069
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), Education, Experience, Output_Age						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of Shea Nut with higher level of education, estimated coefficient = -0.125, p value = $0.185 > 0.05$ (not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- ii. Producers of Shea Nut who have more experience, estimated coefficient = 0.041, p-value = $0.760 > 0.05$ (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.
- iii. Producers of Shea Nut with higher output and are older, estimated coefficient = 0.066, p-value = $0.029 < 0.05$ (statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

Model 5: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{ Experience} + \beta_2 \text{ Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Ownership} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of ownership and output on export status. These factors are significant in understanding how producer-related factors influence their export status.

The **Goodness of Fit** *Value/df* for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory. The **Omnibus Test** likelihood ratio chi-square of 10.505 with a p-value $0.015 < 0.5$ indicates that the model as a whole is statistically significant (appendices 5.2c). Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was rejected. Thus, implying that the models fit significantly better than the (null) models with no predictors. While the **Tests of Model Effects** output ownership contributes discernible effect in the models given all p-values 0.004 less than 0.05. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below;

Table 5.15c: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	-1.448	0.5022	8.309	1	0.004	0.235
Education	-0.098	0.093	1.094	1	0.296	0.907
Experience	0.019	0.138	0.019	1	0.889	1.019
Output_ownership	0.165	0.056	8.821	1	0.003	1.18
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), Education , Experience , Output_ownership						
a Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of Shea Nut with higher level of education, estimated coefficient = -0.098, p value = $0.296 > 0.05$ (not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- ii. Producers of Shea Nut who have more experience, estimated coefficient = 0.019, p-value = 0.889 > 0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.
- iii. Producers of Shea Nut with higher output and more foreign ownership, estimated coefficient = 0.165, p-value = 0.003 < 0.05 (statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

Model 6: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Gender} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of Gender and output on export status. These factors are significant in understanding how producer-related factors influence their export status.

The **Goodness of Fit** *Value/df* for the Deviance and Pearson Chi-Square statistics, the value of Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the value of Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) indicates that the goodness-of-fit of the probit model was satisfactory. While the **Omnibus Test** shows the likelihood ratio chi-square of 2.568 with a p-value 0.463 > 0.5 is not statistically significant (appendix 6.2c). Therefore, the null hypothesis that intercept and all coefficients are zero was rejected. However, there can still be a legitimate significant effect within the model. The **Tests of Model Effects** shows that individually, none of the variables contribute discernible effect in the models. The Parameter Estimates is as presented below;

Table 5.16c: Parameter Estimates

Parameter Estimates						
Parameter	B	Std. Error	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
(Intercept)	-1.218	0.4655	6.843	1	0.009	0.296
Education	-0.086	0.087	0.989	1	0.320	0.917
Experience	0.064	0.131	0.234	1	0.628	1.066
Output_Gender	0.102	0.101	1.018	1	0.313	1.108
(Scale)	1a					
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Intercept), Education , Experience , Output_Gender						

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

a Fixed at the displayed value.

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. Producers of Shea with higher level of education, estimated coefficient = -0.086, p-value = 0.320 > 0.05 (not statistically significant) are less likely to be exporters.
- ii. Producers of Shea who have more experience, estimated coefficient = 0.064, p-value = 0.628 > 0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.
- iii. Male Producers of Shea with higher output, estimated coefficient = 0.102, p-value = 0.313 > 0.05 (not statistically significant) are more likely to be exporters.

5.2.9 Hypothesis Testing- Shea Nuts

H₀₁ – There is no significant relationship between understanding of WTO rules on agriculture and the export behavior of agricultural commodity producers.

The model specified for testing this hypothesis is Model 1: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSU} + \beta_2 \text{TECHU} + \beta_3 \text{ROOU} + \varepsilon_i$. The outcome of the probit regression using the above model showed that understanding of Rules of Origin (ROOU), estimated coefficient = 1.141, p value = 0.000 < 0.05 has a statistically significant impact on export behaviour. On the contrary, understanding of sanitary and Phytosanitary rules (SPSU), estimated coefficient = -0.068, p value = 0.788 > 0.05 and understanding of Technical Rules (TECHU), estimated coefficient = -0.139, p-value = 0.615 > 0.05 have no statistically significant impact on export behaviour. However, given that one independent variable in the model has a significant impact on the dependent variable, the study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between the understanding of WTO rules on agriculture and the export behaviour of agricultural commodity producers.

H₀₂ – There is no relationship between application of WTO rules on agriculture and the export behaviour of agricultural commodity producers

The model specified for testing this hypothesis is Model 2: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSA} + \beta_2 \text{TECHA} + \beta_3 \text{ROOA} + \varepsilon_i$. The outcome of the probit regression using the above model showed that application Rules of Origin (ROOA), estimated coefficient = 1.578, p value = 0.002 < 0.05

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

has a statistically significant impact on export behaviour. However, application of sanitary and Phytosanitary rules (SPSA), estimated coefficient = -0.438, p-value=0.323>0.05 and application of technical rules (TECHA), estimated coefficient = -0.344, p-value =0.307>0.05 have no statistically significant impact on export behaviour. However, given that one independent variable in the model has a significant impact on the dependent variable, the study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between application of WTO rules on agriculture and the export behaviour of agricultural commodity producers in Nigeria.

H₀₃ – Level of engagement with national trade institutions does not affect the export behaviour of agriculture commodity producers

The model specified for testing this hypothesis is Model 3: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SON} + \beta_2 \text{NAQS} + \beta_3 \text{FMITI} + \beta_4 \text{FMARD} + \epsilon_i$. The outcome of the probit regression using the above model showed that engagement with the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON), estimated coefficient = 1.525, p-value =0.00<0.05 has a statistically significant positive impact on export behaviour. In contrast, engagement with the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and rural development (FMARD), estimated coefficient = 0.139, statistically insignificant p-value =0.387>0.05, Federal Ministry of Industries, Trade, and Investment (FMITI), estimated coefficient = 0.087, p-value =0.60>0.05 and National Agricultural Quarantine Services (NAQS), estimated coefficient = 0.472, p-value =0.231>0.05 have no statistically significant impact on export behaviour. However, given that one independent variable in the model has a significant impact on the dependent variable, the study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate hypothesis which states that the level of engagement with national trade institutions has a significant impact on the export behaviour of agriculture commodity producers in Nigeria.

H₀₄ – Producer-related factors do not affect the export behaviour of agriculture commodity producers

The model specified for testing this hypothesis are;

Model 4: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Age} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$,

Model 5: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Ownership} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$ and

Model 6: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Gender} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

First, the outcome of the probit regression using model 4 showed that output with a mediating effect of Age (Output*Age), estimated coefficient = 0.066, p-value =0.029<0.05

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

has a statistically significant positive impact on export behaviour. Whereas all other variables have no significant impact on export behaviour. Secondly, the outcome of the probit regression using model 5 revealed that all the independent variables have no significant impact on export behaviour except output with a mediating effect of Ownership (Output*Ownership), estimated coefficient = 0.165, p-value =0.003<0.05 which has a significant positive impact on export performance. Finally, the outcome of the probit regression using model 6 suggests that none of the independent variables has a statistically significant impact on export behaviour. Given that, at least one variable in models 4 and 5 has a significant impact on export behaviour, the study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate hypothesis which states that producer-related factors have a significant effect on the export behaviour of Shea Nuts producers in Nigeria.

5.3 Summary of Findings

This section sought to examine the ability of the downstream players - producers of the export commodities – to identify market access barriers at the downstream level and the specific objectives are; to examine the extent to which the downstream players understand the WTO standards, evaluate the level of application of the WTO standards by the downstream players, appraise the downstream players' level of participation in commodity export and identify the factors influencing the export of agricultural commodities in Nigeria.

The insight from the descriptive analysis of the survey data indicates that the level of understanding as well as the application of the WTO standards by the downstream players is significantly low. Additionally, the descriptive analysis of the survey data revealed that the downstream players' level of participation in commodity export is very low especially among producers of cocoa and sesame. Findings from the descriptive statistics indicated that majority of cocoa and shea producers are not exporting their produce owing to limited understanding of requirements for exports. On the other hand, compared to cocoa and sesame producers, majority of shea producers are engaged in the export of their commodities. One of the reasons for this is that more shea nut producers have benefitted from government intervention programs targeted at the agricultural sector in Nigeria.

Regarding the factors influencing the export of agricultural commodities in Nigeria, the outcome of the probit regression analysis shows that the understanding and application of WTO rules on agriculture did not have a significant impact on the export behaviour of Sesame and cocoa producers in Nigeria. However, the understanding and application of

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

WTO Rules of Origin had a significant impact on the export behaviour of Shea Nuts producers in Nigeria. The outcome also demonstrated that the level of engagement with national trade institutions had a significant impact on the export behaviour of cocoa and shea nuts producers in Nigeria. Though not statistically significant, results from the application of the probit regression models indicated that agricultural commodity producers with fair understanding of SPS standards and WTO technical rules, especially producers of shea nuts, are more likely to engage in the export of their agricultural commodities. Again, the study found that producers who engage with the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD) and other relevant national trade-related institutions are more likely to engage in the export of their agricultural commodities compared to those who do not. The study also found that level of education has limited effect on the export behaviour producers of agricultural commodities in Nigeria. Finally, the outcome of probit regression analysis suggests that producer-related factors had a significant effect on the export behaviour of sesame, cocoa, and Shea Nuts producers in Nigeria.

Given the low level of understanding and application of the WTO as well as the low participation in commodity export by the downstream players (i.e. in this case, Producers) it was concluded that the downstream level has limited capacity to identify trade barriers. This is worsened by the result that indicated low engagement between majority of agricultural commodities and trade-related institutions in the country. In the absence of improved engagement between producers of agricultural commodities and relevant trade-related institutions, it will be challenging for producers to take advantage of various federal government intervention programs targeted at boosting agricultural output and export.

5.4 Robustness Check

To ensure the reliability and consistency of the findings, a robustness check was conducted using Generalized Linear Model (GLM) Logistic Regression analysis. This method was chosen due to the dichotomous nature of the dependent variable (export status) in the study.

Similarly to the the GLM Probit Regression models used earlier, the GLM Logistic Regression model was specified were specified as follows for each crop:

Model 1:

$$Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPS}U_i + \beta_2 \text{TECH}U_i + \beta_3 \text{ROOU}_i + \epsilon_i$$

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

where:

Y_i is the dependent variable for observation i

a is the intercept

$SPSU_i$ is the value of the predictor variable SPSU for observation i

β_1 is the coefficient for SPSU

$TECHU_i$ is the value of the predictor variable TECHU for observation i

β_2 is the coefficient for TECHU

$ROOU_i$ is the value of the predictor variable ROOU for observation i

β_3 is the coefficient for ROOU

ϵ_i is the error term for observation i

Model 2:

$$Y_i = a + \beta_1 SPSA_i + \beta_2 TECHA_i + \beta_3 ROOA_i + \epsilon_i$$

where:

Y_i is the dependent variable for observation i

a is the intercept

$SPSA_i$ is the value of the predictor variable SPSA for observation i

β_1 is the coefficient for SPSA

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

TECH_{Ai} is the value of the predictor variable TECHA for observation i

β_2 is the coefficient for TECHA

ROO_{Ai} is the value of the predictor variable ROOA for observation i

β_3 is the coefficient for ROOA

ϵ_i is the error term for observation i

Model 3:

$$Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SON}_i + \beta_2 \text{NAQS}_i + \beta_3 \text{FMIT}_i + \beta_4 \text{FMARD}_i + \epsilon_i$$

where:

Y_i is the dependent variable for observation i

a is the intercept

SON_i is the value of the predictor variable SON for observation i

β_1 is the coefficient for SON

NAQS_i is the value of the predictor variable NAQS for observation i

β_2 is the coefficient for NAQS

FMIT_i is the value of the predictor variable FMITI for observation i

β_3 is the coefficient for FMITI

FMARD_i is the value of the predictor variable FMARD for observation i

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

β_4 is the coefficient for FMARD

ϵ_i is the error term for observation i

Model 4:

$$Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience}_{ei} + \beta_2 \text{Education}_{ei} + \beta_3 \text{Age}_{ei} \times \text{Output}_{ei} + \epsilon_i$$

where:

Y_i is the dependent variable for observation i

a is the intercept

Experience_{ei} is the value of the predictor variable Experience for observation i

β_1 is the coefficient for Experience

Education_{ei} is the value of the predictor variable Education for observation i

β_2 is the coefficient for Education

Age_{ei} is the value of the predictor variable Age for observation i

Output_{ei} is the value of the predictor variable Output for observation i

β_3 is the coefficient for Age x Output

ϵ_i is the error term for observation i

Model 5:

$$Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience}_{ei} + \beta_2 \text{Education}_{ei} + \beta_3 \text{Ownership}_{ei} \times \text{Output}_{ei} + \epsilon_i$$

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

where:

Y_i is the dependent variable for observation i

a is the intercept

$Experience_i$ is the value of the predictor variable Experience for observation i

β_1 is the coefficient for Experience

$Education_i$ is the value of the predictor variable Education for observation i

β_2 is the coefficient for Education

$Ownership_i$ is the value of the predictor variable Ownership for observation i

$Output_i$ is the value of the predictor variable Output for observation i

β_3 is the coefficient for Ownership x Output

ϵ_i is the error term for observation i

Model 6:

$$Y_i = a + \beta_1 Experience_i + \beta_2 Education_i + \beta_3 Gender_i \times Output_i + \epsilon_i$$

where:

Y_i is the dependent variable for observation i

a is the intercept

$Experience_i$ is the value of the predictor variable Experience for observation i

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

β_1 is the coefficient for Experience

Education

Gender_i is the value of the predictor variable Gender for observation i

Output_i is the value of the predictor variable Output for observation i

β_3 is the coefficient for Gender x Output

ϵ_i is the error term for observation i

The model was estimated using maximum likelihood estimation, and the results are presented as follows;

5.4.1 Logistic Regression – Sesame

Model 1: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSU} + \beta_2 \text{TECHU} + \beta_3 \text{ROOU} + \epsilon_i$

This Logistic regression model investigates the likelihood of producers of Sesame being exporters based on their understanding of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSU), WTO technical rules (TECHU), and WTO rules of origin (ROOU).

Table 5.1d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test			Exp(B)
			Wald	Chi-Square	Sig.	
Threshold	-1.167	1.5512	.566	1	.452	.311

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

SPSU	.011	.4156	.001	1	.980	1.011
TECHU	.043	.2756	.025	1	.875	1.044
ROOU	-.036	.3290	.012	1	.913	.965
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Threshold), SPSU, TECHU, ROOU						
a. Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for SPSU is 0.011, indicating a very small positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.980$). The Exp(B) value of 1.011 suggests a negligible increase in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in understanding of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules, but this increase is not significant.
- ii. The coefficient for TECHU is 0.043, indicating a small positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.875$). The Exp(B) value of 1.044 suggests a slight increase in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in understanding of WTO technical rules, but this increase is not significant.
- iii. The coefficient for ROOU is -0.036, indicating a small negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.913$). The Exp(B) value of 0.965 suggests a slight decrease in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in understanding of WTO rules of origin, but this decrease is not significant.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

In summary, none of the variables (SPSU, TECHU, ROOU) show a statistically significant relationship with the export status of sesame producers in Nigeria based on this model. The coefficients for all variables are close to zero, and the p-values indicate a lack of significance. Therefore, we cannot conclude that a producer's understanding of WTO rules significantly influences their export status based on this analysis.

Model 2: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSA} + \beta_2 \text{TECHA} + \beta_3 \text{ROOA} + \epsilon_i$

This Logistic regression model investigates the likelihood of producers of Sesame being exporters based on their application of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSA), WTO technical rules (TECHA), and WTO rules of origin (ROOA).

Table 5.2d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test				Exp(B)
			Wald	Chi-Square	df	Sig.	
Threshold	-.954	1.6345	.341		1	.559	.385
SPSA	.195	.3794	.265		1	.607	1.216
TECHA	.458	.9772	.220		1	.639	1.581
ROOA	-.486	.9885	.242		1	.623	.615
Dependent Variable: Export Status							
Model: (Threshold), SPSA, TECHA, ROOA							
a. Fixed at the displayed value.							

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for SPSA is 0.195, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.607$). The Exp(B) value of 1.216 suggests an increase in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in the application of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules, but this increase is not significant.
- ii. The coefficient for TECHA is 0.458, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.639$). The Exp(B) value of 1.581 suggests an increase in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in the application of WTO technical rules, but this increase is not significant.
- iii. The coefficient for ROOA is -0.486, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.623$). The Exp(B) value of 0.615 suggests a decrease in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in the application of WTO rules of origin, but this decrease is not significant.

In summary, none of the variables (SPSA, TECHA, ROOA) show a statistically significant relationship with the export status of sesame producers in Nigeria. The coefficients for all variables suggest modest impacts, but the p-values indicate a lack of significance. Therefore, it cannot be concluded that the application of WTO rules (sanitary and phytosanitary, technical, and rules of origin) significantly influences the export status of producers based on this analysis.

Model 3: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SON} + \beta_2 \text{NAQS} + \beta_3 \text{FMITI} + \beta_4 \text{FMARD} + \epsilon_i$

This model assesses the impact of engagement with key regulatory bodies on export status. These variables represent key institutions that regulate and facilitate trade.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Table 5.3d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test			
			Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Threshold	-2.394	2.4312	.970	1	.325	.091
FMA	-.292	.9409	.096	1	.756	.747
FMI	-.268	.6164	.189	1	.663	.765
SON	.860	1.2269	.492	1	.483	2.364
NQA	.406	.5629	.520	1	.471	1.501
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Threshold), FMA, FMI, SON, NQA						
a. Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for FMI is -0.268, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.663$). The Exp(B) value of 0.765 suggests a decrease in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in engagement with the Federal Ministry of Industries, Trade and Investment, but this decrease is not significant.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- ii. The coefficient for SON is 0.860, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.483$). The Exp(B) value of 2.364 suggests an increase in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in engagement with the Standards Organization of Nigeria, but this increase is not significant.
- iii. The coefficient for NQA is 0.406, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.471$). The Exp(B) value of 1.501 suggests an increase in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in engagement with the National Agricultural Quarantine Services, but this increase is not significant.

In summary, none of the variables (FMA, FMI, SON, NQA) show a statistically significant relationship with the export status of sesame producers in Nigeria. The coefficients suggest varying impacts (positive or negative), but none are statistically significant, indicating that these engagements with governmental bodies do not significantly predict the export status of producers based on this analysis.

Model 4: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Age} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of age and output on export status.

Table 5.4d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test			Exp(B)	
			Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.		
Threshold	-3.904	2.6898	2.107	1	.147		.020
Education	-.183	.1876	.951	1	.330		.833

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Experience	-0.881	1.2479	.498	1	.480	.414
Output_Age	-0.113	.1734	.421	1	.516	.894
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Threshold), Education, Experience, Output_Age						
a. Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for Education is -0.183, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.330$). The Exp(B) value of 0.833 suggests a decrease in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in the level of education, but this decrease is not significant.
- ii. The coefficient for Experience is -0.881, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.480$). The Exp(B) value of 0.414 suggests a decrease in the odds of exporting for each additional year of farming experience, but this decrease is not significant.
- iii. The coefficient for Output_Age is -0.113, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.516$). The Exp(B) value of 0.894 suggests a decrease in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in the output relative to the age of the producer, but this decrease is not significant.

In summary, none of the variables (Education, Experience, Output_Age) show a statistically significant relationship with the export status of sesame producers in Nigeria. The coefficients suggest varying impacts (mostly negative), but none are statistically

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

significant, indicating that these individual characteristics do not significantly predict the export status of producers based on this analysis.

Model 5: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{ Experience} + \beta_2 \text{ Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Ownership} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of ownership and output on export status.

Table 5.5d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test			Exp(B)	
			Wald	Chi-Square	df	Sig.	
Threshold	-4.548	3.6486	1.554	1	.213	.011	
Education	-.172	.1864	.847	1	.357	.842	
Experience	-1.002	1.2506	.642	1	.423	.367	
Output_Ownership	-.330	.6672	.245	1	.621	.719	
Dependent Variable: Export Status							
Model: (Threshold), Education, Experience, utput_Ownership							
a. Fixed at the displayed value.							

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- i. The coefficient for Education is -0.172, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.357$). The Exp(B) value of 0.842 suggests a decrease in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in the level of education, but this decrease is not significant.
- ii. The coefficient for Experience is -1.002, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.423$). The Exp(B) value of 0.367 suggests a decrease in the odds of exporting for each additional year of farming experience, but this decrease is not significant.
- iii. The coefficient for Output_Ownership is -0.330, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.621$). The Exp(B) value of 0.719 suggests a decrease in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in output relative to the ownership of the farm, but this decrease is not significant.

In summary, none of the variables (Education, Experience, Output_Ownership) show a statistically significant relationship with the export status of sesame producers in Nigeria. The coefficients suggest varying impacts (mostly negative), but none are statistically significant, indicating that these individual characteristics do not significantly predict the export status of producers based on this analysis.

Model 6: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Gender} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of Gender and output on export status.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Table 5.6d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test			Exp(B)	
			Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.		
Threshold	-4.969	2.7864	3.180	1	.075	.007	
Education	-.190	.1851	1.050	1	.306	.827	
Experience	-.688	1.2241	.316	1	.574	.503	
Output_Gender	-.359	.2624	1.876	1	.171	.698	
Dependent Variable: Export Status							
Model: (Threshold), Education , Experience , Output_Gender							
a. Fixed at the displayed value.							

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for Education is -0.190, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.306$). The Exp(B) value of 0.827 suggests a decrease in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in the level of education, but this decrease is not significant.
- ii. The coefficient for Experience is -0.688, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.574$). The

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Exp(B) value of 0.503 suggests a decrease in the odds of exporting for each additional year of farming experience, but this decrease is not significant.

- iii. The coefficient for Output_Gender is -0.359, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.171$). The Exp(B) value of 0.698 suggests a decrease in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in output relative to the gender of the producer, but this decrease is not significant.

In summary, none of the variables (Education, Experience, Output_Gender) show a statistically significant relationship with the export status of sesame producers in Nigeria. The coefficients suggest varying impacts (mostly negative), but none are statistically significant, indicating that these individual characteristics do not significantly predict the export status of producers based on this analysis.

5.4.2 Logistic Regression - Cocoa

Model 1: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSU} + \beta_2 \text{TECHU} + \beta_3 \text{ROOU} + \epsilon_i$

This logistic regression model investigates the likelihood of producers of Cocoa being exporters based on their understanding of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSU), WTO technical rules (TECHU), and WTO rules of origin (ROOU).

Table 5.7d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test		Sig.	Exp(B)
			Wald	Chi-Square		
Threshold	13.987	5.4951	6.479	1	.011	10.298
SPSU	.096	.4057	.056	1	.813	1.100

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

TECHU	.626	1.0697	.342	1	.558	1.870
ROOU	1.879	1.1823	2.526	1	.112	6.548
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Threshold), SPSU, TECHU, ROOU						
a. Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for SPSU is 0.096, indicating a positive but negligible relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.813$). The Exp(B) value of 1.100 suggests a slight increase in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in understanding of WTO sanitary and Phytosanitary rules, but this increase is not significant
- ii. The coefficient for TECHU is 0.626, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.558$). The Exp(B) value of 1.870 suggests an increase in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in understanding of WTO Technical Rules, but this increase is not significant.
- iii. The coefficient for ROOU is 1.879, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.112$). The Exp(B) value of 6.548 suggests a considerable increase in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in understanding of WTO Rules of Origin, but this increase is not significant.

In summary, the threshold parameter shows a significant and substantial baseline tendency for cocoa producers to export. However, none of the specific variables related

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

to the understanding of WTO rules (SPSU, TECHU, ROOU) show a statistically significant relationship with the export status of cocoa producers in Nigeria. The coefficients suggest varying positive impacts, but none reach statistical significance, indicating that these factors do not significantly predict the export status of producers based on this analysis.

Model 2: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSA} + \beta_2 \text{TECHA} + \beta_3 \text{ROOA} + \epsilon_i$

This probit regression model investigates the likelihood of producers of Cocoa being exporters based on their application of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSA), WTO technical rules (TECHA), and WTO rules of origin (ROOA).

Table 5.8d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test				Exp(B)
			Wald	Chi-Square	df	Sig.	
Threshold	8.359	2.7260	9.403	1	.002	27.378	
SPSA	.301	.4254	.500	1	.480	1.351	
TECHA	.809	.6677	1.468	1	.226	2.245	
ROOA	.433	.4557	.904	1	.342	1.542	
Dependent Variable: Export Status							
Model: (Threshold), SPSA, TECHA, ROOA							
a. Fixed at the displayed value.							

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for SPSA is 0.301, indicating a positive but negligible relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.480$). The $\text{Exp}(B)$ value of 1.351 suggests a slight increase in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in the application of WTO sanitary and Phytosanitary rules, but this increase is not significant.
- ii. The coefficient for TECHA is 0.809, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.226$). The $\text{Exp}(B)$ value of 2.245 suggests an increase in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in the application of WTO Technical Rules, but this increase is not significant.
- iii. The coefficient for ROOA is 0.433, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.342$). The $\text{Exp}(B)$ value of 1.542 suggests an increase in the odds of exporting for each unit increase in the application of WTO Rules of Origin, but this increase is not significant.

In summary, the threshold parameter shows a significant and substantial baseline tendency for cocoa producers to export. However, none of the specific variables related to the application of WTO rules (SPSA, TECHA, ROOA) show a statistically significant relationship with the export status of cocoa producers in Nigeria. The coefficients suggest varying positive impacts, but none reach statistical significance, indicating that these factors do not significantly predict the export status of producers based on this analysis.

Model 3: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SON} + \beta_2 \text{NAQS} + \beta_3 \text{FMITI} + \beta_4 \text{FMARD} + \epsilon_i$

This model assesses the impact of engagement with key regulatory bodies on export status.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Table 5.9d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test			Exp(B)
			Wald	Chi-Square	df Sig.	
Threshold	7.707	3.0094	6.558	1	.010	23.681
FMARD	.704	.8008	.773	1	.379	2.022
FMITI	.004	.7729	.000	1	.996	1.004
SON	.027	2.0126	.000	1	.989	1.027
NAQS	1.423	.5974	5.674	1	.017	4.150
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Threshold), FMARD, FMITI, SON, NAQS						
a. Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for FMARD is 0.704, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.379$). The Exp(B) value of 2.022 suggests that higher engagement with FMARD more than doubles the odds of exporting, but this increase is not significant.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- ii. The coefficient for FMITI is 0.004, indicating a negligible relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant (p = 0.996). The Exp(B) value of 1.004 suggests no meaningful impact on the odds of exporting based on engagement with FMITI.
- iii. The coefficient for SON is 0.027, indicating a negligible relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant (p = 0.989). The Exp(B) value of 1.027 suggests no meaningful impact on the odds of exporting based on engagement with SON.
- iv. The coefficient for NAQS is 1.423, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is statistically significant (p = 0.017). The Exp(B) value of 4.150 suggests that higher engagement with NAQS significantly increases the odds of exporting by over four times, highlighting its importance as a factor influencing export status.

In summary, the threshold parameter shows a significant and substantial baseline tendency for cocoa producers to export. Among the specific variables related to engagement with federal agencies, only engagement with the National Agricultural Quarantine Services (NAQS) shows a statistically significant positive relationship with the export status of cocoa producers in Nigeria. Engagement with the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD), the Federal Ministry of Industries, Trade and Investment (FMITI), and the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON) does not show significant relationships with export status.

Model 4: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{ Experience} + \beta_2 \text{ Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Age} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of age and output on export status.

Table 5.10d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test	Exp(B)
-----------	---	------------	-----------------	--------

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

			Wald Chi-Square		df	Sig.	
Threshold	10.676	6.8338	2.441	1	.118	43.339	
Education	-.700	.4560	2.354	1	.125	.497	
Experience	1.722	1.2401	1.928	1	.165	5.596	
Output_Age	.667	.3109	4.609	1	.032	1.949	
Dependent Variable: Export Status							
Model: (Threshold), Education, Experience, Output_Age							
a. Fixed at the displayed value.							

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for education is -0.700, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.125$). The Exp(B) value of 0.497 suggests that higher levels of education reduce the odds of exporting by approximately 50%, but this decrease is not statistically significant.
- ii. The coefficient for experience is 1.722, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.165$). The Exp(B) value of 5.596 suggests that more experience significantly increases the odds of exporting by more than five times, but this increase is not statistically significant.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- iii. The coefficient for output related to age is 0.667, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is statistically significant ($p = 0.032$). The Exp(B) value of 1.949 suggests that higher output associated with older age significantly increases the odds of exporting by nearly twice, highlighting the importance of this factor.

In summary, the threshold parameter shows a strong baseline tendency for cocoa producers to export, although it is not statistically significant. Among the specific variables analyzed, only output related to age (Output_Age) shows a statistically significant positive relationship with the export status of cocoa producers in Nigeria. Education and experience do not show significant relationships, although they exhibit varying impacts.

Model 5: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{ Experience} + \beta_2 \text{ Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Ownership} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of ownership and output on export status.

Table 5.11d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test			Exp(B)	
			Wald	Chi-Square	df	Sig.	
Threshold	15.809	9.6159	2.703	1	.100	34.997	
Education	-.454	.5741	.625	1	.429	0.635	
Experience	2.404	1.7121	1.972	1	.160	11.068	
Output_Ownership	2.564	1.2267	4.370	1	.037	12.991	

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Dependent Variable: Export Status

Model: (Threshold), Education, Experience, Output_Ownership

a. Fixed at the displayed value.

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for education is -0.454, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.429$). The Exp(B) value of 0.635 suggests that higher levels of education reduce the odds of exporting by approximately 36.5%, but this decrease is not statistically significant.
- ii. The coefficient for experience is 2.404, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.160$). The Exp(B) value of 11.068 suggests that more experience significantly increases the odds of exporting by more than eleven times, but this increase is not statistically significant.
- iii. The coefficient for output related to ownership is 2.564, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is statistically significant ($p = 0.037$). The Exp(B) value of 12.991 suggests that higher output associated with ownership significantly increases the odds of exporting by nearly thirteen times, highlighting the importance of this factor.

In summary, the threshold parameter shows a strong baseline tendency for cocoa producers to export, although it is not statistically significant. Among the specific variables analyzed, only output related to ownership (Output_Ownership) shows a statistically significant positive relationship with the export status of cocoa producers in Nigeria. Education and experience do not show significant relationships, although they exhibit varying impacts.

Model 6: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Gender} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of Gender and output on export status.

Table 5.12d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test			Exp(B)
			Wald	Chi-Square	Sig.	
Threshold	15.835	9.3531	2.866	1	.090	7533190.068
Education	-.443	.5609	.623	1	.430	.642
Experience	2.437	1.6699	2.129	1	.145	11.436
Output_Gender	1.272	.5937	4.589	1	.032	3.568
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Threshold), Education , Experience , Output_Gender						
a. Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for education is -0.443, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is not statistically significant (p = 0.430). The Exp(B) value of 0.642 suggests that higher levels of education reduce the odds of exporting by approximately 35.8%, but this decrease is not statistically significant.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- ii. The coefficient for experience is 2.437, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. However, this result is not statistically significant (p = 0.145). The Exp(B) value of 11.436 suggests that more experience significantly increases the odds of exporting by more than eleven times, but this increase is not statistically significant.
- iii. The coefficient for output related to gender is 1.272, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting. This result is statistically significant (p = 0.032). The Exp(B) value of 3.568 suggests that higher output associated with gender significantly increases the odds of exporting by more than three times, highlighting the importance of this factor.

In summary, the threshold parameter shows a strong baseline tendency for cocoa producers to export, although it is not statistically significant. Among the specific variables analyzed, only output related to gender (Output_Gender) shows a statistically significant positive relationship with the export status of cocoa producers in Nigeria. Education and experience do not show significant relationships, although they exhibit varying impacts.

5.4.3 Logistic Regression - Shea Nut

Model 1: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSU} + \beta_2 \text{TECHU} + \beta_3 \text{ROOU} + \epsilon_i$

This logistic regression model investigates the likelihood of producers of Shea Nut being exporters based on their understanding of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSU), WTO technical rules (TECHU), and WTO rules of origin (ROOU).

Table 5.13d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test			Exp(B)
			Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	
Threshold	4.637	.9937	21.774	1	.000	13.233

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

SPSU	-0.052	.4591	.013	1	.909	.949
TECHU	-.234	.5320	.194	1	.659	.791
ROOU	1.994	.5020	15.786	1	.000	7.348
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Threshold), SPSU, TECHU, ROOU						
a. Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for SPSU is -0.052, indicating a slightly negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting, but this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.909$). The Exp(B) value of 0.949 suggests that a higher understanding of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules slightly reduces the odds of exporting by about 5.1%, but this effect is not statistically significant.
- ii. The coefficient for TECHU is -0.234, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting, but this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.659$). The Exp(B) value of 0.791 suggests that a higher understanding of WTO technical rules reduces the odds of exporting by approximately 20.9%, but this decrease is not statistically significant.
- iii. The coefficient for ROOU is 1.994, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting, and this result is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The Exp(B) value of 7.348 suggests that a higher understanding of WTO rules of origin significantly increases the odds of exporting by more than seven times, highlighting the importance of this factor.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

In summary, Understanding of WTO rules of origin (ROOU) is a significant positive predictor of export status. However, Understanding of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSU) and WTO technical rules (TECHU) do not show significant relationships with export status.

Model 2: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SPSA} + \beta_2 \text{TECHA} + \beta_3 \text{ROOA} + \epsilon_i$

This logistic regression model investigates the likelihood of producers of Shea Nut being exporters based on their application of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSA), WTO technical rules (TECHA), and WTO rules of origin (ROOA).

Table 5.14d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test			
			Wald	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Threshold	4.031	.8941	20.326	1	.000	56.307
SPSA	-.797	.7996	.994	1	.319	.451
TECHA	-.572	.5868	.950	1	.330	.565
ROOA	2.770	.9006	9.461	1	.002	15.959

Dependent Variable: Export Status

Model: (Threshold), SPSA, TECHA, ROOA

a. Fixed at the displayed value.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for SPSA is -0.797, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting, but this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.319$). The Exp(B) value of 0.451 suggests that the application of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules reduces the odds of exporting by approximately 54.9%, although this effect is not statistically significant
- ii. The coefficient for TECHA is -0.572, indicating a negative relationship with the likelihood of exporting, but this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.330$). The Exp(B) value of 0.565 suggests that the application of WTO technical rules reduces the odds of exporting by approximately 43.5%, although this decrease is not statistically significant.
- iii. The coefficient for ROOA is 2.770, indicating a positive relationship with the likelihood of exporting, and this result is statistically significant ($p = 0.002$). The Exp(B) value of 15.959 suggests that the application of WTO rules of origin significantly increases the odds of exporting by nearly 16 times, highlighting the crucial role of this factor.

In summary, the threshold parameter shows a strong baseline tendency for Shea Nuts producers to export. Among the specific variables analyzed Application of WTO rules of origin (ROOA) is a significant positive predictor of export status while Application of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules (SPSA) and WTO technical rules (TECHA) do not show significant relationships with export status.

Model 3: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{SON} + \beta_2 \text{NAQS} + \beta_3 \text{FMITI} + \beta_4 \text{FMARD} + \epsilon_i$

This model assesses the impact of engagement with key regulatory bodies on export status.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Table 5.15d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test			Exp(B)
			Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	
Threshold	4.963	1.1801	17.683	1	.000	142.971
FMARD	.240	.2714	.784	1	.376	1.272
FMTI	.158	.2861	.305	1	.581	1.171
SON	2.916	1.0822	7.262	1	.007	18.474
NAQS	.730	.6854	1.134	1	.287	2.075
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Threshold), FMARD, FMTI, SON, NAQS						
a. Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. FMARD (level of engagement with the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development) has a coefficient of 0.240, which is not statistically significant at the 5% level ($p = 0.376$). This suggests that FMARD engagement does not significantly influence the odds of exporting Shea Nuts producers in Nigeria.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- ii. FMTI (level of engagement with the Federal Ministry of Industries, Trade and Investment) has a coefficient of 0.158, with a p-value of 0.581, indicating no significant influence on export status.
- iii. SON (level of engagement with the Standards Organization of Nigeria) has a coefficient of 2.916, which is statistically significant ($p = 0.007$). The odds ratio (Exp(B)) of 18.474 indicates that producers who have higher engagement with SON are 18.474 times more likely to export Shea Nuts compared to those with lower engagement, holding other variables constant.
- iv. NAQS (level of engagement with the National Agricultural Quarantine Services) has a coefficient of 0.730, with a p-value of 0.287, indicating no significant effect on export status.

In summary, Engagement with SON significantly influences the export status of Shea Nuts producers in Nigeria, with higher engagement increasing the likelihood of exporting while Engagement with FMARD, FMTI, and NAQS does not show statistically significant effects on export status based on the given model.

Model 4: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{ Experience} + \beta_2 \text{ Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Age} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of age and output on export status.

Table 5.16d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test			Exp(B)
			Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	
Threshold	2.421	.9130	7.034	1	.008	11.262

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Education	-0.224	0.1755	1.625	1	0.202	0.800
Experience	0.068	0.2441	0.077	1	0.782	1.070
Output_Age	0.117	0.0537	4.771	1	0.029	1.124
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Threshold), Education , Experience , Output_Age						
a. Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for Education is -0.224, indicating a negative relationship with export status, though not statistically significant ($p = 0.202$). The odds ratio (Exp(B)) of 0.800 suggests that each unit increase in education level decreases the odds of exporting Shea Nuts producers by a factor of 0.800, but this effect is not significant at the 5% level.
- ii. Experience has a coefficient of 0.068, with a p-value of 0.782, indicating no significant relationship with export status. The odds ratio (Exp(B)) of 1.070 suggests that each additional year of farming experience slightly increases the odds of exporting Shea Nuts producers, but this effect is not statistically significant.
- iii. Output_Age (interaction term between Output and Age) has a coefficient of 0.117, which is statistically significant ($p = 0.029$). The odds ratio (Exp(B)) of 1.124 suggests that for each unit increase in the interaction between Output and Age, the odds of exporting Shea Nuts producers increase by a factor of 1.124, holding other variables constant.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

In summary, Education level and farming experience do not significantly influence the export status of Shea Nuts producers. However, the interaction between Output and Age shows a statistically significant positive effect on export status, indicating that older producers with higher output are more likely to export.

Model 5: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Ownership} \times \text{Output} +$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of ownership and output on export status.

Table 5.17d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test			
			Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Threshold	2.401	.9042	7.050	1	.008	11.033
Education	-.184	.1752	1.107	1	.293	.832
Experience	.029	.2521	.014	1	.907	1.030
Output_ownership	.281	.0977	8.237	1	.004	1.324
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Threshold), Education , Experience , Output_ownership						
a. Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for Education is -0.184, indicating a negative relationship with export status, but it is not statistically significant ($p = 0.293$). The odds ratio (Exp(B)) of 0.832 suggests that each unit increase in education level decreases the odds of exporting Shea Nuts producers by a factor of 0.832, though this effect is not significant at the 5% level.
- ii. Experience has a coefficient of 0.029, with a p-value of 0.907, indicating no significant relationship with export status. The odds ratio (Exp(B)) of 1.030 suggests that each additional year of farming experience slightly increases the odds of exporting Shea Nuts producers, but this effect is not statistically significant.
- iii. Output_ownership (interaction term between Output and Ownership) has a coefficient of 0.281, which is statistically significant ($p = 0.004$). The odds ratio (Exp(B)) of 1.324 suggests that for each unit increase in the interaction between Output and Ownership, the odds of exporting Shea Nuts producers increase by a factor of 1.324, holding other variables constant.

In summary, Education level and farming experience do not significantly influence the export status of Shea Nuts producers. However, the interaction between Output and Ownership shows a statistically significant positive effect on export status, indicating that producers with higher output and who own their farms (or majority-owned by Nigerians) are more likely to export.

Model 6: $Y_i = a + \beta_1 \text{Experience} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 + \text{Gender} \times \text{Output} + \epsilon_i$

This model explores the impact of producer-related factors including experience, education, and the interaction of Gender and output on export status.

Table 5.18d: Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	Hypothesis Test	Exp(B)
-----------	---	------------	-----------------	--------

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

			Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	
Threshold	2.050	.8295	6.107	1	.013	7.767
Education	-.168	.1624	1.073	1	.300	.845
Experience	.113	.2384	.224	1	.636	1.119
Output_Gender	.190	.1803	1.111	1	.292	1.209
Dependent Variable: Export Status						
Model: (Threshold), Education , Experience , Output_Gender						
a. Fixed at the displayed value.						

Source: Author, 2023

The Parameter Estimates above reveal the following;

- i. The coefficient for Education is -0.168, indicating a negative relationship with export status, but it is not statistically significant ($p = 0.300$). The odds ratio (Exp(B)) of 0.845 suggests that each unit increase in education level decreases the odds of exporting Shea Nuts producers by a factor of 0.845, though this effect is not significant at the 5% level.
- ii. Experience has a coefficient of 0.113, with a p-value of 0.636, indicating no significant relationship with export status. The odds ratio (Exp(B)) of 1.119 suggests that each additional year of farming experience slightly increases the odds of exporting Shea Nuts producers, but this effect is not statistically significant.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- iii. Output_Gender (interaction term between Output and Gender) has a coefficient of 0.190, with a p-value of 0.292, indicating no significant relationship with export status. The odds ratio (Exp(B)) of 1.209 suggests that the interaction between Output and Gender does not significantly influence the odds of exporting Shea Nuts producers.

In summary, Education level, farming experience, and the interaction between Output and Gender do not significantly influence the export status of Shea Nuts producers. These findings suggest that while education, experience, and gender-specific output interactions may play a role in export status, they are not statistically significant in this model.

5.4.1 Results Comparison

This analysis aims to investigate the factors influencing the export status of producers of three key crops in Nigeria: Sesame, Cocoa, and Shea Nuts. Six Models (equations) were specified, GLM probit regression was employed to test the hypothesis, while GLM Logistic regression was used for robustness checks. The models were estimated using maximum likelihood estimation. The robustness checks using GLM Logistic regression consistently confirmed the findings from the GLM Probit regression across all three crops.

For Sesame, across all models, the probit and logistic regressions consistently confirm the direction of the relationships between the independent variables and export status. Although none of the variables show statistically significant effects, the robustness checks using logistic regression provide additional support for the hypothesized relationships, reinforcing the conclusions drawn from the probit regression analyses. These findings suggest that the understanding and application of WTO rules, engagement with regulatory bodies, and producer-related factors do not significantly influence the export status of sesame producers in Nigeria, highlighting the need for further investigation into other potential determinants.

Similarly, for Cocoa, the robustness checks using GLM logistic regression confirm the direction and significance of the relationships between the independent variables and export status observed in the probit regression. In most cases, the coefficients' signs are consistent between both methods, reinforcing the trends identified. Specifically, significant factors such as engagement with NAQS, the interaction between age and output, ownership and output, and gender and output were consistently identified across

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

both regression techniques, thereby providing additional support for the hypotheses tested. This consistency enhances the reliability of the findings and their implications for the export status of Cocoa producers in Nigeria.

Finally, in the case of Shea Nuts, the results from the logistic regression across all six models generally align with those of the probit regression, providing robust support for the findings. The key determinants of export status among Shea Nuts producers in Nigeria are their understanding and application of WTO Rules of Origin, engagement with the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON), and specific producer-related factors such as the interaction between age and output, and the interaction between ownership and output. Other factors such as understanding and application of WTO sanitary and phytosanitary rules, technical rules, engagement with other regulatory bodies, education, experience, and the interaction between gender and output do not show significant influence on export status.

Overall, the robustness checks confirmed that across all three crops, the understanding and application of WTO Rules of Origin (ROOU and ROOA) are significant and positive predictors of export status for producers of Sesame, Cocoa, and Shea Nuts. This highlights the critical role of adherence to international trade standards and regulations in enabling producers to access export markets. Additionally, consistent engagement with the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON) is a significant determinant of export status across all three crops. This underscores the importance of regulatory compliance and certification in enhancing export potential.

Finally, producer-related factors also play a role in influencing export status. The interaction between age and output is a significant predictor, suggesting that older producers with higher output are more likely to engage in export activities. This may be due to their accumulated experience and greater production capacity. Similarly, the interaction between ownership (especially foreign ownership) and output positively influences export status, indicating that foreign investment and larger-scale production are crucial for export success. Conversely, education and experience do not show a significant impact on export status, suggesting that other variables such as regulatory engagement and adherence to international standards are more critical determinants.

In conclusion, the findings of this study highlight the multifaceted nature of factors influencing the export status of Sesame, Cocoa, and Shea Nuts producers in Nigeria. The consistent results across probit and logistic regression models underscore the importance of international trade standards and regulatory compliance in enhancing export potential.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

The significant role of producer-related factors, particularly the interactions between age and output, and ownership and output, suggests that demographic and investment-related elements are crucial for export success. However, the lack of significance in education and experience calls for further research to identify other potential determinants. Overall, these insights provide valuable guidance for policymakers and stakeholders aiming to boost the export performance of agricultural producers in Nigeria, emphasising the need for targeted support in areas such as regulatory compliance, international standards, and investment facilitation.

CHAPTER SIX

ANALYSIS OF FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION WITH NIGERIA'S TRADE INSTITUTIONS

6.0 Introduction

This chapter focused on investigating the ability of midstream actors to investigate trade measures which constitute export market access barriers identified by the downstream agents. Therefore, the specific objectives are; to establish the role of the midstream level in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria's export commodities, appraise the mechanisms put in place to enable it to perform its role, examine how well it is performing the role, identify the challenges facing it in performing the role and determine whether there are cases of trade agreement violations known to the trade institutions since the establishment of the WTO Dispute Settlement Understanding. Accordingly, the chapter presents the thematic analysis results from the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which constitute the midstream level in the Nigerian trade environment. The chapter is organized into three sections. The first section presents the Sample Composition of the Focus Group Participants while the second section presents thematic findings based on each research question. Finally, section three presents a Summary of the thematic analysis of the Focus Group Discussion.

6.1 Sample Composition of the Focus Group Participants

The sample for the focus group discussion consisted of 12 participants drawn from the various institutions which constitute the midstream level of Nigeria's trade architecture. Three representatives each, from relevant departments, were drawn the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD) and the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment (FMITI) while 2 representatives each were chosen to represent the Nigerian Agricultural Quarantine Services (NAQS) and the Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC). Others include 1 representative of the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON) and 1 representative of the National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC). The sample composition is shown in Table 6.1 below:

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Table 6.1 Sample Composition

Age (Years)	Frequency	Percentage
30-40	2	17%
41-50	6	50%
50-60	4	33%
Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	7	58%
Female	5	42%
Institution	Frequency	Percentage
FMARD	3	25%
FMITI	3	25%
NAQS	2	17%
NEPC	2	17%
SON	1	8%
NAFDAC	1	8%
Years in Service	Frequency	Percentage
6-10 Years	2	17%
11-15 years	3	25%
16-20 years	4	33%
>20 Years	3	25%

Source: Author, 2023

6.2 Thematic Findings

The focus group discussions began with a personal introduction, an explanation of the research objectives, an explanation of the focus group process, a confidentiality undertaking by the researcher, and the signing of the consent form by the participants. The entire discussion was recorded and focus group notes were taken by the researcher

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA’S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

during the focus group discussion. The format of the focus groups was a semi-structured conversation following the themes outlined in the discussion guidelines (Appendix A). The focus group session was very vibrant and characterized by a robust discussion on the issues raised in accordance with each objective of the study. The focus group session was transcribed (see Appendix B). The data derived from the focus group discussion were coded using the coding process described in the preceding chapter (refer to the methodology chapter). The contents were then analyzed and used to answer the research questions corresponding to the stated objectives as follows:

6.2.1 Research Question 1

The first research question, which is the primary focus for this subsection of the results chapter is specified as follows:

RQ1: What is the role of the midstream level in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria’s export commodities?

The thematic findings in Table 6.2 present a summary of the focus group participants’ perceptions with respect to the role of the midstream level in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria’s export commodities. The thematic codes are presented alongside a few of the responses from the focus group discussion.

Table 6.2: Participants’ Perceptions of the Role of the Midstream Level

Discussion Question	Response	Code
Midstream role	Informing downstream about international rules	¹ INFORMATION
	Ensuring compliance with international rules	² COMPLIANCE
	Investigating violations	³ INVESTIGATION
	Communicating findings to upstream	⁴ COMMUNICATION

The insight from the thematic analysis of the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which form the midstream level in the Nigerian trade environment, concerning the role of the midstream in reducing market access

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

barrier, indicates that the major role of the midstream is to act as a link between the downstream and the upstream. In this respect, all the participants observed that the midstream plays four major roles viz; Informing the downstream about international rules, ensuring compliance with international rules, investigating violations and communicating the findings to the upstream actors for necessary actions. For instance, one of the participants observed, "...The midstream level which comprises the aforementioned trade institutions are there to ensure that producers and exporters (downstream level) are adequately informed about relevant international rules and standards regarding every export commodity and apply them to the fullest before exporting same to a foreign market. Also, where there is a perceived violation, it is the duty of the midstream, after receiving reports from the exporters, to investigate such reports and pass on the findings to the upstream level for necessary actions where the case is confirmed to be a violation or to the exporter where the rejection is found to be due to a lack of adequate compliance with relevant standards." (P003).

The above finding indicates that the midstream level plays a critical role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria's export commodities. Consequently, the failure of the midstream to play its role effectively could limit the ability of a country to engage the WTO dispute settlement understanding. This finding agrees with those of Bahri, (2018) who maintained that domestic institutions are necessary for a country to participate in international negotiations and Akinkugbe, (2021) who stated that the lack of effective trade policy infrastructure could limit the ability of a country to engage the WTO dispute settlement understanding.

6.2.2 Research Question 2

The second research question, which is the primary focus for this subsection of the results chapter is specified as follows:

RQ1: How well is the Midstream level poised to perform its role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria's export commodities?

The thematic findings in Table 6.3 present a summary of the focus group participants' perceptions with respect to how well is the Midstream level poised to perform its role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria's export commodities. The thematic codes are presented alongside a few of the responses from the focus group discussion.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Table 6.3: Participants 'Perceptions of the Midstream's Readiness to perform its Role

Discussion Question	Response	Code
Information Mechanism	there is a comprehensive information mechanism in place	¹ INFORMATION
Compliance Mechanism	there is a comprehensive compliance mechanism in place	¹ COMPLIANCE
Reporting and Investigation Mechanism	there is a formal mechanism for reporting cases of rejections and there are properly defined investigating procedure/Mechanism in the relevant agencies.	¹ REPORTING ² INVESTIGATION
Communication Mechanism	there is a comprehensive communication mechanism in place	¹ COMMUNICATION

First, the insight from the thematic analysis of the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which form the midstream level in the Nigerian trade environment, concerning the role of the midstream in reducing market access barrier, indicates that there is a comprehensive information dissemination mechanism in place. In this respect, all the participants observed that their agencies use a combination of mechanisms including, website, media (traditional and new), Workshops and Training, Technical Assistance, Awareness Campaigns, Collaboration with Stakeholders and Compliance Monitoring to inform downstream actors (agro-producers and exporters) about WTO rules and other international standards. One of the participants observed "...we use various means to inform agro-producers and exporters about WTO rules and other international standards. These include websites, media (traditional and new) Workshops and Training, Technical Assistance, Awareness Campaigns, Collaboration with Stakeholders and Compliance Monitoring. We go to farmers and partner with a lot and visit their farms, especially plant department and tell them the procedures and method of farming. The procedures before you can export them, farming method, processing, storage (preservation). This is to prevent them from been rejected after all

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

their effort and if the necessary procedures are not followed, definitely the commodity will be rejected.” (P001). Additionally, information is disseminated to inform agro-producers and exporters through the National Trade Facilitation Committee (NTFC) which is composed of representatives from both public and private sectors, including trade associations, chambers of commerce, customs brokers, freight forwarders, transporters, and other stakeholders. One of the participants observed “...I know that we have what we call a large national focal point which is domiciled in the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment and the members of that focal point are all trade-related agencies as well as members of the organized private sector occasionally, they do organize workshops..”(P003).

Secondly, the insight from the thematic analysis of the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which form the midstream level in the Nigerian trade environment, concerning the role of the midstream in reducing market access barrier, indicates that there is a comprehensive compliance mechanism in place. All the participants observed that the Nigerian government has put in place various measures to ensure that producers and exporters of agricultural commodities in Nigeria comply with WTO rules and other international rules. These measures include the Implementation of Standards through agencies like the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON) and the Nigerian Agricultural Quarantine Service (NAQS) to ensure that agricultural products produced in Nigeria meet international standards, mandatory Certification of agricultural commodities by relevant government agencies like NAQS and the Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC) before exporting, regular inspections and monitoring of agricultural products to ensure compliance with international standards by NAQS and the provision of Trade-Related Capacity Building by the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment to producers and exporters of agricultural commodities to enhance their understanding of WTO rules and other international rules.

One of the participants observed “...we have various measures in place to ensure that producers and exporters of agricultural commodities comply with WTO rules and other international rules. The Nigerian government has established standards through agencies like the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON) and the Nigerian Agricultural Quarantine Service (NAQS) to ensure that agricultural products produced in Nigeria meet international standards. The Nigerian government requires exporters of agricultural commodities to obtain certification from relevant government agencies like NAQS and the Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC). We also conduct regular inspections and monitoring of agricultural products as well as provide Trade-Related Capacity Building to producers and exporters of agricultural commodities to enhance their understanding of

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

WTO rules and other international rules...” (P007). Also, the Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC) is currently partnering with key stakeholders (internal and external) to ensure that Nigerian produce and products conform to international standards. In this regards a participant observed “...We also make sure that we partner with both external and internal development partners e.g CBI, JAIZ, NIRSAL etc to ensure that our product conforms with quality. Recently, about 3years ago, Nigeria partner with CBI on the development of three products i.e., sesame, cocoa and cashew. 12 SMEs were selected, and they underwent training for 2years and at the end of the day, they were taken on a mission. After that, we always bring experts to look into the quality of their products, packing, content, labelling etc, with this our exporters are doing better...” (P002)

One participant observed “...NAQS, for example, has a process for investigating export rejections and violations of trade agreements. When an export is rejected or a violation is reported, NAQS conducts a thorough investigation to determine the cause of the rejection or violation. This investigation includes a review of the relevant laws, regulations, and standards, as well as an examination of the product itself.” (P006). Similarly, another participant stated “...SON has established procedures for investigating violations of standards and regulations. When a violation is reported, SON conducts an investigation to determine the cause of the violation and identify corrective actions that need to be taken.”(P004) and a third participant stated “...TREU, on the other hand, investigates violations of trade agreements and is responsible for enforcing trade remedies. TREU conducts investigations using a range of methods, including on-site inspections, document review, and stakeholder consultations. After an investigation, TREU may take corrective action to address the violation, including the imposition of trade remedies or the initiation of dispute settlement proceedings.” (P012)

Fourthly, the insight from the thematic analysis of the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which form the midstream level in the Nigerian trade environment, concerning the role of the midstream in reducing market access barrier, indicates that there is a comprehensive communication mechanism in place. In this regards the participants observed that the Nigerian government has established several communication mechanisms to facilitate effective communication between the downstream level (producers/exporters), the midstream level (agencies/institutions relevant to trade), and the upstream (Nigerian representative in the WTO). These mechanisms include the establishment of the National Committee on Trade Facilitation (NCTF) to promote effective coordination and communication among relevant government agencies, the private sector, and development partners; the launch of the Nigeria Trade Information Portal (NTIP) -a web-based platform that provides information

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

on trade-related procedures, regulations, and documentation requirements and the establishment of a WTO Desk within the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment (FMITI) to serve as the focal point for all matters related to Nigeria's engagement with the WTO, including communication and coordination with the Nigerian representative in the WTO. They are intended to ensure that stakeholders are informed and engaged in trade-related issues, which can, in turn, help to promote transparency and facilitate trade. Regarding this, a participant explained “

The National Committee on Trade Facilitation (NCTF) is established to promote effective coordination and communication among relevant government agencies, the private sector, and development partners and it is responsible for developing and implementing trade facilitation policies, including measures to improve communication among stakeholders. In addition, the Nigerian government has established the Nigeria Trade Information Portal (NTIP), which is a web-based platform that provides information on trade-related procedures, regulations, and documentation requirements. The NTIP helps to facilitate communication between producers/exporters and relevant government agencies, as well as with foreign trading partners. Finally, the Nigerian government also maintains a WTO Desk within the Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment (MITI). The WTO Desk serves as the focal point for all matters related to Nigeria's engagement with the WTO, including communication and coordination with the Nigerian representative in the WTO.” (P007).

6.2.3 Research Question 3

The third research question, which is the primary focus of this subsection of the results chapter is specified as follows:

RQ3: How well has the Midstream level performed its role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria's export commodities?

The thematic findings in Table 6.4 present a summary of the focus group participants' perceptions with respect to how well is the Midstream level poised to perform its role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria's export commodities. The thematic codes are presented alongside a few of the responses from the focus group discussion.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Table 6.4: Participants 'Perceptions of the Midstream's Performance

Discussion Question	Response	Code
Effectiveness of Information Mechanism	information mechanism ineffective	¹ INFORMATION
Effectiveness of Compliance Mechanism	compliance mechanism ineffective	¹ COMPLIANCE
Effectiveness of Reporting & Investigation Mechanism	reporting mechanism not well-publicized and investigation not effective	¹ REPORTING ² INVESTIGATION
Effectiveness of Communication Mechanism	communication mechanism not so effective	¹ COMMUNICATION
Existence of Violation Case	No Violation recorded	¹ VIOLATION

First, the insight from the thematic analysis of the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which form the midstream level in the Nigerian trade environment, concerning the role of the midstream in reducing market access barrier, indicates that the information mechanism in place is ineffective as it has not been able to create significant awareness among the downstream level actors. Participants maintained that there exists a huge information gap within and between the various levels of the trade architecture. One of the symptoms of this information gap is the obvious lack of awareness of trade and related issues among the downstream actors. Many producers and exporters are not even aware of the specific rules and regulations in place in the countries they are trying to export to, and this usually results in shipments being rejected at the border or not meeting the necessary standards for export. One participant observed "...The awareness of trade is not much in Nigeria, having series of meeting with FMITI, we are not handling trade the way it is supposed to be, trade should be a real activity..." (P011). Another obvious symptom is the lack of awareness of the WTO rules among key staff of relevant agencies. One participant captured it thus "...Most of the headquarters have no awareness of the WTO dos and don'ts..." (P002).

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

This shows that the trade information system cannot provide accurate and updated information to exporters and policymakers. This could limit the ability of the downstream level to identify potential markets and opportunities, as well as the ability of the midstream level to investigate and gather evidence on trade disputes.

Secondly, insights from the thematic analysis of the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which form the midstream level in the Nigerian trade environment, concerning the role of the midstream in reducing market access barrier, indicates that the compliance mechanism is ineffective. A participant explained "...Our domestic regulatory system is not effective. "Our problem is the domestic environment; we are unable to do the right thing so that when our products go out there, they will not be rejected. If your product met the international standard/specification...Our failure in our domestic regulatory system. When you are rejected, you should have the basis to challenge them if you believe you have done the right thing, such as meeting the specifications..." (P007). Furthermore, the participants observed that Nigeria's food exports have difficulty meeting international standards due to the weakness of its SPS/food safety system, thereby exposing the country's agricultural exports to rejections, bans, or other measures by importing countries, which reduces its competitiveness and market access. The participants also pointed out that due to high level of corruption in key agencies, some exporters bypass the system or bribe their ways through the system and end up exporting substandard commodities which are then rejected at point of entry to the importing country. In this regards, one participant stated "... on the issue of rejection, what we see is lack of compliance by our SME's and farmers..." (P002). Another participant mentioned that "... most Nigerian export rejects resulted from SPS standards and technical measures..." (P007).

Regarding how corruption influences non-compliance, a participant observed "...From the little we heard, some Nigerians prefer to go through unconventional means instead of going through the agency that is responsible for certification. Producers need to approach the relevant agencies to know what to do and get the relevant training to enable them to export correctly..." (P007). Another participant added "...Some SME's cut corners, bring their products for approval and after they are approved, they source for some fake products and export. The point is to avoid exporting diseases or bad products to other countries..." (P006)

Thirdly, the insight from the thematic analysis of the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which form the midstream level in the

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Nigerian trade environment, concerning the role of the midstream in reducing market access barrier, indicates that the reporting mechanism is not well-publicized investigation not effective. The participants observed that many farmers and exporters do not know how to report cases of rejected shipments or violations of trade rules which has resulted in underreporting of market access barriers and a lack of action being taken to address these barriers. As per one participant, "...A product was rejected and we were wondering why the rejection? After several follow-ups, we discovered that it was true. Then we also let it known to them that the certification came from us and they took it back. Most of the exporter/farmer/SME's, when their products are rejected, do not know who to complain to" (P006).

Additionally, the insight from the thematic analysis suggests that the investigating system is not effective. The participants observed that there are delays in investigating cases of rejections of Nigerian agricultural commodities mostly because there are no clear procedures in place for investigating violations of trade rules, and as such, relevant agencies take longer to investigate and in some instances are unable to investigate effectively. One participant observed "... our Investigating mechanisms is not effective; when rejections are reported it takes so much time before it is investigated. Sometimes, nothing is done at all. This is because there are no clear procedures in place for investigating violations of trade rules." (P003).

Fourthly, the insight from the thematic analysis of the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which form the midstream level in the Nigerian trade environment, concerning the role of the midstream in reducing market access barrier, indicates that the communication mechanism is not effective. The participants observed that there is a lack of effective communication and collaboration between the public and private sectors, as well as between the federal and state governments on trade issues which is evident in the lack of proper coordination between relevant agencies and downstream actors. According to a participant, "...there is an obvious lack of coordination between relevant agencies and downstream actors. For example, you can see that there is no clear communication channel between farmers, exporters, and relevant agencies. This is why the midstream cannot perform its role effectively." (P009).

Lastly, the insight from the thematic analysis of the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which form the midstream level in the Nigerian trade environment, concerning the role of the midstream in reducing market

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA’S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

access barrier, indicates that there have been several cases of rejections of Nigerian agricultural commodities by different countries. P009 stated “...the issue of rejection is quite alarming, the feedback that we receive on rejection and there is a particular need for Nigeria to address that issue. What I mean by that, in NAFDAC today, we receive what we call RASFF - food and feed safety alerts - European Commission ...” However, the participants observed that there are no recorded cases of violation because most of the rejections are due to infractions or lack of compliance on the part of the exporters. In this respect, Participant P009 stated “...in the last 10 years, we have analyzed most of these cases of rejection based on what we received and we have discovered that majorly the rejections are based on poor agricultural practice i.e. presence of pests and high level of contaminants in the products.”

6.2.4 Research Question 4

The fourth research question, which is the primary focus of this subsection of the results chapter is specified as follows:

RQ1: what are the challenges of the Midstream level in performing its role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria’s export commodities?

The thematic findings in Table 6.5 present a summary of the focus group participants’ perceptions with respect to the challenges of the Midstream level in performing its role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria’s export commodities. The thematic codes are presented alongside a few of the responses from the focus group discussion.

Table 6.5: Participants’ Perceptions of the challenges of the Midstream

Discussion Question	Response	Code
Inadequate expertise	Shortage of staff with required level of expertise	1EXPERTISE
Lack of Commitment	low stakeholder commitment	1COMMITMENT
Lack of Synergy	inadequate synergy within and among relevant agencies	1SYNERGY
Lack of relevant policies	No policy in place to address loopholes	1POLICY
Lack coordination	No proper coordination	1CORDINATION

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

First, the insight from the thematic analysis of the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which forms the midstream level in the Nigerian trade environment, concerning the role of the midstream in reducing market access barrier, indicates that a major challenge of the midstream is inadequate expertise. The participants observed that the midstream level lacks the necessary knowledge, skills and experience to effectively identify, analyze and report on market access barriers. Participant P007 explained "...Engagement is complex. We lack the relevant diverse expertise. For example, a country like America has specialists in different department unlike Nigeria, where one specialist has to go through the agric department..." Volume of engagement is high. We lack the adequate number of staff to handle effectively...FMITI have a trade department but there is also a need to have dispute department, without this department, it's difficult for the exporter to know where to channel the matter. Inadequate capacity to engage in dispute settlement which you said earlier, to the best of my knowledge, international trade lawyers are very few in this country..." This results in inaccurate or incomplete information being transmitted to the upstream level, which can weaken the case or reduce the chances of success in the WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism.

Secondly, the insight from the thematic analysis of the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which form the midstream level in the Nigerian trade environment, concerning the role of the midstream in reducing market access barrier, indicates that lack of or low stakeholder commitment constitutes a major challenge for the midstream. The participants observed that the midstream level does not have enough support or cooperation from the relevant stakeholders, such as government agencies, trade associations, private sector actors, civil society groups, etc. For example, P004 stated "...It's a lack of knowledge, commitment, and participation. We need to get acquainted with the requirements of what is needed. If aware, we will be able to participate in different dispute settlements..." This results in insufficient resources and the political will to investigate cases.

Thirdly the insight from the thematic analysis of the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which form the midstream level in the Nigerian trade environment, concerning the role of the midstream in reducing market access barrier, indicates that lack of or inadequate synergy within and among relevant agencies is another factor bedeviling the midstream. "...we have different ministries/agencies/organizations but the challenges we are facing is in term of synergies. We don't work together to know what and what we are working towards. Only for

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

agriculture alone, we have different departments but yet no synergies..."(P008). The participants observed that the midstream level does not have a clear division of roles and responsibilities among its different components, such as ministries, departments, agencies, etc.as per P004 "...I will say it's internal, which a lot of us have talked about. When I mean internal, it has to do with regulatory agencies of the FDA's involved in the trading arena, reasons because some of us want to be territorial base on I work with SON and it has to be SON thing without engaging others for us to achieve our common aim... For example, SON is planning to organize a programme that as to do with trade export, and they will invite 2-3 organizations for the programme and you have the stakeholders you want to communicate this information to, SON will not invite NAFDAC to contribute their own path etc. then how will it work? So, between us as organizations/agencies, there is no synergies among us..." This usually results in duplication, overlap or conflict of work, and consequently, waste time and resources and create confusion or inconsistency in the information being transmitted to the upstream level.

Fourthly, the insight from the thematic analysis of the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which form the midstream level in the Nigerian trade environment, concerning the role of the midstream in reducing market access barrier, indicates that lack of relevant policies constitutes a major challenge to the midstream. The participants observed that the midstream level does not have a clear and coherent policy framework that guides its actions and objectives in relation to market access barriers. In this regard a participant P010 stated "...we don't have the relevant policies. Trade institutions need critical policies to guide their operations and mandate their roles in reducing market access barriers. Without relevant policies, we cannot have a clear direction or legal backing to carry out our functions effectively." This results in a lack of direction, priority or strategy in the investigation and data-gathering process.

Lastly, the insight from the thematic analysis of the focus group discussion with the various representatives of the trade institutions which form the midstream level in the Nigerian trade environment, concerning the role of the midstream in reducing market access barrier, indicates that lack of proper coordination constitutes a major challenge to the midstream. The participants observed that the midstream level does not have an effective mechanism or platform for coordinating its activities and exchanging information with the downstream and upstream levels. This results in a lack of feedback, consultation or collaboration among the different levels of trade architecture. According to P005, "...there is no proper coordination; the trade institutions need to coordinate with other stakeholders to reduce market access barriers effectively. Without proper coordination,

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

the trade institutions may not be able to gather the necessary information, implement interventions, or address emerging challenges in a timely and efficient manner, which would limit their ability to reduce market access barriers.”

6.3 Summary of the Thematic Analysis of the Focus Group Discussion

Insights from the focus group discussions highlighted the role and responsibilities of the midstream in facilitating Nigeria's export of agricultural commodities. For one, the midstream level which comprises the aforementioned trade institutions are there to ensure that producers and exporters (downstream level) are adequately informed about relevant international rules and standards regarding every export commodity and apply them to the fullest before exporting same to a foreign market. This indicates that the midstream is responsible for advocacy and sensitization of the downstream about WTO technical rules, SPS standards for exportable agricultural commodities and other relevant technical standards in international markets. Sensitizing downstream players about these standards and specifications is critical to reducing incidences of rejection of Nigeria's agricultural exports in international markets. Some of the focus group participants indicated that there is a comprehensive information dissemination mechanism in place. In this respect, all the participants observed that their agencies use a combination of mechanisms including, website, media (traditional and new), workshops and training, technical assistance, awareness campaigns, collaboration with stakeholders and compliance monitoring to inform downstream actors (agro-producers and exporters) about WTO rules and other international standards. These procedures and mechanisms help to ensure that violations are thoroughly investigated, and appropriate corrective actions are taken to address them. Findings from the analysis of responses to the questionnaires indicated that there is a positive relationship between understanding or appreciation of these standards and the export behaviour of producers of agricultural commodities. Consequently, increased sensitization of agricultural commodity producers about these standards should influence or encourage them to engage in the export of their commodities especially as results from the analysis of the questionnaires circulated to downstream players indicated that a significant number of agricultural commodity producers do not understand international standards for export of different agricultural commodities.

Another useful finding from the focus group discussions highlighted that downstream actors serve as a critical link between downstream players and upstream players. This is because midstream players are responsible for investigating cases of rejection or barriers faced by downstream players. The midstream then escalates the findings of their

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

investigations to the upstream segment for action since the upstream is closest to WTO organs and processes for dispute resolution.

On the question of how well the midstream has performed in carrying out its responsibilities to facilitate export of agricultural commodities, majority of the focus group participants indicated that there is still more for relevant trade institutions to do when it comes to sensitizing downstream players on WTO standards and other international standards for exports. Some of the participants indicated that a significant information gap still exists among most producers of agricultural commodities around these standards. This is confirmed by results which indicated a relationship between engagement with trade institutions and the export performance of agricultural commodities in Nigeria. Essentially, results from the analysis of questionnaires circulated to downstream players indicated that agricultural commodity producers who engage with trade institutions were more likely to engage in the export of their agricultural commodities. It is equally important to note that there are capacity constraints within some trade institutions when it comes to understanding of WTO processes especially the WTO dispute settlement understanding. This may make it challenging for the midstream to effectively investigate violations in a way that makes it easier for the upstream to act on them effectively at the WTO level. Consequently, the upstream should build the capacity of midstream players around WTO standards and processes so that the midstream is better equipped to educate and sensitize the downstream on standards for the export of various agricultural commodities.

CHAPTER SEVEN

THEMATIC ANALYSIS OF THE INTERVIEW

7.0 Introduction

This chapter focused on investigating the ability of upstream actors to initiate action at the WTO on behalf of the producers/exporters. Therefore, the specific objectives are: to establish the role of the upstream level in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria's export commodities and identify the factors preventing it from engaging the WTO Dispute Settlement Understanding on behalf of Nigeria. Accordingly, the chapter presents the thematic analysis results from the interview with the upstream actors. The chapter is organized into three sections. The first section presents the Sample Composition for the interviewees while the second section presents thematic findings based on each research question. Finally, section three presents a Summary of the thematic analysis of the interview.

7.1 Sample Composition of the Focus Group Participants

The sample for the interview consisted of 3 interviewees. The sample includes the Director-General/Chief Trade Negotiator, the Nigerian Office for Trade Negotiations, the honorable minister of the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment and Nigeria's Ambassador to the WTO. These agents serve as the link between the midstream and the WTO. These agents are expected to take the outcome of the investigations by the midstream agents and initiate action at the WTO on behalf of the producers/exporters.

7.2 Thematic Findings

A structured interview was employed to collect data from Nigeria's trade representatives based at the WTO headquarters in Hague and the Nigerian Minister of Industries, Trade and Investment. The interview with the Nigerian representative at the WTO was conducted via telephone while those of the Honorable Minister, Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment and the Director-General/Chief Trade Negotiator, the Nigerian Office for Trade Negotiations, were conducted in person. Both sessions were recorded and transcribed thereafter. A copy of the transcript is designated "appendix B". The data gathered through the interviews were coded and analyzed. For the purposes of

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA’S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

the analysis and discussion of feedback from the interviews, the interviewees are referred to as follows:

- Head of Nigeria Delegation to the WTO: HNDW
- Honorable Minister – Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment: FMITI
- Chief Trade Negotiator: CTN
- Senior Legal Advisor to the DG, WTO: SLA

7.2.1 Role of the Upstream in Addressing Market Access Barriers Faced by Nigeria’s Agricultural Commodities

The first question posed to the interviewees is, “what is the role of the upstream level in reducing market access barriers by Nigeria’s agricultural exports?” The responses provided by the interviewees are analyzed and discussed below:

Table 7.1 presents a summary of the interviewees’ perceptions with respect to the role of the upstream level in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria’s export commodities. The thematic codes are presented alongside a few of the responses from the interview.

Table 7.1: Participants’ Perceptions of the Role of the upstream Level

Discussion Question	Response	Code
Upstream role	Initiate and prosecute cases on behalf of downstream actors,	1INITIATE 2PROSECUTE
	Coordinate with trade-related agencies and private sectors through a national focal point	1COORDINATE
	Train and support stakeholders in producing export commodities	1TRAINING 2SUPPORT
	Communicate with the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment on WTO issues.	1COMMUNICATE

Before highlighting the role of the upstream in addressing market access barriers faced by the Nigeria’s agricultural exports, HNDW highlighted some of the fundamental role and

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

functions of Nigeria's Trade Delegation to the WTO including: *“representation and protection of Nigeria's trade interests; engaging with and updating trade institutions in Nigeria – such as the FMITI, NEPC and SON- on the evolving regulatory landscape for international trade; and engaging with stakeholders at the WTO level to address trade barriers faced by Nigeria's exporters”*. HNDW also noted that the trade delegation leverages available WTO resources to provide capacity building support to trade-related agencies and the organized private sector. In fact, HNDW noted that, *“the WTO has provided some capacity building support to trade-related institutions and the organized private sector around trade rules and SPS standards”*. HNDW also indicated that Nigeria's trade delegation is also responsible for communicating trade concerns by WTO member countries to relevant statutory and regulatory institutions with a view to ensuring that Nigeria does not breach WTO rules. Again, HNDW noted, *“despite series of capacity building workshops organized by the trade delegation together with the WTO, issues around staff turnover and weak coordination between relevant trade institutions present institutional strengthening challenges....it is the responsibility of trade institutions to ensure that knowledge gained from these workshops trickle down to the downstream so that critical standards, such as the SPS standards, can be complied with at that level...this could be responsible for the gap in knowledge of standards for agricultural exporters among producers and exporters”*.

Some of these upstream roles highlighted by HNDW were equally highlighted by FMITI who indicated that, *“Nigeria's delegation to the WTO plays a critical role in trade facilitation especially as they are responsible for engaging with relevant stakeholders -including other WTO member countries- at the high-level to address market access challenges faced by agricultural exporters”*. FMITI also acknowledged that Nigeria's Trade Delegation had in the past organized targeted capacity strengthening workshops around critical WTO standards and rules however, there is still need to ensure that farmers, producers and exporters of agricultural commodities in the country have access to the information shared through these workshops.

Discussion

Based on the information provided by HNDW and FMITI, the upstream is an important part of Nigeria's trade ecosystem given its perceived interaction with the midstream segment. Some of the key roles and responsibilities of the upstream segment of the ecosystem (i.e. as represented by Nigeria's Delegation to the WTO) include: protecting Nigeria's trade interests; engaging with relevant instruments of the WTO to address market access barriers faced by agricultural exporters; institutional strengthening and technical assistance support to trade-related institutions around WTO rules, standards

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

and processes; coordinating with national trade institutions (i.e. midstream segment) and other relevant regulatory institutions to ensure that Nigeria complies with WTO rules. Based on this, one can infer that the upstream is the critical link between Nigeria and the WTO, i.e. Nigeria's trade delegation is responsible for Nigeria's commercial diplomatic efforts on the international scene. This reaffirms the views of Wilkinson & Brouthers (2000) that trade missions or delegations operate as an on-site tutorial, providing learning and experience which allows firms to acquire useful information and expand their knowledge of the exporting process. Similarly, Posada et al., (2020) notes that through their participation in WTO committees, trade delegations equally contribute to trade negotiations including resolving trade disputes with other WTO member countries.

It is necessary to note that for the upstream to effectively carry out its mandate, they must be provided with timely and comprehensive information about market access barriers by the midstream (i.e. national trade-related institutions). One of the interviewees, CTN advised that, "in the absence of timely investigation and reporting of complaints about market access barriers by the FMITI, it becomes challenging for the Nigeria delegation to the WTO to effectively prosecute its responsibilities....the FMITI can coordinate with other relevant agencies -such as the NEPC and the Federal Ministry of Agriculture to establish a digital platform where producers and exporters of agriculture can submit their complaints which would reach the trade mission in real time". CTN also noted that, "where limited complaints are channeled to the upstream actors to act, then there is limited need to engage with the DSU. This could be a contributing factor for Nigeria's low engagement with the WTO's DSU over the years..." Having said this, it is important to note that findings from the focus group discussions indicated that the midstream segment (i.e. some trade institutions) has capacity constraints when it comes to understanding of WTO processes and standards. Consequently, the upstream has a role to play in addressing this particular constraint especially as improving the midstream's understanding of these standards and processes will ultimately filter down to the downstream via sensitization efforts discussed whilst analyzing the focus group discussions. In addition, the upstream can leverage available WTO technical assistance to build the capacity of relevant trade institutions in properly identifying and investigating violations reported by the downstream. This would help ensure that when treating such violations at the WTO level, the upstream has all the required information required to resolve such violations.

From the feedback provided by the interviewees, one challenge that emerged around capacity building support concerned the transmission of knowledge from capacity building workshops targeted at trade institutions to the downstream segment. HNDW indicated that the failure on the part of the FMITI to transmit knowledge and information

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA’S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

communicated through these workshops could be responsible for the low awareness of rules and standards for export of agricultural commodities among producers and exporters. Added advocacy around WTO standards (SPS and TBT requirements) and international specifications for exports is needed to enhance the compliance of the downstream actors, i.e. producers and exporters. In addition, UNIDO (2017) notes that national governments should put in place measures to support the development of a sound risk management system through assisting stakeholders to comply with technical regulations to enhance the transparency of trade procedures. In Nigeria, this can be achieved increased advocacy and capacity building on these standards targeted at the downstream actors.

7.2.2 Performance of Upstream Level

The second interview question posed to the interviewees is, “how well has the upstream level performed its role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria’s export commodities?”

The thematic findings in Table 7.2 present a summary of the interviewees' perceptions with respect to how well the upstream level has performed its role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria’s agricultural exports. The thematic codes from the interviews are presented alongside a few of the responses from the focus group discussion.

Table 7.2: Participants’ Perceptions of the Role of the upstream Level

Discussion Question	Response	Code
Initiation & Prosecution of cases	No case has been initiated or prosecuted	1INITIATE 2PROSECUTE
Coordination	Coordination is being provided through a national focal point	1COORDINATE
Training & Support	Training and support are being provided	1TRAINING 2SUPPORT
Communication	There is regular communication between the upstream FMITI on WTO issues	1COMMUNICATE

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

With respect to the question of how well the upstream has performed in addressing market access barriers faced by Nigeria's agricultural exports, HNDW noted that, *"Nigeria has not tabled or presented any trade dispute to the WTO through the DSU....on certain occasions when complaints have been brought to the attention of the trade delegation by trade-related institutions, these have been addressed through relevant WTO committees rather than through the DSU. These committees have proven to be effective in diplomatic in addressing trade complaints. Discussion of these complaints at committee level is less cumbersome than pursuing such complaints through the DSU instrument"*. CTN, on the other hand, also agreed with HNDW by stating that, *"some trade concerns have been addressed at the committee level on a bilateral note with little or no need to further table it through the DSU which is too expensive a route to follow especially for countries with the limited resources required at that level...tabling complaints at the DSU should be a last resort when engagement at the committee level is unsuccessful"*. Again, HNDW noted that, *"the recent EU ban of beans exports from Nigeria is being addressed through the WTO Committee on Agriculture and there is optimism, that this ban will be lifted soon...in this regard, the engagement of the upstream segment with relevant WTO Committees to address trade barriers faced by Nigerian exporters represents a step in the right direction. However, it is equally important to note that the performance of the upstream is, to some extent, dependent on the performance of Nigeria's trade institutions. In the absence of comprehensive information about trade complaints from these institutions, it becomes challenging for the upstream to deliver on certain aspects of its mandate especially as it concerns managing and effectively handling trade disputes at the WTO level. I perceive an information gap at the ministry level with respect to managing and disseminating information about complaints through the appropriate channels. The Department of Trade and Trade Information Department within the Ministry should establish a system, such as a portal, that can be used to collect feedback from the organized private sector in Nigeria about export challenges. Beyond just collecting this information, the ministry should be able to investigate the extent of such breaches and then escalate it to the trade delegation in Geneva. There is a gap here that makes it challenging for the trade delegation to manage Nigeria's market access challenges. Perhaps, there may be a need to strengthen the capacity of trade institutions on investigating and escalating trade complaints from exporters"*.

CTN noted that, *"Nigeria's delegation to the WTO is an active member of the WTO Committee on agriculture and has used its active membership of this committee to present and discuss some trade challenges faced by agricultural exporters in Nigeria. In view of this engagement, I would say the trade delegation or the upstream, as you say,*

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

has done relatively well given resource constraints and challenges beyond its country. Of course, there is always room for improvement....And when I say, challenges beyond its control, I am referring to some aspects of the current trade regime which is skewed in favour of developed countries than developing member countries. For instance, some WTO member countries, such as the EU, appear to have gone beyond the trade agenda by implementing measures -e.g. carbon border adjustments, child labour etc- that creates artificial market access barriers for other member countries, especially developing countries. Again, the Appellate Body appears to be dysfunctional given issues raised by the US. In view of this, the question then arises as to the extent that the DSU provides or guarantees market access...Besides WTO-related challenges and external challenges, there are also Nigeria-specific challenges, especially lack of coordination between trade institutions and other regulatory agencies, that could influence the performance of the upstream segment. All in all, given these challenges, I would say that the trade delegation has performance relatively well". Again, concerning the performance of the upstream segment, HNDW noted that, *"the Nigeria trade delegation has collaborated with the WTO to organize several capacity building workshops for trade institutions and the organized private sector around SPS and TBT requirements. However, I must admit that these workshops should be extended to the downstream segment and this should be the responsibility of trade-related institutions in the country. By organizing these workshops, the Nigeria trade delegation has contributing to institutional strengthening of Nigeria's trade ecosystem".*

Discussion

Feedback from the interviews suggests that the upstream segment (i.e. as represented by Nigeria's trade delegation or mission to the WTO) has performed relatively well given internal and external challenges it is confronted with in the fulfilment of its mandate. While this is the opinion of some of the interviewees, perspectives on the performance of the upstream is relative. For instance, the upstream cannot be viewed as performing especially as results from the analysis of the downstream segment highlight limited intent of majority of agro producers (downstream segment) to export their commodities coupled with limited understanding of WTO standards and other international standards for export. Furthermore, results from the focus group discussions also highlighted sufficient information gap among the downstream and midstream segments about WTO standards and processes that even makes it challenging for the midstream to effectively carry out their roles and responsibilities.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Internally, the challenges are more Nigeria-specific, e.g. resource constraints, institutional capacity weakness among national trade institutions, and lack of coordination between trade institutions, other regulatory agencies, weak coordination/escalation of complaints to the upstream for resolution, and the organized private sector. Concerning the challenge of lack of coordination between trade-related institutions and other regulatory agencies, one of the interviewees recommended reviving the inter-ministerial Task-Force on Trade Facilitation (TFTF) which was inaugurated in 2011 by the Federal Executive Council under the administration President Goodluck Jonathan. Since 2015, when President Muhammadu Buhari assumed leadership, this Task Force has been inactive. Reviving the TFTF offers a useful way of strengthening coordination between trade and relevant non-trade institutions in the country. In addition to this, there is a need for the federal government to mainstream trade in its national development strategies. OECD (2016) note that the evolving landscape for global trade and investment carry implications for the activities and programs of government ministries responsible for agriculture, finance, infrastructure labour and foreign affairs and vice versa. Consequently, OECD (2016) suggests that it is pertinent for government ministries systematically collaborate to ensure that their policies and programs contribute to strengthening the national environment for trade.

From the conversations, the issue of 'lack of an effective mechanism from receiving, investigating and reporting feedback from producers and exporters about market access barriers to the upstream segment' emerged as a critical challenge that has implications for the performance of Nigeria's trade mission to the WTO. If the midstream segment fails in its responsibility of collecting, documenting and appropriately reporting market access barriers or breaches by a WTO member country to the delegation, the delegation is handicapped in its capacity to fulfil its mandate of protecting Nigeria's trade and foreign commercial interests. Put simply, the performance of the upstream segment is intertwined with the performance of the midstream segment.

Based on feedback from the interviewees, the process for managing information or feedback from the private sector or producers has not been optimal and this influences the degree to which the delegation can effectively engage with available WTO mechanisms for resolving trade disputes. This issue further reinforces the issue of capacity constraints in Nigeria's trade-related institutions that has made it challenging for the country to achieve the objectives of its national trade policy. One of the interviewees, CTN, recommended digitalizing the process for receiving and managing feedback about complaints from the downstream segment. This could take the form of an online portal

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

that can be used by the private sector (i.e. exporters and producers) to report complaints about market access barriers. Such a portal is being used in India and as such, should be replicated in Nigeria. This portal would help in formalizing the process for documenting feedback from the downstream segment about market access barriers. Beyond documenting such complaints, the interviewees also highlighted the need to strengthen the capacity of FMITI -through its Department of Trade and its Trade Information and Complaint Unit- to investigate complaints so that a comprehensive report can be escalated to the delegation for action. In the absence of comprehensive reports about such disputes, it becomes challenging for the delegation to resolve them at the WTO level.

Another feedback from the interviews that is worthy of note concerns the observation by the interviewees about the resolution of trade disputes through the DSU. In this regard, the resolution of disputes does not have to be through the DSU. Some of the complaints that Nigeria has raised about other member countries and vice versa have been addressed at the committee with little or no need for pursuing them through the DSU. Essentially, engagement with the DSU is seen as a last resort when engagement at the committee level and other diplomatic efforts fail in resolving such complaints. Examples were cited about how the trade delegation is engaging with the WTO Committee on Agriculture to resolve the EU ban on beans exports from Nigeria. This could perhaps point to the reason for Nigeria's low engagement with the DSU mechanism. Again, it is essential to note that resolving trade disputes at the Committee-level is more cost effective and less resource-demanding than the DSU route.

Based on feedback from the interviewees, it is fair to conclude that the upstream segment of Nigeria's trade ecosystem has performed relatively well given internal and external challenges that it is confronted with in fulfilling its mandate. Some pointers from the interviews support this position: engagement with relevant WTO Committees, especially the WTO Committee on Agriculture- to resolve market access barriers faced by exporters of agricultural commodities; and the organization of several workshops on SPS and TBT requirements for trade institutions and the organized private sector has contributed towards strengthening Nigeria's trade ecosystem. Despite these positive observations, it is necessary to note that there is still need to transmit learnings from these workshops to the downstream segment. Ideally, the FMITI in collaboration with other relevant trade institutions, should lead efforts to sensitize the downstream segment around SPS, TBT and other critical requirements for agricultural exports. This would significantly contribute to reducing market access barriers faced by exporters and producers of agricultural

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA’S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

commodities in Nigeria. One area where the upstream has not performed well concerns the significant information gap among the midstream and downstream segments about existing and emerging international standards and requirements for the export of agricultural commodities. The upstream needs to invest in capacity strengthening of national trade institutions considering the symbiotic relationship among all three segments of Nigeria’s trade ecosystem.

7.2.3 Challenges Faced by the Upstream Segment in Eliminating Market Access Barriers

The third interview question posed to the interviewees is, “what are the challenges of the upstream level in performing its role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria’s export commodities?”

The thematic findings in Table 7.3 present a summary of the interviewees’ perceptions with respect to the challenges of the upstream level in performing its role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria’s export commodities. The thematic codes are presented alongside a few of the responses from the interview.

Table 7.3: Participants’ Perceptions of the challenges of the Midstream

Discussion Question	Response	Code
Internal Factors	lack of domestic mechanisms to identify, investigate and communicate trade barriers to WTO Delegation, Lack of Expertise or Capacity to Litigate in the WTO and lack of knowledge and awareness about the benefits of WTO DSU provisions among government officials and business entities	1DOMESTIC 2MECHANISM 3CAPACITY 4AWARENESS
External Factors	Long duration of case prosecution, complexity of the system, cost of prosecuting cases and Skewed WTO Provisions.	1DURATION 2COMPLEXITY 3LITIGATION COST 4UNFAIRNESS

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

In the previous question, the interviewees highlighted some of the challenges making it difficult for the upstream to perform its role in reducing market access barriers faced by Nigeria's agricultural exports. In response to this question, SLA highlighted the importance of member countries having a system in-country for collecting feedback from exporters about market access barriers they face in international markets. SLA further noted that, "in the absence of adequate information about the extent of these market access barriers, it becomes challenging for member countries' trade missions to effectively carry out their responsibilities at the WTO level....I must admit that WTO litigation processes are cumbersome hence, the need for the governments of member countries to ensure that their trade delegations have the required resources, especially expertise in trade jurisprudence and WTO dispute resolution procedures. This expertise is required to effectively navigate the complex landscape of trade dispute litigation and resolution". In response to this particular question, HNDW highlighted underlying issues with some WTO rules and agreements that pose a challenge when it comes to developing countries' engagement with the WTO's dispute resolution process. HNDW remarked, "Under the domestic support pillar, there is what we call the aggregate measurement of support. It allows some members who have that entitlement to provide some kind of market price support both product and non-product specific to their producers in Agriculture. We have in total over 32 countries that have their right, and so that entitlement enables them to concentrate support on any product they choose. In fact, some developed countries have been known to exceed the 5% maximum allowable annually for the application of agricultural subsidies without being penalized. Meanwhile, when developing countries exceed the maximum of 10% allowable for the application of agricultural subsidies, developed member countries are quick to raise issues about it. Overall, subsidies applied by developed member countries significantly undermines the competitiveness of Nigeria's producers...In view of this, one can see that there are aspects of the current trade regime that appear to be skewed in favour of developed member countries than their developing counterparts. This poses a serious challenge for trade delegations when seeking to resolve trade disputes through the DSU and even through relevant WTO committees".

Again, HNDW noted, "coupled with capacity constraints in trade-related institutions in Nigeria, especially expertise in WTO rules and trade standards, there is also the challenge of lack of coordination between trade and relevant non-trade institutions in Nigeria. This limited coordination *affects the ability of the Nigeria trade delegation to effectively carry out its mandate including those related to market access barriers that*

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

affect Nigeria's global trade interests...The trade delegation can only act on comprehensive information about the export challenges escalated by the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment. It is the duty of the Ministry to identify and thoroughly investigate these market access barriers so that comprehensive information is escalated to the trade delegation. Effective resolution of disputes either through relevant committees or the DSU is dependent on comprehensive information about the export challenges faced by the private sector".

Some of the concerns highlighted by HNDM and SLA were also restated by FMITI. FMITI indicated that, *"I acknowledge that capacity constraints in the Ministry is an impediment to resolving some of the barriers faced by Nigerian exporters. We are taking steps to address some of these challenges including ensuring that relevant trade departments in the Ministry are staffed with people with expertise in WTO processes including litigation processes for dealing with trade disputes with other WTO member countries...the ministry is also trying to strengthen its engagement with the private sector in Nigeria to streamline export processes including establishing mechanisms for ensuring that exporters comply with standards and specifications for export of various agricultural commodities. Although there are unfair trade practices by some WTO member countries that affect Nigerian exporters, there are situations where failure by some exporters to comply with certain set standards and specifications lead to justified rejections in the international market. To address this particular problem, the ministry -in partnership to the trade delegation, the ministry of Agriculture, NAFDAC, and the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON)- has organized some capacity building for representatives of the organized private sector around SPS requirements and relevant specifications. In partnership with the SON and Ministry of Agriculture, we are also strengthening processes for certification of some exportable agricultural commodities. These measures will go a long way in addressing the export challenges faced by Nigerian exporters of agricultural commodities".* What can be inferred from this particular comment is that although there are external market access barriers that are somewhat unfair and unjustified that limit access to international markets for Nigerian exporters of agricultural commodities,

HNDW also highlighted the cost implications of pursuing litigation through the DSU as another key challenge affecting the ability of the upstream to address market access barriers faced by exporters of agricultural commodities. HNDW noted, *" it is expensive to staff and maintain a trade delegation in Geneva and this makes it challenge to staff the trade delegation with specialist expertise. To put things into proper perspective, Nigeria*

THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS

maintains missions around the world including its trade mission in Geneva; so this resource constraint affects the ability of the trade delegation to effectively carry out its responsibilities on certain levels...I should also note that DSU litigation processes are very expensive and complex for many countries especially developing member countries like Nigeria. This is why earlier in the interview, I indicated that Nigeria's trade delegation prefers to address complaints through relevant WTO Committees than the DSU. Addressing such complaints through the DSU only comes as a last resort considering its cost implications". Again, this shows that engagement with relevant WTO committees provides a cost-effective alternative to the resolution of trade disputes.

Discussion

The analysis of feedback from the interviews highlighted several challenges affecting the capacity of the upstream segment to effectively carry out its role in reducing market access barriers faced by Nigerian exporters. One of the challenges concerns the lack of a formal mechanism for collecting feedback from exporters about market access barriers in international markets. It is the responsibility of the FMITI to establish a system for collecting information about market access barriers from exporters of agricultural commodities. The FMITI can digitize this process for ease of reporting by exporters. Another challenge concerns the lack of coordination among government ministries that makes it challenging for the upstream to domesticate compliance with WTO rules and processes.

The complexity, duration, and cost of WTO litigation processes also pose a challenge to the upstream segment. The complexity and financial implications of WTO litigation processes is well-documented in literature and was highlighted as a challenge by the interviewees. Grasstek (2013), for instance, notes that the complexity and cost of the WTO's dispute resolution system partly explains the limited engagement of some member countries. With respect to the duration of litigation processes, Bhati (2017) suggests that when delays in WTO dispute resolution become the standard, they cast doubt on the importance of the WTO's rules-based system itself. Basically, an erosion of trust in this system can result in the re-emergence of power orientation in the multilateral trading system. Such delays could lead to affected member countries looking for other solutions that are outside the legal and institutional framework of the WTO, such as taking unilateral action. Again, Bhati (2017) notes that developing countries tend to suffer the most from delays in processing cases. Streamlining litigation processes is critical for enhancing Nigeria and other Africa countries' engagement with the DSU. In addition, there is a need

THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS

to look at the application of the 'aggregate measurement of support provision' that appears to benefit developed countries than their developing counterparts as this also contributes to challenges in resolving complaints by developing countries.

Capacity constraints were also highlighted as another key challenge affecting the ability of the upstream segment to address market access barriers faced by Nigerian exporters. Regarding the issue of capacity constraints among developing countries, Xiangchen et al., (2019) note that there is overall universality coupled with distinguished particularity as they participate in negotiations, rule-making and dispute resolution at the WTO. In addition to the limited capacity on DSU procedures and processes, the ability of each developing country to participate in the multilateral process is also connected with the historical background, political system, and social structure of each country (Xiangchen et al., 2019). Furthermore, Abdul-Latif (2021) further opines that the limited participation of African countries in the DSU could be symptomatic of deeper structural economic weaknesses in the continent, and perhaps not necessarily a reflection of the failure of the DSU itself. Based on the interviews, the upstream segment faces capacity constraints and its ability to resolve these capacity constraints is hampered by fiscal constraints, i.e. the Nigerian government must prioritize its financial challenges given in-country development issues coupled with the cost of managing its diplomatic missions around the world. Having discussed the analysis of feedback from the interviews, the next section summarizes the key findings from the thematic analysis of the interviews.

7.3 Summary of the Thematic Analysis of the Interview

On the role of the upstream segment (i.e. Nigeria's delegation to the WTO in Geneva) in reducing market access barriers faced by Nigerian exporters of agricultural commodities, the interviewees highlighted among other things the following: the protection of Nigeria's foreign trade interests; engaging with relevant instruments -especially the WTO Committee on Agriculture- to address complaints raised by Nigerian exporters; engaging with the midstream segment to domesticate compliance with WTO rules and obligations; and institutional strengthening and capacity building support to national trade-related institutions on WTO rules, agreements, and procedures. Analysis of feedback from the interviews also indicated that over the years, the trade delegation in Geneva has collaborated with the WTO to organize some capacity building workshops for the organized private sector, trade and non-trade institutions. However, there is a need for the midstream segment to ensure that learnings from these workshops are equally

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

transmitted to the downstream segment to boost their compliance with international trade requirements.

Concerning the performance of the upstream segment in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria's agricultural exports, the interviewees indicated that this segment has performed well given existing internal and external constraints. For one, despite low engagement with the DSU, the trade delegation has utilized its participation in some WTO committees, including the WTO Committee on Agriculture, to address some complaints around barriers faced by the Nigerian exporters. In addition, the trade delegation has also engaged with these committees to also resolve complaints brought by WTO member countries against Nigeria. Furthermore, the delegation's institutional and capacity strengthening support to national trade institutions and the organized private sector - around WTO rules and processes including SPS and TBT requirements- also serves as a positive indication of the upstream's performance in addressing barriers faced by the countries agricultural exports. The upstream segment is currently engaging with national trade institutions, especially the FMITI and Federal Ministry of Agriculture, to formalize the complaints and feedback mechanism for Nigeria exporters. Digitalizing the process was suggested by some of the interviewees.

Regarding the challenges faced by the upstream segment in performing its role of resolving market access barriers for Nigeria's export commodities, discussion of feedback from the interviewees highlighted some internal and external challenges. Some of the internal challenges highlighted by thematic analysis of interviewees' feedback include: lack of internal system for identifying and collecting feedback from exporters and the private sector about market access barriers; weak coordination between trade and non-trade institutions in Nigeria; and resource/capacity constraints with respect to maintaining the trade delegation in WTO. In addition to these internal challenges, the upstream segment also faces external challenges that are beyond its control. Some of these external challenges as highlighted by the thematic analysis of the interviews include: the complexity and cost of WTO litigation processes; the duration of DSU cases; limited trade jurisprudence expertise in Nigeria's trade delegation; and skewed provisions in WTO rules -such as aggregate measurement of support provision- that hamper the competitiveness of Nigeria's exports. It is equally important to note that the performance and ability of the upstream segment in addressing market access barriers for Nigeria's exports is linked the performance of the midstream segment.

CHAPTER EIGHT

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

8.0 Introduction

This chapter discusses the implication of the results for the research questions. Accordingly, the chapter is organized into three sections: the first section discusses the findings and their implication for the stated research questions. The second section triangulates the findings across the three different levels, while section three focuses on explaining the outcome of the research using the principal-agent theory.

8.1 Discussion of findings

8.1.1 Discussion of findings at the downstream level comprised of Nigerian Agricultural producers

The study aimed to assess whether downstream players in Nigeria, specifically producers of agricultural commodities, could identify market access barriers and factors influencing exports. The results showed that the understanding and application of WTO standards among producers was low, and their participation in commodity exports was minimal. While knowledge of WTO Rules of Origin had a significant impact on the export behavior of Shea Nut producers, it did not have a significant effect on Sesame and Cocoa producers. Engagement with national trade institutions had a significant impact on the export behavior of Cocoa and Shea Nut producers. Finally, producer-related factors significantly affected the export behavior of all three commodities. Overall, the study concludes that downstream players in Nigeria lack the ability to identify trade barriers due to their low participation in commodity export and low understanding of standards for agricultural commodity exports.

The study also found that the understanding and application of WTO standards among producers was low. This is not surprising, as it is consistent with existing research on the challenges faced by developing countries in effectively utilizing the WTO dispute settlement mechanism. Several studies have documented the difficulty that developing countries, particularly those in Africa, face in implementing and benefiting from the rules-based trading system of the WTO, due to a range of factors, including limited institutional capacity, lack of resources, inadequate legal and regulatory frameworks, and weak market infrastructure. For example, a study by Khan and Mahmud (2017) examined the

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

impact of WTO dispute settlement on developing countries and found that although the system has the potential to help developing countries defend their rights and interests, they face significant challenges in accessing and utilizing it effectively. The study identified several factors that limit the participation of developing countries in the dispute settlement process, including lack of information, limited expertise, high litigation costs, and complex legal procedures. Similarly, a study by Adenikinju and Olusegun (2016) examined the challenges faced by Nigerian exporters in accessing foreign markets, and found that inadequate infrastructure, poor quality standards, and limited access to information and technology were among the key obstacles. Their study also highlighted the need for increased awareness and capacity building among Nigerian exporters to enable them to take advantage of the opportunities offered by international trade agreements, including the WTO.

Overall, the finding that the understanding and application of WTO standards among producers in Nigeria is low underscores the need for increased capacity building of producers, institutional strengthening of trade-related institutions, and awareness-raising efforts to improve the country's participation in the WTO dispute settlement mechanism. This could include targeted training programs for producers, government officials, and other stakeholders, as well as efforts to improve market infrastructure and regulatory frameworks. By addressing these challenges, Nigeria could enhance its competitiveness in international trade and boost the export of key agricultural commodities.

The study found that Nigeria's export market share is quite low and many producers have little or no interest in exporting, i.e. they are more focused on producing for the domestic market. Analysis of the survey data revealed that 92.7% of Cocoa producers and 85.4% of shea butter producers are currently not exporting any of their produce. This low level of export is due to a myriad of factors including lack of market information, low level of output, high transactional costs for export, the complexity of the export process, and high rejection rates for Nigeria's agricultural exports among others. Moreover, Ojeme (2022) notes that the high rejection rate is due to food safety concerns, technical barriers, non-adherence to best practices, disregard for basic requirements, and inefficiency of national trade institutions. Since most of the rejection cases are a result of failure on the part of Nigerian exporters, it is only natural that there would be no need to file any complaint at the DSU, hence the country's low level of participation in the WTO's dispute settlement mechanism.

Furthermore, the relationship between low export participation and the use of the WTO DSU can be explained from three perspectives. First, Bohanes & Garza (2012) postulate that larger WTO members trade greater volumes of more varied goods to a greater

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

number of trading partners, which in turn results in an increased number of possible trade disputes thus, giving them an increased predisposition to bring disputes to the WTO dispute settlement mechanism. Secondly, Shaffer & Sutton (2014) note that the size of a country's export market increases its capacity to retaliate or negotiate. This point is important owing to the prevailing perception that the DSU lacks the capacity to enforce its judgement and hence, there is little or no incentive for weaker countries to pursue cases through the DSU especially as many of them lack the capacity to retaliate against stronger member countries. Where there is a need to use this alternative, a country with a huge market size may exercise leverage by offering market access or threatening to withdraw access to foreign goods and services (Shaffer & Sutton, 2014). Finally, low market share or volume of export has a positive correlation with level of utilization of the WTO DSS. Studies have shown that developing countries tend to have smaller aggregate and disaggregate trading stakes (Bahri, 2016) and these low volumes, often in competitive markets with low-profit margins, makes it difficult to charge mark-ups to cover any non-economic cost such as litigation costs associated with maintaining or enforcing market access rights. Essentially, for a country with small trade volumes, the opportunity cost of pursuing litigation serves as a disincentive for engaging with the WTO's DSU especially considering the high cost of litigation (Abdul-latif, 2021).

It is only logical that a country would weigh its revenue from the export of certain items against the cost (in resources - money and time) of instituting a case at the WTO. Therefore, a country with a low market share may not be motivated to use the system. The above assertions are in congruence with those of Bown and Hoekman, (2005), Nordstrom, (2005) and (Alavi, 2007) who observed that a countries' level of engagement in the DSM is determined by its shares of world trade, numbers of traded products, numbers of trading partners and the retaliation capacity. Alavi (2007) further explained that the probability of encountering disputable trade measures is proportional to the diversity of a country's exports over products and partners, i.e. countries with a high trade volume and diverse export portfolio would be expected to bring more complaints to the DSU than smaller and less diversified exporters. This theory has been found to predict the actual pattern of complaints across countries' especially when the cost of litigation is controlled for (Alavi, 2007).

Furthermore, the outcome of the probit regression based on equation 1 revealed that understanding of WTO rules on agriculture does not have a significant impact on the export behaviour of Sesame and cocoa producers in Nigeria. However, the understanding of WTO Rules of Origin as measured by Question 17 in the questionnaire, has a significant impact on the export behaviour of Shea nut producers in Nigeria. Similarly, the

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

outcome of the probit regression model based on equation 2 shows that the application of WTO rules on agriculture does not have a significant impact on the export behaviour of Sesame and cocoa producers in Nigeria. However, the application of WTO Rules of Origin as measured by Question 17 in the questionnaire, has a significant impact on the export behaviour of Shea nut producers in Nigeria. These findings are in congruence with those of Otsuki et al., (2001a), Henson et al., (2000a,b), Henson and Loader, (2001) and World Bank, (2005) who all opined that non-tariff measures such as SPS and TBT requirements can act as a disguised restriction to trade, especially for developing countries. Neeliah et al., (2013) further explained that these measures are seen as disguised restrictions for developing countries due to the inadequate technical and financial resources to comply with new laws, complex procedures around plant and animal health, compliance requirements on exporters which imposes costs such as the cost of modernizing the production system, processing, storage, and quality control equipment. To further buttress this point, there is a need to examine the SPS, TBT and Rules of Origin in more detail.

The WTO's Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures (SPS) agreement sets out rules for countries to protect human, animal, and plant life or health from risks arising from the importation of food and agricultural products. This can include measures such as food safety regulations, animal and plant health regulations, and inspection and certification requirements. These measures can affect the export of agricultural commodities from Nigeria as it leads to additional compliance costs and requirements for compliance which discourages agricultural producers from exporting their commodities. For agricultural commodity exports from Nigeria, the SPS measures may require that certain food safety or animal and plant health standards be met before the products can be exported to other countries. This could include requirements for inspections, certifications, and testing to ensure that the products meet the importing country's standards. Failure to meet these requirements can result in the rejection of the shipment, which serves as a barrier to export.

The Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) agreement sets out rules for countries to ensure that technical regulations, standards, and testing, inspection and certification procedures do not create unnecessary obstacles to trade. This can include measures such as labeling requirements, packaging regulations, and testing and certification procedures. Like SPS, TBT measures also add additional compliance costs for Nigerian exporters, making it more difficult for them to access foreign markets.

Rules of origin refer to the criteria used to determine the national source of a good, which can affect whether a good is eligible for preferential treatment, such as reduced tariffs,

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

under certain trade agreements. These rules can also affect the export of agricultural commodities from Nigeria by determining whether or not a product meets the requirements to be considered of Nigerian origin, and therefore eligible for preferential treatment in certain markets.

In summary, the SPS, TBT and Rules of Origin agreements of the WTO can affect the export of agricultural commodities from Nigeria by adding additional costs, requirements for compliance and determining the origin of the good, which can make it more difficult for Nigerian exporters to access foreign markets.

Additionally, the outcome of the probit regression-based Equation 3, suggests that the level of engagement with national trade institutions has a significant impact on the export behavior of cocoa and shea nuts producers in Nigeria. As expected, the level of engagement with national trade institutions can impact the export behavior of farmers in Nigeria in several ways. The national trade institutions covered by this study are: the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD), Nigeria Agricultural Quarantine Services (NAQS), Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment (FMITI), Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC) and Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON). These institutions make up the midstream level of the Nigerian trade environment. Engagement with any of these institutions is supposed to influence the export behavior of producers positively. However, this study found that: engagement with FMITI (Question 7) had a negative impact on the export behavior of sesame and cocoa farmers; engagement with FMARD (Question 6) had a negative impact on the export behavior of sesame producers; and engagement with SON (question 8) had a negative impact on the export behavior of cocoa producers. These results could be due to various factors such as policies, regulations, and programs implemented by these organizations that negatively impact the export behavior of farmers. Further research is needed to determine the specific reasons why engagement with these organizations had a negative impact on the export behaviour of sesame and cocoa producers in Nigeria.

Finally, the outcome of the probit regression based on equations 4,5 and 6 indicates that producer-related factors, as expressed, have a significant effect on the export behavior of sesame, cocoa, and Shea Nuts producers in Nigeria. This finding agrees with that of Luhwago, (2020) who found that producer-related factors such as gender and experience are the major determinants of Rice supply for export markets in Tanzania. The finding is also similar to that of Dawana et al. (2018) who established that the age of a producer is one of the factors influencing rice traders 'participation in in export markets in Ethiopia. The study also agrees with Moore (2006) who demonstrated that producer-related factors including size (output), age, experience and ownership status are significant determinants

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

of the decision to export or not to export. The finding is also in tandem with that of Adesiyani et al., (2020) who suggested that Age of farmer, Sex(gender), Level of formal education, experience, Farm size (and by implication output) are among the major factors influencing farmers' willingness to export yam in Ibarapa East and Ibarapa Central Local Government Areas of Oyo State, Nigeria. To explain the influence of these producer-related factors on export behavior, let take a closer look at each of them.

i. Age of Producer (equation 4)

The age of a producer can influence a producer's decision to participate in exporting agro commodities in a few ways. Firstly, older producers may have more experience and established networks in the industry, which can make it easier for them to navigate the export process and find buyers. They may also have more financial resources and stability, which can be important for meeting the investment commitments and costs required to export. On the other hand, younger producers may be more open to new technologies and marketing strategies, which can help them to be more competitive in the export market. They may also be more likely to take risks, which can be beneficial when entering new markets. Additionally, the age of a producer can also be related to the age of their farm or business. A more mature farm may have more established infrastructure and equipment that are more suited for export. Younger farms may require more investments to develop the necessary infrastructure and equipment to meet storage, packaging and other compliance requirements. In summary, both older and younger producers can have advantages and disadvantages when it comes to participating in exporting agro commodities. Age is one of many factors that can influence a producer's decision to export, but it is not the only one. Other factors such as access to markets, government policies, and the economic environment of the country can also play a significant role.

i. Gender (equation 6)

Gender can influence agro commodity producers' participation in export in various ways. Firstly, women may face more barriers to participation in the export market due to societal and cultural norms. They may have less access to resources such as land, credit, and technology, which can make it more difficult for them to produce and export high-quality goods. Additionally, they may be less likely to be included in networks and training programs that provide information and support for exporting. Secondly, women may face discrimination in the export market, which can make it more difficult for them to access markets, negotiate fair prices for their goods, and establish relationships with buyers. This can limit their opportunities to participate in the export market. Thirdly, women-led agro-

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

commodity producers may face additional challenges as they are not only facing gender discrimination but also discrimination based on their leadership roles. Despite these challenges, Nziku & Struthers (2018) note that female entrepreneurs, instead of being disadvantaged by the so-called 'weak ties' that bind their business networks, actually enjoy compensating benefits which can be referred to as the *strength of weak ties* (SWT).

However, some studies, such as Njobe and Kaaria (2015), show that women-led agro-commodity producers, despite facing these challenges, tend to be more efficient and effective, with a better return on investment. In summary, gender can influence agro commodity producers' participation in export by creating barriers to access to resources, networks, and training programs, and facing discrimination in the export market, which can limit opportunities for women to participate. But also, studies show that women-led agro-commodity producers tend to be more efficient and effective than their male counterparts.

ii. Level of formal education (equations 4, 5 and 6)

The level of formal education can influence a producer's decision to participate in the export of agro commodities in a few ways. Firstly, producers with higher levels of formal education may have better knowledge of international trade laws and regulations, which can make it easier for them to navigate the export process and comply with requirements. They may also have better communication and negotiation skills, which can be important for building relationships with buyers and closing deals. Additionally, they may have a better understanding of global market trends and consumer preferences, which can help them to identify new export opportunities and make strategic decisions. Moreso, producers with higher levels of education may have more knowledge and skills in areas such as marketing, finance, and logistics, which are important for exporting agro commodities. Furthermore, higher education also increases the access of the producer to information and resources that can help them to be more competitive in the export market. They may also have more knowledge about the trade agreements and the regulations of the export markets, which can help them to avoid costly mistakes.

On the other hand, producers with lower levels of formal education may face more challenges when it comes to exporting agro commodities. They may have less knowledge and skills in areas such as marketing, finance, and logistics, which can make it more difficult for them to navigate the export process and find buyers. They may also have less access to information and resources such as market intelligence and trade promotion services that can help them to be more competitive in the export market.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

In summary, the level of formal education can play a significant role in a producer's decision to participate in exporting agro commodities. Producers with higher levels of education may have more knowledge, skills and access to information and resources that can help them to be more successful in the export market, while producers with lower levels of education may face more challenges. It is important to note that formal education is not the only way to acquire the knowledge and skills needed for export. For example, some producers may have gained experience and knowledge through on-the-job training or by participating in trade fairs and exhibitions.

iii. Experience (equations 4, 5 and 6)

The number of years of experience a producer has can influence their export participation in several ways. Firstly, an experienced producer may have a better understanding of the international market and the requirements of foreign buyers. They may also have established relationships with international buyers and be more aware of the regulations and procedures involved in exporting. This can make it easier for them to navigate the export process and increase their chances of success. Secondly, experienced producers may have access to more resources such as finance and technology that allow them to produce and export higher-quality goods. This can increase their competitiveness in the international market. Finally, experienced producers may have a reputation for producing high-quality goods and may have a good reputation with buyers, making it more likely that they will be selected to participate in exporting. In summary, an experienced producer may have a better understanding of the international market, established relationships with foreign buyers, access to resources and reputation that allows them to produce and export higher-quality goods, making it more likely that they will participate in exporting.

iv. Output (equations 4, 5 and 6)

Output refers to the amount of a particular agricultural commodity that is produced by a farmer or group of farmers. The level of output can influence a producer's decision to participate in exporting their commodity. If a producer has a high output, they may be more likely to participate in exporting as they have a larger quantity of the commodity to sell on the global market. Conversely, if a producer has a low output, they may be less likely to participate in exporting as they may not have enough of the commodity to make it economically viable.

Furthermore, the relationship between output, economies of scale, and cost can influence a farmer's decision to export their agricultural commodities. Economies of scale refer to the cost advantages that a producer can achieve by increasing their output. As a farmer increases their output, they may be able to reduce their average costs per unit of output

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

by spreading fixed costs over a larger number of units. This can make it more profitable for the farmer to export their commodities. However, as the output increases, the cost of production also increases. This is known as the law of increasing costs. If the cost of production exceeds the price that the farmer can get for the commodity on the export market, it may not be profitable for the farmer to participate in exporting. In this case, the farmer may choose to sell their commodities in the domestic market instead.

Therefore, in summary, a farmer will consider output, economies of scale and cost when deciding whether to export their agricultural commodities. They will weigh the potential profit from exporting against the costs of production and the price they can get for the commodity in the export market. If the potential profit outweighs the costs, the farmer is more likely to export their commodities, and if not, the farmer may choose to sell the commodities in the domestic market.

v. Ownership (equation 5)

Ownership status, specifically the amount of share owned by local investors or foreign investors, can influence a farmer's decision to export agricultural commodities in various ways. If a farmer's operation is primarily owned by local investors, they may be more inclined to sell their commodities in the domestic market because the local market is more familiar and accessible to them. Additionally, local investors may also be more likely to invest in domestic marketing and distribution infrastructure, which can make it more profitable for the farmer to sell their commodities in the domestic market. On the other hand, if a farmer's operation is primarily owned by foreign investors, they may be more inclined to export their commodities because foreign investors tend to have more access to export markets and export infrastructure. Foreign investors may also be able to offer the farmers better prices for the commodities, which can make it more profitable for the farmers to export their commodities.

It is worth mentioning that a mixed ownership status (by both local and foreign investors) can also have an influence on a farmer's decision to export. In this case, the farmers may have the opportunity to access both domestic and export markets and choose the most profitable option. Kim & Park (2011) note that for producers, participating in exports is a high-risk activity that involves sunk costs, revenue volatility due to exchange rate fluctuations, limited knowledge of market conditions and tougher competition. The agency problem influences a producer or firm's decision to export through attitude toward risk.

In summary, the ownership status of a farmer's operation can influence their decision to export agricultural commodities as foreign owners have more access to international markets where they can maximize returns from their export as opposed to selling solely

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

to the domestic market where the operation is located. Furthermore, foreign owners have the resources to ensure that international standards for exports are met by local producers.

8.1.2 Discussion of findings from the midstream level comprised of Nigeria's Trade Institutions

This thesis examined the ability of midstream actors -made up of Nigerian trade institutions- to investigate trade measures that act as barriers to Nigeria's export market access. The specific objectives were to establish the midstream role, appraise the mechanisms in place, evaluate its performance, identify challenges, and determine trade agreement violations. The findings revealed that the midstream segment acts as a link between downstream and upstream actors and is responsible for educating downstream actors, ensuring compliance, investigating violations, and communicating results of investigations to upstream actors. While there is a comprehensive mechanism in place to enable the midstream to perform its role, it has been ineffective owing inadequate expertise, low stakeholder commitment, limited coordination between national trade institutions, and lack of relevant policies supporting international trade.

Overall, the study found that the midstream level is unable to perform its role effectively due to some factors including: limited capacity to educate the downstream actors on export requirements as well as furnish them with relevant information regarding exports in a timely manner; inadequate monitoring of the export process and; and limited capacity to effectively investigate identified trade barriers and communicate same to the country's WTO Delegation.

It has been argued that the successful use of the WTO dispute settlement rests on the meaningful organization and collaboration among various governmental agencies as well as between the public and private sectors (Shaffer & Melendez-Ortiz, 2012). Hoekman and Mavroidis (2000) cited in Alavi, (2007) present the overall dispute process in two stages – 'upstream', which is that part of the process before a case is officially brought before the DSM, and 'downstream', which is after a case has been officially initiated. According to Shaffer (2003), as cited in Anyiwe and Ekhator (2013), "a country's trade-policy infrastructure plays the central role during the first stage. It is at this stage that information is gathered, analyzed and transferred to the government, which then decides whether to pursue a case or not". In addition to the importance of capacity to investigate trade barriers, the functioning of the trade-policy environment is critical for countries' engagement in the WTO's dispute settlement process. Based on the findings of this study, the Nigerian trade-policy infrastructure is unable to perform this function effectively. It was

THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS

established that identified trade institutions have a proper understanding of their roles in trade matters, and that there are certain mechanisms put in place to facilitate export and handle issues of violations. However, these institutions find it challenging to carry out their responsibilities and fulfil their mandate to downstream actors. Findings from the study revealed the following: there is no synergy within and between trade institutions; trade institutions are not committed to carrying out their roles in the trade process; and there is inadequate communication across Nigeria's trade architecture. All of these are, of course, consequences of lack of proper supervision and monitoring of the activities of trade institutions. This confirms the findings of Anyiwe and Ekhaton, (2013) that developing countries typically have weak trade-policy infrastructures, a shortage of trained personnel, and lack of adequate knowledge about the WTO DSU system thereby limiting their ability to participate in dispute settlement. This contrasts with what is obtainable in developed countries like the US and the EU where the trade architecture is comprehensive and effective coupled with the existence of institutionalized linkages between private companies and the public sector.

There is no gainsaying that the decision to pursue a case at the WTO lies predominantly with the governments of member states. The government is charged with the onerous task of selecting a case, evaluating whether it will be worth going forward with and thereafter managing the litigation process. Therefore, information is a key requirement and embodies a considerable part of the litigation costs for initiating a WTO dispute. This is not what is obtainable in Nigeria as the trade infrastructure is not well-poised to gather case specific information and provide same to the upstream and/or the legal advisors. This would definitely increase the fixed costs incurred from building knowledge of WTO rules and procedures in both government and industry circles and establishing institutional processes to facilitate participation in dispute settlement.

8.1.3 Discussion of findings from the upstream level comprised of Nigeria's WTO Representatives

The objective of the study at this level was to examine the ability of the upstream actors, made up of Nigeria's WTO trade representatives, to initiate and prosecute cases on behalf of the downstream actors. The study found that there are several factors preventing the upstream agents from initiating cases on behalf of the downstream actors. These factors are broadly categorized into internal and external factors. Internal factors refer to country-related issues which in this case are: lack of domestic mechanisms to identify and communicate trade barriers to WTO Delegation, lack of expertise or capacity

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

to litigate in the WTO and lack of knowledge and awareness about the benefits of WTO DSU provisions among government officials and business entities. External factors are issues related to the WTO and these include: the duration of case prosecution; the complexity of the system; the cost of prosecuting cases; and skewed WTO provisions.

8.1.3.1 Internal factors

This segment discusses the internal factors which were found to be limiting Nigeria's participation in WTO dispute settlement. The internal factors consist of country-related issues which in this case are: lack of domestic mechanisms to identify and communicate trade barriers to WTO Delegation; lack of expertise or capacity to litigate in the WTO; and lack of knowledge and awareness about the benefits of WTO DSU provisions among government officials and business entities.

i. Lack of domestic mechanisms to identify and communicate trade barriers to WTO Delegation.

This study found that lack of domestic mechanisms to identify and communicate trade barriers to WTO Delegation was one of the factors impeding Nigeria's engagement with the WTO's DSU. This finding agrees with Bahri, (2018) who stated that poor information channels and ineffective governance structures lead to problems in gathering evidentiary documents relating to trade barriers, their impact, nature and magnitude of injury and their WTO inconsistency and hence, limit a country's ability to participate in the WTO DSU. Similarly, Nottage, (2009) mentioned that a member's participation in the WTO dispute settlement activities will be a function of its ability to perceive injuries to its trading prospects, identify who is responsible, and mobilize resources to bring a legal claim or negotiate a favorable settlement. This implies that the successful utilization of the WTO dispute settlement necessarily requires strategic coordination and effective cooperation among different governmental agencies as well as between the public and private sectors. Nigeria, like many other developing countries, are among the members that face the most severe difficulties in meeting these coordination challenges primarily due to their lack of experience and also their failure to prioritize litigation coordination.

Furthermore, coordination between different ministries or departments is crucial for the proper functioning of any government, particularly in the formulation, adoption, implementation, and evaluation of policy. This is even more indispensable in the context of international trade policies and dispute resolution, the competence of which is not

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

restricted to one agency. This study found that there is a lack of inter-ministerial/inter-agency coordination in Nigeria's trade environment, and this has a direct impact on the country's ability to file complaints and/or respond effectively to a complaint.

ii. Lack of expertise/capacity to litigate in the WTO

Owing to the complexity of dispute settlement process in the WTO, developing countries like Nigeria require in-house technical capacity to navigate the complex procedures and requirements to successfully pursue trade-related litigation. A major factor restricting Nigeria's full participation in the WTO dispute settlement is insufficient human resources. Nigeria's representation in the WTO is limited to a handful of officials. Being small in size is only one part of the equation. The other interlinked part is having skilled and versatile WTO delegations. Many of the representatives in Nigeria's trade delegations attend numerous daily meetings - often taking place at the same time - without the ability to develop, much less maintain mastery of the WTO's procedures and rules. Deep understanding of how WTO panels hold hearings and make decisions is critical for utilizing the dispute settlement system. Nigeria needs to dedicate a small portion of its annual budget, despite her constraints, to train their personnel if the country wants to be more of an active participant than a mere observer in the dispute settlement process.

In contrast, members such as the United States and the European Union, due to the number of cases in which they are involved in the WTO Dispute Settlement mechanism, have extensively developed domestic expertise to engage in WTO litigation (David, 2018). Notwithstanding this, these countries frequently recruit external advisors to support them in the most complex disputes. Analysis of the dispute system Mechanism, 2016). This means that the assistance to be provided will not be very effective in dealing with the problem of lack of capacity. Furthermore, the Advisory Centre on WTO Law (ACWL) was established to provide legal support to developing countries. Developing countries must be members of the ACWL in order to receive services from it. Based on results from the interview, Nigeria has not utilized the free legal support available through the ACWL. This again indicates how Nigeria's low engagement with the DSU is a factor of domestic challenges.

iii. Lack of knowledge/awareness about the benefits of WTO DSU provisions among government officials and producers/exporters.

According to previous studies, insufficient knowledge and awareness about the benefits of WTO DSU provisions among government officials and business entities further

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

constrain developing countries' ability to maneuver and utilize the DSU provisions for their legitimate trade interests (Abdul-latif, 2021; Alotaibi, 2015; Amirbekova, 2015; Bahri, 2018; Bohanes & Garza, 2012; Razaranaina, 2022). This study found that there is a significant lack of knowledge/awareness about the benefits of WTO DSU provisions among government officials and producers/exporters in Nigeria.

Shaffer (2003) opined that equipped with the experience, expertise, and confidence to navigate WTO rules, governments can develop bargaining strategies which they can employ to amicably resolve (and diffuse) trade conflicts, thereby protecting their industries' trade interests in the 'shadow of a potential WTO litigation'. With better bargaining and litigation strategies, and with the consequentially enhanced capacity to raise credible litigation threats, Member States can improve their "terms-of-trade" through effective negotiation with (or successful litigation against) other Member States. Favourable "terms-of-trade" can further generate wide economic, social and environmental benefits for its economic sectors and society at large (Gallanter, 2001). The overarching ambit of WTO dispute settlement is now encompassing areas beyond business, as Panels and the Appellate Body have interpreted and clarified issues that go well beyond law and economics, such as those relating to strategic raw material, green technology, consumer welfare, public health, and purely social concerns (Bahri, 2016). Hence, it is understandable that, against a limited legal representation by Member States, WTO DSU can generate far-reaching economic and non-economic benefits for governments, businesses and other private entities (Bahri, 2016). Whereas the developed countries and more experienced developing, like Brazil and China, are aware of and exploiting these benefits of the DSU, Nigeria, like many other developing countries are still missing out on it. This accounts for the lack of motivation to even try or participate in WTO dispute settlement.

In conclusion, a significant number of the problems limiting Nigeria's participation in WTO dispute settlement are internal (country-related) issues. This agrees with extant literature. According to Bahri, (2016), most of the DSU participation challenges faced by developing countries are deeply rooted in the domestic context. Bahri (2016) asserted that one cannot refute the fact that most of the DSU participation challenges faced by developing countries are deeply rooted in the domestic context of these countries and therefore, solutions can best be found at the domestic level. For example, the paucity of lawyers and government officials trained and experienced in WTO law can, to some extent, be blamed for high litigation costs especially as the lack of domestic legal expertise necessitates hiring expensive overseas lawyers. Paucity of information and evidential documents with a complaining or responding government is mainly due to lack of inter-

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

ministerial coordination and disengaged private stakeholders, and it sometimes results in increasing the litigation cost as information is purchased from overseas agencies. Litigation of a dispute at the WTO DSU is largely dependent on how that dispute is handled at the domestic level. For instance, a case that is poorly handled (perhaps because the impugned trade barrier is insufficiently investigated, or the arguments are not examined by experienced litigators or the claims are poorly substantiated) at the domestic level generally stands a relatively lower chance of success at the international level. Hence, in practice, the future of WTO litigation is partially predetermined by the way it is handled at the domestic level. Therefore, Nigeria and other developing countries in similar situations, should deal with such hurdles directly at the domestic level. In similar vein, it is essential for developing countries to develop domestic strategies for information-gathering, monitoring, consultation, litigation, and enforcement of awards as this will develop their capacity to effectively participate in WTO dispute settlements.

8.1.3.2 External factors

This segment discusses the external factors which were found to be limiting Nigeria's participation in WTO dispute settlement. External factors are issues related to the WTO and these include: the duration of case prosecution, the complexity of the system, the cost of prosecuting cases and Skewed WTO Provisions.

i. Duration of case

Resolving trade disputes is one of the core activities of the WTO. A dispute arises when a member government believes another member government is violating an agreement or a commitment that it has made in the WTO. The Dispute Settlement Understanding (DSU) of the WTO establishes a set of rules and procedures and provides a forum for resolving trade disputes between WTO member countries. When disputes cannot be resolved, the DSU authorizes the use of trade sanctions against the member country, which is in violation of a WTO agreement.

The time it takes to resolve a dispute is an important aspect of the success of the dispute settlement system. "Justice deferred is justice denied," is a widely known moral maxim. Particularly in a model that compensates for past injuries, that is so. Accordingly, DSU Article 4.7 grants 60 days for the consultation procedure, after which the complaining party may request the establishment of a panel. The composition and creation of the panel must be completed within a maximum of 45 days. DSU Article 12.8 states that the time from the date of the panel's formation to the date of its final report shall, as a general rule, not extend six months. In cases of urgency, particularly those relating to perishable goods, the purpose of the panel shall be to release its report within three months. DSU

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Article 12.9 specifies that, if the panel is unable to meet such time limits, it may prolong the time needed. However, the clause stipulates that 'in no case may the time from the formation of the tribunal to the dissemination of the report to the Members extend nine months. For the consideration of the appeal, the DSU stipulates that it will usually be completed within 60 days and that in no case should the proceedings extend 90 days. If we add all these phases, we shall have a cumulative span of about 12 months from consultations to the implementation of standard panel procedures, and at most 15 months if the panel extends the time. If the panel 's decision is appealed, we shall have a limited term of 15-16 months or 18-19 months if the panel has prolonged the time (Afari-djan, 2020).

Delay in the settlement of the WTO cases was also highlighted in various previous studies regarding the WTO cases involving African nations. For instance, the case of Pakistan v. South Africa indicates that the stated case, which is currently in the consultation phase has taken slightly more than five years. In addition, the WTO DS578 (Tunisia v. Morocco), which is currently in the panel hearing phase is also expected to take more than two years to conclude. The insight from the analysis of these two WTO cases suggests that in the scenario where the participating nations do not arrive at a mutual agreement, the cases in disputes are likely to take long to resolve. An analysis of WTO cases by Afari-djan, (2020) revealed that cases involving developed countries as both respondent and complainant spent an average of 3-6 months more compared with cases where developing countries were either respondent or complaint which took much longer. Therefore, the issue of delays in the conclusion of the WTO cases can be a significant barrier that impedes the participation of African countries in the WTO dispute settlement process.

ii. Complexity of the system

According to Nottage, (2009), a number of WTO Members and commentators argue that the WTO dispute settlement system is overly complicated and expensive resulting in insurmountable human resource as well as financial implications for developing countries. This study found that this holds true for Nigeria. With the more complex and rule-oriented system of WTO DSU, the Member States require higher relative capacity to use the adjudicatory mechanism than they required under the previous trading regime, i.e., they require more resources to monitor and enforce their international trade rights. Busch and Reinhardt cited in Bahri, (2016) observe that WTO Member States, in order to participate effectively at WTO DSU, require 'experienced trade lawyers to litigate a case', 'seasoned politicians and bureaucrats to decide whether it is worth litigating a case', 'staff to monitor trade practices abroad', 'domestic institutions necessary to participate in international

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

negotiations', and sufficient market power to ensure compliance and threaten retaliation in cases of non-compliance. This demand for greater resources has posed many participation challenges to Nigeria and other developing countries at WTO DSM.

Furthermore, the various WTO DSU clauses/provisions are highly technical and complex in nature. The implication is that most African nations with limited legal human resource expertise find it difficult to interpret the specific WTO DSU provisions. This aspect is an important consideration for African nations who need to evaluate their legal options and whether it is worthwhile to pursue a specific legal recourse as part of their duties and obligations under the WTO dispute settlement system (Abdul-latif, 2021).

iii. Cost of prosecuting cases

With the more complex and rule-oriented system of WTO DSU, the Member States require a higher relative capacity to use the dispute settlement mechanism than they required under the previous trading regime; that is, they require more resources to monitor and enforce their international trade rights. This demand for greater resources is tantamount to higher cost and this frustrates Nigeria and other developing countries' access to WTO DSM, which, according to Razaranaina, (2022), in turn negatively impacts the legitimacy of WTO as a global forum for negotiations and dispute settlement.

Developing-country concerns with the high costs of WTO litigation stem from many governments lacking sufficient internal WTO legal expertise to conduct disputes themselves. Where internal expertise is lacking, governments are required to hire external legal counsel. It is undeniable that the cost of hiring private legal counsel to litigate WTO disputes has increased exponentially in recent years. Commentators have estimated that 'a "litigation only" bill of US\$500,000 to an exporter for a market access case is likely to be fairly typical (Nottage, 2009). This figure could be increased substantially when a private law firm is hired to litigate the case before the WTO. According to estimates, private law firms can charge anywhere from \$250 to \$1,000 per hour in fees, leading to total fees anywhere between \$100,000 to over \$1,000,000 and could increase even further in more complex cases (Malkawi, 2012). In fact, legal fees could be much greater, with reports of fees for parties in panel proceedings more than US\$10 million. For example, the legal fees incurred in the Japan and United States case dealing with the issue of Measures Affecting Consumer Photographic Film and Paper was recorded by the Panel Report to be more than 10 million US dollars (Anyiwe & Ekhator, 2013).

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

These increased costs can be attributed, in part, to the multiple stages of WTO dispute settlement under the DSU whereby challenged measures may be subject to reviews by a panel, the Appellate Body, an arbitrator determining the reasonable period to comply, further reviews to determine compliance, as well as arbitration on the level of suspension of concessions (Razaranaina, 2022). The binding nature of WTO dispute settlement also means that governments (and the companies behind them) are taking each dispute far more seriously, which seems to lead to more detailed and costly submissions. It also has been observed that the lack of retrospective remedies for businesses affected by illegal protectionist measures gives respondents an incentive to further complicate, hence delay, the dispute settlement process (Nottage, 2009).

The costs of participation in these multiple stages of WTO dispute settlement are compounded by a trend towards increasingly complex and technical submissions. The WTO agreements that came into effect in 1995 include legal standards that hinge on detailed scientific or economic determinations that were not as central under the GATT. For example, with the introduction of the Agreement on the Application of Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures ('SPS Agreement'), scientific evidence of human, animal and plant risks has been heavily litigated (Alotaibi, 2015). Similarly, provisions requiring detailed economic analysis have been the subject of a few recent disputes under the Agreement on Subsidies and Countervailing Measures and the Agreement on Agriculture ('SCM Agreement') (Nottage, 2009). In these disputes, success requires the input of technical experts that may also need to be contracted externally at additional costs. A lack of technical expertise is often given as an explanation for why developing countries have hardly initiated WTO dispute settlement proceedings under the SPS Agreement (Amirbekova, 2015). In contrast, developed-country governments have brought several disputes under the agreement (Bahri, 2016). This situation is surprising as a large proportion of developing-country exports are in agricultural products and the SPS Agreement ensures that trade measures on animals, plants and their products are not used as disguised restrictions on international trade.

iv. Skewed WTO Provisions.

The concern about the distributive justice system is one of the challenges facing African nations in their involvement with the WTO DSM. This study found that the perception of skewness of some WTO provisions has limited Nigeria's participation in the WTO dispute settlement. The perceived unfairness in the distributive justice system is based on the general perception among African countries that the WTO rules are mainly skewed to support the economic/political interests of the advanced nations (Naif, 2015). For example, there are complaints that the restrictive WTO agreements on agricultural

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

subsidies and the anti-dumping legislation under articles 1, 2.1 and 12.2.2 have the potential to adversely affect the overall competitiveness of African firms in the global trade. This has caused many African countries to avoid seeking legal recourse from the WTO DSM due to the perceived inequity and lack of confidence in the entire legal process.

8.2 Overall Findings

The main aim of the study was to investigate the factors responsible for Nigeria's inability to use the WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism to boost the export of key agricultural commodities. The study hypothesized that effective participation in the WTO Dispute settlement process requires downstream, midstream and upstream actors to perform specific roles.

At the Downstream level, the study found that the understanding and application of WTO standards by the downstream players in Nigeria is significantly low. Similarly, the level of participation in commodity export is also very low. Also, the study found that the factors influencing the export behavior of agricultural commodities producers varied depending on the commodity in question, but the level of engagement with national trade institutions had a significant impact on cocoa and shea nuts producers' export behavior.

Furthermore, at the Midstream level, the study found that the midstream level plays a significant role as a liaison between downstream and upstream actors, informing downstream agents about international rules, ensuring compliance with these rules, investigating violations, and communicating findings to upstream actors for necessary actions. However, the study found that these mechanisms are ineffective due to several factors, including inadequate expertise, low stakeholder commitment, lack of synergy, absence of relevant policies, and poor coordination.

Finally, at the Upstream level, the study found that there are several factors preventing upstream agents from initiating cases on behalf of the downstream actors. These include internal factors such as lack of domestic mechanisms to identify and communicate trade barriers to WTO Delegation and lack of expertise or capacity to litigate in the WTO. External factors include the duration of case prosecution, the complexity of the system, the cost of prosecuting cases, and skewed WTO provisions.

Overall, the study found that there are several factors preventing effective participation in the WTO Dispute settlement process in Nigeria. The downstream level lacks the necessary understanding and application of WTO standards, while the midstream level's mechanisms are ineffective due to various factors. The upstream level faces both internal

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

and external factors preventing them from initiating cases on behalf of the downstream actors. This confirms the study's main hypothesis which states that the Nigerian trade architecture is subdivided into three distinct segments namely downstream, midstream and upstream and for the country to participate effectively in the WTO Dispute settlement process, the downstream level must be able to identify market access barriers, the midstream must be able to investigate, gather data and transmit to the upstream level while the upstream level should be able to initiate and prosecute cases on behalf of the downstream actors. As observed, the findings show that each level has a critical role to play. However, all three levels are unable to play their roles effectively due to various factors. Therefore, for Nigeria to be able to utilize the WTO DSU, these factors must be examined and properly addressed.

8.3 The principal-agent theory and the research outcomes

The principal-agent theory provides a useful framework for understanding the challenges faced by Nigeria in engaging with the WTO dispute settlement system. The theory helps to explain the outcome of the research by examining the relationship between the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade & Investment (FMITI), as the agent, and the producers and trade groups in Nigeria, as the principals. The theory highlights the possibility of a conflict of interest between the agent and the principals, where the agent may not act in the best interest of the principals. In this context, the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade, & Investment (FMITI) is the agent, while the producers and trade groups in Nigeria are the principals.

In this case, the principals, who are the producers and trade groups, are interested in increasing market access for agricultural commodities through engagement with the WTO dispute settlement system. On the other hand, the FMITI, as the agent, is responsible for representing the country's interests in the WTO and engaging in dispute settlement processes. However, the FMITI may not necessarily prioritize the interests of the principals, leading to a lack of engagement with the WTO dispute settlement system. Interestingly, extant literature shows that there are several instances that could make the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade & Investment (FMITI) not prioritize the interests of the principals, who are the producers and trade groups in Nigeria. Some of these instances include conflicting priorities, information asymmetry, limited resources, lack of accountability, and political interference. Regarding conflicting priorities, the FMITI may have conflicting priorities that take precedence over the interests of the principals. For instance, the ministry may prioritize the country's overall trade interests over the specific interests of the producers and trade groups (Holmstrom, 1979; Eisenhardt, 1989).

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

On Information asymmetry, the principals may not have the necessary information to ensure that the FMITI is acting in their best interest. This information asymmetry can result in the FMITI making decisions that are not aligned with the principals' interests (Akerlof, 1970). Concerning limited resources, the FMITI may have limited resources, which could impact its ability to prioritize the interests of the principals. For example, the ministry may not have the necessary funds or personnel to investigate identified market access barriers or to engage in the dispute settlement process (Prendergast, 2002; Villena & Villena, 2015). Furthermore, the FMITI may not be held accountable for its actions, which could result in a lack of motivation to prioritize the interests of the principals. Without adequate accountability mechanisms, the ministry may not feel compelled to act in the best interest of the producers and trade groups. Finally, Political interference can also affect the FMITI's ability to prioritize the interests of the principals. For instance, political pressure may influence the ministry's decisions, leading to a conflict of interest with the producers and trade groups.

The study's findings reveal that there is a lack of coordination and capacity among the stakeholders, with each group failing to fulfil its role effectively. The downstream actors, who are the producers and exporters of agricultural commodities, lack the knowledge and understanding of WTO rules, making it challenging for them to identify market access barriers. The midstream actors, who are the trade-related or trade support institutions, lack the capacity to investigate identified market access barriers, gather data, and communicate effectively with the upstream players. The upstream players, who are Nigeria's WTO representatives based in Geneva, lack the initiative to take action at the WTO on behalf of the producers and exporters. This lack of coordination and capacity can be explained by the principal-agent theory. The FMITI, as the agent, may not prioritize the interests of the principals, leading to a lack of coordination and capacity among the stakeholders. The theory suggests that the principals may not have the necessary information or expertise to ensure that the agent is acting in their best interest. Therefore, the lack of engagement with the WTO dispute settlement system can be attributed to a lack of coordination and capacity among the stakeholders, which is a result of the principal-agent problem.

Furthermore, the study found that the lack of engagement in the WTO dispute settlement system is caused by both internal and external factors. The internal factors, such as a lack of domestic mechanisms to identify and communicate trade barriers and a lack of expertise or capacity to litigate in the WTO, can be attributed to the principal-agent problem. The FMITI, as the agent, may not be taking the necessary steps to address these internal factors, leading to a lack of engagement in the dispute settlement system.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Several reasons may be responsible for the FMITI not taking the necessary steps to address the internal factors that inhibit Nigeria's engagement in the dispute settlement system including a lack of sufficient resources, lack of political will or commitment from the government and a lack of necessary expertise on the part of the FMITI.

Firstly, the FMITI may not have sufficient resources, including human and financial resources, to effectively carry out its functions. This lack of resources could affect the FMITI's ability to identify market access barriers, investigate them, and communicate them to the WTO delegation for action. On the challenge of lack of resources, Nigeria's trade negotiators have often cited inadequate resources (financial, human, and institutional) as key constraints to their effective participation in multilateral trade negotiations (UNCTAD, 2018).

Secondly, there may be a lack of political will or commitment from the government to engage in the dispute settlement system. The FMITI may be limited in its ability to act due to political considerations, such as concerns about how engaging in disputes may affect Nigeria's relations with other countries or the fear of negative media coverage. On this point, the world bank stated averred that political will is required to pursue a successful trade policy, stating that it is necessary to take the political risk of promoting trade for the benefit of the economy and society because if there is no political will, trade policy will be ineffective (World Bank, 2019).

Thirdly, the FMITI may lack the necessary expertise or capacity to litigate effectively in the WTO. The dispute settlement system is complex, and engaging in disputes requires specialized knowledge and skills. The FMITI may not have sufficient expertise or capacity to navigate the system effectively and secure favourable outcomes for Nigeria. Incidentally, Nigeria's weak capacity for international trade negotiations and implementation of trade policy has been cited as a major obstacle to the effective implementation of trade policy (World Bank, 2019).

Fourthly, there may be a lack of awareness or understanding about the benefits of the WTO dispute settlement system among government officials and business entities. The FMITI may not be taking the necessary steps to raise awareness and educate stakeholders about the benefits of the system and how to engage in it effectively. This has been confirmed by UNCTAD in its 2018 African Investment Report, 2018 when it stated that the lack of awareness and information is a key factor that impedes the participation of stakeholders in the WTO negotiations (UNCTAD, 2018).

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

In conclusion, the principal-agent theory helps to explain the lack of engagement with the WTO dispute settlement system by highlighting the possibility of a conflict of interest between the agent, FMITI, and the principals, who are the producers and trade groups. The lack of coordination and capacity among the stakeholders can be attributed to the principal-agent problem, which leads to a lack of engagement in the dispute settlement system. The study's findings provide insights into how Nigeria can address these challenges by improving coordination and capacity among the stakeholders and ensuring that the FMITI prioritizes the interests of the principals. The study found that the internal factors inhibiting Nigeria's engagement with the WTO dispute settlement system are spread across the upstream, midstream, and downstream players. The external factors, such as the duration of case prosecution, complexity of the system, cost of prosecuting cases, and skewed WTO provisions, also play a significant role in inhibiting Nigeria's engagement with the WTO dispute settlement system. Addressing these factors will require a concerted effort from all stakeholders involved in Nigeria's trade infrastructure, including government officials, trade support institutions, producers, and exporters. Ultimately, improving Nigeria's engagement with the WTO dispute settlement system will lead to increased export market access for agricultural commodities and promote economic growth and development in the country.

8.4 Summary

This study examined the factors preventing Nigeria from engaging the WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism and leveraging this instrument to boost the export of key agricultural commodities in Nigeria. Based on the review of extant literature on the engagement of developing countries and African countries in the World Trade Organization (WTO)the

Dispute Settlement Mechanism since its establishment, the study established that the challenges may be classified into two broad categories: Country-related (internal factors) and WTO-Related (external factors). The study postulated that in order for Nigeria to participate effectively in the WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism, both internal factors and external factors must be sufficiently addressed. Therefore, the study adopted a comprehensive conceptual framework which further subdivided the internal factors across three distinct segments of the Nigerian trade architecture namely: downstream, midstream and upstream. The study was generally based on the hypothesis that for Nigeria to engage the WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism effectively, the downstream level must be able to identify market access barriers, the midstream must be able to investigate, gather data and transmit to the upstream level while the upstream level

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

should be able to initiate and prosecute cases on behalf of the downstream actors. The entire study was underpinned by the principal-agent theory and a mixed-method approach was adopted.

At the downstream level the study focused on the ability of the actors to identify and report market access barriers. To gain a better perspective, the study first determined the export status and the factors influencing the export behaviour of the downstream actors. The ability of the downstream actors to identify market access barriers was also measured using the level of Knowledge and application SPS, TBT and Rules of Origin. A total of 100 producers of each of top three Nigeria's exported Nigeria agricultural commodities; Cocoa, Sesame and Shea Nuts were drawn to represent the downstream actors. A quantitative approach was adopted for this segment and data were collected using a well-structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistics and probit regression were used to analyse the primary data collected. The outcome revealed that most of the producers were neither exporting at the time nor have the intention to export. The outcome also showed that understanding and application of WTO rules on agriculture has a significant impact on the export behavior of Shea Nuts producers but not Sesame and cocoa producers, the level of engagement with national trade institutions has a significant impact on the export behavior of cocoa and shea nuts producers in Nigeria and producer-related factors have a significant effect on the export behavior of sesame, cocoa and Shea Nuts producers in Nigeria. It is essential to note that information obtained during the focus groups discussions indicated that compared to cocoa and sesame producers, more shea nut producers have taken advantage of some of the federal government's intervention programs implemented through the Central Bank of Nigeria and the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. Overall, the study found that the level of understanding and application of WTO rules was very low among the producers, therefore, it was concluded that the downstream actors were unable to Identify Market access barriers.

To determine the ability of the midstream level to investigate, gather data and communicate to the upstream, the study adopted a qualitative approach. Data were collected through a focus group meeting with participants who were purposively sampled the relevant trade institutions including the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment (FMITI), Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD), Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON), Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC), National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC), The Nigerian Office for Trade Negotiations (NOTN) and the Nigeria Agricultural Quarantine Service (NAQS). The data collected was coded and analyzed using content analysis. The

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

outcome suggests that the midstream level is not able to investigate, gather data and communicate to the upstream effectively.

First, the study found that the midstream level plays a crucial role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria's export commodities. Furthermore, the focus group discussions revealed cases of rejections, but these were mainly due to a lack of awareness/understanding and/or proper application of WTO rules by downstream actors (producers and exporters) and shortcomings on the part of midstream actors (trade institutions). Second, the study found that although there is a formal mechanism for reporting cases of rejection, there is a problem with awareness of how to do so. The study also found that there is no well-defined mechanism for investigating reported violations of WTO agreements. Third, despite the existence of a comprehensive communication mechanism to facilitate cooperation and synergy among trade institutions, there is a lack of effective communication due to a lack of inter-agency cooperation and synergy within and among relevant agencies.

Finally, to evaluate the ability of the upstream level to initiate action at the WTO on behalf of the producers/exporters, the study adopted a qualitative approach and used a semi-structured interview to collect data from the purposively selected participants including the honorable minister of the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment and Nigeria's Ambassador to the WTO. The sole aim of the interview segment was to establish the comprehensive role of the upstream agents in reducing market access barriers and to identify the factors inhibiting their ability to engage the WTO Dispute Settlement mechanism on behalf of Nigerian exporters. The data gathered through the interviews were coded and analysed using a content analysis technique. The outcome revealed that the upstream has a crucial role to play in reducing market access barriers for Nigerian agricultural commodity producers and exporters. Furthermore, the outcome of the content analysis showed that factors limiting Nigeria's ability to engage the WTO Dispute Settlement mechanism are in two broad categories: external and internal factors. The internal factors are: lack of domestic mechanisms to identify and communicate trade barriers to WTO Delegation; Lack of Expertise or Capacity to Litigate in the WTO and lack of knowledge and awareness about the benefits of WTO DSU provisions among government officials and business entities while the external factors include: the duration of case prosecution, complexity of the system, the cost of prosecuting cases and Skewed WTO Provisions.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Overall, the study found that the downstream actors -which in this case are Cocoa, Sesame, and Shea Nuts producers- are unable to identify market access barriers given their low participation in export and low understanding and application of WTO rules (SPS, TBT and Rules of Origin), the midstream lack the capacity to investigate identified market access barriers, gather data and communicate to the upstream for further actions, and the upstream lacked what it takes to initiate action at the WTO on behalf of the producers/exporters. Therefore, the study concludes that Nigeria has not been able to engage the WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism because of inadequacies across the three segments of the country's trade architecture coupled with some WTO-related factors.

8.5 Conclusions

This study examined the factors preventing Nigeria from participating in the WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism and leveraging this instrument to boost the export of its key agricultural commodities. The study acknowledges that since the inception of the WTO in 1995, Nigeria has never participated in the WTO dispute settlement process as either respondent or litigant. The study theorized that the Nigerian trade architecture is subdivided into three distinct segments namely downstream, midstream and upstream; and for the country to participate effectively in the WTO Dispute settlement process, the downstream level must be able to identify market access barriers, the midstream must be able to investigate, gather data and transmit to the upstream level while the upstream level should be able to initiate and prosecute cases on behalf of the downstream actors. To examine this theory, the study employed a mixed-research design approach and gathered data from a systematic literature review, surveys, focus group discussions and interviews. The data collected were analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative techniques accordingly. The outcome of data analysis revealed that the downstream actors are unable to identify market access barriers given their low participation in export and low understanding and application of WTO rules (SPS, TBT and Rules of Origin).

Insights from the thematic analysis of feedback from the focus group discussion demonstrated that the midstream lacks the capacity to investigate identified market access barriers, gather data and communicate to the upstream for further actions. Furthermore, insights from the thematic analysis of interview indicates that the upstream level faces both internal and external factors preventing them from initiating cases on behalf of the downstream actors. This confirms the study's main hypothesis which states that the Nigerian trade architecture is subdivided into three distinct segments namely downstream, midstream, and upstream. Effective engagement with the WTO dispute

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

settlement process relies on the strengthening the capacity of these three segments to carry out their respective responsibilities in the trade process. On the other hand, the principal-agent theory helps to explain the lack of engagement with the WTO dispute settlement system by highlighting the possibility of a conflict of interest between the agent (i.e. trade institutions) and the principal (i.e. the producers and trade groups). The lack of coordination and capacity among the stakeholders can be attributed to the principal-agent problem, which leads to a lack of engagement in the dispute settlement system. The study established that the factors preventing Nigeria from engaging the WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism can be broadly categorized into internal and external factors. The internal factors are spread across the upstream, midstream, and downstream players while the external factors (i.e. the duration of case prosecution, complexity of the system, cost of prosecuting cases, and skewed WTO provisions) has to do with the WTO and are beyond the jurisdiction of the country. Based on the foregoing, the study concludes that Nigeria has not been able to engage the WTO Dispute Settlement Understanding because of inadequacies across the three segments of the country's trade architecture coupled some WTO-related factors.

8.6 Recommendations

Based on the results from the analysis of quantitative and qualitative data collected, these are the main recommendations of the research:

General Recommendations

- i. There is a need to establish an inter-ministerial coordination platform of relevant trade institutions to drive the country's trade policy and boost export of agricultural commodities. This platform should consist of the following government institutions: FMITI (chair); FMARD (co-chair); NEPC; and SON. It will support information sharing on technical standards for export of agricultural commodities and enhance cooperation towards localizing these standards across the six geopolitical regions with emphasis on reaching rural farmers across the 774 LGAs.
- ii. In line with the economic agenda of the current administration which seeks to diversify Nigeria's economy through export of agricultural commodities, there is a need for the federal government to provide sufficient funding to the FMARD to enable it to carry out broad sensitization of rural farmers on

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

technical standards across the 774 LGAs. This sensitization exercise will enable rural farmers apply or consider these standards at the pre-production phase.

- iii. For effective implementation of the revised national trade policy, there is a need to address human capacity constraints inherent in trade institutions especially the FMITI. In addition to recruiting people with the requisite trade expertise to take up positions within the Department of Trade, training of existing staff on WTO trade procedures/policies, and SPS standards will contribute to strengthening the capacity of the country's trade institutions. Furthermore, national trade institutions should take advantage of technical assistance support offered by WTO especially National capacity building programs and utilize platforms such as the trade obstacle alert mechanism-set up by the ITC.
- iv. There is a need for mandate mapping of relevant trade institutions to address the problem of overlapping mandates and duplication of roles and responsibilities among relevant government institutions. This should build on the expected results from establishing an inter-ministerial coordination platform for facilitating trade in agricultural commodities.
- v. Build capacity of the trade regulatory agencies including SON, NQAS NEPC, NAFDAC on WTO procedures and technical standards governing trade in agricultural commodities.
- vi. Establish a department within the FMITI to provide high quality business advisory services and export solutions to agricultural commodity producers and exporters especially around SPS and Rules of Origin requirements.
- vii. Implement Nigeria's national quality policy related to trade competitiveness and standardization.
- viii. Establish an unfair international trade investigation authority within the FMITI to investigate claims of unnecessary market access barriers by WTO member countries. This will contribute to making the investigating mechanism for

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

dealing with market access barriers by WTO member countries more structured than is the case at present.

Recommendations for Strengthening Agricultural Producers' Capacity to Export

In line with the findings of this study, the recommendations for strengthening the downstream level are as follows:

- i. Increase awareness and education on SPS, TBT, and rules of origin: the government and private sector can work together to increase awareness and education among Nigerian agro commodity producers on the SPS, TBT, and rules of origin measures that are required by importing countries, and how to comply with these measures. Furthermore, the government can invest in building capacity among Nigerian agro commodity producers to implement regulations, as well as provide the necessary infrastructure and equipment to meet these regulations;
- ii. Facilitate compliance with TBT measures: the government and private sector can invest in providing Nigerian agro-commodity producers with the necessary equipment, technology, and expertise to comply with TBT measures;
- iii. Provide technical assistance for meeting rules of origin: the government and private sector can provide technical assistance to help Nigerian agro commodity producers understand and meet the rules of origin requirements;
- iv. Build capacity to implement regulations: the government can invest in building capacity among Nigerian agro commodity producers to implement regulations, as well as provide the necessary infrastructure and equipment to meet these regulations; and
- v. Export facilitation: the government should streamline and simplify export processes and procedures so that it is easier and less bureaucratic for producers and exporters of agricultural commodities.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Recommendations for Strengthening Nigeria's Trade Institutions

In line with the findings of this study, the recommendations for strengthening the midstream level are as follows:

- i. Adopting and adapting a more functional institutional framework like that of Brazil which has been one of the most successful developing countries in terms of engaging the DSU;
- ii. The FMARD should have a dedicated department concerned with Nigeria's export commodities. The department should focus on training on standards for specific target export market as technical standards for export of agro commodities differs from country to country;
- iii. An inter-ministerial/stakeholder platform involving the FMARD, FMITI, the Federal Ministry of Foreign affairs and private sector stakeholders should be established and properly coordinated. The role of the Federal Ministry of Foreign Affairs in tis trade platform is to handle the political and diplomatic aspects of trade. In this regard, Brazil should be considered an example of a country that successfully built an institutional structure to create and maintain strategic inter-agency coordination as well as public-private partnerships;
- iv. Building technical and legal capacity: Nigeria can invest in building the technical and legal expertise necessary to effectively navigate the WTO dispute settlement process. This can include training for government officials and legal professionals, as well as building a strong team of experts to handle trade disputes. To this end, establishing a dedicated international trade law unit may thus be desirable to improve coordination among governmental agencies. Both Argentina and Thailand provide interesting examples of the benefit that such unit can bring to a government's structure; and
- v. Institutional Strengthening: Nigeria can work to strengthen its institutions, such as its judiciary, so that they are better equipped to handle disputes related to international trade. This can include providing training and resources, as well as implementing reforms to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the institutions. Furthermore, the government should demonstrate political will to engage with the WTO's dispute settlement mechanism by allocating resources to support trade-related institutions in this regard.

Recommendations for Strengthening the WTO DSU

In line with the findings of this study, the recommendations for strengthening the upstream level are as follows:

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- i. The study found that high-cost implications and technical complexities are the major factors preventing developing countries like Nigeria from engaging the DSU. Therefore, it is recommended that the DSU should be restructured to make it more user-friendly; less expensive and less technical;
- ii. Address the issue of duplicating and competing mandates among trade institutions in Nigeria that leads to inefficiencies in the management of international trade and handling of trade restrictions being experienced by agro producers/exporters. Furthermore, there is a need to ensure that these institutions are staffed by qualified personnel who have expertise around WTO processes, procedures, and international trade law.

8.7 Suggested Areas of Further Research

While this research focused on exploring Nigeria's engagement with WTO's DSS especially in relation to market access barriers faced by its agricultural commodity exports, there is need for additional research to explore how trade tariffs and non-tariff measures encourage or discourage African countries from engaging in the export of refined or processed agricultural commodities.

During the literature review, the researcher unearthed the influence of national values on trade outcomes. For instance, the recent sanctions on Russia in relation to its invasion of Ukraine poses serious challenges for the nomenclature of global trade in future. Consequently, there is equally a need to conduct a study that explores how national values (i.e. human rights, democracy etc) is shaping the global trade landscape. Another area of future research concerns examining the effects of direct and indirect trade costs on capacity of RECs in Africa to achieve their goals and objectives.

Another finding of this research concerns the lack of technical capacity among trade institutions in Nigeria as it relates to understanding of the WTO's dispute settlement mechanism. Consequently, there is need for a study that assesses Nigeria's institutional capacity for international trade. Such research could explore the potential for additional technical assistance support that reduces the learning curve between developing and developed countries as it relates to engaging with and actively participating in critical aspects of the WTO's dispute settlement processes. Furthermore, this research could also examine the current WTO Agreement on Agriculture with a view to determining if it is biased in favour of developed countries compared to their developing counterparts.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

REFERENCES

Abbot, R. (2009) 'Are Developing Countries Deterred from Using the WTO Dispute Settlement System? Participation of Developing Countries in the DSM in the years 1995 – 2005'. *ECIPE Working Paper*, vol. 1, pp.12 - 13

Ackere, A. (1993) The principal/agent paradigm: its relevance to various functional fields. *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 70 pp.83-103.

Adams, R., Phillipa-Dee, J. & Greg, M. (2003) The trade and investment effects of preferential trading arrangements: old and new evidence. Canberra: Australia Productivity Commission

AfreximBank (2020) Transforming Africa's Trade: Informal Cross-Border Trade in Africa in the Context of the AfCFTA. African Trade Report [online]. Accessed from: <https://afrcorp-media-prod.s3-eu-west-1.amazonaws.com/afrexim/African-Trade-Report-2020.pdf> [17 October 2022]

Aher, A. (2022) Theories of international trade: an overview. Accessed from: <http://sim.edu.in/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/International-trade-theories.pdf> [9 April 2023]

Ajayi-Kadir, S. (2020) Emerging issues disrupting Nigeria's non-oil export and innovative solutions. Presentation at NEPC Export Conference, May.

Alavi, A. (2007) African countries and the WTO's dispute settlement mechanism, *Development Policy Review*, vol. 25(1) pp.25-42.

Alesina, A. & Wacziarg, R. (1998) Openness, country size and government. *Journal of Public Economics*, vol. 69(3) pp.305-321.

Alesina, A. (2002) The size of countries: does it matter? Harvard Institute of Economic Research, Discussion paper No. 1975. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University

Alvarez-Jimenez, A. (2009) Improvements to the WTO Decision-Making Process: Lessons from the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank. In Steger, D. (ed.) *Redesigning the World Trade Organization for the Twenty-First Century*. Waterloo: Wilfried Laurier University Press

Bagwell, C.B. & Staiger, R., W. (2015) Is the WTO Passe? Policy Research Working Paper 7304, World Bank Group.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Balchin, N., Calabrese, L., Mendez-Parra, M. & te Velde, D., M. (2018) Nigeria and the Africa Continental Free Trade Area: potential impacts and Nigeria's readiness. Discussion Paper, December.

Bandura, R. & Hammond, M. (2018) The world of work in developing countries. Center for Strategic and International Studies [online] April 19. Accessed from: https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/resrep22496.5.pdf?refreqid=excelsior%3A0b50ab6b80f98bb777a2873ec161d8f5&ab_segments=&origin=&initiator=&acceptTC=1 [12 April 2023]

Beghin, J. (2008) Non-tariff barriers. In Darlauf, S. & Blume, L. (eds) *The New Palgrave Dictionary of Economics*. 2nd Edition. London: Palgrave Macmillan

Besson, F. & Nehdi, R. (2004) Is the WTO Dispute Settlement Biased Against Developing Countries? An Empirical Analysis. EconPapers No. 330600022.

Bhatia, U., S. (2017) The problems of plenty: challenging times for the WTO's Dispute Settlement System. *Address by Chairman of Appellate Body*, June 8.

Bircher, U. & Butler, M. (2007) *Information economics*. London: Routledge

Blomstrom, M. and Kokko, A. (1997) 'Regional Integration and Foreign Direct Investment', NBER Working Paper 6019.

Bolton, P. & Dewatripont, M. (2004) *Contract theory*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press

Bown, C. (2004), 'Developing countries as plaintiffs and defendants in GATT/WTO trade disputes', *The World Economy*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 59-80.

Bown, C. (2009) Self-enforcing trade: developing countries and WTO dispute settlement. Washington DC: Brookings Institution Press

Bown, C. P. (2003) Participation in WTO dispute settlement: complainants, interested parties and free riders. *Working Paper*. Accessed from: <http://people.brandeis.edu>

Bown, C., P. (2005) Participation in WTO Dispute Settlement: Complainants, Interested Parties and Free Riders, *World Bank Economic Review*, vol. 19(2) pp.287-310

Bown, C., P. (2019) The 2018 US-China trade conflict after 40 years of special protection. Working Paper 19-7, Petersen Institute for International Economics. Accessed from: <https://www.piie.com/system/files/documents/wp19-7.pdf> [18 January 2020]

Brander, J., A. & Spencer, B., J. (1985) Export subsidies and international market share rivalry. *Journal of International Economics*, vol. 18(2) pp. 83-100.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Breuss, F. (2001) WTO Dispute Settlement from an Economic Perspective: More Failure than Success? IEF Working Papers / Research Institute for European Affairs, Vienna University of Economics & Business Administration

Brewer, T. & Young, S. (1999) WTO Disputes and Developing Countries, *Journal of World Trade*, vol. 35(5) pp.196-182.

Busch, M. & Reinhardt, E. (2000) Bargaining in the Shadow of the Law: Early Settlement in GATT/WTO Disputes, *Fordham International Law Journal*, vol. 24 pp. 158-162.

Busch, M. and Eric Reinhardt, E. (2003) "Developing Countries and General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade/World Trade Organization Dispute Settlement," *Journal of World Trade*, vol. 37(4) pp.719-732

Busch, M.L. & Reinhardt, E. (2003) Developing countries and general agreement on tariffs and trade / World Trade Organization Dispute Settlement, *Journal of World Trade*, vol 37(4) pp.719-735.

Cali, M. & Montfaucon, A., F. (2021) Non-tariff measures, import competition, and exports. World Bank Policy Research working Paper [online] No. 9801. Accessed from: <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/994091633707638412/pdf/Non-Tariff-Measures-Import-Competition-and-Exports.pdf> [5 April 2023]

Cash, J. (2023) China says it has never deliberately pursued trade surplus with the US. Opinion Piece [online] March 23. Accessed from: <https://www.reuters.com/world/china/china-says-it-has-never-deliberately-pursued-trade-surplus-with-us-2023-03-23/> [10 April 2023]

Cattaneo, N. & Fryer, D. (2002) Intra versus inter-industry specialization, labour market adjustment and poverty: implications for regional integration in Southern Africa. *Trade and Industrial Policy Strategies Working Paper*, No. 15, TIPS, Johannesburg

Cepal, (2014) International Trade and Inclusive Development: Building Synergies. Santiago, Chile: Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC)

Chad Bown, C. (2004) "On the Economic Success of GATT/WTO Dispute Settlement". *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, vol. 86(3) p.811

Chang, P. L. (2002) The Evolution and Utilization of the GATT / WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism, *Singapore Management University Working Paper Series*, No. 13.

Chang, W., W. (2011) Trade disputes in practice. *Vignana Vahini Journal of Management*, vol. 1(1) pp.33-45.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

- Coase, R., H. (1937) The nature of the firm. *Economica*, vol. 4(16) pp.386-405.
- Collis, J. & Hussey, R. (2005) *Business research: a practical guide for undergraduate and postgraduate students*. 3rd Edition. London: Palgrave Macmillan
- Coulibaly, S., Kassa, W., Zeufack, A., G. (2022) Africa in the New Trade Environment: Market Access in Troubled Times. Washington, DC: World Bank
- Croome, J. (1995) *Reshaping the World Trading System*. Geneva: WTO
- Cuyper, I., R., P., Hennart, J., Silverman, B., S. & Ertug, G. (2020) Transaction cost theory: past progress, current challenges, and suggestions for the future. *Academy of Management Annals*, vol. 15(1) pp.111-150.
- Davey, W., J. (2009) "Compliance Problems in WTO Dispute Settlement", *Cornell Journal of International Law* [online] Issue 1, Article 5, at pp. 126-128. Available at: <http://www.scholarship.law.cornell.edu/cilj/vol42/iss1/5> [13 April 2023]
- Davey, W., J. (2009) Compliance problems in WTO dispute settlement. *Journal of International Law*, vol. 1(5) pp.126-128.
- Davey, W.J. (2003), 'The case for a WTO permanent panel body', *Journal of International Economic Law*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 177-86.
- Davis, C. & Bermeo, S. (2009) Who files? Developing country participation in GATT/WTO adjudication, *JOP*, vol. 71 1036
- Davis, D., R. (1998) The home market, trade and industrial structure. *American Economic Review*, vol. 88 pp.1264-1276.
- De, P. (2005) Effects of infrastructure on regional income in the era of globalization: new evidence from *South Asia*. *Asia Pacific Development Journal*, vol. 12(1) pp.81-107.
- De, P. (2006) Regional trade in Northeast Asia: why do trade costs matter? *CNAEC Research Series* 06-02, Korea Institute for International Economic Policy, Seoul.
- De, P. (2006) Trade, infrastructure and transaction costs: the imperatives for Asian Economic Cooperation. *Journal of Economic Integration*, vol. 21(4) pp.708-735.
- Deloitte (2019) Nigeria's finance bill 2019: key changes and implications. Accessed from: <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/ng/Documents/tax/ng-newsletter-nigerias-finance-bill-2019.pdf> [2 January 2020]

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Deraniyagala, S. & Fine, B. (2003) New trade theory versus old trade policy: a continuing enigma. *Cambridge Journal of Economics*, vol. 25(6) pp.809-825

Devuyst, Y. & Serdarevic, A. (2007) The World Trade Organization and Regional Trade Agreements: Bridging the Constitutional Credibility Gap. *Duke Journal of Comparative & International Law*, vol. 18(1).

Dixit, A., K. & Stiglitz, J., E. (1977) Monopolistic competition and optimum product diversity. *The American Economic Review*, vol. 67(3) pp.297-308.

Dodd, S. & Cattaneo, N. (2006) Theoretical approaches to the analysis of trade and poverty and a review of related literature on South Africa. South Africa Labour & Development Research Unit: University of Cape Town

Duval, Y. (2006) Cost and benefits of implementing trade facilitation measures under negotiations at the WTO: an exploratory survey. *ARTNeT Working Paper No. 3*, UNESCAP, Bangkok

Fugazza, M. (2013) *The economics behind non-tariff measures: theoretical insights and empirical evidence*. Geneva: UNCTAD

Gailmard, S. (2012) *Accountability and the principal-agent theory*. Oxford: Oxford Handbook of Public Accountability

Galanter, M. (2001) Contract in Court; or Almost Everything You May or May Not Want to Know about Contract Litigation, *WIS. L. Rev.* pp.577, 579 (Contracts Symposium 2001)

Ganslandt, M. & Markusen, J., R. (2001) Standards and related regulations in international trade: a modelling approach. In Maskus, K. & Wilson, J., S. (eds) *Quantifying the impact of technical barriers to trade: can it be done?* Ann Harbor: University of Michigan Press

Girma, S., Greenaway, D. & Kneller, R. (2004) Does exporting increase productivity? A micro-economic analysis of matched firms. *Review of International Economics*, vol.12(5) pp.855-866.

Gokmen, G., Vermeulen, W., N. & Vezina, P. (2020) The imperial roots of global trade. *Journal of Economic Growth*, vol. 25 pp.87-145.

Graewert, T. (2020) Conflicting laws and jurisdictions in the dispute settlement process of regional trade agreements and the WTO. *Contemporary Asia Journal of Arbitration*, vol. 1(2) pp. 287-334.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Hoekman, B. & Kostecki, M., M. (2001) *The political economy of the world trading system*. Oxford: Oxford University Press

Hoekman, B. and Mavroidis, P. (2000) *Enforcing WTO Commitments: Dispute Settlement and Developing Countries – Something Happened on the Way to Heaven*. Trade and Development Center, Geneva: WTO

Holmes, P., Rollo, J. and Young, A. R. (2003) *Emerging trends in WTO dispute settlement back to the GATT? World Bank Policy Research Paper*, No. 31333.

Holmes, P., Rollo, J. and Young, A.R. (2003) *Emerging trends in WTO dispute settlement back to the GATT? World Bank Policy Research Paper*, No.3133.

Holmsotrom, B. & Milgrom, P. (1991) *Multitask principal-agent analyses: incentive contracts, asset ownership, and job design*. *Journal of Law Economics and Organization*, vol. 7 pp.24-52.

Horlick, G. N. (2005) *African countries and the WTO's settlement system*. Accessed from: <http://www.ictsd.org>

Horn, H., Mavroidis, P.C. and Nordstrom, H. (1999) *Is the use of the WTO dispute settlement system biased? CEPR Discussion Paper*, No.2340.

Horn, H., Mavroidis, P.C. and Nordstrum, H. (1999) *Is the use of the WTO dispute settlement system biased? CEPR Discussion Paper*, N. 2340.

Horn, H., Nordstrom, H. and Mavroidis, P. (1999) "Is the Use of the WTO Dispute Settlement System Biased?" *CEPR Discussion Paper 2340* (1999).

https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/dispu_e/dispu_e.htm#:~:text=The%20WTO%20has%20one%20of,350%20rulings%20have%20been%20issued. Retrieved 4th May, 2023.

Hu, W. (2019) *China as a WTO developing member, is it a problem? CESP Policy Insights* [online] No. 2019/16. Accessed from: https://www.ceps.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/PI2019_16_WH_China-as-a-WTO-developing-member.pdf [7 April 2023]

Imboden, N. & Nivet-Claeys, A. (2008) *Cotton and the LDCs in the WTO: Negotiation and Litigation: Two Sides of the Same Coin*. In Duran, E. (ed.) *The Doha Era and Beyond: the Coming of Age of Developing Countries in the Multilateral Trading System*. London: Cameron May

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

International Monetary Fund (IMF) (2016) Nigeria: Country Report. Report No. 16/101. Accessed from: <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/scr/2016/cr16101.pdf> [27 December 2019]

Jackson, J., H. (1998) *The World Trade Organization: Constitution and Jurisprudence*. Chatham House Papers. London: Royal Institute of International Affairs

Jackson, J., H. (1998) *The World Trading System*. 2nd Edition. United States: MIT Press

Jara, A. (2012) Progress Report on Informal Consultations to Enhance Efficiency of the Panel Process. Presentation to the Graduate Institute of International and Development Studies in Geneva, March 13.

Jensen, M. & Meckling, W. (1976) Theory of the firm: managerial behaviour, agency costs, and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, vol. 3(4) pp.305-360.

Jeroh, E. & Okoye, E. (2015) Impact assessment of bank consolidation on the performance of commercial banks in Nigeria. *Economica*, vol. 11(5).

Jouanjean, M., A., te Velde, D., W., Balchin, N., Calabrese, L. & Lemma, A. (2016) Regional infrastructure for trade facilitation: impact on growth and poverty reduction. London: ODI

Kassa, W. & Sawadogo, P., N. (2021) Trade creation and trade diversion in African RECs: drawing lessons for the AfCFTA. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper [online] No. 9761. Accessed from: <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/215761630345612049/pdf/Trade-Creation-and-Trade-Diversion-in-African-RECs-Drawing-Lessons-for-AfCFTA.pdf> [4 April 2023]

Kessie, E. & Addo, K. (2002) African countries and the WTO negotiations on the dispute settlement understanding. Accessed from: <https://www.ictsd.org/sites/default/files/event/2008/05/african-countries-and-the-wto-negotiations-on-the-dispute-settlement-understanding.pdf>

Kim, S. & Park, D. (2011) Ownership structure and export performance: firm-level evidence from the Republic of Korea. *ADB Working Paper*, No. 295. Accessed from: <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/30441/economics-wp-295.pdf> [8 June 2023]

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Kleen, P. & Page, S. (2005) Special and Differential Treatment of Developing Countries in the World Trade Organization. Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Sweden: Global Development Studies, EGD Secretariat

Klein, B., Crawford, R., G. & Alchian, A., A. (1978) Vertical integration, appropriate rents and the competitive contracting process. *Journal of Law & Economics*, vol. 21(2) pp.297-326.

Krishna, P. & Mitra, D. (1998) Trade liberalization, market discipline and productivity growth: new evidence from India. *Journal of Development Economics*, vol. 56(2) 447-462.

Krugman, P. (1980) Scale economies, product differentiation, and the pattern of trade. *American Economic Review*, vol. 70(5) pp.950-959.

Lane, J. (2014) Organization theory: principal-agent perspective. *Global Journal of Human Social Science*, vol. 14(7) pp.45-51.

Lenz, G. (2012) *Follow the leader: how voters respond to politicians' performance and policies*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press

Lester, S., (March 2, 2022). Ending the WTO Dispute Settlement Crisis: Where to from here? [https://www.iisd.org/articles/united-states-must-propose-solutions-end-wto-dispute-settlement-crisis#:~:text=World%20Trade%20Organization%20\(WTO\)%20dispute,and%20leaving%20the%20dispute%20unresolved](https://www.iisd.org/articles/united-states-must-propose-solutions-end-wto-dispute-settlement-crisis#:~:text=World%20Trade%20Organization%20(WTO)%20dispute,and%20leaving%20the%20dispute%20unresolved). Retrieved 4th May, 2023.

Liedong, T., A. (2019) Nigeria's border closure has implications for Africa's economic integration. *Mail & Guardian Newspaper*, October 29.

List, F. (1856) *The national system of political economy*. Philadelphia: Lippincott & Co.

Matoo, A., Mulabdic, A. & Ruta, M. (2019) Trade creation and trade diversion in deep agreements. Working Paper [online] June 3. Accessed from: <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/328491559591517896-0050022019/original/TradeCreationanfTradeDiversion.pdf> [3 April 2023]

Mavroidis, P.C. (2000) Remedies in the WTO legal system: between a rock and a hard place, *European Journal of International Law*, vol. 4 pp. 763-813

McMillan, M., Page, J., Booth, D. & te Velde, D., W. (2017) Supporting economic transformation: an approach paper. Supporting Economic Development Programme. London: ODI

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Melitz, M., J. (2003) The impact of trade on intra-industry reallocations and aggregate industry productivity. *Econometrica*, vol. 17(6) pp.1695-1725.

Michalopoulos, C. (1998) *Developing countries' participation in the World Trade Organization*. Washington, DC: World Bank

Michalopoulos, C. (1999) The developing countries in the WTO, *World Economy*, January.

Monyakane, M. (2006) Special and differential treatment under the World Trade Organization with Specific reference to the application of the WTO agreement on Agriculture. University of South Africa: Thesis

Mosoti, V. (2005) Africa in the first decade of WTO dispute settlement. *Journal of International Economic Law*, October.

Mutume, G. (2006) Ne barriers hinder African trade: health standards in rich countries limit continent's ability to export. African Renewal [online] January. Accessed from: <https://www.un.org/africarenewal/magazine/january-2006/new-barriers-hinder-african-trade> [16 December 2022]

Muuka, G., K. (2001) Africa's market access under WTO, AGOA and the EU's EBA initiative: dimensions, dilemmas, and prospects. Proceedings of a World Bank Seminar on the Legal Aspects of International Trade. Accessed from: <http://siteresources.worldbank.org/INTLAWJUSTICE/Resources/trade.pdf> [20 January 2020]

Narayanan, S. (2003) Dispute Settlement Understanding of the WTO: Need for improvement and clarification. Working Paper [online]. Accessed from: <https://www.icrier.org/pdf/wp117.pdf> [10 April 2023]

National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2017) Foreign trade in goods statistics. *Quarterly Report*, December.

Njobe, B. & Kaaria, S. (2015) Women and agriculture: the untapped opportunity in the wave of transformation. Feeding Africa Conference Background Paper, October 21-23. Accessed from: https://www.afdb.org/fileadmin/uploads/afdb/Documents/Events/DakAgri2015/Women_and_Agriculture_The_Untapped_Opportunity_in_the_Wave_of_Transformation.pdf [8 June 2023]

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Nziku, D., M. & Struthers, J. (2018) Female entrepreneurship in Africa: Strength of weak ties in mitigating principal-agent problems. *Journal of Small Business & Enterprise Development*, October.

OECD (2016) *Making it happen: aid for trade*. Paris: OECD Publishing

Ohnsorge, F. & Yu, S. (2021) *The long shadow of informality: challenges and policies*. Washington DC: World Bank

Olapade, Y. & Onyekwena, C. (2021) Quantifying the impact on Nigeria of the African Continental Free Trade Area. Brookings Institute, September 22.

Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (1997) *Market Access for the Least-Developed Countries: Where Are the Obstacles?* OECD: Paris

Otaha, J., I. (2012) Dutch disease and the Nigerian economy. *African Research Review*, vol. 6(1) pp.82-90.

Park, Y.D. & Panizzon, M. (2002) WTO dispute settlement 1995-2001: a statistical analysis, *Journal of International Economic Law*, pp.221-244.

Picciotto, S.O.L. (2005) The WTO's Appellate Body: Legal Formalism as a Legitimation of Global Governance, *Governance* vol. 18(3) pp.477-503.

Posada, K., C., Ganne, E. & Piermartini, R. (2020) The role of WTO Committees through the lens of specific trade concerns raised in the TBT Committee. Staff Working Paper ERSD [online] May. Accessed from: https://www.wto.org/english/res_e/reser_e/ersd202009_e.pdf [17 May 2023]

Presidential Committee on Impact & Readiness Assessment of AfCTA (2019) African Continental Free Trade Area: impact and readiness assessment. *Committee Report* vol 1, April 2019.

PriceWaterHouseCoopers (PwC) (2014) A privatized power sector: the pain and the glory. Policy Brief, July. Accessed from: <https://www.pwc.com/ng/en/assets/pdf/pwc-a-privatized-power-sector-the-pain-and-the-glory.pdf> [11 April 2023]

PriceWaterHouseCoopers (PwC) (2019) Nigeria Economic Outlook: Top 10 Themes for 2019. Accessed from: <https://www.pwc.com/ng/en/assets/pdf/nigeria-economic-outlook-2019.pdf> [4 January 2020]

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

PwC (2015) A guide to doing business in Nigeria. Report [online] September. Accessed from: <https://www.pwc.com/ng/en/assets/pdf/a-guide-to-doing-business-in-nigeria.pdf> [13 April 2023]

PwC (2019) AfCTA: Thriving in a new Africa. Policy Brief [online] November. Accessed from: <https://www.pwc.com/ng/en/assets/pdf/afcfta-2019.pdf> [28 December 2019]

Razaranaina, N. (2022) The developing countries under the WTO's dispute settlement resolution process: a way to protect companies in today's global trading competition. *Journal of Modern Economy*, vol. 13(3).

Read, R. (2005) Trade dispute settlement mechanisms: the WTO dispute settlement understanding in the wake of the GATT. Lancaster Management School Working Paper [online] vol. 12. Accessed from: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/1555396.pdf> [2 April 2023]

Reich, A. (2017) The effectiveness of the WTO dispute settlement system: a statistical analysis. EUI Working Papers [online] vol. 11. Accessed from: https://cadmus.eui.eu/bitstream/handle/1814/47045/LAW_2017_11.pdf [11 April 2023]

Reich, A. (2017) The effectiveness of the WTO dispute settlement system: a statistical analysis. EUI Working Paper LAW, vol. 11. Accessed from: https://cadmus.eui.eu/bitstream/handle/1814/47045/LAW_2017_11.pdf [17 November 2022]

Rindfleisch, A. (2019) Transaction cost theory: past, present and future. *Academy of Marketing Science*, July 11.

Roberts, M. (2008) The US-China trade relationship: explaining US anti-dumping duties on China. Stanford Center for International Development Working Paper No. 360, May.

Rose, A. (2006) Size really doesn't matter: in search for a national scale effect. *Journal of the Japanese & International Economies*, vol. 20(4) pp.482-507.

Salawu, D., Oyebanjo, D., Obafemi, D. & Oyeley, D. (2021) International trade in goods and services in Nigeria: overview. Thomson Reuters Practical Law [online] 1 June. Accessed from: [https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/w-016-4262?transitionType=Default&contextData=\(sc.Default\)](https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/w-016-4262?transitionType=Default&contextData=(sc.Default)) [14 October 2022]

Saunders, M., N., K., Thornhill, A. & Lewis, P. (2005) *Research methods for business students*. 5th Edition. London: Pearson

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Sen, S. (2010) International trade theory and policy: a review of the literature. *Levy Economics Institute Working Paper*, No. 635.

Serences, R. & Kozelova, D. (2021) Dumping -unfair trade practice. SHS Web of Conferences [online] vol. 92. Accessed from: https://www.shs-conferences.org/articles/shsconf/pdf/2021/03/shsconf_glob20_06033.pdf [6 April 2023]

Shaffer, G. & Melendez-Ortiz, R. (2012) Dispute settlement at the WTO: the developing country experience, ICTSD

Shaffer, G. (2003) How to make the WTO dispute settlement system work for developing countries: some proactive developing country strategies, Working Draft. Accessed from: <http://www.ictsd.org/dlogue/2003-0207/shaffer.pdf>

Shaffer, G. (2005) Weaknesses and proposed improvements to the WTO dispute settlement system: an economic and market-oriented view. *Paper Prepared for WTO at 10: A look at the Appellate Body*, Sao Paulo, Brazil, May 16-17.

Sitonik, N. (2017) Functionality of the dispute settlement system: a World Trade Organization's (WTO) approach. *Global Journal of Politics and Law Research*, vol. 4(2) pp.19-28.

Statista (2021) Nigeria: distribution of gross domestic product (GDP) across economic sectors from 2011 to 2021. Accessed from: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/382311/nigeria-gdp-distribution-across-economic-sectors/> [21 October 2022]

Statista (2022) Oil industry in Nigeria: statistics and figures. Accessed from: <https://www.statista.com/topics/6914/oil-industry-in-nigeria/#topicOverview> [13 April 2023]

Stevens, C., Anderson, E. & Kennan, J. (2005) The impact of the reform of international trade on urban and rural change. IDS Working Paper, No. 245. Institute of Development Studies: University of Sussex

Templars Law (2002) Deregulation of Nigeria's telecommunications sector: implications and developments. Working Report, May.

Tirkey, A. (2019) The WTO dispute settlement system: an analysis of India's experience and current reform proposals. Observer Research Foundation (ORF) Working Paper, September.

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Tsoukas, H. & Chia, R. (2011) *Research in the sociology of organizations: philosophy and organization theory*. Bradford: Emerald Publishing

UNCTAD (2016) The unseen impact of non-tariff measures: insights from a new database. Accessed from: https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/ditctab2018d2_en.pdf [14 October 2022]

UNCTAD (2020) Made in Africa: Rules of Origin for enhanced intra-African trade. Press Release [online] 26 June. Accessed from: <https://unctad.org/press-material/facts-figures-0> [18 October 2022]

UNIDO (2017) The role of standards and quality infrastructure in trade facilitation. Presentation at the Trade Facilitation Forum in Geneva, January. Accessed from: https://unctad.org/system/files/non-official-document/FrankVanRompaeey_UNIDO_NTFCForum_Jan2017.pdf [18 May 2023]

Van den Bossche, P. & Zdouc, W. (2017) *The law and policy of the World Trade Organization: text, cases and materials*. 4th Edition. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press

Van Grassek, C. (2013) *The history and future of the WTO*. Geneva: WTO Publications

Varma, S., Madhukar, V., Abhyarantne, A. & Bankhad, K. (2017) Trade creation and trade diversion: India's experience in APTA and ISCECA. Conference Paper [online] February 11. Accessed from: <https://www.freit.org/WorkingPapers/Papers/TradePolicyRegional/FREIT1189.pdf> [3 April 2023]

Viner, J. (1950) *The Customs Union Issue*. New York: Carnegie Endowment for International Peace

Viner, J. (2014) *The customs union issue*. London: Oxford University Press

White, W., D. (1992) Information and the control of agents. *Journal of Economic Behaviour & Organization*, vol. 18 pp.111-117.

Wigwe, C. & George, I., F. (2017) Dumping and antidumping in international trade: the international economic law perspective. *Journal of Jurisprudence & Contemporary Issues*, vol. 9(1) pp.22-31.

Williamson, O., E. (1985) *The economic institutions of capitalism*. New York: Free Press

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

Wolfrum, R., Stoll, P. & Seibert-Fohr, A. (2007) *WTO: Technical barriers and SPS measures*. Netherlands: Koninklijke Brill NV, Leiden

World Trade Organization (WTO) (2017) Trade policy review: Nigeria. Accessed from: https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/tpr_e/s356_e.pdf [22 December 2019]

World Trade Organization (WTO) (2018) Resolving trade disputes between WTO members: WTO dispute settlement. Accessed from: <http://www.wto.org/disputes> [18 February 2020]

WTO (2004) Evaluation of the WTO dispute settlement system: results to date. In Handbook on the dispute settlement system. Geneva: WTO

WTO (2021) Dispute Settlement Activity – Some Figures. Accessed from: https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/dispu_e/dispustats_e.htm [10 April 2023]

WTO (2023a). Dispute settlement.

WTO (2023b). Members continue push to commence Appellate Body appointment process.

https://www.wto.org/english/news_e/news22_e/dsb_28mar22_e.htm#:~:text=At%20a%20meeting%20of%20the, trading%20system%20as%20a%20whole. Retrieved 4th May, 2023.

Xiangchen, Z., Qingjun, X. & Jinyong, W. (2019) Capacity constraint: a fundamental perspective for the development issue at WTO. *Journal of World Trade*, vol. 53(1) pp.1-38.

Yuan, X. & Zhang, Y. (2018) *Brief analyses of technical barriers to trade: based on the case of lighters in Wenzhou*. China: School of Xi'an University of Science and Technology

Zandt, F. (2021) Africa's biggest economies. Statista [online] December 9. Accessed from: <https://www.statista.com/chart/26371/african-countries-with-the-highest-gdp-over-time/> [16 October 2022]

Zimmerman, T., A. (2007) WTO Dispute Settlement: General Appreciation of the Role of India. In Padmaja, K. (ed.) *WTO and Dispute Resolution*. Hyderabad: the Ifcai University Press

**THE WTO DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING AS A TOOL FOR ELIMINATING
MARKET ACCESS BARRIERS FOR NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS**

ANNEX A: QUESTIONNAIRE

ANNEX B: FOCUS GROUP GUIDE

Introduction

Researcher introduces his or herself. Researcher must make sure all focus group participants sign the consent forms. The participants will be informed that all information obtained during this research will be kept confidential and used solely for the purpose of the research. The purpose of the focus group session is to understand the role of the midstream segment of Nigeria's trade ecosystem in addressing market access barriers faced by producers and exporters of agricultural commodities.

The focus group session is expected to last for between 45 minutes to 1 hour.

Focus Group Questions

Question 1: What is the role of the midstream level in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria's export commodities?

Question 2: What is your perspective on the readiness of the midstream level in carrying out its role to facilitate export of agricultural commodities?

Question 3: How well has the Midstream level performed its role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria's export commodities?

Question 4: What are the challenges of the Midstream level in performing its role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria's export commodities?

ANNEX C: INTERVIEW GUIDE

Introduction

Research introduces his or herself. Researcher must make sure all interviewees sign the consent forms. Interviewees will be informed that all information obtained during the course of this research will be kept confidential. The purpose of the Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) is to understand the role of the upstream segment of Nigeria's trade ecosystem in addressing market access barriers faced by producers and exporters of agricultural commodities.

Each interview is expected to last for between 30 to 45 minutes.

Interview Questions

Question 1: What is the role of the upstream level in reducing market access barriers by Nigeria's agricultural exports?

Question 2: How well has the upstream level performed its role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria's export commodities?

Question 3: what are the challenges of the upstream level in performing its role in reducing market access barriers for Nigeria's export commodities?